

**O‘ZBEKISTON RESPUBLIKASI OLIY TA'LIM, FAN VA
INNOVATSIYALAR VAZIRLIGI**

BUXORO DAVLAT UNIVERSITETI

**EFFECTIVE WAYS OF ORGANIZING
LEARNER CENTERED CLASSES
IN ENGLISH LANGUAGE CLASSROOM**

Xalqaro miqyosdagi ilmiy-amaliy anjuman

MATERIALLARI TO'PLAMI

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Maqolalarni to'plovchi va nashrga tayyorlovchi Ingliz adabiyotshunosligi va tarjimashunoslik kafedrasida o'qituvchilari L.X.Xaydarova va N.S. Zokirova

Ushbu to'plamda jamlangan maqolalar qiyosiy tilshunoslik, tarjimashunoslik va madaniyatlararo muloqot masalalari, qiyosiy adabiyotshunoslik va adabiy oqimlar rivoji masalalari, xorijiy tillarni o'qitishning zamonaviy yondashuvlari va istiqbollari, O'zbekistonda tarjima maktabi yaratish va uni rivojlantirishda innovatsion g'oya va texnologiyalarni qo'llash masalalari doirasida mutaxassislarning tajriba va fikr almashinuvini ta'minlashga xizmat qiladi.

Til – millat ko‘zgusi, madaniyat xaritasi

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O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Shavkat Mirziyoyev tomonidan o‘zbek tiliga davlat tili maqomi berilganligining 30 yilligi munosabati bilan so‘zlagan nutqida keltirilgan: “Kimda-kim o‘zbek tilining bor latofatini, jozibasi va ta’sir kuchini, cheksiz imkoniyatlarini his qilmoqchi bo‘lsa, munis onalarimizning allalarini, ming yillik dostonlarimizni, o‘lmas maqomlarimizni eshitsin, baxshi va hofizlarimizning sehrli qo‘shiqclariga quloq tutsin” satrlari tilning millat ko‘zgusi, uning haqiqiy sarchashmasi ekanligidan dalolatdir.

Yurtimizda so‘nggi yillarda nafaqat o‘zbek tili, balki xorijiy tillarni o‘qitish va o‘rganishga e’tibor davlat siyosati darajasiga ko‘tarildi. Xorijiy tilni bilmay turib jahon miqyosida fan-texnika sohasida amalga oshirilayotgan zamonaviy kashfiyotlar, yangiliklardan nafaqat bebahra qolish, balki millatlararo integratsiya jarayonidan uzilib qolish mumkin. Vatanimizning umidli kelajagi xorijiy tilni mukammal egallagan yoshlar qo‘lida, deya aytish mumkin. Shunday ekan, xorijiy tilning jahon standartlariga mos ravishda o‘qitilishi, ta’limning eng yangi trendlari asosida olib borilishi, ta’lim jarayonida madaniyatlararo muloqotni o‘rnatishda tarjima, til va adabiyot yo‘nalishlarining uyg‘unlashtirilishi mazkur yilning “Insonga e’tibor va sifatli ta’lim yili” deb nomlanishiga hamohangdir.

Shu o‘rinda Mahmudxo‘ja Behbudiyning: dunyo donishmandlari asarlaridan xabardor bo‘lish, jahon adabiyoti durdonalaridan chinakamiga lazzatlanish, shuningdek, zamonasini anglash, taraqqiyot uchun chet tilini bilish o‘ta muhimligi haqidagi qarashlari beixtiyor yodimizga keladi. Chunonchi, jadidlar yetakchisi millat farzandlari o‘z manfaati, jamiyatda muhim mavqe va obro‘ga ega bo‘lishi uchun xorijiy tilni bilishi zarurligi haqida so‘zlab, qat’iyat bilan “Xulosa, bugun bizlarga to‘rt tilga tahrir va taqdir etguvchilar kerak”, deya ta’kidlagan edi.

Til o'rganish nafaqat alifbo, lug'at va grammatikani o'z ichiga olgan murakkab jarayon bo'lib, matn mazmunini, masalan, xulq-atvor va madaniy me'yorlarini o'rganishni o'z ichiga qamrab olishi zarur. Yangi axborot texnologiyalari tufayli ish jarayonlari, kundalik hayot tarzi, ta'lim va kundalik muloqot jarayonlarida madaniyatlararo o'zaro ta'sirning barcha xususiyatlari ko'z o'ngimizda o'zgarib bormoqda. Masalan, talabalar qandaydir yangi tilni o'rganayotganlarida, bir tildan ikkinchi tilga tarjima qilish amaliyotida yangi til mazmuni haqida va bu tilni o'rganish jarayonida ushbu til xususiyatlari bilan birgalikda xalq madaniyati bilan ham bevosita muloqot qilish qobiliyatiga ega bo'ladilar. Har qanday tilni o'rganish uchun ular nafaqat tilni, balki u bilan bog'liq barcha xususiyatlarni: joy, makon, tarix va madaniyatni o'rganish jarayonidan o'tadilar. Shunday qilib, ular tilda gaplashish orqali o'sha til madaniyatiga, ya'ni til va madaniyat o'rtasidagi o'zaro bog'liqlik kuchi va mohiyatiga avtomatik ravishda singib ketishlari mumkin.

Til va madaniyat doirasida tildan tashqari, real dunyoda mavjud bo'lgan madaniy voqelikda qo'llaniladigan lingvistik shakllar emas, balki boshqa ramziy tizimlar mavjuddir: biz madaniyat deb ataydigan odatlar, e'tiqodlar, yodgorliklar va madaniy hodisalar shular jumlasidandir. Madaniyatga aylanish uchun tildagi har bir tarkibiy qism ma'noga ega bo'lishi kerak. Bu xuddi biz kundalik turmushimizda hayotimiz uchun zarur bo'lgan narsalarga e'tibor qaratganimizdek gap.

Xulosa qilib ayta olamanki, til va madaniyat o'rtasidagi munosabatlarga e'tibor qaratishga urinish, nega madaniyatni o'qitish chet tili o'quv dasturining ajralmas qismi bo'lishi kerak. Adabiyotlarni chuqur tahlil qilish, jahon badiiy, ilmiy adabiyotining eng sara namunalarini tillararo tarjima qilish madaniyat va uning chet tillarini o'rganish jarayonidagi ahamiyatli jihatlarini yaxshiroq tushunishga hissa qo'shadi. Til o'rganish yoki o'qitish talabalarning kommunikativ kompetensiyasini rivojlantirishga qaratilgan bo'lib, u faqat o'rganilayotgan chet tilining grammatik, leksik va fonologik xususiyatlarini bilish

va tushunish bilan cheklanib qolmasligi, balki o‘sha til madaniyatini o‘rganish yoki o‘rgatish bilan ham shug‘ullanishi kerak.

TA'LIM TIZIMIDA CHET TILLARINI O'RGATISHNI TAKOMILLASHTIRISHDA ILG'OR TAJRIBALAR

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Bugungi kun zamonaviy ta’lim talablari zamirida yoshlar ongi va bilimni XXI asr uchun muhim bo‘lgan hayotiy ko‘nikmalar bilan boyitish maqsadi o‘z aksini topadi. Bunday ko‘nikmalarning eng muhimlari ta’lim tizimining ilk bosqichlari: maktabgacha va umumiy o‘rta ta’lim jarayonida shakllantiriladi va bugungi kunda “4 K” ko‘nikmalari sifatida o‘quv jarayoniga tatbiq etilmoqda. Bu ko‘nikmalar tarkibiga kommunikatsiya (muloqot), kritik (tanqidiy) fikrlash, kreativlik, kooperatsiya va kollaborativ kompetensiyalarini shakllantirish vazifalari kiradi. Kommunikativ vositalardan foydalanishni dars jarayonida o‘rgatish, til o‘rganish bilan bog‘liq darslarni sifatli tashkil etish o‘quvchilarda lingvomotivatsiyaning shakllanishiga olib keladi.

Zamonaviy jamiyatda ona tilidan tashqari ko‘pgina xorijiy tillarda ham samarali muloqot qila oladigan, kollaborativ faoliyatda muvaffaqiyat qozona oladigan, kreativ tafakkur asosida o‘z sohasida yangilik va qulayliklarni joriy eta oladigan, qolaversa, tanqidiy fikrlash asosida o‘zida mavjud bo‘lgan kamchiliklarni bartaraf eta olish imkoniyatiga ega bo‘lgan mutaxassislarga ehtiyoj kuchli ekanligini tan olmay ilojimiz yo‘q.

Tayanch kompetensiyalar ichida yetakchi o‘rinda turuvchi muloqot jarayoni - atrofdagilar o‘rtasida hamkorlik faoliyati ehtiyojidan yuzaga keladigan axborot almashinuvi hisoblanadi. Uning turi va shakllari har xil bo‘ladi. Asosiy vazifalari esa insonlarning o‘zaro bir birlarini tushunishlarini ta'minlash asosida ijtimoiy tajribaga asos solish hamda kishilarni u yoki bu faoliyatga sifatli tayyorlash hisoblanadi. Shuning uchun zamonaviy dunyoda chet tillarini o‘rgatish

jamiyat ravnaqi uchun katta rol o'ynaydi. Til o'rganish keng ahamiyatga ega bo'lib, xalqaro va davlatlararo aloqalarni mustahkamlash, yoshlarning kooperativ ishtiyoqini oshirishga yordam beradi.

Til o'rganish bilan bog'liq ta'lim jarayonini qachon samarali deb atash mumkin?

Asosiy ta'lim muammolarini hal qilish chet tilini o'rgatish tizimida eskirgan o'qitish usullarini innovatsion shakllar asosida o'zgartirish va jahonning ilg'or tajribalari bilan boyitish hamda til o'rgatish texnikalarini takomillashtirish bilan bog'liq hisoblanadi. Chet tilini o'rgatish jarayonini takomillashtirish uchun dars jarayonida loyihalar tayyorlash, muammolarni hal etishga qaratilgan amaliy faoliyat, mustaqil ishlash jarayonlari asosida o'z-o'zini tarbiyalash ko'nikmalarini ham shakllantirib boorish talab etiladi. Shuningdek, zamonaviy talablar mazmunida o'quvchilarni chet tilini o'rganishga qiziqtirish va ularda o'zlashtirish motivatsiyasini shakllantirishning bir qolipdagi modellarini o'zgartirish ham muhim hisoblanadi. Ilg'or tajribalarga asoslangan jarayonni tashkil etishda bugungi kun ehtiyojlarini inobatga olish muhim hisoblanadi. Bunda chet tilini o'rganish uchun o'quvchilarda motivatsiyani oshirish maqsadida o'qitishning optimal usullaridan foydalanish talab etiladi.

Shaxsning shakllanishida samarali muloqotning ijobiy ta'sirini inobatga olgan holda undan foydalanishning mazmunli va tizimlashtirilgan yo'nalishlarini ishlab chiqish pedagoglar oldida turgan muhim vazifa hisoblanadi. Bunday tizimli yondashuv ijobiy ijtimoiy tajribani egallash imkonini beradi. Shu bilan birga ma'naviy, intellektual, moddiy va madaniy tajribalarni egallash, insonning dunyoni va o'zini anglashi, buning natijasida – ijtimoiylashuv bosqichlarini muvaffaqiyatli o'tashga yo'naltiradi. Shuningdek, chet tilarini mukammal o'rganish, millatlararo muloqot vositasi sifatida undan foydalanish, umumiy madaniyat va nutq madaniyatini egallash, shaxsiy muvaffaqiyatga erishish, professional yo'nalishni tanlash, individual ijodiy salohiyatni kashf etish uchun ham zarurligini unutmazlik lozim.

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar

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Innovative ways of teaching active words of the Lesson

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New Methodology

Annotation:

In language teaching, educators are continually seeking innovative methodologies to enhance students' proficiency and engagement. One such approach gaining traction is the MFP (Meaning, Form, Pronunciation) technique. This article explores the principles of the MFP technique and its practical applications in English language teaching classrooms.

Key words: MFP, technique, approach, innovative methodology, accuracy, fluency ,CLT

In today's world, language learners want to speak and communicate effectively in the language they're learning. Whether for personal, academic, or professional reasons, the ability to use language confidently is crucial. Communicative Language Teaching (CLT) is a modern approach that focuses on exactly that - helping learners communicate authentically. Unlike old methods that centered on memorizing grammar rules, CLT prioritizes practical language use. It's not just about knowing the rules; it's about using the language in real-life situations. In CLT classrooms, students engage in activities that mirror everyday conversations. They talk, listen, read, and write in ways that resemble genuine

interactions. In a CLT classroom, teachers act more like guides. They facilitate activities where students communicate with each other, collaborate on projects, and solve problems using the language they're learning. This approach empowers learners to take ownership of their language learning journey and builds their confidence in using the language. But CLT doesn't work alone. It's often complemented by the Meaning, Form, Pronunciation (MFP) technique, which provides a structured approach to language learning. MFP ensures that learners not only understand the meaning of words and phrases but also grasp their grammatical structure and pronunciation.

By integrating CLT and MFP, educators create inclusive environments where learners from diverse linguistic and cultural backgrounds feel respected and valued. Students engage in communicative tasks that allow them to practice language in real-life contexts while receiving explicit instruction on grammar and pronunciation from the MFP technique.

This combination fosters a sense of community and mutual respect in the classroom. Learners interact using the target language, building connections and understanding different perspectives. Ultimately, CLT and MFP make language learning practical, enjoyable, and relevant to everyday life besides, CLT and MFP offer a dynamic and effective approach to language teaching. By emphasizing authentic communication and providing structured language instruction, educators empower learners to develop the language skills and confidence needed to succeed in a globalized world. Unlike traditional methods that focus solely on grammar rules or vocabulary drills, the MFP technique adopts a holistic approach that considers the interconnectedness of language components.

The first component of the MFP technique is meaning, which involves contextualizing language within meaningful contexts. Rather than presenting language in isolation, educators introduce vocabulary, grammar structures, and expressions within authentic communicative situations. This helps students understand how language functions in real-world contexts and fosters comprehension and retention.

The second component of the MFP technique is form, which involves teaching the grammatical and structural aspects of language. Educators provide explicit instruction on grammar rules, sentence structures, and language patterns,

guiding students in understanding how language is constructed. By focusing on form, students develop accuracy and precision in their language production and gain confidence in expressing themselves fluently.

The third component of the MFP technique is pronunciation, which addresses the phonological aspects of language. Educators pay attention to pronunciation patterns, stress, intonation, and rhythm, helping students develop clear and intelligible speech. Through interactive activities such as pronunciation drills, role-plays, and listening exercises, students improve their speaking and listening skills and enhance their overall communicative competence. While implementing the MFP technique in language classrooms involves a variety of instructional strategies and activities tailored to students' proficiency levels and learning objectives.

1. **Vocabulary acquisition:** When introducing new vocabulary, educators incorporate meaning, form, and pronunciation components simultaneously. For example, they may use visual aids, context clues, and word collocations to convey meaning, provide examples of word usage to illustrate form, and model correct pronunciation through repeated practice and feedback.
2. **Grammar instruction:** When teaching grammar structures, educators follow a scaffold approach that integrates meaning, form, and pronunciation. They present grammar rules in context, provide opportunities for guided practice and application, and incorporate pronunciation practice to reinforce language patterns.
3. **Speaking and listening activities:** In speaking and listening activities, educators design tasks that require students to engage with language in meaningful ways. For example, they may organize role-plays, debates, or group discussions that prompt students to use target language structures, practice pronunciation, and negotiate meaning with peers.

The MFP technique offers a comprehensive framework for language teaching that integrates meaning, form, and pronunciation in a systematic and coherent manner. By adopting this approach, educators can optimize students' language learning experiences, foster communicative competence, and empower learners to use language effectively in real-life situations. Through thoughtful implementation of the MFP technique, language classrooms become dynamic environments where students engage actively, develop proficiency, and achieve meaningful language learning outcomes. Furthermore, by using the MFP

framework, learner not only understands the meaning, but also recognizes its grammatical structure and learns how to pronounce it correctly.

This approach facilitates a comprehensive understanding and usage of the phrase in context.

List of literatures:

1. "Approaches and Methods in Language Teaching" by Jack C. Richards and Theodore S. Rodgers
2. "Teaching by Principles: An Interactive Approach to Language Pedagogy" by H. Douglas Brown
3. "Communicative Language Teaching Today" by Jack C. Richards -
4. "How Languages are Learned" by Patsy M. Lightbown and Nina

**REFLECTION ON THE RESULTS OF THE SURVEY ON THE
IMPACT OF GENDER DIFFERENCE ON THE LANGUAGE**

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Introduction. The influence matters of gender differences on language have become one of the main issues of sociolinguistics since the early 1970s. The series of researches conducted in this field proved that there is a distinct difference between male and female speech in terms of vocabulary, tone, syntactic structure and speaking style. In addition, from this period, the tradition of describing the language phenomenon in relation to society and the people who are its members was born in the science of linguistics.

Literature review. Well-known linguists such as Lakoff R, Tanin D, and Cameron M studied gender differences in pronunciation, intonation, vocabulary and speech style in their research from the perspective of sociolinguistic research, and analyzed the factors of origin of these differences and the reasons for changes in these factors.

Since words are the most active element of language in the learning process, the difference in the speech of men and women is also visible in the choice of

words. In this regard, Lakoff's opinion, which emphasizes that women's vocabulary is superior to men's, attracts attention. According to the linguist, women in society spend more time on activities that men spend less time on, such as shopping and choosing gifts. When choosing a gift or buying clothes, women pay more attention to color, and color identifying words observed in women's speech are not seen in men's vocabulary are. For example, colors such as *azure*, *mauve*, *aquamarine* are incomprehensible to men in the system of words denoting color in the English language. Alternatively, adjectives such as *adorable*, *charming*, *lovely*, *fantastic*, and *heavenly* among the adjectives in the English language are rare in men's speech.

Researchers Ning and Day found out that men and women also differ in their choice of conversation topics. For example, men often choose the topics of politics and economics, while women prefer to talk about family and education. The reason for this is that women are busier with family and raising children than men.

There is also a difference in the use of humor and joke between men and women. According to Coates, men and women use jokes for different purposes. Jennifer Hay identifies three main functions of humor too: to emphasize power differences, to provide self-protection and to create or maintain solidarity. The last two is mostly count for women's purposes to use jokes in their conversation.

According to Karlsson (2007), there is a discussion about the characters uses by female and male. According to him, the female character uses intensifiers (so, such), hedges(I think, you know, I really, I mean, I suppose), tag questions (You didn't- did you?), minimal responses (yeah, mhm, right). Yet, as he point out, men use minimal responses in order to let the woman know he is not interested in what she has to say, taboo words: the man uses taboo words which are supposed to be more frequently used among males than females (Shit! God damn it!),and mostly commands: „give me some paper!“, „Hand me the sport

magazine by the sofa!” whereas women seem to be more polite using “please”, “Could you...” and etc.

Research Methodology. This survey research deals with a small-scale, quantitative survey on the impact of gender variation in the language use among English (native) speakers on the points mentioned in literature review section of the survey research rationale.

Research objective. The objective of the survey research is to find out if there is a gender variation in the language use among the English (native) speakers on the points mentioned in different researches conducted on this issue before.

Research questions.

Do men and women use language differently?

How do they speak differently?

What specific or common differences are there in their speech?

Does this difference have any impact on their communication?

Significance of the survey. This survey will show to what extent the research findings in terms of the impact of gender difference on the language and communication are close to reality and to identify if there have appeared some differences as a matter of time and the changes in society.

Participants. Michigan state university students and scholars are invited to become participants of this survey as representatives of native English speakers. The results of the survey will be used for researcher’s personal further enhancement on the research.

Research survey tool. A survey questionnaire consisting of 12 yes/no questions is used as a tool.

Results. According to survey results, the level of the use of hedges in speech is confirmed by both man and women. In his research, Lakoff researches the specifics of women’s speech in the process of using “hedges”, i.e. speech “obstacles” such as *sort of, I mean, actually, really, well* he noted that it can be

found more often than men. In addition, the survey results show that the use of the “taboo” words and “intensifiers” used by both genders are different.

Conclusion. In conclusion, it can be said that human beings use language to achieve a specific goal that reflects personal or social values, and the limitation of language use due to social environment mainly causes gender difference. Social context is an important link between gender and language. The interlocutor’s speech during the dialogue also differs with the role played by people in the social environment.

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THE CONCEPT OF A LINGUISTIC CORPUS

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ANNOTATION: *Corpus linguistics is a field of linguistics concerned with the creation and improvement of text corpora, as well as their use as a tool for linguistic research.*

KEY WORDS: *linguistic corpus, written texts, comparison of languages, terminological and phraseological phrases, representativeness.*

INTRODUCTION

Before talking about corpus linguistics, it is necessary to define the very concept of a linguistic corpus. In English it will be linguistic corpus or text corpus,

plural linguistic corpora (corpuses is used less frequently). There are quite a few definitions that agree on one thing: a corpus is “a certain philological object.”

Here are some definitions:

- a corpus is a verbal unity organized in a certain way, the elements of which are texts or specially selected excerpts from texts;
- a corpus is a set of linguistic data from a particular language in the form of recorded utterances or written texts, available for analysis;
- a corpus is a set of natural texts in any language, oral or written, which is stored electronically and allows computerized searching;
- perhaps the most comprehensive definition: a corpus is a collection of text excerpts in electronic form, selected according to external criteria in order to most fully represent a language or variation of a language. Functions as a data source for linguistic research. (John Sinclair)

Here are examples of cases:

- texts by a specific writer or writers;
- texts for a specific decade or century;
- modern texts on a certain topic;
- modern texts that adequately represent the language or society.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY

One of the definitions stated that a corpus can be either oral or written. In general, there is an opinion that linguistic corpora are neither oral, nor written, nor printed, but represent the fourth texture of speech - texts on machine media - the same digital text. However, one can argue with this view.

It is clear that a corpus is a set of texts with which you can do something. But what can the body do? The answer may seem surprising: the body itself cannot do anything. But we can use special software to search the corpus for something and do some calculations. What can we look for? First of all, these are words and phrases that have cultural or linguistic significance.

In addition, the subject of the search may be any marks that you have added to the corpus, for example, the mark “noun”.

Here are examples of what a corpus search can give us:

- all uses of the selected word in its immediate context;
- variations and consistency in the use of vocabulary;
- words that most often appear next to the selected word;
- the most important differences between the two sets of texts;
- how a particular writer uses words and phrases;
- intertextuality: the meaning of a word as the sum of its uses;
- hidden (potential) models of vocabulary use;
- development of concepts over time;
- comparison of languages.

DISCUSSION AND RESULTS

In particular, the most relevant for us, as translators, is the ability to search for contexts of words that have several translation equivalents, as well as the selection of equivalents of terminological and phraseological phrases in parallel corpora, which we will discuss in the following lectures.

The most important property of a corpus is representativeness, that is, the ability to reflect all the properties of the problem area. Representativeness is determined by phonetic, morphological, syntactic and stylistic parameters of the corpus. It is representativeness that distinguishes a corpus from a simple set of texts. Last but not least, representativeness depends on the size of the case.

The reason for the recent increase in interest in corpus research is the advent of computers, which have made it possible to process huge amounts of text. In addition, more and more scientists are inclined to believe that introspection as a method of language learning is not always adequate, and to rely more scientifically on natural data. Well-known corpus linguists Tony McEnnery and Andrew Wilson write that we need to use empirics and introspection, both artificial and natural data. Corpus linguistics in no way denies the value and

necessity of speech data not presented in corpus form. In addition, it is impossible to extract all possible linguistic conclusions from a corpus of texts, that is, the corpus of texts is not self-sufficient.

Thus, Chafe believes that a corpus linguist should not only describe the phenomena of language, but also try to explain them. In general, the focus of corpus linguistics is the linguistic personality, that is, its speech activity, mass communication, and the problem of its description.

Corpus linguistics	Traditional linguistics
Focus on speech learning	Focus on language learning
The goal is to describe the language as it manifested itself in speech, presented in the form of a specially selected corpus of texts.	The goal is to describe and explain the language
In his research he relies on data from a text corpus.	In his research he relies on data from a text corpus.
In his research he relies on data from a text corpus.	Prefers quantitative methods Prefers qualitative methods
Sees himself as part of a tradition based on empirical methods	Sees himself as part of a tradition based on rationalistic methods
The text is considered as some physical entity	The text is considered as some abstraction
Compilation of grammar of specific languages	Study of language universals
The focus is on form	The focus is not only on form, but also on content
Views texts from a global perspective	Views texts from a local perspective

Focuses its attention on the broadest possible view of the text, unrestricted by any dogma	Analyzes some specific, artificially limited problem area
In its conclusions it relies on observation of speech activity, manifested in the form of texts.	It relies on intuition in the selection of speech material, in the selection of empirical materials of its research
Often uses probabilistic methods and statistics for primary processing of speech material	Prefers logical reasoning

CONCLUSION

In conclusion a corpus in linguistics is a collection of texts collected into a single whole according to certain criteria corresponding to a specific research task and reflecting a particular area of language use. In modern linguistics, a corpus usually means a corpus of texts in electronic form. After all, it was the use of computer technology that transformed the corpus from one of the methods of working with language material into a convenient and effective research tool, and corpus linguistics into an independent discipline.

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**INGLIZCHA VA O'ZBEKCHA DINIY MATNLAR TARJIMA
TAHLILIDA ISLOMIY TERMINLAR--PAYG'AMBARLAR ISMLARI
TARJIMATADQIQI**

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Abstract

This article intends to analyze religious terms, especially nominative nouns: Prophets' names both in Uzbek and English languages and gives a clear understanding of translation analysis through comparing the ways of translation and finding differences in results of counted terms within religious texts. The main aim of this article is finding novelty while translating and interpreting Prophets' names.

Annotatsiya

Bu maqola ingliz va o'zbek tillarida diniy matnlar tahlilini olib borishga, shuningdek diniy manbalarda ismi keltririlgan payg'ambarlar ismlarining--atoqli otlarning 2 til doirasida tarjima jarayoni tahlili va unda ishlatilgan tarjima usullarini tushunish va izlashga qaratilgan. Maqolaning asosiy maqsadi tilshunos sifatida diniy terminlarning xususan atoqli otlarning tarjimada ahamiyat berilmagan jihatlarini ochib berib , yangiligiga xizmat ko'rsatishdir

Аннотация

Целью этой статьи является анализ религиозных текстов как на узбекском, так и на английском языках, и она направлено на изучение и анализ способов перевода собственные имена пророков данных в

религиозных книгах. Основной целью статьи считается открытие и объяснение в особенности религиозных терминов особенно собственных имен.

Key words: Corpus, corpus linguistics, religious terms, nominative words, Prophets' names, transformation types

Kalit so'zlar: Korpus, korpus lingvistikasi, diniy atamalar, so'zlar chastotasi, diniy terminlar, atoqli otlar, payg'ambarlar ismlari

Ключевые слова: Корпус, корпусная лингвистика, религиозные термины, религиозные термины,

Kirish

Mamlakatimiz miqyosida hozirgi kunga kelib xorijiy tillarning o'rganilishi, undagi tadqiqotlarning olib borilishi, tillar tahlili, qiyoslanilishi, tarjimasi va tildagi terminlarni tushunish juda ham ahamiyatlidir. Ayniqsa ingliz-o'zbek tillari Korpusini yaratishda diniy terminlar ichida atoqli otlarning tarjimadagi ahamiyati beqiyosdir. Undagi olib borilgan tadqiqotlar korpus foydalanuvchilari uchun ham ayniqsa nafli bo'lar edi agar diniy terminlar korpusida Qur'oni Karimda, Hadislarda va boshqa diniy manbalarda zikri keltrilgan Payg'ambarlar ismlari tarjimasi o'rganilsa.

Shunday qilib korpus yaratishda nega aynan bizga diniy atamalar ichida atoqli otlarni o'rganish zarur degan savol tug'ulishi tabiiydir. Bu savolning yechimi esa quyidagicha javob bo'la olardi

- Korpus yordamida yangi tildagi matnlarda uchragan so'zlarning tahlili olib borish mumkin
- Shuningdek eng dolzarb va ko'p ishlatiladigan so'zlarning diniy terminlar lug'atini yaratishda ham bevosita xizmat qiladi
- Hamda eng zamonaviy ingliz tiliga arab tilidan kirib kelayotgan so'zlarning ayniqsa atoqli otlarning yangiligini, o'zlashma va tubdan o'zgargan so'zlar ekanligini ham ko'rsatib beradi.

Biz bilamizki, hozirgacha O'zbekistonda bir necha olimlar Korpus sohasida o'zlarining keng tadqiqotlarini olib borganlar, Jumladan: Raupova L., Elov B., Abjalova M., Alayev R. O'zbek tilining ta'limiy korpusi va uning imkoniyatlari bo'yicha, Zaxarov V., Mengliyev B., Xamroyeva Sh. Korpus lingvistikasi: korpus tuzish va undan foydalanish borasida o'quv qo'llanma va bir necha ishlar olib borilgan.

Biroq bularning deyarli ko'pchiligi Payg'ambarlar ismlari tarjimasiga bag'ishlanmagan. Shu sababdan ham bu maqoladagi tarjimasiga keltirilgan atoqli otlar tadqiqot ishining yangiligini ko'rsatib beradi

Metodlar

Ushbu maqolada, solishtirish (Comparative), Observation & Corpus analysis (Kuzatish tahlil) metodlari qo'llanildi.

Discussion

Agar diniy asarlardagi terminlar tahlilini payg'ambarlar ismlarining to'g'ri tarjimasiga bilan tushunilsa maqsadga muvofiq bo'lar edi. Chunki ba'zi bir ismlar tarjima jarayonida e'tibordan chetda qolib ketilishi mumkin.

Masalan: **John** --*Yahyo alayhissalom*

Ko'pchilik Yahyo alayhissalomning bu ismlarini tarjimada payqamasligi mumkin. Biroq diniy matnlar xususan tarjimonlar tomonidan ingliz tiliga tarjima qilingan Qur'on kitobi ham bu ismni John deb tarjima qilinishini ko'rsatib beradi.

Bundan tashqari Qur'onda zikri kelgan payg'ambarlar ismlarini **Talal Itani** va boshqa tarjimonlar tomonidan quyidagicha tarjima qilinganligining guvohi bo'lishimiz mumkin:

- David --Dovud alayhissalom
- Jesus--Iso alayhissalom 6:85
- Isaac--Is'hoq alayhissalom

- Jacob--Yoqub alayhissalom 6:84
- Noah--Nuh alayhissalom 6:84
- Ishmael--Ismoil alayhissalom 6:86
- Elijah--Yas'a alayhissalom 6:86
- Jonah--Yunus alayhissalom 10-Yunus surasida
- Joseph-Yusuf alayhissalom
- Abraham--Ibrohim alayhissalom
- Moses--Musso alayhissalom 6:154
- Shuaib--Shuayb alayhissalom 7:88/90
- Luqman--Luqmon alayhissalom
- Zechariah-- Zakariyo alayhissalom

Xulosa

Ushbu mavzu tadqiqi olib borilishi davomida quyidagi yangiliklar aniqlandi:

- A. Ingliz va o'zbek tillari korpusini yaratishda bizga diniy atamalar ayniqsa atoqli otlar tarjimasi muhim rol o'ynashi juda ham ahamiyatli
- B. Hozirgacha diniy atamalar uchun ingliz-o'zbek tillari uchun korpus tahlili va tadqiqi bo'yicha O'zbekistonda ozchilik tomonidan tadqiqot olib borilganligi
- C. Yahyo alayhissalom ismlari --to'laligicha tarjimada o'zgarganligi -- John--"replacement" transformation
- D. Shuaib-Shuayb alayhissalom--Transcription Transformation
- E. Elijah-Yas'a alayhissalom--replacement va hokazo

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INGLIZ VA O'ZBEK KORPUSLARINING O'ZIGA XOS XUSUSIYATLARI

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada Inglizcha va o'zbekcha korpuslar va ularning hajmi , ularda foydalanilgan adabiyot turlari , so'z ko'lamini, foydalanuvchiga taqdim eta oladigan imkoniyatlari haqida so'z boradi va bu ma'lumotlar ularni bir biridan farqini va ko'lamini aniqlab olishga yordam beradi. Shuningdek korpus lingvistikasi va uning ahamiyati , bugungi kunda tutgan o'rni haqida ham tegishli ma'lumotlar berilgan.

Annotation: This article provides information about English and Uzbek corpora and their size, the types of literature used in them, the scope of words, the possibilities they can provide to the users, and this information defines their difference and scope. It helps to get relevant information about corpus linguistics, its importance and its place today.

Аннотация: В данной статье рассказывается об английских и узбекских корпусах и их размере, видах используемой в них литературы, объёме слов, возможностях, которые они могут предоставить пользователю, и эта информация определяет их различие и объём. Также дается актуальная информация о корпусной лингвистике, ее значении и месте сегодня

Kalit so'zlar: elektron lug'at , til korpusi, milliy korpus, lingvistika, token qidiruv, lingvodidaktika, axbarot texnologiyalari

Kirish

Bugungi kunda jadal rivojlanib borayotgan axborot texnologiyalari dunyo tillarinig birmuncha imkoniyatlaridan foydalanish borasida misli ko'rinmagan imkoniyatlar eshigini ochdi. Zamonaviy elektron lug'atlar buning yaqqol misoli bo'lib , ularni tuzish va ulardan foydalanish birmuncha til imkoniyatlarini egallashda samarador bo'lsa, til korpuslarining vazifasi , samaradorligi , bu borada tutgan o'rni beqiyos bo'lib kelmoqda. Ma'lumki, kompyuter texnologiyalarining korpus tilshunosligida qo'llanilishi natijasida til korpuslari

asosida soʻzning qoʻllanish davri va chastotasini aniqlash, terminologiya sohasini rivojlantirish, gap qurilishini oʻrganish va tahlil qilish, tarjima dasturlari uchun n-tilli baza yaratish, uslubiyatni oʻrganish, elektron lingvodidaktikani rivojlantirish, ayniqsa, turli lugʻatlarni yaratish imkoniyatlari kitoblardan avtomat jarayoniga oʻtdi va koʻplab qulayliklarni yuzaga keltirdi.

ADABIYOTLAR TAHLILI VA METODLAR

Yuqorida taʼkidlab oʻtganimizdek, elektron lugʻatlarni yaratishda til korpuslari kerakli soha terminalogiyasida birlamchi vosita boʻlib xizmat qiladi. Shuningdek, ikki yoki koʻp tilli parallel korpuslarning tarjima bazasi yordamida tarjimon lugʻatlari [Boliang Zhang 2020], avtomatik tarjima dasturlarining lingvistik bazalarini shakllantirishda yirik resurs vazifasini bajaradi. Qisqa qilib aytganda, muayyan tilning milliy korpusi -bu shu tilning koʻp funksiyali va maqsadli korpusidir. Masalan “uzbekcorpora” Oʻzbek tilining milliy korpusi , Oʻzbek tilining taʼlimiy korpusi , Oʻzbek tili korpusi buning yaqqol misolidir. Oʻzbek tilining milliy korpusi Oʻzbekiston Respublikasi innovasiya vazirligining 2021 yilgi 30-turdagi “Oʻzbek tilining milliy korpusini loyihalash va dasturiy majmua ishlab chiqish” (2020-2022) mavzusidagi amaliy loyiha doirasida bajarilgan. Oʻrnatilgan tartibda oʻtkazilgan tanlov natijalari boʻyicha ushbu loyihani bajarish uchun Oʻzbekiston Respublikasi Vazirlar Mahkamasi huzuridagi Oʻzbek tilini rivojlantirish jamgʻarmasi bilan shartnoma tuzilgan. Bu korpus 6 boʻlimdan iborat boʻlib, bu boʻlimlar foydalanuvchiga loyiha haqida maʼlumotlar berib cheklanmasdan , korpusdagi mavjud matnlarning statistik va konkordans tahlillarini beradi. Shuningdek korpusda soʻzlar matnda qanday holatda uchragan boʻlsa, shu holatda keltirilgan va kompyuter yordamida ularni statistik jihatdan ishlashning imkoni paydo boʻldi. Masalan : Alpomish dostonining Fozil Yoʻldosh oʻgʻli variantining elektron lugʻati olingan . Doston MS Word dasturida tayyorlangan 623 Kb hajmli *.txt formatdagi fayldan iborat boʻlib , dostonning ushbu varianti dastur yordamida qayta ishlangan soʻng unda

jami 14413ta soʻz ishlatilgan va ularning qoʻllanilishi 82106 soʻzni tashkil qilgan. Elektron lugʻatda 82106ta birlik hosil boʻlgan. Oʻzbek tilining milliy korpusi foydalanuvchiga maʼlum bir soʻzning grammatik tavsifi , leksik maʼnosi va soʻzning ishlatilish oʻrinlari va turli birikmalar bilan birikish holatlarini ochib koʻrsatib beradi.

NATIJALAR VA MUNOZARA

Shuni taʼkidlash oʻrinliki, har qanday korpus bazasida tilning barcha uslublariga mansub oʻta katta hajmdagi matnlarning boʻlishi , matnlarning lingvistik, morfologik va sintaktik jihatdan teglanishi, korpusning meta-maʼlumotlari mavjud boʻlishi zaruriy talablardan hisoblanadi. Mazkur talablar Oʻzbek tilining milliy korpusi bilan bir qatorda Oʻzbek tilining taʼlimiy korpusida ham oʻz aksini topgan . Bu korpus, asosan, taʼlim jarayonida til oʻrgatish taʼlim jarayonida turli amaliy mashgʻulotlarni bajarish, tadqiqot jarayonida matn elementlaridan foydalanish, taʼlimga oid fan sohalari terminologiyasini shakllantirish kabi masalalarda asosiy vosita hisoblanadi. Bir necha yillar davomida olib borilgan tadqiqotlar va 2020-2021-yillardagi amaliy saʼy-harakatlar natijasida Toshkent davlat oʻzbek tili va adabiyoti universiteti Kompyuter lingvistikasi va raqamli texnologiyalar hamda Amaliy tilshunoslik va lingvodidaktika kafedralari hamkorligida AM-FZ-201908172 raqamli “Oʻzbek tilining taʼlimiy korpusini yaratish” mavzusidagi amaliy loyiha doirasida OʻZBEK TILINING TAʼLIMIY KORPUSI yaratildi. Bugungi kunda mazkur korpusda 1) mosfoanalizator (avtomatik morfologik tahlil); 2) soʻz(shakl)ni boʻgʻinlarga ajratish; 4) izoh (lar)ini taqdim etish; 5) antonimlarini koʻrsatish; 6) sinonimizator (qidiruvga yozilgan soʻzga uning maʼnodoshlarini taqdim etish dasturi); 7) soʻzning talaffuzdosh (paronim)ini uning izohi bilan berish; 8) qidiruvga berilgan soʻz bilan bogʻliq “Ona tili qomusiy lugʻati”dan maʼlumotlarni taqdim etish; 9) qidiruvga berilgan soʻz qatnashgan iboralarni koʻrsatish; 10) uning turli xususiyatlari boʻyicha darajalanish qatorini namoyish etish

imkoniyatlari mavjud. Ta'lim jarayonida ta'limiy korpusdan foydalanish o'quvchiga tilni egallashning professional-relevant aspektlarini yuzaga chiqarish imkonini yaratadi. Masalan, til kurslarida bo'lajak tarjimonning e'tiborni leksik birliklarga, huquqshunosda esa terminologiyaga qaratish ko'nikmasini shakllantiradi. Ta'limiy korpus talaba e'tiborini matndagi birlikni bog'lab turuvchi vositani farqlashga ham qaratadi. Shunday yo'l bilan korpus tilni o'rganuvchi ta'lim oluvchilar guruhiga kasbga yo'naltirilgan ta'limda asosiy omil sanalgan differensial yondashuvni qo'llashga zamin yaratadi.

Inglizcha korpuslar haqida so'z yuritganimizda bu sohada naqadar keng qamrovli ishlar olib borilganiga guvoh bo'lishimiz mumkin. Bir qancha inglizcha korpuslar mavjud bo'lib ularning har biri o'z tarixi, o'ziga xos afzalliklariga egaligi bilan foydalanuvchiga har tomonlama mukammal ishlash imkonini beradi. Britaniya milliy korpusi(BNC) ni nazarda tutadigan bo'lsak, bu korpus 20- asrning 2-qismida og'izaki nutqni o'stirish va il imkoniyatlarida yanada kengroq foydalanish uchun yaratilgan. Korpusning yuz million so'zdan iborat ekanligi uning maqsadga qanchalik muvofiq ekanligini ko'rsatib beradi. Korpus 10% og'izaki va 90% yozma manbalardan iborat bo'lib, yozma qismi turli mintaqaviy gazeta va jurnallar, akademik kitoblar, ilmiy va ommabop jurnallardan ko'chirmalar va nashr etilgan va etilmagan xatlardan iborat bo'lsa, og'izaki qismi yozilmagan norasmiy suhbatlarning ortografik transkripsiyalardan, yosh izlanuvchilarning demografik jihatdan muvozanatli tarzda yozib olingan matnlari, og'izaki nutq namunalari va telefon, radio so'zlashuvlaridan yozib olinganligi e'tirof etilgan. Britaniya milliy korpusi monolingual bo'lishiga qaramay unda international so'zlarni ham uchratish mumkin. Shu bilan bir qatorda korpus juda ko'p turli uslublar va navlarni o'z ichiga oladi va biron bir mavzu sohasi, janr yoki registr bilan cheklanmaydi.

XULOSA:

Xulosa qilib aytganda , korpus lingvistikasi bugungi kunda sodir bo'layotgan bir qancha muammolarni hal qilishda salmoqli o'ringa ega. Inglizcha va o'zbekcha korpuslar funksional va tuzilish jihatdan bir biridan farq qilsada , o'zining xususiyatlari va o'ziga xosligi bilan ajralib tursada, lingvistik yuksalishga xizmat qiladi va foydalanuvchiga bir qator qulayliklar taqdim etadi. Shuni ta'kidlash joizki, korpusdagi so'zlar ro'yxatini yaratish oson va tez amalga oshirilmasada , natijalar har doim qiziqarli bo'ladi.

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TWO GROUPS OF COSMONYMS

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ABSTRACT: *This article talks about the features of the formation of cosmonyms and the linguists' different approaches to the terminology of celestial bodies. The ancient ancestors of the peoples of Central Asia had astrological experiences based on observing the position of the planets and stars in the sky and the direction of movement in the sky.*

KEYWORDS: *onomastics, cosmonym, celestial objects, ancestors, proper name, geographical name*

Linguistic analysis of cosmonyms in the Uzbek language can be divided into two groups with different characteristics. The first group is also common to most of the Turkic languages made based on the internal possibilities of our language or the Uzbek people and their close socio-political and cultural relations with other peoples' literary language and during historical development cosmonyms that are firmly rooted in the lexicon of dialects. The second group consists of cosmonyms that entered the Uzbek language only as a result of the development of science. An important difference between them is defined by the fact that the creator of cosmonyms in folk dialects and literary language is the people, and the creator of the second group of cosmonyms is a specific person or persons. Yu.A. Karpenko stated that the author who named the space object, the fact that the time and place of the name are given emphasizes that this is a common feature of the group.¹

In the existing scientific literature, we observe that this group of cosmonyms is studied under the term scientific cosmonyms. But in Uzbek, the term scientific cosmonyms causes some discomfort. First of all, in the works created by our ancestors and which are unique scientific sources of world astronomy, the cosmic objects are mostly named in the same way as in today's literary language and folk dialects. For example, let's pay attention to the opinions of Abu Rayhan Beruni about the name of the star Surayyo: "Surayyo is six stars that are gathered, and it

¹ Карпенко Ю.А. Названия звездного неба. М., 1985. С.12.

is actually taken from “Sarva”. “Sarva” means “gather” and “many”.² According to some, the reason why the stars are called by this name is that when they set, it rained and “sarva”, that means wealth, was created. It seems that the name of the constellation “Savr” is used in the same form and content both in scientific literature and in folk traditions. We observe this situation in the works of the leading representatives of world astronomy such as al-Battani, al-Farghani, al-Khorazmi, Abulvafa Buzhoni, Abu Mahmud Khojandi, Abdurrahman al-Sufi, Umar Khayyam, Mirza Ulughbek, Qazizada Rumi, and Ali Kushchi.

Therefore, it is logically unreasonable not to include them among scientific cosmonyms or, on the contrary, not to consider the names of spatial bodies used in their scientific works among the cosmonyms of folk languages and dialects.³ In general, how they are used cannot be the main criteria for dividing the cosmonyms into groups such as folk language dialectal cosmonyms and scientific cosmonyms. Secondly, classifying the names of heavenly bodies in this way leads to the idea that the names of spatial bodies, which are not included in the list of scientific cosmonyms, are unscientific. To overcome such inconveniences and to fully express the main lexical-semantic features of this group of cosmonyms, we decided to study them under the term neocosmonym.

The fact that it is the name of a spatial body is the only common feature of folk cosmonyms and neocosmonyms, and the specific aspects of neocosmonyms are more clearly visible when they are compared with folk cosmonyms. In particular, the spatial bodies representing these two groups differ sharply from each other in their important aspects. More specifically, folk cosmonyms refer only to objects in space visible to the human eye, while neocosmonyms refer only to objects that can be seen with optical observation instruments. For example,

² Абу Райхон Беруний. Хикматлар. Тошкент, 1973. 31-бет.

³ Primov A.I. O‘zbek tili kosmonimlarining lisoniy xususiyatlari: f.f.n. dis. avtoref. Toshkent, 2009.

while all the languages of the world have space names expressing the concept of the Moon, the names that express the crater and other parts of the surface of the moon did not exist before the creation of modern optical observation devices.

For example, as a result of giving the name of the Earth's mountains to the mountains on the Moon, such names as the Alps and the Caucasus Mountains, the Carpathian Mountains, and the Altai Mountains appeared; Names of the lunar surface that determine the location of the object arose: Central Gulf, Marginal Sea; On the back side of the moon is the Eastern Sea, the Southern Sea; names dedicated to specific people or cities: Humboldt Sea, Smith Sea, Struve Sea, Moscow Sea, etc.

There are also craters on the Moon named after philosophers and scientists who became famous for their great discoveries, including archaeologists Schliemann and Evans, linguists such as Champollion, who discovered the secrets of ancient Egyptian writing, and Ventris, who read the Cretan-Mycenaean script.

Folk names develop along with the national language. Changes in them occur without any agreement and instructions according to the nature of the language. The ranks of neocosmonyms expand based on information released to the scientific community as a result of special agreements by major astronomical organizations, as in artificial languages such as Esperanto.

It is correct to conclude that the main factor in dividing space names into two groups in this way is not what kind of cosmic body they represent, but whether they represent a cosmic object that can be observed by the human eye or not. Because the main factor in this regard is the cosmic body that the name represents, let's say, all the names of the planets should be included in the series of folk cosmonyms or neocosmonyms. However, the names of planets such as Venus (Zukhra), and Mars (Mirrix, Bahrom) are popular cosmonyms, and the names of the planets Uranus, Neptune, and Pluto are neocosmonyms. If we take into account that the next three planets are not visible to the human eye, but were

discovered through special optical devices, our opinion becomes clearer. At the same time, it should be noted that in neocosmonyms, which spatial object the name represents is one of the important signs. This is, of course, because those regions of the universe cannot be seen by the human eye. Therefore, it is appropriate to research neocosmonyms by dividing them into types such as names of planets and their satellites (planets discovered with optical devices), names of stars and constellations, names of asteroids, names of comets, names of meteoroids, names of the surface of the moon (selenonyms).

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ATOQLI OTLAR TARJIMASIDA TRANSLITERATSIYA VA TRANSKRIPTSIYA.

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada atoqli otlar tarjimasida yuzaga keladigan qiyinchiliklar va ularni transformatsiyalar yordamida hal qilish usullari yoritilgan.

Ayniqsa transliteratsiya va transkripsiya texnikasidan foydalanish usullari atroflicha tahlil qilingan.

Asosiy tushunchalar: atoqli otlar, transliteratsiya, transkripsiya., tushirib qoldirish, morfologik moslashuv;

Atoqli otlarni tarjima qilishga to‘g‘ri kelganda bu jarayonni qanchalik qiyin va mas‘uliyatli ekanligini har bir tarjimon yaxshi his qiladi. Afsuski hali ham “atoqli otlar hech qachon tarjima qilinmaydi” degan fikr ko‘pchilik ongida chuqur ildiz otgan. Shunga qaramay tarjimonlar bu turdagi so‘zlarni tarjima qilishganda turli xildagi tarjima uslublaridan foydalanganligiga guvoh bo‘lamiz. Bularga tarjima qilmaslik, mo‘ljaldagi tilga so‘zni transkripsiya yoki transliteratsiya asosida olib o‘tish, mo‘ljaldagi tilga morfologik moslashuv, madaniy moslashuvlar misol bo‘lishi mumkin. Shuni ta’kidlash lozimki, tarjimonlar har doim ham atoqli otlarni tarjima qilayotganda bir xil texnikani ishlatmaydilar. Shunday qilib, atoqli otlarning tarjimasi arziyas masala emas, aksincha, juda nozik qaror qabul qilish jarayonini o‘z ichiga olishi mumkin, bu esa tarjimon tomonidan uni mo‘ljaldagii tilga tarjima qilishdan oldin atoqli otning ma’nolarini diqqat bilan ko‘rib chiqishni talab qiladi. Berilgan ot turdoshmi yoki atoqlimi, qaror qabul qilish har doim ham oson emas. Har ikki turdagi otni ifodalashi mumkin bo‘lgan holatlar mavjud. Masalan, ma’lum bir xususiyatga ishora qiluvchi turdosh ot noyob ma’lumotga ega bo‘lgan atoqli otga aylanishi mumkin. Metaforik qo‘llaniladigan shaxsiy atoqli otlar turdosh otlarga aylanishi mumkin: U o‘zini Napoleon deb hisoblaydi.

Atoqli otlar bir qancha usullar bilan tarjima qilinishi mumkin. Birinchidan, atoqli otlar manba matndan butunligicha olib o‘tilishi mumkin (tarjima qilinayotgan tilning xususiyatlariga qarab transliteratsiya yoki transkripsiya asosida). Ikkinchidan, uni qisman manba tilidan olib o‘tish va qisman tarjima qilish mumkin. Uchinchidan, uni mo‘ljaldagi tilga u yoki bu nomlar bilan almashtirish mumkin. Nihoyat, u butunlay tushirib qoldirilishi mumkin. Sanab o‘tilgan usullardan birinchi usul haqida atroflicha fikr yuritamiz.

Tarjima transkripsiyasini - manba so'zining tarjima tiliga fonetik taqlidi bilan yuzaga keluvchi formal rekonstruktsiya deb atash mumkin. Tarjimaning yana bir usuli transliteratsiya - tarjima tilining alifbosi bilan asl leksik birliklarini, manba so'z shakliga taqlidan qayta yaratish jarayonidir. Boshqacha qilib aytganda, transkripsiya yoki transliteratsiya (to'liq yoki qisman), manba tilidagi voqelikni ifodalobchi so'zni to'g'ridan to'g'ri tarjima qilinayotgan mo'ljaldagi tilga olib o'tishdir, bunda manba tildagi so'z uning yozilishi asosida yoki talaffuzi asosida o'zlashtiriladi. Muassasalarning nomlari haqida gap ketganda, ayniqsa, lavozimlar, muayyan mamlakat uchun xos, ya'ni ijtimoiy-siyosiy hayotini qamrab oluvchi so'zlar tarjima qilinayotganda transliteratsiya tez-tez ishlatiladi. Adabiy tarjimada transliteratsiya usuli keng tarqalgan bo'lib, ayniqsa badiiy, jurnalistik, ilmiy asarlarda sezilarli iz qoldirgan. Masalan, Britaniya ijtimoiy hayoti bilan bog'liq so'zlar; "Mis", "Ser", "mayor" va boshqalar.

Boshqa tilga tarjima qilib bo'lmaydigan so'z yo'q, hech bo'lmaganda so'zni tavsiflab tarjima qilish mumkin. Ammo manba tildagi tushunchaning leksik jihatdan aniq ma'nosini bildirish kerak bo'lganda va shu bilan bir vaqtda mo'ljaldagi tilda shu tushunchaning aniq ekvivalenti bo'lmaganda transliteratsiya yordamga keladi.

Transliteratsiya va transkripsiya atoqli otlar, xalqlar va qabilalarning nomlari, geografik joy nomlari, biznes muassasalari nomlari, kompaniyalar, firmalar, davriy nashriyotlar nomlari, sport jamoalari nomlari, rok-musiqachilari guruhi nomlari, madaniy inshootlar va boshqalarni tarjima qilish uchun ishlatiladi. Ushbu nomlarning katta qismi transkripsiya, kamdan-kam hollarda, transliteratsiya yordamida tarjima qilinadi: Hollywood [JDS 5] [5] - Hollywood [Per. 241] [6] Pencey [J.D.S. 5] - Pensi [Per. 241] Bank of London - London Banki

Minnesota-Minnesota Wall Street Journal - Wall Street Jurnal

Transkripsiyadan fantastik mavjudotlarning nomlarini tarjima qilishda ham foydalaniladi: bunda folklor adabiyot nazarda tutiladi:

Hobbit - The Hobbit, goblin – goblin. [Kazakova, b. 75]

Xorijiy tilda uchraydigan atoqli otlar - haqiqiy yoki xayoliy shaxslarning ismlari bo'lsin va geografik nomlarni tarjima qilishda eng muhimi tarjimaning tovush dizayni masalasidir va shunga mos ravishda - ularning yozuvi ham katta rol o'ynaydi. Ikki til tizimdagi fonetik va ularning fonemalaridagi farqlar qanchalik katta bo'lsa, shunchalik hal qilinishi kerak bo'lgan savol ham katta bo'lib turadi.

Agar har ikkala tilda ham (masalan, G'arbiy roman tillari, nemis va finno-ugor tillarida) alifboning umumiy o'xshash tizimi mavjud bo'lsa, tarjimadagi nomlar va asl matnlar umumiy ko'rinishidagi tovushni rad etib, faqat ularning yozuvini aniq takrorlash asosida tarjimaga erishiladi (transliteratsiya). Albatta, ikki til o'rtasida sezilarli fonetik farqlar bo'lsa (masalan, ingliz va arab tillari o'rtasida) ularning fonetik tomonini faqat qisman va shartli ravishda tarjima qilish mumkin va bunda odatda tovush va yozuvni mo'ljaldagi tilga olib o'tish sodir bo'ladi.

Odatiy atoqli otlar (shaharlar, daryolar, mashhur tarixiy shaxslar), ya'ni umumiy foydalaniladigan ismlar haqida gap ketganda, tarjimon an'anaga ko'ra yo'l tutadi - haqiqiy tovushga yaqinlashishga harakat qiladi. Ba'zan an'anaviy imlo chet tilidagi nomning fonetik shakliga etarlicha yaqin bo'ladi, masalan: "Shiller", "Bayron", "Dante", "Brandenburg" va shunga o'xshash.

Gohida mavjud bo'lgan amaliyotda atoqli otlarni tarjima qilishda transkripsiya yoki transliteratsiya ko'pincha etarli emas: tegishli nom ramziy funktsiya bajarsa, noyob ob'ektning nomi bo'lsa, masalan, laqablar - bu o'ziga xos nom chunki u ob'ektning individual xususiyatlarini va xarakterini aks ettiradi. Bunday hollarda transkripsiyadan tashqari semantik tarjimaning kombinatsiyasi yordamga keladi.

Masalan, adabiyotda V. S. Moemning (W. S. Maugham) "Teatr" romani rus tiliga "Aktyorlar" deb tarjima qilinganligi romandagi qahramonlarning asosiy xususiyatlarini ochib berishga yordam bergan.

Turli mamlakatlardagi ta'lim muassasalari nomlarini tarjima qilishda ham ba'zi muammolar paydo bo'lishi mumkin. Shunday qilib, Amerika ta'lim tizimida ba'zi so'zlar turli xil ta'lim muassasalari uchun keng qo'llaniladi, bu biznikidan mutlaqo

farq qiladi. Masalan, Institut so'zi oliy ta'lim muassasasini yoki tadqiqot yoki ma'muriy idoralarni ifodalash uchun ishlatiladi, ingliz tilida so'zlashadigan mamlakatlarda institut so'zi faqat ikkinchi ma'noda ishlatiladi va shuning uchun har doim ham asosiy kontseptsiyani bildirishi qiyin bo'ladi.

Whooton School [JDS 20] – Huton Maktabi [Per. 250]

Xulosa qilib aytganda, atoqli otlarni tarjimada bir nechta usullar bilan ifodalash mumkin: Ularni manba matnidan o'zgarishsiz olib kirish mumkin; Ularni mo'ljaldagi tilning fonologik / grafaologik tizimiga mos kelishi uchun o'zgartirish mumkin; Ular mo'ljaldagi o'quvchiga notanish dunyo bilimi bo'lsa, tushuntirish yo'li bilan kontekst kengaytirilishi mumkin; Ba'zan ular butunlay tashlab ketilishi mumkin. Bunda tarjimon bu so'zni asosiy voqelikka aloqasi yo'qligi tufayli shu uslubni qo'llaydi.

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THE PROBLEM OF LINGUISTIC DIFFERENCES BETWEEN THE ORIGINAL TEXT AND THE TRANSLATED TEXT

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Abstract: In modern research, text is considered as the basic unit of communication, possessing integrity and coherence. A literary text occupies a special place in text typology, since it simultaneously reflects both the objective world and the author's vision of reality. The content, meaning and functions of a literary text are determined by the intention of the author-addressee, and its interpretation depends on the goals and background knowledge of the reader-addressee.

Key words: interlingual and intercultural communication, equivalence and adequacy, discourse, cohesion and coherence, functionally equivalent, grammatical substitution.

Translation is a complex process of interlingual and intercultural communication, the basic categories of which are equivalence and adequacy.

In the modern theory of translation studies, there is no single definition of the relationship between these two categories: some linguists consider them identical, others believe that equivalence absorbs adequacy and vice versa.

A translation is functionally equivalent to the original, provided that it comprehensively conveys the content of the source text, the author's intentions and the meanings relevant to the original communicative situation.

For a functionally equivalent translation, equivalent relations at the lexical-semantic and grammaticosyntactic levels are not enough: it requires reliance on the communicative-pragmatic characteristics of the source text.

The category of functional equivalence covers correspondences at the lexical-grammatical and communicative-pragmatic levels, i.e. describes linguistic and speech correspondences, thereby making the category of adequacy redundant.

A text is a relatively integral linguistic work, characterized by modality, purposefulness, belonging to a certain functional style, reflecting regional and social variations of the language.

A literary text is the realization of the author's picture of the world, expressed using purposefully selected and sequentially arranged linguistic means. The reader's interpretation of a literary text depends on socio-cultural factors.

Discourse is the result of the actualization of language taking into account extralinguistic factors. The opposition text - discourse is based on the opposition language - speech, since the text is the main linguistic unit, and discourse is a speech work.

The main formal textual categories include cohesion and coherence, which are largely determined by the norms of language. The basic content categories of the text include the image of the author, information content, time and space. The author sets the spatio-temporal framework in the artistic world being created and decides what information will be reflected in the text. The interpretation of a literary text depends on the reader's position in time and space and on the extent to which his life experience coincides with the author's experience.

Translation is a process of interlingual and intercultural communication, the result of which is a speech work that expresses the meaning of the source text using the target language.

Equivalence is a multidimensional concept that describes the commonality of the original and translation texts at the communicative-pragmatic, lexical-semantic and syntactic levels. Adequacy is a normative and evaluative category that reflects the choice of translation strategy in accordance with the communicative situation.

The concepts of equivalence and adequacy have different objects and contents and are not identical to each other. In addition, a mandatory condition for equivalence is the presence of content-formal correspondence of the translated

text to the original text, which is achieved at the linguistic level. But communicative conditions are the conditions of speech communication, therefore, adequacy is related to the level of speech.

In the translation process, the main ways to achieve functionally equivalent relations at the lexical-semantic level are cohesion and coherence, which are used if lexical units implement one of the dictionary meanings. In the process of translating a literary text, the modulation technique turns out to be the most effective, because in a literary text, words “acquire” contextual meanings and acquire a special stylistic coloring. Combinations of techniques are also possible, for example: modulation and generalization, modulation and specification. Specification and generalization are opposite in nature, although they can interact with each other.

Proper names are subject to transliteration, which is based on phonetic transcription and the establishment of sound-letter similarities.

To establish functionally equivalent relations at the grammatical-syntactic level, grammatical transformations are effective, such as: dividing and combining sentences, grammatical replacements, antonymic translation, permutations, changing word order. The most commonly used technique is grammatical substitution, which is explained by significant differences in the systems and norms of the differently structured source (English) and target (Russian) languages. Effective ways to achieve communicative-pragmatic equivalence are not only compensation and descriptive translation, but also semantic development, leading to the specification or generalization of the meaning of the original. Modulation becomes possible when in the source language there are synonymous ways of expressing the content of reality, which, in turn, have equivalents in the target language.

At the same time, it becomes obvious that the equivalence of both the lexical-semantic and grammatical-syntactic levels implies the mandatory preservation of the communicative and pragmatic characteristics. Only the conceptual content is capable of determining the choice of meanings relevant to the original communicative situation, which, therefore, must be preserved in translation, and the inevitable losses are compensated by applying translation transformations: transliteration, tracing, generalization, specification, modulation / semantic development, division and combination of sentences, grammatical replacement, rearrangement, antonymic translation, descriptive translation, compensation.

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INGLIZ VA O‘ZBEK TILLARIDAGI “BAXT” BOSH LEKSEMALI MAQOLLARDAGI UNIVERSAL VA MILLIY JIHATLAR

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada ingliz va o'zbek tillarida yangicha tahlil metodlari, hozirgi globallashuv, standartlashuv, integratsiyalashuv va madaniyatlarning aralashuvi yuz berayotgan jarayondagi turli xalqlar tili va madaniyatini o'rganish, ularni qiyosiy tahlil qilish, til va madaniyat mushtarakligini tadqiq etish dolzarb vazifalardan ekanligi asoslanadi.

Kalit so'zlar: Zamonaviy tilshunoslik, til va madaniyat, madaniyatning tarkibiy qismlari, ma'naviy meros, folklor namunalari, ajdodlar tajribasi.

Abstract: In this article, the similarities and differences of proverbs with the meaning of happiness in English and Uzbek.

Xalq madaniyatini ko'rsatishda maqollar eng faol vositalardan biri sifatida bugungi kunda tilshunoslikda lingvokulturologik izlanishlar jarayonining muhim mavzularidan biriga aylanmoqda. Har bir maqol, uning fikricha, xalqning turmush tarzini qisqa va lo'nda umuman olganda to'laligicha ifodalay oladigan ko'zgudir. Maqollarning lingvokulturologik sifatlariga to'xtalgan holda olimlardan Nida maqollarni o'rganishda bevosita tilni va o'sha xalqning madaniyatini o'rganish bu tabiiy hol deb hisoblaydi. Tilda mavjud bo'lgan leksema o'sha xalqning turmush tarzidan ya'ni xalq tilidan kelib chiqqan bo'lib, bu bevosita maqollarda ishtirok etadi va maqollar orqali xalqning madaniyati aks etadi. Maqollarning lingvokulturologik xususiyatlariga to'xtalar ekanmiz, millatlarning o'ziga xos milliy xarakteri va mentaliteti haqida so'z ochmay ilojimiz yo'q, albatta. Chunki xalqning o'ziga xos madaniyati, tarixi va urf-odatlarini ixcham holatda yetkazib beruvchi xalq maqollari xalqning mentalitetini ifodalashda yetakchi o'rinda turadi. Maqollar xalq ijodiyotining bebaho namunasi bo'lib, o'sha xalqning milliy madaniy xususiyatlarini, dunyoqarashi va millatning ruhiyatini ifodalaydi. Turli tillarning maqollariga to'xtalar ekanmiz, ular o'sha til egasi bo'lmish xalqning

tarixiy, ma'naviy va moddiy madaniyati ko'zgusi ekaniga guvoh bo'lamiz. Shu sababli, turli til maqollarini qiyosiy o'rganish millatning o'ziga xos madaniy va milliy qirralarini ochishga yordam beradi, boshqacha qilib aytganda, o'sha xalqning mentalitetini ko'rsatadi. "Mentalitet" tushunchasi tilshunoslik paradigmasiga kiritilganiga hali ko'p bo'lmagan bo'lsada, hozirda juda keng doirada qo'llanilmoqda. Tor ma'noda mentalitet "fikrlash doirasi, dunyoqarashi" mazmunida foydalanilsa, keng ma'noda esa "xalqning axloqi, tarbiyasi va tasavvuri tushuniladi". Mentalitet tushunchasini tilshunos V. fon Gumboldt qarashlarida ham ko'rishimiz mumkin. Uning fikricha, mentalitet – bu "xalqning nafaqat tilida, balki adabiyoti, dini va boshqa ma'naviy jabhalarida ham o'z aksini topgan xarakteridir".⁴ Shunday ekan, yuqorida aytib o'tilganidek, bu "milliy xarakter" xalqning dini, siyosati, urf – odatlari, ijtimoiy qatlami, turmush tarzi, tarixi va hatto geografik o'rni bilan ham chambarchas bog'liq. Kundalik hayotimizda uchrovchi turli xil narsalarni hamisha ikki xil, ya'ni bir-biriga qarama-qarshi jihatlari orqali bilamiz. Bular ichida eng ko'p uchrovchi hodisalardan yaxshilik va yomonlik, baxtlilik va baxtsizlik holatlaridir. Yoki tilimizda bularni ijobiy bo'yoqdor so'zlar va salbiy bo'yoqdor so'zlarga ajratamiz. Baxtlilik va baxtsizlik leksemalarining maqollarda keng ko'lamda uchrashi tabiiy holdir. Chunki maqollar xalqning hayotiy haqiqatga nisbatan qarashlarini va munosabatlarini ko'rsatuvchi hodisadir. Shu o'rinda ingliz va o'zbek maqollarida uchrovchi baxtlilik va baxtsizlik mavzusidagi maqollar xalqning ushbu tushunchalarga bo'lgan munosabatlarini yaqqol ifoda etadi. Keltirilgan fikrlarimizni isbotlash maqsadida quyida bir qator baxtlilik va baxtsizlik mavzusidagi ayrim o'zbek va ingliz maqollarining semantik tahlillarini keltirib o'tamiz. Xulosa qilib aytganda, maqollar bu xalqning madaniy merosidir. Ularda o'sha xalqning barcha o'y – fikrlari, dunyoqarashi, turmush tarzi, fe'l – atvori va e'tiqodi aks etadi. Har bir millat o'ziga xos tavsiflarga ega ekan, bu

⁴ Гумбольдт В. фон. Избранные труды по языкознанию. - Москва: Прогресс. - С. 1984, стр.43.

ularning maqollariga ham ta'sir etmay qolmaydi. Hatto maqollardagi mavzular o'xshash bo'lsa-da, ulardagi obrazlar takrorlanmasligi bilan ajralib turadi. Aynan ana shu tasvirlar maqollardagi milliy bo'yoqdorlikni ta'minlaydi. Ta'kidlab o'tganimizdek, maqollar bu xalq og'zaki ijodining mahsuli bo'lib, xalqning hayotiy tajribasi va orzu-intilishlarini, umuman olganda hayotga bo'lgan munosabatini qay daraja baholashining natijasidir. Quyida keltiradigan maqollarimiz orqali o'zbek va ingliz xalqining baxt va baxtsizlikka nisbatan bergan baholarini yanada aniqroq tushunib olish maqsadida quyidagi maqollarni ham ko'rib chiqamiz.

Demak, bugungi kunda maqollarni, xususan, xalq ijodiyotini o'rganish, tadqiq qilish bugungi kunda juda muhim ahamiyat kasb etmoqda. Maqollar faqat folkloristik nuqtayi nazardan o'rganilibgina qolmasdan, balki tilshunoslikning, lingvokulturologiyaning ham obyektiga ham aylanib ulgurgan. Maqollar xalqimizning milliy, madaniy–ma'naviy avlodan–avlodga o'tib kelayotgan merosi hisoblanadi. Bu meros madaniyatimizning ham namunasi sanaladi. Til va madaniyatning o'zaro yaqinligi va aloqadorligi ularni yagona metodologik asosda o'rganish imkonini beradi. O'zbek xalq maqollari aforizmlar tarkibida ham o'rganiladi. Maqol jumla, nutq hodisasi sifatida oddiy hodisani tashqi tomondan aks ettiradi, aniq dalil yoki aniq vaziyatni bildiradi. Maqollar - yagona mantiqiy mazmunga ega bo'lib bir-biridan tamoman farqli leksik – grammatik tarkibdan iborat bo'lishi mumkin. “baxt” tushunchasini ifoda etuvchi o'zbek xalq maqollari o'zbek mentalitetiga, milliy madaniyatiga oid jihatlarni ham namoyon qiladi. Biror xalq hayotida mavjud va kundalik hayotda faol qo'llaniluvchi leksemalar tilda o'z qiyofasini yaratadi va xalqlarning milliy mentalitetini ko'rsatishda maqollarda ishtirok etmay qolmaydi. Maqollarning semantik jihatdan guruhlarga ajratilishi uning qo'llanish doirasi kengayishiga, o'rganilishining osonlashishiga olib keladi.

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INGLIZ TILIDA SO‘Z URG‘USINI O‘QITISHNING SAMARALI METODLARI

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu tezisdagi ingliz tilini o‘rganuvchilarda eng ko‘p uchraydigan talaffuz muammolari, so‘z urg‘usi bilan bog‘liq xatolarni bartaraf etish uchun juda samarali natijalar bera oladigan, til o‘rganuvchilarida so‘z urg‘usi ko‘nikmasini shakllantirishga ko‘maklasha oladigan o‘qitish usullari bayon etiladi.

Kalit so‘zlar: Urg‘u normalari, audiolingual metod, semantik ta‘sir, farqlash funksiyasi, so‘z tarixi, so‘z qolipi

Annotation: In this thesis, effective teaching methods that can help to eliminate the most common pronunciation problems in English language learners, word stress errors which can occur during learning a language are

given. These methods help them to increase their skill of word stress formation.

Key words: The norms of stress, audiolingual method, semantic effect, differentiation function, the history of the word, the model of the word

Leksik urg‘u ingliz tilidagi nutqning muhim birligi sifatida gap urg‘usi va ritmni o‘rganishdan oldin talabalar yaxshi bilishi kerak bo‘lgan til hodisadir. Turli tilshunoslar tomonidan bildirilgan fikrlarga tayangan holda ingliz tilida so‘z urg‘usining juda murakkab hodisa deyish mumkin. Shunday ekan bunday leksik urg‘uni o‘qitish jarayoni ham oson kechmaydi, albatta. Faqatgina, aniq yo‘naltirilgan samarali usullar va metodlar orqali pedagoglar ijobiy natijalarga erishish mumkin. Qiyinchiliklarning asosiy sababi shundan iboratki, ingliz tilidagi urg‘uning o‘ziga xos jihatlarining ko‘pligi, ya’ni uning o‘zgaruvchanligi, urg‘uga ta’sir etuvchi omillar ko‘pligi, tilshunoslarning urg‘u normalariga nisbatan qarama-qarshi fikrlarining ko‘pligi, nutqda esa o‘zbek tiliga nisbatan o‘z ahamiyatining ustunligi, uning boshqa til satihlari (morfemika, morfologiya, leksikologiya, etimologiya) bilan chambarchas bog‘liqligi, akustik va artikulyatsion belgilarining o‘ziga xos jihatlari mavjud ekanligi, darajalanish xossasining mavjudligidir. Chet tilini o‘rganuvchilar asosan qiyosiy aspektda tilni tahlil qilish orqali o‘zlashtirishlari oson kechadi. Biroq, ingliz tilidagi urg‘uni o‘zbek tiliga taqqoslash mushkuldir

Keltirilgan tamoyillar va maqsadlar asosida mavjud bo‘lgan qiyinchiliklarni yengish va urg‘u ko‘nikmasini tez sur’atda shakllantirish uchun quyidagi qulay usullardan foydalanish maqsadga muvofiqdir.

1. Audiolingval metoddan foydalanish: ushbu metod orqali asosan talaffuz va tinglab tushunishni o‘rgatishga asoslangan chet tilini o‘qitishning keng tarqalgan metodlaridan biridir. Audiolingval so‘zi lotin tilidan kelib chiqqan bo‘lib,

audire-tinglash, eshitish, lingua-til ma'nolarini bildiradi. Agarda "audiolingval metodi" atamasi so'zma-so'z tarjima qilinadigan bo'lsa, "tinglash-gapirish metodi", ya'ni "tilni tinglash-gapirish" yo'li bilan o'rganish ma'nosini bildiradi.⁵ Ushbu metod urg'uni

o'qitishda samarililigi ushbu metodda mavjud bo'lgan bir qancha faktorlar ko'rsatib beradi. Jumladan, tildagi normalar avvalam bor og'zaki nutqqa tatbiq qilinib, o'qish va yozish tinglab tushunish va gapirish ko'nikmalaridan so'ng amalga tatbiq etiladi. Ko'proq takrorlash va taqlid qilish mashqlaridan foydalaniladi. Bundan tashqari tilni o'rgatish davomida ko'proq autentik materiallardan, til sohiblarining asl nutqlari yozib olingan tasmalar qo'llanilishi maqsadga muvofiq bo'ladi. Yuqoridagi ustunliklarga qaramay, ushbu metodning ham o'ziga xos kamchiliklari mavjud. Chunki, u ona tilini dars jarayonidan butunlay chiqarib tashlashga asoslangandir. Urg'uni o'rganish mobaynida esa tillarni o'zaro taqqoslab o'rganishni va shu yo'l orqali yo'l qo'yilishi mumkin bo'lgan xato va kamchiliklarni bartaraf etishni taqozo etadi. Ikkinchi qulay usul quyidagicha:

2. Eng avvalo urg'uning ahamiyati va uni hosil qilishni o'rganishdan boshlash maqsadga muvofiqdir. Masalan, urg'uning ahamiyatini eng oddiy yo'l bilan tushuntirish uchun o'qituvchi dastlab ingliz tilidagi kamida ikki bo'g'inli bo'lgan so'zni tanlab olib, urg'uni so'zning turli bo'g'inlarida yaqqol qo'llaydi. Masalan, **COMputer**, **compUter**, **computER** so'zlari kabi. Keyin o'qituvchi talabalardan qaysi biri eng maqbul kelayotganini so'raydi. O'rganuvchilar esa tezda eng to'g'ri urg'uga ega so'zni ajratib oladilar (**compUter** so'zini). Bu jarayon orqali ular qolgan ikki so'zda qo'llangan noto'g'ri urg'uning nutqqa qay darajada o'z ta'sirini ko'rsatayotganining guvohi bo'ladilar. Buning uchun o'qituvchi so'zlarni kontekstda ham qo'llab urg'uni birma-bir ko'rsatib berishi kerak. Bu esa

⁵ Ходжаев М, Қаҳҳорова М. Чет тилини ўқитиш методикаси. –Т.: Fan va texnologiya, 2013. –В. 7-8.

talabalarning urg‘u va nuqsonlarsiz nutq o‘rtasidagi o‘zaro aloqani tushunib yetishlariga yordam beradi. Urg‘uni hosil usuli barcha tillarda ham bir xil jarayonda kechmaydi, albatta. Ingliz va o‘zbek tillari dinamik urg‘u oilasiga kiradi. har ikkala til urg‘usi uchun ham zarb muhim ahamiyatga egadir. Masalaning ikkinchi tomoni esa shundaki, ingliz tilidagi urg‘uni hosil qilishda faqatgina zarbning o‘zi ishtirok etmasligidadir. Shu sababli ham dastlab urg‘u o‘rnidan ko‘ra uni hosil qilish o‘rgatilishi til o‘rganish jarayonini osonroq bo‘lishiga yordam beradi. Buning uchun esa o‘qituvchi ma’noga ega bo‘lmagan bo‘g‘inlar ketma-ketligini yaratib undagi bir bo‘g‘inni qolganlariga qaraganda aniqroq, cho‘ziqroq, balandroq va tovushning yuqori toni orqali talaffuz qiladi (**baBIba** kabi). Bu esa chet tilini o‘rganuvchilarda urg‘u konseptiga qo‘yilgan ilk qadamdir. Keyinchalik esa ushbu mashqni real so‘zlarga tadbiq qilinadi (**diREctor** kabi).

3. Urg‘uga doir turli mashqlar va interfaol usullardan foydalanish. Ingliz tilida so‘z urg‘usi murakkab jarayondir. Bunda pedagogning asosiy vazifasi esa aynan shu murakkablikni osonlashtirishdan iboratdir. Buning uchun o‘qituvchi turli so‘zlardagi urg‘uning o‘rnini aniqlashda yordam beruvchi turli-tuman mashqlarni qo‘llashi kerak. Zamonaviy urg‘uni o‘qitish metodikasida turli urg‘u modellarini yaratib olish, bu jarayonda asosan katta(urg‘uli bo‘g‘in uchun) va kichik(urg‘usiz bo‘g‘in uchun) aylanalardan foydalanish allaqachon urfga aylangan. Misol uchun avval aralash tartibdagi so‘zlar keltiriladi, keyin esa shu berilgan so‘zlarni guruhlariga ajratish, belgilangan jadvalga joylashtirish uchun materiallar til o‘rganuvchilariga tarqatiladi. Bathroom, control, crowded, event, Empty, guitar, against, alarm, argue, lovely, pavement, prefer, prevent, protect, routine, improve, retired, jumper, lawyer, scissors, stomach, towels, wedding, without kabi so‘zlar beriladi

Oo	oO
bathroom	control

O‘rganuvchilarning asosiy vazifasi namunadagi kabi berilgan so‘zlarni jadvalga muvofiq tarzda joylashtirishdir. Albatta, bu yerda faqat ikki bo‘g‘inli so‘zlar misolidagi mashq tashkillangan bo‘lsa, o‘qituvchi bog‘inlar sonini ularga mos qoidalar o‘zlashtirilishi bilan ko‘paytirib boradi. Dars mobaynida urg‘u ko‘nikmasini shakllantirish uchun turli o‘yinlardan ham foydalanish mumkin. Buning uchun yuqoridagi kabi bir nechta so‘zlar yozilgan materiallar har bir talabaga tarqatiladi. Talabalarga berilgan so‘zlarning har biri ma’lum bir urg‘u tartibiga ega bo‘lib, ularning o‘yin paytidagi ahamiyatini tushuntirib, muayyan vaqt ichida xuddi o‘zlariniki kabi urg‘u qolibi va tartibiga ega bo‘lgan talabani topishlari kerak bo‘ladi. Misol uchun birinchi talabada quyidagi so‘zlar bor: bicycle(O o o), parrot (O o), imagine(o O o). Ikkinchi talabada esa potato (o O o) , open (O o), excellent(O o o)so‘zlari bor. Ishtirokchilar o‘yin davomida barcha o‘z sheriklarini qidiradilar va urg‘u qoliblari o‘zlariniki bilan bir xil tartibda bo‘lgan guruhlariga ajraladilar. Qaysi guruh a‘zolari birinchi bo‘lib o‘z sheriklarini to‘g‘ri va to‘liq topa olsalar, o‘sha guruh o‘yin g‘olibiga aylanadi.

4. Leksik urg‘uni faqatgina fonetika darslarida emas, qolgan fanlarning ham bir qismi sifatida o‘qitish maqsadga muvofiqdir. Chunki, leksik urg‘uning murakkabligi uning tilshunoslikning boshqa satihlari bilan ham izchil bog‘liqligidir. Xulosa qilib aytadigan bo‘lsak, ayni paytda ingliz tilini o‘rganuvchi o‘zbek talabalarda uchrab turadigan inferentiv fonetik xatoliklar hali ham dolzarbligicha qolmoqda. Bunday xatoliklar esa fonetik hodisalardan biri bo‘lmish so‘z urg‘usidan foydalanish jarayonida ham yaqqol ko‘zga tashlanadi. So‘z urg‘usi ko‘nikmasini shakllantirish murakkab va ko‘plab xatoliklarga sabab

bo'luvchi hodisadir. Shunday ekan, ingliz tili so'z urg'usini tez va oson o'rgatish uchun pedagoglar innovatsion darslarni tashkil etishlari, turli mashqlardan foydalanishi, darsga interfaol usullarni tadbiq qilishi, ko'proq autentik materiallardan foydalanishi, tilning boshqa sathlarini o'rganayotgan paytda urg'uga murojaat qilinishi, ya'ni uning paydo bo'lishi, vazifasi bilan bog'liq bo'lgan hodisalar bilan tanishtirib borishi, boshqa til bo'limlarida ham urg'udan foydalanish ijobiy samaralarga olib keladi.

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MAQOLLARNING INGLIZ VA O'ZBEK TILLARIDA MUQOBILLASHGAN TAHLILI

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada ingliz va o'zbek tillaridagi frazeologik birliklar, ya'ni maqol va matallar talqini va ifodasi ko'rib chiqildi. Misollar keltirilib tahlil qilindi.

Kalit so'zlar: maqol, matal frazeologiya, xalq og'zaki ijodi

Аннотация: В данной статье рассмотрены толкование и выражение фразеологизмов английского и узбекского языков, то есть пословиц и поговорок. Были приведены и проанализированы примеры.

Ключевые слова: пословица, фразеология, народное творчество

Abstract: In this article, the interpretation and expression of phraseological units in the English and Uzbek languages, that is, proverbs and sayings, was considered. Examples were given and analyzed.

Key words: proverb, matal phraseology, folk art

Har bir millat va elatning o'zligini, tarixi, madaniyati va milliy qadriyatlarini

ifodalovchi omillardan biri xalq og'zaki ijodidir. Xalq og'zaki ijodi asrlar davomida sayqallanib, xalq orasida aytilib, avlodan-avlodga o'tib kelayotgan ma'naviy meroslardan biridir. Xalq og'zaki ijodining takrorlanmas janrlaridan biri bu maqoldir.

Maqol (lotincha "proverbium" dan - maqol) xalqqa ma'lum, takrorlanib va aniq aytilgan to'liq so'z bilan aytilgan so'z; ular aqlni yoki odamlarning amaliy tajribasiga asoslangan holda haqiqatni ifoda etadilar. Taniqli tilshunos V.Mider o'z kitobida maqolga quyidagicha ta'rif beradi: «Maqol - bu xalqning hikmat, haqiqat, axloq va an'anaviy qarashlarini metafora, sobit va esda qolarli shaklda o'z ichiga olgan qisqa, umuman ma'lum jumla. avloddan avlodga o'tib kelmoqda» Ta'rifdan ko'rinib turibdiki, maqollar odatda metafora asosida va majoziy ma'noga ega. Maqol tushunchasi uchun bir qancha olimlar ko'plab ta'riflarni

berishgan bo'lsada, Miderning ta'rifi ular orasida eng yaxshi ta'rif deb hisoblanadi. Maqol tilning oddiy birligi emasligi sababli, bu hikmatli so'zlar yoki odamlar yoki millatning an'anaviy fikrlari bilan metafora ma'nosini beradigan tayyor jumla. Bundan tashqari, ular qisqa vaqt ichida nafaqat shaxs tomonidan yaratilgan balki maqol uzoq vaqt davomida xalq so'zlari sifatida aniq millat mahsulidir.

Ular yillar va asrlar davomida inson hayotining odatiy vaziyatlari ramkalari yoki modellari sifatida qoldirilgan. Ch. C. Doyl ularni minimal xalq she'rlari sifatida tekshirishni taklif qiladi, adabiyotda, chunki ular dialoglarni jonlantiradi yoki she'riyatga yoki nasrga turli yo'llar bilan ta'sirchanlik va hissiylik beradi. Ko'rinib turibdiki, maqollarning paydo bo'lishi va shakllanishi, bundan tashqari ularni xalq tomonidan jonli suhbatga kiritish ba'zan ancha uzoq vaqt talab etadi. Ingliz va o'zbek tillari uzoq tarixga ega deb ishoniladi. Ingliz tili lotin tilidan kelib chiqqan, shuning uchun juda ko'p ingliz paremiologiya zaxiralari lotin asoslariga ega; ularning ba'zilari tarixiy shakllarga o'xshashdir, ba'zilari esa eskilariga nisbatan o'zgarishga duch kelgan. Ko'p yillar davomida boshqa tillar ham ingliz tiliga ta'sir ko'rsatgan. Natijada, ba'zi maqollar ko'pincha maqollarni ingliz tiliga tarjima qilish yo'lida ulardan olinadi.

O'zbek va ingliz xalq maqollari sirasiga kiruvchi maqollardan:

Inglizcha: A bad beginning makes a bad ending

O'zbekcha: Yomonchilik bo'lganda, qor ustiga muz yog'ar.

Inglizcha: A good beginning makes a good ending.

O'zbekcha: Yaxshi yil — bahoridan, Yomon kun — saharidan ma'lum.

Ular singari maqollar eng ommabop maqollar sirasiga kiradi. Biror ishning natijasi qanday bo'lishi, uning qanday boshlanishiga bog'liq ekanligi maqollarda ham o'z aksini topa olgan. Odatda boshlagan ishimizning yakuni uni qanday ruhiyatda boshlashimizga va yon - atrofimizdagilarni bunga bo'lgan munosabatiga bog'liq bo'ladi. Shuning uchun ham ishni yaxshi boshlasak yaxshi, aksincha, yomon boshlasak, yomon yakun topishi maqollarda ifodalangan. Bunga qo'shimcha qilib quyidagi maqolni ham keltirib o'tsak bo'ladi.

Inglizcha: In every beginning think of the end.

O‘zbekcha: Yaxshi yerga yotsang, Yaxshi tush ko‘rasan.

Yomon yerga yotsang, Yomon tush ko‘rasan,

Demak, har bir boshlamoqchi bo‘lgan ishimizning yakuni uni qanday boshlashimizga bog‘liq ekanligi yuqorida keltirib o‘tgan maqollarimizda ifodalangan. Ushbu maqollarning tahlilidan kelib chiqib, har ikki tildagi variant bir xil ma‘no- mazmun anglatayotganini ko‘rishimiz mumkin.

O‘zbek va ingliz tillaridagi maqollarda o‘zining g‘oyat mazmunga boy ekanligi bilan ajralib turuvchi maqollardan yana biri “Every cloud has a silver lining” va maqolning o‘zbekcha varianti qilib: “Har yaxshida bir “ammo” bor, Har yomonda — bir “lekin” olingan. Inglizcha keltirilgan “Every cloud has a silver lining” aslida o‘zbek tiliga – “Har bir bulutning kumush hoshiyasi bor”, - deb tarjima qilinadi. Keltirilgan tarjima orqali biror ibratli fikrni darhol anglab olish biroz qiyin. Inglizchadan o‘zbekchaga qilingan tarjimada maqol oddiy bir gapdek bo‘lib qolgan. Agar berilgan tarjimani mazmunan tahlil qiladigan bo‘lsak, bulutning kumush hoshiyaga ega ekanligi aslida yomg‘irning yog‘ishi bilan baholanadi. Bir qarashda maqolda ishlatilgan so‘zlar “cloud”- “bulut” yoki “silver”- “kumush” hech qanday salbiy ma‘noga ega emas. Biroq maqolning umumiy mazmunidan kelib chiqadigan

bo‘lsak, havoning bulutli bo‘lishi salbiy holatni ifodalasa, bulut bo‘lib yer-u zaminga yomg‘ir yog‘ishi va bu orqali xalqqa risq-nasiba kelishi ijobiy hodisa sifatida baholanadi. Ko‘chma ma‘noda ifodalangan bulutning kumush hoshiyasi yomg‘ir yog‘ib, elga rizq ulashishi, tabiatni musaffo qilishi va ba‘zan insonlar qalbidagi g‘uborni yuvishi bilan baholangan.

Endi maqolning o‘zbekcha muqobil varianti bilan tanishib chiqsak. O‘zbekcha varianti qilib “Har yaxshida bir “ammo” bor, Har yomonda — bir “lekin” keltirilgan. Maqolning ma‘nosi shuni anglatadiki, inson hech qachon butunlay yomon yoki butunlay yaxshi bo‘lolmaydi. Har bir yomon deb qaralgan shaxs yoki narsa-buyumning ham o‘ziga yarasha yaxshi tomonlari va har bir

yaxshining o'ziga xos yomon jihatlari bo'lishi mumkin. Shu bugungi kungacha o'zbek xalq maqollari orasida xalq tomonidan faol tarzda ishlatilib kelinayotgan ushbu maqol o'zbeklar uchun aynan yuqorida keltirgan vaziyatimizda ishlatiladi.

XULOSA

Xulosa qilib aytganda, ingliz va o'zbek xalq maqollari bu xalqlarning madaniy merosidir. Ularda ingliz va o'zbek xalqning barcha o'y – fikrlari, dunyoqarashi, turmush tarzi, fe'l – atvori va e'tiqodi aks etadi. Har bir millat o'ziga xos tavsiflarga ega ekan, bu ularning maqollariga ham ta'sir etmay qolmaydi. Hatto ayrim ingliz va o'zbek maqollardagi mavzular o'xshash bo'lsada, ulardagi obrazlar takrorlanmasligi bilan ajralib turadi. Aynan ana shu tasvirlar maqollardagi milliy bo'yoqdorlikni ta'minlaydi.

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ROLE, USE AND TYPES OF LEXICAL TRANSFORMATIONS IN THE TRANSLATION PROCESS

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Annotation. In this article, the authors analyze the key aspects of the use of lexical transformations in the context of translating scientific texts. The authors explore the reasons for the use of lexical transformations and their features in a scientific style, examining in detail each transformation used. The article concludes that it is necessary to use an integrated approach in translation transformations to ensure the adequacy of the translation. The importance of

knowledge in the professional field for translators is emphasized, which emphasizes the relevance of their training in the field of professional communication in modern society.

Key words: lexical transformations, translation of scientific texts, lexical units, transcription, transliteration, tracing, specification, generalization.

РОЛЬ, ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЕ И ТИПЫ ЛЕКСИЧЕСКИХ ТРАНСФОРМАЦИЙ В ПРОЦЕССЕ ПЕРЕВОДА

Аннотация. В данной статье авторы анализируют ключевые аспекты использования лексических трансформаций в контексте перевода научных текстов. Авторы исследуют причины применения лексических трансформаций и их особенности в научном стиле, детально рассматривая каждую использованную трансформацию. В статье делается вывод о необходимости использования комплексного подхода в переводческих трансформациях для обеспечения адекватности перевода. Подчеркивается важность знаний в профессиональной области для переводчиков, что акцентирует актуальность их подготовки в сфере профессиональной коммуникации в современном обществе.

Ключевые слова: лексические трансформации, перевод научных текстов, лексические единицы, транскрипция, транслитерация, калькирование, конкретизация, генерализация.

TARJIMA JARAYONIDA LEKSIK TRANSFORMATSIYANING ROLI, ISHLATILISHI VA TURLARI

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada mualliflar ilmiy matnlarni tarjima qilish kontekstida leksik o'zgarishlardan foydalanishning asosiy jihatlarini tahlil qiladilar. Mualliflar leksik transformatsiyalarni qo'llash sabablarini va ularning xususiyatlarini ilmiy uslubda o'rganadilar, ishlatilgan har bir transformatsiyani batafsil ko'rib chiqadilar. Maqolada tarjimaning y etarliligini ta'minlash uchun tarjima transformatsiyalarida kompleks yondashuvdan foydalanish zarurligi

to'g'risida xulosa qilinadi. Tarjimonlar uchun kasbiy sohadagi bilimlarning ahamiyati ta'kidlangan, bu ularni zamonaviy jamiyatda kasbiy aloqa sohasida o'qitishning dolzarbligini ta'kidlaydi.

Kalit so'zlar: leksik transformatsiyalar, ilmiy matnlarni tarjima qilish, leksik birliklar, transkripsiya, transliteratsiya, kalk , konkretlashtirish, umumlashtirish.

Introduction. Learning a foreign language not only expands the boundaries of knowledge and allows you to follow the latest scientific and technical achievements, but also contributes to the comprehensive development of the individual. This is especially important in the modern world, where knowledge quickly becomes outdated and new discoveries require continuous updating of information. Literature books in original version is quite eye-catching, especially in genres such as fiction, detective and historical novels, are often published in English, making translation a critical task for the reader who is not so close to the source language culture. However, even a large number of professional translators are not always able to cope with the huge amount of masterpiece that appears every day. This article focuses on the study of lexical transformations used in the process of translating literary texts. The authors propose to include this aspect in the curriculum of high school students and students of non-linguistic specialties. The study is focused on the translation of literary texts from English. To achieve the goal, the following tasks were set: determining the essence of lexical transformations, analyzing their types, as well as studying the features of translation using them.

Results and its discussion. One of the key difficulties in the translation process is related to the polysemy of lexical units, when one word can denote several objects or concepts. Depending on the context, there may be a need to emphasize the unique, occasional meaning of a word. In any case, semantics plays a central role in translation, including the semantic structure of words, their

context and scope. Also important is the compatibility of words, which varies depending on the language. It is necessary to comply with the compatibility rules of a particular language in order to make the translation understandable to the reader. The diversity of the semantic scope of a word affects the breadth of its compatibility and can lead to different translation options for one text.

The literary style of speech is characterized by a number of features, including diction, sentence structure and syntax, nature of figurative language, rhythm and component sounds, rhetorical patterns (e.g. narration, description, comparison-contrast, etc.) point of view and symbolism. The literary style is also distinguished by creative and artistic content and more carefully structured and rhetorical effect of the used word flow. Furthermore its emotive and descriptive quality of the given material.

Let's turn to the analysis of the characteristics of translation transformations used when translating literary articles from the Britannica website. It is known from practice that pure forms of translation transformations are rare; usually they are mixed, as demonstrated in the examples below. In the process of translating literary texts, we integrated various transformations, combining, for example, replacement with specification and generalization with omission, against the background of grammatical changes.

In the process of translating literary texts, special attention is paid to transliteration, a method that involves the reproducing the word from the source language in the letters of the target language. This method is often used to translate personal names, geographical names, positions, magazines, unique names, place names, and specialized terms. For example, in the original version of the 'Harry Potter' heptology the names of the faculties of 'Hufflepuff', 'Ravenclaw' are changed into 'Пуффендуй' and 'Когтевран' in Russian translation while in Uzbek they are given in transliteration way like 'Reyvenklo', 'Haflpaf'.

Transliteration, a method of reproducing a word letter by letter, is also important when translating literary texts, especially when creating new terms. For

example, in fiction books are used whose names are translated by transliteration: "Albus Dambldor", "Akromanrul", "Kentavr", "Kvidditch", "Sliznort" .

Interestingly, these two techniques - transcription and transliteration - can be combined to achieve a more accurate translation, providing a harmonious combination of the phonetic and graphic aspects of the language. This allows the translation to be adequately adapted to the linguistic nuances of the target language, while preserving the original meaning and style of the literary text.

In the process of translating literary texts, tracing plays an important role, which includes a literal translation of the constituent parts of the original expression. This method helps to create new terms and expressions that are close in meaning to the original. For example, the name of the first book "Harry Potter and the Philosopher's Stone" is translated as "Garri Potter va Hikmatlar Toshi" In this case, tracing helps maintain the accuracy and structure of the original text.

In addition, an important aspect of translation is specification. This technique is used when an English word has a broader meaning and requires replacement with a narrower concept in the target language. For example, the phrase "Herbology is the study of magical and mundane plants and fungi. In Herbology, students learn to care for and utilize plants, and learn about their magical properties, and what they are used for." is translated as "Herbologiya sehrli va oddiy o'simliklar va zamburug'larni o'rganadi. Gerbologiyada talabalar o'simliklarga g'amxo'rlik qilishni va ulardan foydalanishni o'rganadilar, ularning sehrli xususiyatlari va ular nima uchun ishlatilishini o'rganadilar.". Here, specification helps to clearly convey the author's thoughts to the reader, while maintaining semantic accuracy.

Overall, these translation techniques play a key role in maintaining the accuracy and clarity of literary text, allowing readers to fully understand the topic under study. They promote accurate translation of fictional ideas and concepts, making imaginary topics easier to understand.

Descriptive translation is a translation method that is used when there is no direct correspondence to a word or phrase in the original language. In such cases, the translator can either use a descriptive translation, which can be quite extensive, or introduce a new loanword into the target language. When translating literary texts, the translator, as a rule, focuses on specialists familiar with the imaginary terminology of the author and descriptive translation may not be appropriate.

Conclusion. In conclusion, it should be emphasized that when translating literary texts, fictional translation transformations are usually used to achieve the adequacy of the translation. It is rare to single out a single transformation in its pure form. The main task of the translator is to find the correct combination of transformations, taking into account the functional style of the original text and using the appropriate linguistic means in the target language. It is important to remember the characteristic features of literary texts, such as information content, logic and clarity, as well as the significant role of terminology. All these aspects of translation should be taken into account when teaching a foreign language both at school and at university, especially in the context of the widespread use of online translators by students.

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EVFEMIYA - MURAKKAB LINGVISTIK, IJTIMOY VA

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada evfemiya hodisasining shakllanishi, lisoniy birlik va ijtimoiy hodisa sifatida uning o'rganilishi dolzarbligi, jamiyat ongida shakllanib borishi va tilda kengayib borishi bilan bir qatorda semantik, pragmatik va sotsiolingvistik jihatdan ko'rib chiqish muhim ekanligi haqida yoritib berilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: evfemizm, lingvomadaniy yondashu, ijtimoiy hodisa, lisoniy birlik, evfemizatsiya, sotsiologik, semantic, pragmatik.

Kirish. Evfemizmlarni o'rganish dolzarb lingvistik muammodir, chunki so'nggi o'n yilliklarda evfemizmlarning shakllanish jarayoni ma'lum bir tezlikda sodir bo'lmoqda. Bu hozirgi vaqtda evfemizmlarning shakllanishiga va ularning tilda kuchayishiga hissa qo'shadigan eng katta omillardan biri yangi ijtimoiy munosabatlarni shakllantirishning kuchli vositasi bo'lish qobiliyati, evfemizmlarning faqat omma orasida tarqala boshlaganligi bilan izohlanadi.

Aksariyat hollarda evfemizmlar faqat stilistik sinonim yoki ba'zi bir lisoniy birlikning o'rnini bosuvchi vosita emas. Ular hissiy dominantni siljitadi va ma'lum bir hodisaning yangi talqinini, uni ko'rib chiqishga yangi nuqtai nazarni taklif qiladi va hodisaga yangi axloqiy baho beradi. Shunga asoslanib, ma'lum bir nutqda ko'p sonli evfemizmlarning paydo bo'lishi juda simptomatikdir: bu inson

hayotining ushbu sohasidagi ijtimoiy yo'riqnomalarning o'zgarishini ko'rsatadi.

Quyida ko'rsatilgandek, ko'plab zamonaviy evfemizmlar yangi ijtimoiy-siyosiy ta'limotlarning paydo bo'lishi va jamiyat ongida mustahkamlanishi natijasidir. Shu bilan birga, evfemizmlar, bir tomondan, ijtimoiy ongda allaqachon sodir bo'lgan siljishlarni aks ettirsa, ikkinchi tomondan, ularning o'zi jamiyatda yangi g'oyalarning tarqalishi va mustahkamlanishiga hissa qo'shadi.

Asosiy qism. Evfemiya murakkab lingvistik, ijtimoiy va kognitiv hodisadir. Uni nafaqat leksik-morfologik, balki qiyosiy, lingvomadaniy, sotsiolingvistik, semantik va funksional-pragmatik jihatlarida ham ko'rib chiqish maqsadga muvofiqdir. Evfemizatsiya jarayonlariga bag'ishlangan tadqiqotlar leksikologiya, sotsiolingvistika va pragmalingvistikada mavjud. Leksik-morfologik yondashuv bizga evfemizmlarning shakllanishi muammosini ajratib ko'rsatish va evfemizmlarning har xil turlari modellarini qurish imkonini beradi.

Semantik jihat evfemizm ma'nosining tarkibiy birliklarini, ularning bayonotning hissiy rangini o'zgartirishdagi rolini va evfemizm ma'nosi bilan u o'rnini bosadigan so'z yoki iboraning ma'nosi o'rtasidagi farqni o'rganishni o'z ichiga oladi. So'nggi o'n yillikda evfemizm muammolarini pragmatik nuqtai nazardan ochib beruvchi asarlar paydo bo'la boshladi. Pragmatika til va so'zlovchi o'rtasidagi munosabatni, xususan, gap muallifining muayyan lingvistik vositani tanlashining sabablarini o'rganadi.

Evfemizmning deyarli barcha mavjud ta'riflari u yoki bu ma'noda uning pragmatik tomonini, ya'ni evfemizmlarni qo'llash maqsadini aks ettiradi (bayonotni yumshatish, ma'ruzachining suhbatdoshi nazarida o'z maqomini oshirishga urinishi, muvaffaqiyatli muloqotni targ'ib qilish va boshqalar). Funksional-pragmatik yondashuv nutqdagi evfemizmlarning amal qilishini, ular qo'llanilgan nutq turlarini va muayyan sohada qo'llanish chastotasini ko'rib chiqish imkonini beradi.

Ijtimoiy lingvistikaning o'rganish sohasi evfemizmni o'rganishda turli ijtimoiy guruhlar vakillari tomonidan evfemizmlarni qo'llashdagi farqlar kabi

muhim jihatni o'z ichiga oladi. Qiyosiy tadqiqot usuliga asoslangan lingvomadaniy yondashuv turli tillardagi evfemizmning milliy madaniy o'ziga xosligi haqidagi savolni ko'tarishga imkon beradi.

Dunyoning lingvistik rasmining milliy o'ziga xosligini va turli tillarda so'zlashuvchilarning nutq xatti-harakatlarini o'rganish zamonaviy tilshunoslikning dolzarb vazifasidir. Bu muammo lingvokulturologiya, etnopsixolingvistika, tilshunoslik va mintaqashunoslik, nutq etnografiyasi kabi tilshunoslik fanlarining diqqat markazida bo'ldi. Til va nutq xatti-harakatining milliy o'ziga xosligi nutq odobining o'ziga xos xususiyatlarida, nutqni qurish qoidalarida, har bir til madaniyatiga xos janrlar tizimining mavjudligida, milliy o'ziga xos voqelikni bildiruvchi lisoniy bo'shliqlar va lug'aviy birliklarning mavjudligida namoyon bo'ladi.

Bizningcha, evfemizmni o'rganish tillarning milliy-madaniy o'ziga xosligini ochib berish nuqtai nazaridan juda istiqbolli. Evfemizmlar milliy mentalitetning xususiyatlarini aks ettiradi, ma'lum bir madaniyatda qoralangan hodisalarni aniqlaydi. Evfemizmlarning shakllanishi ayniqsa faol sodir bo'lgan turli tillarning leksik-semantik sohalarini taqqoslash tabular tizimidagi farqlarni, turli til madaniyatlariga xos bo'lgan munosib va odobsizlik haqidagi g'oyalarni aniqlash imkonini beradi. Muayyan nutq turida evfemizmlarning qo'llanish chastotasi va umuman nutqiy muloqotning evfemizm darajasi ma'lum bir til jamoasi nutq odobining o'ziga xos xususiyatlari bilan chambarchas bog'liq.

Turli xalqlarning nutqiy xulq-atvori turli qadriyatlar tizimiga asoslanadi. Ba'zi tilshunoslik madaniyatlarida to'g'ridan-to'g'rilik va ochiqlik qadrlansa, boshqalarida xushmuomalalik mulohazalari birinchi o'ringa chiqadi, bu esa so'zlovchilarni allegoriyalar, qochqin iboralar va turli xil yumshatishlarga murojaat qilishga majbur qiladi. Bu muqarrar ravishda evfemizmlarni qo'llash chastotasiga ta'sir qiladi. Biroq, til madaniyatlarining milliy o'ziga xoslik darajasini bo'rttirib ko'rsatmaslik kerak. Dunyoning lingvistik suratlarida milliy o'ziga xos lahzalar bilan bir qatorda umuminsoniy xarakterga ega bo'lgan

hodisalar, jumladan, semantik universallar va lingvistik-pragmatik maksimlar ham mavjud.

Hozirgi vaqtda har qanday psixik va lingvistik kategoriya geterogen deb e'tirof etiladigan lingvistik kategoriyalarni maydon tashkil etish nazariyasiga mos ravishda evfemizm muammolarini yoritish ham dolzarb bo'lib bormoqda. U prototip hodisalarni (ya'ni ma'lum bir toifaning mohiyatini eng aniq aks ettiruvchi hodisalarni) o'z ichiga olgan yadroni va ma'lum bir toifaning kamroq tipik vakillarini o'z ichiga olgan periferiyani ajratib turadi.

Xulosa. Bizning fikrimizcha, evfemizmga tatbiq etilganda bunday yondashuv juda samaralidir, chunki u tadqiqotga turli xil birliklarni, ya'ni melioratsiya darajasi har xil bo'lgan birliklarni, turli evfemizm usullaridan foydalangan holda kiritish va evfemizmning maydoncha tashkil etilishini tavsiflash imkonini beradi. Ushbu ishda evfemizmni uch jihat: semantik, pragmatik, sotsiolingvistik jihatdan ko'rib chiqish va ushbu turkumning o'zagi bilan bog'liq evfemizm prototipini va periferik sohalarga tegishli evfemizmlarni aniqlashga imkon beradigan evfemizmlarni tasniflash metodologiyasi ishlab chiqilgan. Shuni ta'kidlash kerakki, evfemizmlarning tavsifi turli xil nutq turlari bo'yicha notekis. So'nggi yillardagi eng ko'p tadqiqotlar siyosiy nutq va jaranglarga bag'ishlangan bo'lib, muloqotning boshqa sohalari esa soyada qolmoqda. Bu holat bizni amaliy boblarda tibbiy-pedagogik munozaralarga murojaat qilishga undadi, bu nutqlarda muhokama qilinadigan masalalarning o'ziga xos xususiyatlaridan kelib chiqib, evfemizatsiya jarayonlari faol sodir bo'ladi.

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THE USE OF AUTHOR'S CORPUS IN TEACHING ENGLISH

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Annotation

In the realm of English language teaching, educators constantly seek innovative methods to engage students and deepen their understanding of linguistic nuances. One such approach gaining traction is the utilization of authors' corpora in the classroom. Author's corpus refers to a collection of texts written by a specific author, analyzed using computational tools to unveil patterns, vocabulary usage, and stylistic features unique to that writer. This article explores the significance of employing author's corpora in the teaching process, elucidating its benefits and offering practical examples to demonstrate its efficacy.

Keywords: author`s corpus, corpora, syntactic structures, concordance, vocabulary acquisition, metaphors, pedagogical potential

Annotatsiya

Ingliz tilini o'qitish sohasida o'qituvchilar doimiy ravishda talabalarni jalb qilish va ularning lingvistik tafovutlarni tushunishlarini chuqurlashtirish uchun innovatsion usullarni izlaydilar. Bunday yondashuvlardan biri bu darsda mualliflik korpusidan foydalanishdir. Mualliflik korpusi deganda ma'lum bir muallif tomonidan yozilgan matnlar to'plami tushuniladi, u yozuvchiga xos bo'lgan naqshlar, lug'at qo'llanilishi va stilistik xususiyatlarini ochish uchun hisoblash vositalaridan foydalangan holda tahlil qilinadi. Ushbu maqola o'qitish jarayonida mualliflik korpusidan foydalanishning ahamiyatini o'rganadi, uning afzalliklarini yoritadi va samaradorligini ko'rsatish uchun amaliy misollar keltiradi.

Kalit soʻzlar: mualliflik korpusi, korpus, sintaktik tuzilmalar, konkordans, lugʻatni oʻzlashtirish, metafora, pedagogik salohiyat

Аннотация

В сфере преподавания английского языка преподаватели постоянно ищут инновационные методы, позволяющие привлечь учащихся и углубить их понимание языковых нюансов. Одним из таких подходов, набирающих обороты, является использование корпусов авторов в классе. Авторский корпус — это совокупность текстов, написанных конкретным автором, проанализированных с использованием вычислительных инструментов для выявления закономерностей, использования словарного запаса и стилистических особенностей, уникальных для этого автора. В данной статье исследуется значение использования авторских корпусов в учебном процессе, раскрываются его преимущества и предлагаются практические примеры, демонстрирующие его эффективность.

Ключевые слова: авторский корпус, корпуса, синтаксические структуры, конкорданс, словарный запас, метафоры, педагогический потенциал.

Introduction. Author's corpora provide invaluable insights into the linguistic fingerprint of writers, offering a window into their stylistic preferences, lexical choices, and syntactic structures. By compiling and analyzing a substantial body of an author's work, educators can unearth recurring themes, rhetorical devices, and idiosyncrasies that characterize their writing style. For instance, the use of concordance tools allows students to observe how authors employ specific words or phrases across different contexts, shedding light on their semantic range and connotations. The teacher becomes less a provider of input and facts about language and more a facilitator and consultant, or, at the learner-centred end, a co-researcher.⁶

Analysis. One of the primary advantages of utilizing author's corpora in English language teaching lies in its ability to enrich vocabulary acquisition. By immersing students in authentic literary texts, replete with rich and varied lexical expressions, educators can cultivate a deeper appreciation for language nuances while expanding their vocabulary repertoire. For example, analyzing Shakespeare's corpus⁷ enables students to encounter archaic words and phrases in context, fostering a nuanced understanding of Elizabethan English while enhancing their language proficiency.

Author's corpora also serve as a fertile ground for exploring stylistic features and rhetorical devices employed by writers. Through close examination of sentence structures, figurative language, and narrative techniques, students gain insights into the artistry of language and the intricacies of literary craftsmanship.

⁶ Gabrielatos, C. (2005). [Corpora and language teaching: Just a fling, or wedding bells?](http://www.tesl-ej.org/ej32/a1.html) *TESL-EJ*, 8(4), 1-37. <http://www.tesl-ej.org/ej32/a1.html>

⁷ <https://www.opensourceshakespeare.org/>

Furthermore, author's corpora play a pivotal role in fostering language proficiency by exposing students to authentic language use in context. By engaging with excerpts from renowned authors across different genres and time periods, learners develop a more nuanced understanding of language variation, register, and discourse conventions. For instance, comparing the linguistic features of contemporary authors like J.K. Rowling with canonical writers such as Charles Dickens provides students with insights into the evolution of the English language and its sociocultural influences. Incorporating technology into the classroom amplifies the pedagogical potential of author's corpora, enabling students to interact with texts dynamically and explore linguistic patterns autonomously. Utilizing concordance software, such as AntConc or Corpus Linguistics Toolkit, empowers students to conduct their own corpus-based analyses, thereby fostering critical thinking and research skills. Additionally, online platforms like Corpus of Contemporary American English (COCA) offer access to vast repositories of authentic texts, allowing educators to curate customized corpora tailored to specific teaching objectives and student interests.

Conclusion. In conclusion, harnessing author's corpora in the process of teaching English represents a paradigm shift in language pedagogy, offering a multifaceted approach to language learning that integrates literary analysis, vocabulary acquisition, and stylistic exploration. By immersing students in the rich tapestry of literary texts and leveraging computational tools to dissect linguistic patterns, educators can cultivate a deeper appreciation for the artistry of language while enhancing language proficiency. As technology continues to evolve, author's corpora stand poised to revolutionize English language teaching, ushering in a new era of immersive and engaging pedagogy that empowers students to become adept communicators and critical thinkers in the global landscape of language and literature.

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TYPES OF PHRASEOLOGISMS AND SPECIFIC CHARACTERISTICS IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGE.

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Abstract: In this article, while studying the unique features of phraseological units in the English and Uzbek languages, their comparative-typological analysis is carried out.

Key words: phraseological units, phraseologism, stable word combinations, synonymy.

Аннотация: В данной статье при изучении уникальных особенностей фразеологизмов английского и узбекского языков проводится их сравнительно-типологический анализ.

Ключевые слова: фразеологизмы, фразеологизмы, устойчивые словосочетания, синонимия.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada ingliz va o'zbek tillaridagi frazeologik birliklarning o'ziga xos xususiyatlarini o'rganish bilan birgalikda, ularning qiyosiy-tipologik tahlili olib boriladi.

Tayanch soʻzlar: frazeologik birliklar, frazeologizm, turg'un soʻz birikmalari, sinonimiya.

A phraseological unit is a unit related to language and speech as a linguistic phenomenon. A linguistic unit consisting of the combination of more than one independent lexeme and having a figurative and spiritual nature is called a phraseological unit: 'the hair on the top is standing up, the vinegar does not raise water; to show the white feather, to play the first fiddle'.

Phraseological unit is also referred to as phrase, phraseologism, stable compound, stable compound, phraseological compound.

The following are the main signs of phraseological units:

1. Two or more lexemes are part of the phraseological unit.
2. Phraseological unit represents a single lexical meaning.
3. The words in the phraseological unit have lost their lexical meaning.
4. Phraseological unit as a stable combination with a free combination is only in the homonymic state.
5. A phraseological unit can be replaced only as a whole
6. Phraseological unit comes in a syntactic function as a whole in the structure of the sentence.

According to the constituent of a phraseological unit, a compound lexeme is similar to a phrase and a sentence. However, they live more ready and stable in the mind of the language community, like a joint lexeme. In other words, the phraseological unit has the nature of generality characteristic of all linguistic units

in the language and appears as a feature in the speech. So, a phraseological combination is not a speech event, but a language event. Also, the phraseological unit has a nominative meaning, so it is put on the same line as the lexeme, and it is called a nominative unit larger than the lexeme.

Two phenomena are distinguished in the content plan of phraseological units: 1) lexical meaning, more precisely, phraseological meaning; 2) methodological assessment. The meaning of a constituent morpheme, lexeme is usually embodied as a sum of meanings specific to the language units that make it up, and the meaning of the whole is understood based on the meaning of the parts. A phraseological unit is a linguistic unit, but its meaning is not equal to the simple sum of the meanings inherent in lexemes. In relation to the meaning of the lexemes in the meaning of phraseological units, the denominator is embodied as a superlative meaning, which may not depend on the meaning of the lexemes in the meaning. Due to the fact that the meaning of phraseological units is not a simple sum of the meanings specific to lexemes, but a new meaning built on top of them, there seems to be a break between the plan of expression and the plan of content in phraseological units. Specific meanings do not directly explain the general meaning. Therefore, the connection between the plan of expression and the plan of content in phraseological units becomes conditional. Here, more than one word as a whole undergoes semantic development based on a certain image, by means of transfer. Such a superimposed figurative meaning based on a certain image is called a phraseological meaning.[1.2]

By studying the semantic properties of phraseological units, it was determined that they contain phraseological polysemy, phraseological synonymy, phraseological antonymy, phraseological homonymy and paronymy phenomena [1].

Phraseological synonymy - synonymy is one of the semantic microsystems between language units, and also among phraseological units. In order to call two

phraseological units synonymous, they must have the same meaning. Without it, it is impossible to talk about synonymy. It is not appropriate to understand the same meaning as the same meaning. Each synonym has its own edge of meaning, in addition to the general meaning of this nest of synonymy. Synonyms usually differ in one or more ways, one of which may be a difference in meaning. For example, to be in a bad mood and to be down in the mouth are synonyms of the phraseological unit: to be in a bad mood and to be down in the mouth. These synonyms, regardless of their other characteristics, differ in terms of meaning: in the latter, the meaning is somewhat stronger. When defining phraseological synonyms, the basis of another image is also taken into account. For example, a mouth, a shingle, a pinch of synonym phraseological units are based on various images: the organ of speech, a part of a head of grapes, the amount to be pinched.

Synonymous phraseological units should be distinguished from variants of one phraseological unit. For this, it is necessary to pay attention to the word-components of phraseological units. There is no doubt that phraseological units that do not have the same word-component in the lexicon are synonyms. For example, from thread to needle, mirid to secret, from hair to tail, which means "in every detail, to the smallest detail", is a mutual synonym of the phraseological unit, and they do not have a common word-component [2].

Synonymy is a phenomenon defined on the basis of meaning. The same ambiguity is determined between phrases in monosemantic phraseological units. If a polysemantic phraseological unit participates in a synonymous relationship, it should be derived not from a phraseological unit, but from a concrete phraseological meaning.

Phraseological antonymy. Antonymy is one of the phenomena determined on the basis of the semantic relationship between language units, and it is also found in phraseological units at the level of words. Determining antonymy, on the one hand, leads to a deeper understanding of the lexical meaning of phraseological

units, on the other hand, it helps to distinguish between the meanings of one phrase in polysemy, and on the third hand, it is useful in defining synonyms.

In short, phraseological units in each language have their own linguistic features. But in all languages, phraseological units serve as language wealth. Polysemantic phraseological units serve to enrich the lexical structure of the language and speech and embody the meanings of emotional coloring.

Phraseological units play an incomparable role in conveying the uniqueness, lifestyle, material and spiritual values, history, culture, and customs of the peoples of the world into their own language. Phraseological units are related to how individuals use language units, as well as the basic rules and language norms that regulate their use. Use of phraseological units in speech, translation of their use in terms of national-cultural universality, differential and paradigmatic features, ways of transition from folk oral creativity to literary language, semantic features, artistic-stylistic possibilities, form and meaning explanation in terms of problems, the importance of elucidating their place in the national language, the necessity of a dictionary suitable for modern linguistics is presented. Speaking about the contextual features of phraseological units, it can be said that there is a classification of phraseological structures according to the context, which are designated as phraseomes and idioms.

CONCLUSION

Distinctions in semantic and stylistic tasks performed by words with the same real meaning in different languages, as well as differences in the combinations of such words in different languages, are extremely important for both practice and translation theory. They often cause great practical difficulties and are of great theoretical interest, because they differ in the semantic and stylistic functions of words with the same real meaning in different languages, and the way such words enter different languages.

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KORPUS LINGVISTIKASI MATERIALLARIDAN FOYDALANGAN HOLDA GRAMMATIKANI O`QITISH MODELI

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada grammatikani o`qitishda korpusga asoslangan materiallardan foydalanish va ularning qanchalik samarador yoki samarador emasligi va o`tkazilgan tajribalardan namunalar va ularning natijalari keltirilgan.

Kalitso`zlar: korpus, korpora, korpus materiallari, ingliz tili grammatikasi, korpus lingvistikasi

Bugungi kunda texnologiyalar asrida yashar ekanmiz, hayotimizning har jabhasida ularni ko`rishimiz mumkin. Shu jumladan ta`limni ham internet, elektron doskalar va zamonaviy platformalarsiz tassavur qilish qiyin.

Prezidentimiz Shavkat Mirziyoyev: “Maktabda o‘qitish metodikasi o‘zgarmasa, ta’lim sifati ham, mazmuni ham, muhit ham o‘zgarmaydi” deya ta’kidlaganlar [1]. Shunday ekan, o‘qituvchi ham zamon bilan hamnafas yashash va an’anaviy metodlardan voz kechib ta’lim tizimini yangi bosqichga olib chiqishga harakat qilish lozim.

Ma’lumki, chet tillarini o‘qitishda birinchi o‘rinda albatta uning grammatikasi o‘rgatiladi. Grammatika shu paytgacha an’anaviy metoddan foydalangan holda o‘qitilgan va bujarayon haligacha davom etib kelyapti. Lekin darsliklarda berilgan ko‘rsatmalar real hayotda ishlatilish holatlari kam uchraydi. An’anaviy metod biroz eskirgandek shu kunlarda. Ingliz tili grammatikasini xorijiy til sifatida o‘rganuvchi o‘quvchilarga o‘rgatish shu soha o‘qituvchilari uchun bir qator qiyinchiliklar keltirib chiqarishi mumkin. Ayniqsa o‘quvchilar shu tilde insho yozganlarida yoki ilmiy maqolalarni o‘qimoqchi bo‘lganlarida, bu to‘siqlar yaqqol ko‘zga tashlanadi. Ular o‘rganayotgan an’anaviy grammatika kitoblari afsuski to‘liq yechim bo‘la olmaydi. Axborot texnologiyalari rivojlangan asrda yashayotgan ekanmiz, xorijiy tillarni ushbu texnologiyalardan foydalanib o‘rganish talabalar, o‘quvchilar, shujumladan, barcha til o‘rganuvchilar uchun yanada qulay bo‘ldi. Turli xildagi elektron lug‘atlar, ijtimoy platformalar, shu qatorda You tube, Instagram, Facebook kabilar boshqa bir chet tilini o‘rganish uchun vaqtni tejabgina qolmay, o‘rganish jarayonini yanada qiziqarli qilib, barchani o‘ziga jalb etib kelmoqda. Internet manbalaridan foydalanish ham ancha samarali, lekin ma’lumotlar ko‘pligidan qay birini ishlatish ham yana bir muammoga sabab bo‘ladi. “Real” hayotda foydalaniladigan grammatika uchun korpusdan foydalanish ancha qulay. 90- yillarning oxiriga kelib Korpus tushunchasi fanga kirib keldi.

Korpus atamasi O‘zbekistonda hali yangi hisoblanib bu bo‘yicha olimlarimiz endi izlanishlar olib borishmoqda. Ammo chet elda bir qator mashhur tilchilar jumladan: Leech, Biber, Johansson, Francis, Hunston, Conrad, and McCarthy lar

o'z kitoblarida atroflicha ma'lumot berib o'tganlar. Biber D va Conrad ning "Real grammar. Corpus based approach to English" [2] kitobida korpusga asoslanib haqiqiy grammatikani o'rgatish nazariy va amaliy jihatlari ko'rib chiqilgan.

Korpus atamasiga turli olimlar turlicha izoh berishgan. Ulardan J. Sinkler [3] quyidagi ta'rifni keltiradi: "Korpus- elektron shakldagi til matnlarining to'plami bo'lib, tashqi mezonlarga muvofiq tanlangan, lingvistik tadqiqotlar uchun ma'lumot manbasi hisoblanadi". Bundan ko'rinib turibdiki, korpus turli til matnlaridan tarkib topgan, yirik va cheksiz ma'lumotlarni o'z ichiga olgan, foydalanuvchilari uchun nafaqat onlayn balki offlayn ham foydalanish mumkin bo'lgan yozma va og'zaki matnlar to'plamidir. Hozirda korpusdan chet tilini o'qitishda foydalanish tajribalar misolida ko'rib chiqilmoqda. Vanessa va Linsquid [2007] [4] grammatikani o'qitishda korpus materiallaridan foydalanish qanchalik samara berishini sinab ko'rishdi. Ular talabalarni ikki guruhga: nazorat va tajriba guruhlariga ajratishdi. Ularga ma'lum bir grammatik mavzular, masalan, ega va kesimning qo'llanilishi, artikllardan foydalanish va boshqalar o'rgatildi. Nazorat guruhiga doimgidek an'anaviy metoddan foydalangan holda mavzu tushuntirildi. Tajriba guruhiga esa korpusdan qanday foydalanish tushuntirilgandan so'ng, onlayn mashqlar berib borildi. So'nggida natijalar shuni ko'rsatdiki, talabalar korpus orqali o'rganishga ijobiy munosabat bildirishgan va har doimgi kitoblardan o'rganishdan ko'ra ancha foydaliroq ekanligini ta'kidlashgan. Shunga qaramasdan, tajriba davomida ba'zi muammolar ham uchragan. Masalan, o'quvchilar korpusda judayam keng ma'lumotlar bazasiga duch kelishadi va bu vaqt yoqotishlariga, katta tanlov oldida qolishlariga sabab bo'ladi. Yana bir muammo o'qituvchilarning o'zlari hali korpusdan foydalanish bo'yicha to'liq ma'lumot va tajribaga ega emasligida. Korpusdan foydalana olish o'quvchilarning til bilish darajasiga ham qisman bog'liq. Til o'rganishni endi boshlayotganlar, ya'ni "beginner" hamda "pre-intermediate" darajadagi o'rganuvchilar grammatikani o'rganish uchun korpusdan foydalanish ancha qiyin

ekanligini ta'kidlashgan. Lekin darajasi balandroq o'quvchilar korpusni afzal ko'rishadi.

O'tkazilgan tajribalar shuni ko'rsatadiki, korpusga asoslangan materiallardan foydalanib grammatikani o'rgatish an'anaviy metoddan ko'ra ancha samaraliroq va bu borada bir qator izlanishlar olib borilmoqda. Chet tilini o'sha tilda so'zlashuvchilar qo'llaganidek o'rganish ko'pgina qulayliklar olib keladi.

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TARJIMADA PRAGMATIKANING KOMMUNIKATIV TA'SIRI

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Pragmatika tarjima nazariyasida muhim o'rin tutadi, chunki aynan pragmatika insonning vaziyatlarga bo'lgan munosabatini shakllantiradi, buning natijasida matn u yoki bu tarzda qabul qiluvchida ma'lum bir reaksiyani uyg'otib, kerakli

ta'sirga erishiladi. Tildagi belgilarni ko'rib chiqadigan bo'lsak, ular odatda quyidagilar bilan tavsiflanadi:

Semantika (semantik ma'no, belgilarning ularning ma'no va ma'nolariga munosabati).

Sintaktika (belgilarning bir-biriga munosabati).

Pragmatika (odamlar belgilarga munosabati). Bundan xulosa qilishimiz mumkinki, har bir matn kommunikativdir, ya'ni u manbadan retseptorga uzatiladigan ma'lumotlarni o'z ichiga oladi, ular uni qayta ishlashlari va qabul qilingan xabarga ma'lum munosabatni bildirishlari kerak. Axborotni qabul qilish va idrok etish orqali retseptor matn bilan muayyan munosabatga kiradi. Bunday munosabatlar pragmatik munosabatlar deb ataladi, bu esa til belgilarining kishiga ta'sir qilish, u yoki bu reaksiyaga sabab bo'lishiga olib keladi. Har qanday ma'lumot shunday xususiyatlarga ega va u pragmatik ta'sir (kommunikativ effekt) deb ataladi.

“Har bir gap qandaydir kommunikativ effekt olish maqsadida yaratilgan, shuning uchun pragmatik salohiyat gap mazmunining eng muhim qismini tashkil qiladi. Bundan kelib chiqadiki, tarjima matnida tarjima pragmatikasi muhim o'rin tutadi. Shunday qilib, tarjimon tarjimaning maqsadiga qarab, asl nusxaning pragmatik salohiyatini qayta yaratish yoki uni o'zgartirish orqali retseptorga kerakli ta'sir yuborish haqida o'ylashi kerak. Shuning uchun tarjimaning pragmatik jihatlarini o'rganish tarjima nazariyasining asosiy vazifalaridan biridir”

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Shunday qilib, 20-asrning 30-yillarida paydo bo'lgan pragmatika atamasi semiotikaning belgilar va bu belgilar foydalanuvchilari o'rtasidagi munosabatni o'rganuvchi bo'limidir. Shunga ko'ra, tarjimonning ishi har doim asl muallif o'z matni orqali o'quvchiga qanday ta'sir qilishni va xuddi shunday ta'sirni ta'minlashi bilan birga keladi. Bu ta'sir uchta asosiy xususiyatni o'z ichiga oladi: 1)

⁸ Kommisarov 1978

Malumotning mazmuni: Misol uchun, sizning mashinangiz o'g'irlanganligi haqidagi xabar sizga yangi mobil telefon berilganligi haqidagi xabarga munosabatingizdan farq qiladi. 2) Xabarni idrok etish xabarning qanday tushunilishiga va til belgilarning tabiatiga bog'liq. Masalan, bir xil ma'noga ega bo'lgan xabarlar ma'lum darajada taassurot yaratadigan turli xil stilistik ohanglarga ega bo'lgan so'zlarda berilishi mumkin. 3) Pragmatik ta'sir: Bu gap to'g'ridan-to'g'ri ma'lum bir gapni idrok etgan shaxs tomonidan belgilanadi. Masalan, sizning oilangizda bola tug'ilganligi haqidagi xabar yaqin va uzoq qarindoshlar va sizga mutlaqo begonalar tomonidan boshqacha qabul qilinadi. Shunday qilib, bu fakt gapning mazmuni va shakliga bog'liq bo'lgan pragmatik ta'sir har xil turdagi retseptorlarga nisbatan to'liq yoki qisman sodir bo'lmasligi mumkinligini ko'rsatadi. Bu shuni anglatadiki, har qanday so'z pragmatik potentsialga ega bo'lib, u turli darajada aloqa harakatlarida mavjud. V.N.Komissarov ham lingvistik adabiyotda tarjimaning pragmatik jihati uch xil nuqtai nazardan ochiladi, deb hisoblaydi. Birinchi nuqta nuqtai nazaridan, asl so'zlarning pragmatik ma'nolarini uzatish haqida savol tug'iladi. Ikkinchisida tarjima pragmatikasi ma'lum bir tarjima aktining pragmatik vazifasini bajaradi. Uchinchidan, asl va tarjimada kommunikativ ta'sir tengligini ta'minlash uchun tarjimani pragmatik moslashtirish zarurati mavjud.⁹ Komissarovning fikriga ko'ra, "tarjima pragmatikasi - bu tarjima jarayonining borishi va natijasiga asl nusxaning pragmatik imkoniyatlarini takrorlash zarurati va tarjimani oluvchiga kerakli ta'sirni ta'minlash istagining ta'siridir".

Binobarin, kommunikantlarning matnga pragmatik munosabati kommunikantlarning muayyan milliy, ijtimoiy yoki kasbiy guruhlariga mansub bo'lishi, shuningdek, matnda qanday til birliklari ishlatilishi bilan belgilanadi. Shunday qilib, tarjima matnda ko'proq sezuvchanlik va ma'lumotlariga ega bo'lishini talab qiladi va tinglovchi yoki o'quvchi ma'lumotni boshqa turda bo'lishini taxmin qiladi. Tarjimaning maqsadi asl nusxadagi (pragmatik

⁹ Komissarov 1978

munosabatlar) ta'sir xarakterini saqlab qolishdir, lekin bu tarjima xabarining o'zida muayyan o'zgarishlarni talab qilishi mumkin. Tarjima matni uni tarjima sifatida ajratib turadigan hech qanday grammatik yoki semantik xususiyatlarga ega bo'lishi mumkin emas, buning sababi undagi grammatika va semantikaning Tarjima tiliga tegishli bo'lishi va asl nusxadan faqat pragmatikani olish mumkinligi bilan bog'liq. Shuning uchun tarjimaning vazifasi asl nusxadagi pragmatikani saqlab qolishdir. Ammo asl nusxaning pragmatikasi grammatika va semantikaga asoslanadi, shuning uchun bularning barchasi ma'lum bir tarzda tanlanishi va adekvat tarjima deb ataladigan narsaga birlashtirilishi kerak.

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NATIONAL CLOTHES AND TRANSLATION PROBLEMS

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Abstract. National culture is passed down from generation to generation based on customs and traditions that have been formed over centuries. The unique characteristics of each nation are reflected in its culture. Translating the culture of a nation to readers of another nation requires a high level of skill from the translator. In particular, in such cases, the translator must be able to fully convey in the translation work those aspects that reflect the culture of the original book.

This article analyzes how the national characteristics are interpreted by the translator in the English translation of the work “Shum bola” by Gafur Gulom. In the process of translation, the translator is required to possess a great proficiency and linguistic flexibility in expressing national characteristics in another language. Furthermore, translating a work without losing its original meaning is also one of the challenges of the translation process. In this article, we delve into the intricacies of translating “Shum Bola” and the inherent complexities of bringing author’s narrative in English.

Key words: *translated works, artistic translation, linguistic and cultural features in translation, translator, types of translation, author, realia, national characteristics.*

Introduction. In order to preserve the national color in the translation process and bring it to a perfect level in another language, the translator must be closely familiar with that nation, and be able to feel its subtleties. A translator is an excellent bridge between two languages and two nations, through his ability to translate, the subtlest aspects of the people and nation are reflected. In particular, a special approach is required from the translator when translating the original words of the translated work into another language.

The great uzbek writer Gafur Gulom, distinguished by his emotional depth and lyrical language, made a great contribution to the development of Uzbek literature. He used rich metaphors and images to express his thoughts and feelings. His works explore various aspects of human existence, such as the transitory nature of life and the search for spiritual pleasure.

Literature analysis and methods.

For a translator, knowing the characteristics of two languages, i.e. foreign language and native language, is good practical knowledge, but it is not enough for translation. In addition to knowing the characteristics of the language, the translator should have a good knowledge of a number of principles developed in the theory of translation, and also have good reliable skills. “Shum Bola” is a

unique guide for ethnographers. Because it contains vivid stories about cities and villages in Tashkent and its surroundings, their cultural life, names, place names, children's games, and household lifestyle. This information was preserved in the translation, and the general meaning of the work was not lost, on the contrary, the spirit of nationalism in the work was skillfully conveyed. There are versions of the work translated into several foreign languages. F.Shaikhutdinova and A.Naumov translated the story into Russian, V.Grimych into Ukrainian, and I.Tokhtasinov into English.

Literary translation can be said to be almost on the same level as artistic creation in terms of its complexity and difficulty. The reason is that the work, which is the fruit of the author's talent and skill, needs to be recreated in accordance with the original with other language tools. Knowing the language is not enough for the translation of works of art, for this it is necessary to be aware of the talent of creativity and the science of art. According to the requirements of realistic translation, the translator should recreate the original as a work of art based on the unity of form and content, and preserve national and individual characteristics. Because every artistic work is written by a representative of a certain nation, and it will certainly contain characteristics that reflect the nationality.

The process of transferring cultural elements to another language environment through translation is a complex issue. Culture is a complex set of everyday life experiences that includes history, social system, religion, daily customs and traditions.

In the short story "Shum Bola", Gafur Gulam creates the image of a teenager with simple, innocent and pure natural qualities. The work is based on the adventures of an orphan, decorated with sharp humor. Although there are some autobiographical elements in the work, it tells about the adventures of Uzbek children. Due to the economic issues in the country, unemployment problem has arisen in the city. The fate of children like Amon, It Obid, Bit Obid, Turobboy,

Yoldosh, Husni, Salih, Abdullah, Polathoja, Miraziz in the story are similar to each other. Amon was separated from his mother, Yoldosh was separated from his parents, and the hero of “Shum Bola” was also separated from his father. If you pay attention to people’s professions, they are knife makers, collectors of scraps, tailors, jewelers, kerosene sellers, petty traders, etc.

It is noticeable that the words specific to the nationality are especially related to the image of these professions and clothes. For example, let’s pay attention to the translation of the sentence “... *bari mog’orlab ketgan surp yaktak kiyib olgan*”. In order to preserve the national color, the translator left some words in their original state without translating them, and defined them at the bottom of the page. Another reason for using this method is that there is no exact translation of these words, because they are only national in nature, and in English society such items are not used, or place names and names are not found. For example:

“*He wore a yaktak on his shoulder*” in the book the word “yaktak” is given like “oriental robe”, it is written at the bottom of the page. Or another example: “*Mullah had already tied his salla as a belt*”, in this sentence the word “salla” is defined like this: “A kind of head dress tied around the head, usually made of silk”, or in another part of the book “*He had put on his salla and his eyebrow and face were red and green*” the same word “salla” is translated as “turban”.

Conclusion. In the translation of humorous works serious linguistic and cultural problems are hidden, and life events are reflected in them. In the translation of each work, the mentality, outlook, and character of the nation are revealed. Gafur Gulam’s work “Naughty Boy” is a unique work in the history of Uzbek literature. In the story, not only the life of that time, but also the culture and traditions of the Uzbek nation are expressed. When the reader reads the translation of the work, the images presented in the original come to life without any changes, and he can clearly imagine items, clothes, etc. that are unfamiliar to him and of national importance. This shows how familiar the translator is with the culture of the original language and how skillfully he can illuminate it.

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**INGLIZ VA O‘ZBEK TILLARIDA YASAMA OTLARNING O‘XSHASH
VA FARQLI TOMONLARI**

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada ingliz va o‘zbek tillarida yasama, ya’ni qo‘shma otlarning o‘xshash va farqli tomonlari, ularning qanday usullar bilan yasalishi yoritib beriladi va har ikki tildan misollar keltirilib tahlil qilinadi.

Kalit so‘zlar: semantik usul (konversiya), fonetik , leksik-sintaktik, kompozitsiya, affiksatsiya

Abstract: In this article, the similarities and differences of compound nouns in English and Uzbek, the ways in which they are formed, and examples from both languages are analyzed.

Key words: semantic method (conversion), phonetic, lexical-syntactic, composition, affixation

Ma'lumki qo'shma so'zlar har tilda turli xil o'rganilib kelinadi. Bu fikrni uzoqqa ketib o'tirmasdan bizga yaqindan tanish bo'lgan o'zbek, rus, nemis va ingliz tillarida ko'rish mumkin. O'zbek tilida ham ingliz tilida ham qo'shma so'zlarning o'ziga xos o'rganilishi bor va ularning o'rtasida turli xil o'xshashliklar va farqlar mavjud. Umuman olganda, qiyoslanayotgan tillarda qo'shma otlar quyidagi usullar bilan hosil qilinadi:

1. Semantik usul (konversiya)
2. Fonetik usul
3. Leksik-sintaktik usul
4. Kompozitsiya
5. Affiksatsiya

O'zbek tilida **semantik usul** bilan so'z yasash o'ta shartlidir. Bunday usulda so'z yasashga quyidagi misollarni keltirish mumkin: tosh - kamen (ot), tosh - qaynab chiqmoq (fe'l); ich - ichki qism (ot), ich (fe'l) - ichmoq kabi. Bu usulda polisemantik so'zlar orasidagi ma'no ipi uzilib omonimlik hosil bo'ladi. O'zbek tilida bir so'z turkumining boshqa so'z turkumiga ko'chishi natijasida yangi so'z yasaladi. Katta - sifat, katta - ot; semiz - sifat, semiz ot. Semantik usulni ingliz tilida esa quyidagi so'zlarda ko'rish mumkin, ya'ni bu so'zlar bir so'z turkumidan boshqa so'z turkumiga ko'chish orqali hosil bo'ladi. Masalan: answer – javob (ot) to answer - javob bermoq(fe'l), clean – toza (sifat) to clean - tozalamoq (fe'l)[1]

Fonetik usul ingliz tilida turli usullarda hosil qilinadi :

- urg'uning o'rnini o'zgartirish bilan: increase ['inkri:s] - o'sish, ko'payish to increase [in'kris] - ko'paymoq export ['eksporto:t] - eksport to export [iks'po:t] - eksport qilmoq
- undosh tovushlar almashinuvi yo'li bilan: advice [ed'vais] - maslahat to advise [ed'vaiz] - maslahat bermoq life [laif] - hayot to live [liv] - yashamoq
- unli tovushlar almashinuvi yordamida: song [song] - ashula, qo'shiq sing [sing] - kuylamoq, qo'shiq; aytmoq food [fu:d] - ovqat feed [fi:d] - ovqatlanirmoq, ovqatlanmoq. [2]

O‘zbek tilida ham deyarli xuddi shunday usullar bilan hosil qilinadi, ya’ni :

- urg‘u vositasida so‘z yasaladi: yangi - hozir (ravish), yangi toza, (новыи) (sifat), 'olma - fe'l (harakat), olm'a - ot (meva), qatlama - ovqat (ot), qatlama harakat (fe'l).
- Unli va undosh tovush almashinishi usuli: ko‘r — ko‘z, aka - uka;
- Unli tovushlarni cho‘zish orqali: silamoq – siylamoq.
- Tovushlarni ikkilantirish usuli bilan: qatiq – qattiq. Tovushlarning birini tushirish bilan: sol ~ ol, toshmoq – oshmoq. Tovushlarning o‘rnini almashtirish bilan: siq — qis, chuk - kuch.

O‘zbek tilida so‘z qo‘shib so‘z yasash usuliga yaqin turgan tiplardan biri **leksik-sintaktik** usuldir. Bunda so‘z birikmasi yoki gaplar tarkibidagi elementlarning qo‘shilib ketishi natijasida yangi so‘z paydo bo‘ladi: **O‘zi** bilarmon, holbuki, bari bir kabi.

Leksik - sintaktik ingliz tilida esa so‘zlar bilan birgalikda predloglar, olmoshlar qo‘shish orqali yasaladi. Masala: forget - me - not - bo‘tako‘z (gulning nomi). stick - in - the mud - g‘ayratsiz, sust, kam harakat.

Kompozitsiya qo‘shma otlarning yasalishining yana bir xususiyati ularning ikkala komponenti ham urg‘u oladi. Hattoki urg‘u oladigan qo‘shma so‘z ajratib yozilsa ham uning har ikkala qismiga ham birdek urg‘u tushadi. Masalan, *football; armchair; mailbox* va boshqalar. Ammo istisno tariqasida *manKIND* so‘zini olishimiz mumkin. O‘zbek tilida qo‘shma so‘zlarning o‘rganilishida yakdillik yo‘q. Zero ayrim olingan bir til birligining o‘zi qo‘shma so‘z yoki bo‘lmasa so‘z birikmasi sifatida izohlaniladi. Masalan, “og‘ir oyoq” til birligi o‘zbek tilining izohli lug‘atida “og‘ir oyoq” deb ajratib yozilib, so‘z birikmasi sifatida beriladi va shu sahifaning o‘zida “og‘iroyoq” xomilador ma’nosida qo‘shma so‘z deb izohlaniladi va bu til birligining ikkinchi qo‘shma so‘z variantini to‘g‘riroq deb ma’qullaniladi [4,88].

Xulosa qilib aytganda, ikkala holatda ham mazkur til birliklarining nima sababdan qo‘shib yozilishi yoki nima sababdan ajratib yozilishi va ularning birga

yoki ajratib yozilgan holatlarida ma'no jihatdan o'zgarish yoki farqi bor yo'qligiga izoh berilmaydi. Ingliz va o'zbek tillaridagi qo'shma ot yasalishidagi qoliplarni chogishtirib o'rganish shu tillarga xos xususiyatlarni yanada chuqurroq o'rganishga, ularning mohiyatini anglashga ko'maklashadi.

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Phraseological Units in English and Their Analysis

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Abstract: This thesis explores the multifaceted role of phraseological units in the English language, focusing on their structure, usage, cultural implications, and implications for language teaching, translation studies, and cross-cultural communication. The study begins with an overview of phraseological units, defining them as fixed combinations of words with non-compositional meanings, and classifying them into various types such as idioms, collocations, phrasal verbs, proverbs, and fixed expressions.

Keywords: phraseological units, English language, idioms, collocations, proverbs, cultural implications, cross-cultural communication.

A phraseological unit, also known as a phraseme or multi-word expression, refers to a fixed combination of words with a specific meaning that differs from the literal interpretation of its individual components. These units include idioms, collocations, proverbs, fixed expressions, and other recurrent word combinations commonly used in language. The importance of phraseological units in language lies in their vital role in communication, contributing to fluency, expressiveness, and cultural richness. Native speakers commonly use phraseological units in everyday discourse, contributing to the naturalness and authenticity of language use. Learners of a language must acquire proficiency in understanding and using these units to achieve fluency and sound more like native speakers. Many phraseological units are deeply rooted in cultural contexts, reflecting the history, values, beliefs, and traditions of a particular community or society. Studying phraseological units provides valuable insights into the cultural aspects of language, helping learners develop cultural competence and cross-cultural communication skills.

Phraseological units contribute to the richness and diversity of language by introducing variation in style and register. Different genres of discourse, such as formal writing, informal conversation, or specialized domains, may employ specific sets of phraseological units, each serving different communicative purposes.

Phraseological units play a crucial role in language communication, enriching language use with expressiveness, cultural insights, and authenticity. Studying and analyzing these units provide valuable insights into the structure, usage, and cultural aspects of language, benefiting language learners, educators, translators, and researchers alike. They can be classified into various types based on their linguistic properties and characteristics. Some common types include:

1. Idioms: Fixed expressions whose meaning is not deducible from the literal meanings of their individual words (e.g., "kick the bucket" meaning to die).

2. Collocations: Word combinations that frequently co-occur in language use due to lexical, grammatical, or semantic associations (e.g., "strong coffee" instead of "powerful coffee").

3. Phrasal Verbs: Verbs combined with one or more particles (e.g., prepositions or adverbs) that together convey a distinct meaning different from the sum of their parts (e.g., "take off" meaning to depart suddenly or to become successful).

Phraseological units are dynamic linguistic entities that adapt and evolve over time in response to cultural changes, linguistic innovation, and contact with other languages. Borrowings, loan translations, and calques from other languages contribute to the enrichment and diversification of a language's phraseological repertoire. Similarly, sociohistorical events and technological advancements may give rise to new idiomatic expressions that reflect contemporary cultural realities. To illustrate of various types of phraseological units here some examples

1. Idioms: "Kick the bucket" - to die, "Break the ice" - to initiate conversation in a social setting

2. Collocations: "Strong coffee" - commonly used combination of words indicating the type of coffee, "Heavy rain" - natural pairing of words to describe the intensity of rainfall

3. Phrasal Verbs: "Break up" - to end a romantic relationship

4. Proverbs: "A stitch in time saves nine" - advocating for timely action to prevent larger problems

5. Fixed Expressions: "By and large" - to summarize or indicate a general trend.

These examples demonstrate the diverse range of phraseological units found in English, each serving unique communicative purposes and often

conveying meanings that extend beyond the literal interpretation of their individual words.

Phraseological units play a crucial role in language communication, contributing to fluency, expressiveness, and cultural richness. They encompass various types, including idioms, collocations, phrasal verbs, proverbs, and fixed expressions, each with its own linguistic properties and communicative functions. Comparative analysis of phraseological units across different languages and cultures reveals both universal themes and culturally specific nuances in the expression of cultural concepts.

In conclusion, phraseological units serve as linguistic repositories of cultural knowledge, offering valuable insights into the values, beliefs, and practices of a society. By examining the cultural dimensions of phraseological units, researchers can deepen their understanding of language as a dynamic reflection of human culture and identity.

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INVESTIGATION OF LEXICAL BORROWING DYNAMICS IN THE RUSSIAN LANGUAGE

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ANNOTATION

This thesis explores the phenomenon of borrowing terminology in the Russian language, focusing on the significant influx of new lexical and terminological units from foreign languages, particularly through Anglicisms and Americanisms, at the turn of the 20th-21st centuries. It highlights the role of globalization and the dominance of the English language in introducing foreign words into Russian, especially within the context of the rapidly evolving sectors of technology, economy, business, and tourism.

Keywords: *language borrowing, Russian language, word formation, transition, Anglicisms, Americanisms, globalization, international tourism, terminological adaptation.*

RUS TILIDAGI LEKSIK O'ZLASHTIRILISH DINAMIKASINING

TADQIQOTI

ANNOTATSIYA

Bu tezis rus tiliga terminologiyada o'zlashtirish hodisasini o'rganadi, ayniqsa, 20-21-asr boshlarida chet tillaridan, xususan, anglikizmlar va amerikanizmlar orqali yangi leksik va terminologik birliklarning katta oqimiga e'tibor qaratadi. Globalizatsiyaning va ingliz tilining ustunligining rus tiliga chet so'zlarini kiritishdagi rolini, ayniqsa, tez rivojlanayotgan texnologiya, iqtisodiyot, biznes va turizm sohalaridagi kontekstda ta'kidlaydi.

Kalit so'zlar: *leksik o'zlashrish, rus tili, so'z yasalishi, o'tish, anglikizmlar, amerikanizmlar, globalizatsiya, xalqaro turizm, terminologik moslashuv.*

ИССЛЕДОВАНИЕ ДИНАМИКИ ЛЕКСИЧЕСКОГО

ЗАЙМСТВОВАНИЯ В РУССКОМ ЯЗЫКЕ

АННОТАЦИЯ

Данный тезис исследует феномен заимствования терминологии в русском языке, сосредотачиваясь на значительном притоке новых лексических и терминологических единиц из иностранных языков, особенно через англицизмы и американизмы, на рубеже 20-21 веков. Здесь подчеркивает роль глобализации и доминирования английского языка во внедрении иностранных слов в русский, особенно в контексте быстро развивающихся секторов технологий, экономики, бизнеса и туризма.

Ключевые слова: *заимствование языка, русский язык, словообразование, англицизмы, американизмы, глобализация, международный туризм, терминологическая адаптация.*

Introduction. Significant enrichment of the vocabulary of modern Russian language occurs through the borrowing of new lexical and terminological units and the "avalanche-like" word formation (emergence of neologisms from the resources of the Russian language).

As Zavarzina G.A. stated borrowing, undoubtedly, is due to the openness of modern society: globalization and the strengthening of the position of the English language have led to a rapid influx of foreign words, primarily English-based Americanisms, into the Russian literary language [1; p.63].

Modern researchers agree that the main source of borrowings for the Russian language at the turn of the 20th-21st centuries has been the American variant of the English language. However, the language system has consistently demonstrated its stability by filtering out "unnecessary" lexical units and subjecting borrowed words to changes according to its own laws. Studies show that the expansion of the terminological composition of the international tourism subsystem in the Russian language at the turn of the 20th-21st centuries primarily occurs through various types of borrowing.

Main part. The turn of the 20th-21st centuries is marked by the development of various spheres of public life: high technology, economy, business, computer

technology. Marinova states that at this moment that a huge number of Anglicisms, particularly Americanisms, emerged, resulting in the American-centric nature of modern global culture [2; p.397]. The formation of the tourism industry in Russia takes place using foreign, primarily American and Western European, experience. Therefore, active borrowing of Anglicisms as one of the most productive ways of term formation in the "tourism" terminological system is an obvious fact that can be attributed to a typological feature of the Russian language [3, p. 19].

Foreign neologisms expand the composition of all thematic groups in the international tourism terminology subsystem in the Russian language of the modern period: I. Names of forms and types of international tourism (e.g., ecotourism, e-tourism, intensive tourism, caravanning, etc.). II. Designations of concepts related to the organization of the infrastructure of international tourism: 1) transportation provisions of the international tourism industry and their specific features (e.g., airfare, shuttle service, interrail, low-cost, etc.); 2) names of consumer accommodation systems and their specifics (e.g., pet-friendly hotel, capsule hotel, aparthotel, boutique hotel, congress hotel, condominium hotel, bungalow, villa, suite, hostel, parking, etc.); 3) names of phenomena and concepts related to food in the field of international tours (e.g., continental breakfast, European plan, duty-free, minibar, catering, lobby bar, snack bar, etc.); 3) designations of concepts related to information and excursion support in international tourism (e.g., animation, Disneyland, oceanarium, water park, etc.).

The main trend in the adaptation processes of borrowed terms of the international tourism subsystem in the Russian literary language is practical transcription, that is, the traditional focus on the phonetic features (peculiarities of pronunciation) of the etymon of the borrowed word in the source language.

Conclusion. Thus, it should be noted that currently the basic terminology system of international tourism is English-language and borrowing is one of the main means of replenishing the terminology of international tourism. The active

processes of borrowing terms are due to the need of society and language to nominate new tourism concepts, the tendency towards language economy and the desire to universalize the terminology of international tourism. At the same time, the existence and functioning of many variants of borrowed terms is undoubtedly evidence of the dynamics of the development of international tourism terminology.

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O‘ZBEK VA INGLIZ TILSHUNOSLIGIDA PRETSEDENT NOMLARGA BO‘LGAN MADANIY TA‘SIRLAR

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Annotatsiya: Tillar jamiyat madaniyati, tarixi va an'alarining aksidir. Har bir tilning o'ziga xos xususiyatlari va qoidalari bor va ularni o'rganish jamiyatni yaxshiroq tushunishga yordam beradi. Tillarning ana shunday xususiyatlaridan biri pretsedent otlarning ishlatilishidir. Pretsedent otlar matnda, nutqda yoki suhbatda ilgari ishlatilgan va yana murojaat qilingan otlardir. Ular tilning tuzilishi va ishlatilishini tushunishda muhim ahamiyatga ega. Ushbu maqola ingliz va o'zbek tillaridagi pretsedent otlar, ularning qo'llanilishi va ahamiyatini o'rganishga qaratilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: Tilshunoslik, Pretsedent otlar, Ingliz tili, O'zbek tili, Sintaksis, Semantika, Diskurs tahlili, Kognitiv ishlov berish, Olmoshlar, Ot so'z birikmalari, Uyushma, Muloqot, Oldindan, Olmosh integratsiyasi, Qiyosiy tahlil.

Kirish: Pretsedent otlarning tildagi ta'rifi va ahamiyati. Pretsedent otlar, tilshunoslik nuqtai nazaridan, muayyan hodisalar, belgilar yoki tushunchalar bilan bog'liqligi tufayli madaniy, tarixiy yoki adabiy ahamiyatga ega bo'lgan otlarni anglatadi. Ushbu otlar ko'pincha jamiyatda umumiy tushuncha yoki mos yozuvlar nuqtasini keltirib chiqaradi va tildan foydalanishga ma'no qatlamlarini qo'shadi.

Ismlar shunchaki yorliqlar emas ular jamiyatning qadriyatlari, an'analari va jamoaviy o'ziga xosligini aks ettiruvchi madaniy artefaktlardir. Madaniyatning nom berish amaliyotiga ta'siri, ayniqsa, shaxs ismlari, joy nomlari va boshqa muhim unvonlarni o'z ichiga olgan pretsedent nomlarda yaqqol namoyon bo'ladi.¹⁰ Ushbu maqolada biz o'zbek va ingliz tilshunosligi o'rtasidagi qiyosiy tahlilga e'tibor qaratib, madaniyat va pretsedent nomlar o'rtasidagi murakkab munosabatni ko'rib chiqamiz. Madaniy omillar ushbu ikki xil lingvistik landshaftdagi nomlanish qoidalarini qanday shakllantirishini o'rganib, biz o'zlikni

¹⁰ Ruzikulovna, A. D. (2020). Linguocultural and linguopoetic study of the precedent names in Uzbek language. ANGLISTICUM. Journal of the Association-Institute for English Language and American Studies, 9(9), 45-54.

shakllantirish va lingvistik tasvirning murakkabliklari haqida qimmatli tushunchalarga ega bo'lamiz.

O'zbek va ingliz madaniyatida nom qo'yish qoidalari tarixiy, ijtimoiy va lingvistik kontekstlarda chuqur ildiz otgan. O'zbek madaniyatida ismlar ko'pincha oilaviy ahamiyatga ega bo'lib, shaxslar ajdodlar yoki hurmatli shaxslar nomi bilan atalgan.¹¹ Bundan tashqari, diniy e'tiqod va madaniy urf-odatlarini aks ettiruvchi o'zbek shaxs ismlarida islomiy ta'sirlar yaqqol namoyon bo'ladi. Aksincha, inglizcha nomlash konventsionalari tarixiy voqealar, diniy mansubliklar va ijtimoiy tendentsiyalar ta'sirida ko'proq rang-barangdir. Masalan, familiyalar ko'pincha ajdodlar kasbini yoki geografik kelib chiqishini bildiradi va ingliz nomlash amaliyotining ko'p qirrali xususiyatini ta'kidlaydi.

Pretsedent nomlar ham o'zbek, ham ingliz jamiyatlarida muhim ijtimoiy-madaniy ahamiyatga ega. O'zbek madaniyatida ismlar o'ziga xoslik va nasl-nasab belgisi sifatida qaraladi, ijtimoiy rishtalar va qarindoshlik rishtalarini mustahkamlaydi. Shaharlar, daryolar va tog'lar kabi joy nomlari tarixiy rivoyatlar va geografik ahamiyatga ega bo'lib, odamlarda tegishlilik hissi va madaniy merosni shakllantiradi. Xuddi shunday, ingliz tilida so'zlashuvchi jamiyatlarda pretsedent nomlar tarixiy voqealar, mustamlakachilik merosi va ijtimoiy qadriyatlarni aks ettiruvchi madaniy belgi bo'lib xizmat qiladi. Pretsedent nomlarning ahamiyati tarixiy yodgorliklarni asrab-avaylash va nom berish amaliyoti orqali taniqli shaxslarni xotirlashda yaqqol namoyon bo'ladi.

Pretsedent nomlarning shakllanishi va rivojlanishiga tarixiy voqealar va til taraqqiyoti ta'sir ko'rsatadi. O'zbek tilshunosligida arab va forscha unsurlarning o'zlashtirilishi leksikani boyitdi, shaxs va joy nomlarining rang-barang bo'lishiga xizmat qildi. Xuddi shunday, ingliz pretsedent nomlari vaqt o'tishi bilan lotin, frantsuz va german tillari ta'sirini o'z ichiga olgan holda

¹¹ Tayirovna, A. S. (2023). LINGUOCULTURAL RESEARCH OF THE CONCEPT "EDUCATION" IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES. *European International Journal of Pedagogics*, 3(03), 11-15.

rivojlandi. Ismlarning etimologiyasi lingvistik landshaftlarni shakllantirgan madaniy almashinuvlar, migratsiya va istilolar haqida tushuncha beradi.

O'zbek pretsedent nomlariga ko'p madaniyatli ta'sirlar mintaqadagi turli etnik va til guruhlarining tarixiy almashinuvi va aralashishini ham aks ettiradi. Natijada o'zbek nomlari o'zbek xalqining murakkab va boy merosini aks ettiruvchi lisoniy elementlarning uyg'unligini namoyon etadi.

O'zbek tilida *madaniy bayramlar, diniy bayramlar, an'anaviy voqealar* va tarixiy bosqichlardan ilhomlanib, oldingi nomlarga sezilarli ta'sir ko'rsatadi. Mana bir nechta misollar:

Navro'z bilan bog'liq ismlar: - *Navro'zbek:* O'zbekistonda nishonlanadigan "Navro'z"ni, forscha Yangi yilni "o'zbek" bilan birlashtirib, madaniy o'ziga xoslikni aks ettiruvchi nom. - *Bahrom:* "Omad" yoki "farovonlik" ma'nosi, Navro'zning ijobiy ruhi bilan bog'liq ism.

Islom bayramlari: - *Layli:* Muborak Ramazon oyida muhim voqea bo'lgan Qadr kechasi Laylatul Qadr dan ilhomlangan ism. - *Ismoil:* Islomiy ahamiyatga ega bo'lgan, payg'ambar bilan bog'liq bo'lgan, ko'pincha diniy bayramlarda tanlangan ism.

Mustaqillik bayrami va tarixiy shaxslar: - *Islom Karimov:* O'zbekistonning birinchi prezidenti Islom Karimovning nom qo'yish amaliyotiga ta'sirini aks ettirish. - *Mustaqillik:* "Mustaqillik" ma'nosi, O'zbekiston mustaqilligini nishonlash uchun tanlangan nom.

Xalq an'analari: - *Dilfuza:* "dil" (yurak) va "fuza" (mo'llik)ni o'zida mujassam etgan nom bo'lib, o'zbek madaniyatida nishonlanadigan ijobiy fazilatlarni aks ettiradi.

- *Bahromjon:* "bahrom" (omad) so'zini "-jon" mehr qo'shimchasi bilan birlashtirgan ism.

Madaniy meros: - *Amir Temur:* O‘zbek tarixining ko‘zga ko‘ringan arbobi Amir Temur (Temur)ning tarixiy merosini aks ettirish. - *Feruza:* O‘zbekistonda madaniy ahamiyatga ega bo‘lgan an‘anaviy qimmatbaho tosh turkuazdan ilhomlangan ism.

O‘zbek tilshunosligida pretsedent otlarni o‘rganish tarixiy taraqqiyot, lingvistik xususiyatlar va nom qo‘yish amaliyoti bilan bog‘liq kontekst omillari haqida qimmatli ma‘lumotlar beradi. Ko‘chmanchi qabilalar, islom urf-odatlar va oila nasl-nasabining ta‘siri o‘zbek nomlash an‘analarining boy gobelenini shakllantirgan.

Ingliz va o‘zbek tillarida nom qo‘yish amaliyoti dinamik va davom etayotgan madaniy almashinuvlar, globallashuv va migratsiya natijasida rivojlanishda davom etishini tan olish muhimdir. Jamiyatlar o‘zaro bog‘liqlik kuchayib borayotgani sari ko‘p jamiyatlarning ta‘siri kuchayadi. Konventsionalarni nomlash bo‘yicha madaniyatshunoslik ikkala tilning leksikasini va madaniy amaliyotini shakllantirishda davom etadi.¹² Ushbu davom etayotgan evolyutsiya ko‘p madaniyatli ta‘sirlarning til va nomlash an‘analariga doimiy ta‘siridan dalolat beradi.

Pretsedant otlar madaniy me‘yorlar va qadriyatlarni qanday aks ettirishini o‘rganar ekanmiz

Madaniy ramz: Pretsedent otlar ko‘pincha madaniy qadriyatlar va me‘yorlarni o‘zida mujassamlashtirgan lingvistik belgilar vazifasini bajaradi. Masalan, "*Amerika orzusi*" yoki "*Fransuz inqilobi*" kabi atamalar kengroq ijtimoiy intilishlarni yoki tarixiy qo‘zg‘olonlarni o‘zida mujassam etgan.

Kollektiv xotira va identifikatsiya: Bu otlar umumiy xotirani qurishga hissa qo‘shadi, umumiy tajribani ifodalaydi va madaniy o‘ziga xoslikni

¹² Саидов Ё., Умурова Х. Лингвокультурологик тадқиқотлар методологияси // Наманган давлат университети илмий ахборотномаси. –Наманган: 2020. –Б. 297-304.

shakllantiradi. "*Holokost*" yoki "*Magna Karta*" nafaqat tarixiy voqealarni uyg'otadi, balki chuqur madaniy ahamiyatga ega.

Ijtimoiy tuzilmalar va ideallar: Pretsedent otlar jamiyatning muvaffaqiyat, adolat yoki axloq haqidagi tasavvurini belgilaydigan ijtimoiy tuzilmalar va ideallarni o'zida mujassam etgan. "*Feminizm*" yoki "*Fuqarolik huquqlari harakati*" kabi atamalar jamiyatning tenglik va adolatga intilishlarini qamrab oladi.

Til madaniyat ko'zgusi sifatida: Pretsedent otlarning evolyutsiyasi vaqt o'tishi bilan madaniy paradigmalarning o'zgarishini aks ettiradi. Tildan foydalanishdagi o'zgarishlar, masalan, "*barqarorlik*" yoki "*uyg'onish*" kabi atamalarning kiritilishi zamonaviy madaniy tashvish va qadriyatlarni aks ettiradi.

Adabiyotda hikoya qurilishi: Adabiyotda mualliflar madaniy me'yorlarni aks ettiruvchi rivoyatlarni qurish uchun pretsedent otlarni strategik tarzda qo'llaydilar. "*Vizantiya*" yoki "*Gotik*" kabi atamalardan foydalanish muayyan madaniy kontekstlarni va estetik imtiyozlarni bildirishi mumkin.

Efemer va rivojlanayotgan ma'nolar: Pretsedent otlarning ma'nolari o'zgaruvchan ijtimoiy qadriyatlarga moslashib, madaniy evolyutsiyaga duchor bo'ladi. "*Ozodlik*" yoki "*Taraqqiyot*" kabi atamalarning qayta talqin qilinishi vaqt o'tishi bilan madaniy istiqbollardagi o'zgarishlarni aks ettiradi.

Siyosiy va tarixiy ma'nolar: Pretsedent otlar ko'pincha muayyan davrlar bilan bog'liq qadriyatlarni o'zida mujassam etgan siyosiy va tarixiy ma'noga ega. "*Sovuq urush*" yoki "*Aparteid*" ismlar tarixiy va siyosiy mafkuralarni qamrab oladigan misollardir.

Aslini olganda, pretsedent otlar madaniy me'yorlar va qadriyatlarni kristallashtiradigan lingvistik tomirlar vazifasini bajaradi. Ular jamiyatning kollektiv ongini, uning tarixiy sayohatini va uning o'ziga xosligini

shakllantiradigan ideallarni tahlil qilish uchun lingvistik ob'ektivni taqdim etadi.¹³ O'zbek va ingliz tilshunosligi o'rtasidagi tafovutlarga qaramay, ikkala madaniyat ham madaniyatning pretsedent nomlarga chuqur ta'sirini ko'rsatadi. O'zbek ismlarini qo'yishda oila a'zolari va diniy mansublikka urg'u berilgan bo'lsa, inglizcha nom qo'yish amaliyoti xilma-xilligi va tarixiy murakkabligi bilan ajralib turadi. Shunga qaramay, pretsedent nomlarga berilgan ijtimoiy-madaniy ahamiyat universal bo'lib qolmoqda, bu madaniyatning lingvistik tasvir va o'ziga xoslik qurilishiga doimiy ta'sirini ta'kidlaydi.

Madaniyatning pretsedent nomlarga ta'siri til chegaralaridan oshib, o'zbek va ingliz jamiyatlarida nomlanish qoidalari va o'ziga xoslik shakllanishini shakllantiradi. Pretsedent nomlarning ijtimoiy-madaniy ahamiyatini anglash orqali biz til, madaniyat va o'zlikni anglash murakkabliklarini chuqurroq tushunamiz. Oldinga qarab, nomlash amaliyoti dinamikasi bo'yicha keyingi tadqiqotlar madaniy xilma-xillik va til merosiga bo'lgan munosabatimizni boyitishi mumkin.

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¹³ Рихсиева Г. Лингвопоэтик тадқиқ асослари бўйича мулоҳазалар // Ўзбек тили ва адабиёти. –Т.: 2003. – Б. 84-86.

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ALTERNATIVE ANALYSIS OF ENGLISH PROVERBS AND APHORISMS IN UZBEK

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Introduction to Proverbs and Aphorisms: Proverbs and aphorisms, succinct expressions of wisdom or advice, have long been an integral part of human communication across cultures and languages. They encapsulate the collective wisdom of societies, offering insights into shared values, beliefs, and experiences. In English language and literature, proverbs and aphorisms are pervasive, often passed down through generations and woven into the fabric of everyday speech. From Benjamin Franklin's famous aphorisms to Shakespeare's timeless proverbs, these concise phrases serve as memorable guides for navigating life's complexities.

Translation Challenges: Translating English proverbs and aphorisms into Uzbek presents a myriad of challenges due to linguistic and cultural differences between the two languages. Firstly, the idiomatic nature of many English expressions often poses difficulties in finding equivalent equivalents in Uzbek, which may lack direct parallels. Additionally, nuances in syntax, word choice, and cultural connotations can complicate the translation process. For instance,

idioms related to weather or animals may carry different cultural associations in Uzbekistan compared to English-speaking countries.

Moreover, the cultural richness of English proverbs and aphorisms may not easily resonate with Uzbek audiences if their origins and historical contexts are unfamiliar. Translators must navigate these cultural disparities delicately to ensure the essence and intended meaning of the original expression are preserved.

Cultural Context: The interpretation and understanding of English proverbs and aphorisms in Uzbekistan are profoundly influenced by the cultural context of the country. Uzbekistan's rich tapestry of traditions, values, and social norms shapes the perception of these expressions in unique ways. Traditional Uzbek culture places a high value on hospitality, respect for elders, and the importance of community, which may color the interpretation of proverbs and aphorisms related to these themes.

Furthermore, Uzbekistan's history of Islamic influence and Soviet legacy adds layers of complexity to the cultural context. Islamic teachings on morality and ethics may intersect with English proverbs conveying similar virtues, while the Soviet era introduced ideological perspectives that may contrast with Western notions embedded in some aphorisms.

In conclusion, translating and interpreting English proverbs and aphorisms in Uzbekistan requires careful consideration of linguistic nuances and cultural contexts. By understanding the challenges and complexities involved, scholars and translators can delve deeper into the cross-cultural exchange of wisdom encapsulated in these timeless expressions.

Language Nuances: The linguistic nuances between English and Uzbek languages can significantly affect the translation and interpretation of proverbs and aphorisms. One of the key challenges arises from the differences in idiomatic expressions, where phrases with similar meanings in English may not have direct equivalents in Uzbek, and vice versa. For example, the English proverb "A penny

saved is a penny earned" relies on the concept of saving money, which may not translate directly into Uzbek due to differences in economic practices or currency.

Wordplay is another aspect that can be challenging to translate. English proverbs often employ puns, alliteration, or rhymes to convey meaning, which may not be easily replicated in Uzbek. Figurative language, such as metaphors and similes, also varies between the two languages, requiring translators to find creative solutions to convey the intended message effectively.

Adaptation and Interpretation: In Uzbek culture, English proverbs and aphorisms are adapted and interpreted through the lens of local customs, beliefs, and values. Direct translation may not always capture the essence of the original expression, leading to alternative interpretations that resonate more deeply with Uzbek audiences. For instance, the English proverb "Actions speak louder than words" may be interpreted in Uzbek as "Deeds reveal the truth," emphasizing the importance of demonstrating one's intentions through actions rather than mere promises. Cultural nuances play a significant role in shaping alternative interpretations of English proverbs and aphorisms in Uzbekistan. For example, expressions related to family dynamics or social hierarchies may be reinterpreted to reflect Uzbek traditions of respect for elders and communal solidarity.

Literary Examples:

English: *"Don't count your chickens before they hatch."*

Analysis: While the literal translation is maintained, the Uzbek version emphasizes the cautionary aspect of not presuming success prematurely.

English: *"The early bird catches the worm."*

Analysis: This Uzbek interpretation underscores the importance of timely action, albeit in a different metaphorical context.

English: *"Every cloud has a silver lining."*

Analysis: While the English proverb suggests finding hope in adversity, the Uzbek version employs a different metaphor, emphasizing the potential for unexpected blessings.

In each example, the essence of the original expression is preserved while adapting to the linguistic and cultural nuances of the Uzbek context. Through such adaptations, English proverbs and aphorisms continue to resonate with Uzbek audiences, offering timeless wisdom that transcends cultural boundaries.

Impact on Communication: Understanding English proverbs and aphorisms can significantly enhance cross-cultural communication between English speakers and Uzbek speakers. These expressions serve as cultural bridges, allowing individuals from different backgrounds to connect and relate to shared human experiences. Knowledge of English proverbs can help English speakers better understand Uzbek culture and vice versa, fostering empathy and mutual respect.

However, misunderstandings can arise if cultural differences are not taken into account. For example, the English proverb "Curiosity killed the cat" may not translate directly into Uzbek and could be misinterpreted if not explained properly. Moreover, idiomatic expressions that rely on cultural references may confuse non-native speakers if they are unfamiliar with the context. Therefore, effective communication requires sensitivity to cultural nuances and clear explanations of unfamiliar expressions.

Educational Significance: Studying English proverbs and aphorisms in Uzbekistan offers numerous educational benefits. Incorporating these expressions into language learning curricula enriches students' understanding of both languages and cultures. By exploring the meanings and origins of proverbs, students develop linguistic proficiency and cultural competence. Moreover, analyzing the similarities and differences between English and Uzbek expressions promotes critical thinking and intercultural awareness. Furthermore, studying proverbs provides insights into the historical, social, and philosophical aspects of both English and Uzbek societies. It encourages students to reflect on universal themes such as love, friendship, and perseverance, transcending linguistic boundaries.

Literary Critique: The translation and interpretation of English proverbs and aphorisms in Uzbek literature require careful consideration and skill. Translators must balance fidelity to the original text with the need to convey the intended meaning effectively in the target language. Successful translations capture the essence of the original expression while adapting to the linguistic and cultural context of Uzbekistan.

However, some translations may take creative liberties or depart from the original meaning to accommodate cultural differences. While this can enrich the text and make it more accessible to Uzbek readers, it may also alter the intended message of the original expression. Therefore, critical analysis of translations is essential to assess their effectiveness and fidelity to the source material.

Future Directions: Future research in the field of alternative analysis of English proverbs and aphorisms in Uzbek can explore several avenues. Scholars could investigate the reception and interpretation of translated proverbs in Uzbek literature and society, examining how these expressions contribute to cultural identity and communication practices. Additionally, comparative studies of proverbs across different languages and cultures can shed light on universal themes and values.

Collaboration between linguists, translators, and cultural scholars is essential for advancing our understanding of cross-cultural communication through proverbs and aphorisms. By fostering interdisciplinary dialogue and research, future studies can deepen our appreciation for the rich tapestry of human expression and enhance intercultural understanding in an increasingly interconnected world.

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**O‘ZBEK VA INGLIZ TILLI FE’L ZAMONLARI QIYOSIY
TIPOLOGIYASIDA GRAMMATIK SHAKL VA MA’NO
MUNOSABATLARI**

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Annotatsiya: Til grammatikasida ma’no va shakl munosabatlarini qiyoslash orqali ular o‘rtasidagi o‘zaro mutanosiblik va farqli jihatlar mukammalroq o‘rganiladi. Mazkur ilmiy izlanishda ingliz va o‘zbek tili fe’l so‘z turkumi zamon kategoriyasining grammatik shakl hamda ma’no munosabatlari o‘zaro qiyoslash orqali tahlil qilinadi. Qiyosiy tahlillar natijasida har ikkala tildagi kategorial birliklar klassifikatsiyasi va shakl hamda ma’no munosabatlari tahlil qilindi. Umumiy holatda mazkur tahlillar til korpusini yaratishda hamda uning tahliliy natijasini o‘rganishda ko‘maklashadi.

Kalit so‘zlar: fe’l zamonlari, grammatik shakl, grammatik ma’no, qiyosiy tipologiya, til korpusi

Kirish. Fe’l so‘z turkumi boshqa so‘z turkumlaridan ustunlik jihati u ma’no, grammatik shakllar va sintaktik vazifalarga boydir. Fe’l so‘z turkumi ish-harakatni, mavjudlikni, holatni va munosabatni zamon nuqtai nazaridan aniqlagan holda jarayon tarzida voqelik bilan bog‘laydi.¹⁴ Har ikkala tilda fe’lning ish-harakatni holatni yoki munosabat ma’nosini bildirishi uning grammatik kategoriyalari ko‘pligini ifodalaydi. Ingliz tilida fe’lning shaxs-son, aspekt, mayl, nisbat, zamon, modallik kabi grammatik kategoriyalari farqlanadi. Yu.S.Maslov ta’kidlaganidek, fe’l vaqt davomida sodir bo‘ladigan belgining, harakatning grammatik ahamiyatini ifodalaydigan so‘z turkumi bo‘lib hisoblanadi. Harakatning grammatik ahamiyatini keng ma’noda tushunish mumkin. U nafaqat harakat va tom ma’nodagi faoliyatni ifodalaydi, balki holatni va ma’lum bir

¹⁴ <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/fe-l-so-z-turkumi-va-uning-leksik-semantik-tasnifi/viewer>
(murojaat sanasi: 16.09.2023.)

predmet yoki shaxsning mavjudligini ko'rsatadi.¹⁵ O'zbek tili grammatikasida ham fe'llarda shaxs-son, mayl, zamon, nisbat, bo'lishli va bo'lishsizlik, o'timli va o'timsiz kabi kategoriyalar mavjud.

Ilmiy ish metodi. Har ikkala o'zbek va ingliz tilida zamon kategoriyasi o'rganilganda asosan vaqt (zamon) va borliq (makon) tushunchasi hamohangligi tushuniladi. Ingliz tilida ham, o'zbek tilida ham fe'llarning hozirgi, o'tgan va kelasi zamondagi harakatlarni ifodalashi nazarda tutiladi.

Tishunos olim G. A. Abdurahmonova fe'l zamonlarini quyidagi sxema asosida tadqiq etadi. (*Sxema 1*)¹⁶

Yuqorida ko'rsatib o'tilgan sxemada vaqtning borliqqa nisbati ko'rsatilgan bo'lib, bunda nutq jarayoning hozirgi va kelasi zamon oralig'ida joylashgan. Bu esa mantiqiy nuqtai nazardan uchta zamon: hozirgi, o'tgan va kelasi zamon farqlanishini ko'rsatadi.

Zamon kategoriyasi ingliz tilida juda keng ko'lamli lingvistik fenomen bo'lib, harakatning vaqtga (zamonga) nisbatan sodir bo'lganini, sodir bo'layotganini va sodir bo'lishini anglatadi.

Ingliz tilida zamonlar aspekt kategoriyasi bilan chambarchast bog'liq bo'lib, lingvistik fenomen sifatida ularni chambarchast bog'liqligi yaxlit zamoni ma'nosini ifodalaydi. Shuning uchun ham ingliz tilda ko'pchilik hollarda 26 ta

¹⁵ Ю. Маслов. Введение в языкознание: Учеб. для филол. спец. вузов. -2-е изд., перераб. и доп.—М.: Высш. шк., 1987.—272 с

¹⁶ Абдурахмонова Г. ва бошқалар. Ўзбек тили грамматикаси. 1 том, - Тошкент “Ўқитувчи” 1981.

fe'l zamon mavjud degan noto'g'ri xulosa qilinadi. Mazkur yo'nalishda E. G. Dobronetskaya izlanish olib boradi va quyidagi diagrammada ifodalaydi. (Sxema 2)¹⁷.

Vaqt chizig'idagi nuqta harakat momentini bildiradi. Yarim doiralalar vaqt chizig'ining nuqtasidan ajratilgan (harakat momentini) munosabatini bildiradi. Vaqt oralig'ining o'sib borishi, keyinchalik o'tmish, hozirgi va kelajakni ko'rsatadi. Quyida keltirilgan diagrammalar noaniq, davomli va tugallangan zamonlarning harakatlarini ko'rsatadi. Kesilgan chiziqlar vaqt davrini ko'rsatadi. Dobronetskayaning ushbu ta'rifi bosqichdagi harakatni mantiqiy aniqlashga asoslangan. Vaqt chizig'ining boshida va oxirida belgilanmagan igna ish-harakatning boshlanishi noma'lum, lekin oxiri aniq ekanligini ko'rsatadi. Igna vaqt chizig'idan boshlanib, fazoga ketadi degan ma'noni anglatadi.

Yuqoridagi sxemadan ingliz tili fe'llarida aspekt kategoriyasi (indefinite - noaniq; continuous-davomli; perfect-tugallangan, perfect continuous-tugallangan

¹⁷ Добронетская Э. Г. Грамматические трудности английского языка. Ленинград. «Просвещение» 1961.

davomli zamon) zamon kategoriyasi bilan chambarchast bo'liqligi ko'rsatib o'tilgan.

Ingliz tili fe'llarining noaniq (indefinite/simple) aspekti asosan doimiy, odatiy va umumiy ish-harakatlarni ifodalab keladi: *Students usually get up earlier. (Talabalar odatda vaqtlitroq uyg'onishadi); We watched TV with our family yesterday. (Biz kecha oilamiz bilan kecha televizor tomosha qildik.); They will meet us tomorrow. (Ular ertaga bizlarni uchratishadi.); davomli* (continuous) aspekt ish-harakatning davomiyligini bildiradi: *We are learning foreign language now (Biz hozir xorijiy tillarni o'rganayapmiz); Were you joining us at 4 o'clock yesterday. (Kecha soat 4 da bizga qo'shilgandingiz); The director of company will be waiting for us at 3 o'clock tomorrow (Kompaniya direktori ertaga soat 4 gacha bizni kutayotgan bo'ladi); tugallangan* (perfect) aspektida ish harakat tugallanganlik ma'nosini ifodalaydi: *I have not done this work yet (Men hali bu ishni bajarmadim); The author had written the novel in 1999 on the 4th of May. (Muallif asarni 1999 yil 4 mayda yozib bo'ldi); Anvar will have gone to the cinema tomorrow by 5 o'clock. (Anvar soat 5 gacha kinoteatrqa borgan bo'ladi); tugallangan davomli* (perfect continuous) aspekti ish-harakatning ma'lum bir davr mobaynida davom etib turganligini ifodalaydi: *I have been working in this factory for 5 years (Men 5 yildan beri shu fabrikada ishlayapman); Had you been cleaning the room before they came?(Ular kelishidan oldin siz xonani tozalagandingizmi?);*

O'zbek tilida zamon kategoriyasi ingliz tilidagi kabi ish-harakatning zamon va makonga nisbatan munosabatini ifodalaydi. O'zbek tilida fe'llarda aspekt kategoriyasi mavjud emas.

O'zbek tili grammatikasida fe'l zamonlarini tadqiq qilishda bir qator qarashlar ilgari surilgan. Bunga sabab qadimiy turkiy til asosida fe'l zamonlarining talqin qilinishi ko'rsatiladi. Tilshunos olim A. Fitrat¹⁸ kelasi

¹⁸ Фитрат А. Сарф. 1-китоб.- Тошкент: "Фан". 1925.-88 б.

zamonni 5 guruhga bo'ladi: a) imperativ fe'llar, b) o'tgan zamon, c) o'timli fe'llar (yozg'ayin), d) shartli fe'llar (yozsam), e) vibrativ fe'llar (yozsamchi). Bunday guruhlanish qadimiy turkiy tillarning xususiyatiga asoslangan.

A. Sulaymonova¹⁹, A. Hojiev²⁰ and J. Juraeva hozirgi zamon fe'llarini 2 ga bo'ladi: a) aniq hozirgi zamon, b) hozirgi kelasi zamonga bo'ladi. A. Hojiyev hozirgi kelasi zamonni noaniq hozirgi kelasi zamon va aniq hozirgi kelasi zamonga ajratadi. Tilshunos olim J. M. Jurayevning fikricha kelasi zamon 5 guruhga ajratiladi: a) hozirgi-kelasi zamon, b) noaniq kelasi zamon, c) kelasi qat'y zamon d) kelasi tarixiy qat'y zamon, e) kelasi zamon davom fe'li.

O'zbek tili fe'llarining o'tgan zamoni tilshunis olim A. G'ulomov²¹ 6 guruhga bo'ladi: a) aniq o'tgan zamon, b) tarixiy o'tgan zamon, c) uzoq o'tgan zamon, d) o'tgan zamon hikoya fe'li, e) o'tgan zamon eshituv fe'li f) tugallangan o'tgan zamon yoki o'tgan zamon davom fe'li.

Natijalar tahlili. Masalaning yechimi sifatida tilshunos olim A. Hojiyev va J. Jo'rayevalarning bir-biriga qarama-qarshi qo'yilgan xulosalarini izohlash mumkin. Bunda har ikkala olimning umumiy yondashuvi zamon gramatik shakllarini uch guruhga bo'lib (o'tgan zamon shakllar, hozirgi zamon shakllari va hozirgi-kelasi zamon shakllari) o'rganish bo'lgan bo'lsa, J. Jo'rayeva²² kelasi zamon shakllarini guruhlarga bo'ladi hamda hozirgi-kelasi zamonni kelasi zamon tarkibida tadqiq qiladi. Demak, xulosa o'rnida shuni aytish mumkinki zamonaviy o'zbek tilida fe'l zamonlarining 3 ta: hozirgi, o'tgan va kelasi zamon shakllari mavjud va ular tilshunos olimlar tomonidan tadqiq qilinib guruhlarga bo'lingan bo'lsada, ularda yaxlit apekt kategoriyasi mavjud emas.

¹⁹ Сулаймонова А. Ҳ. ва бошқалар. Феъл замонлари. – Тошкент: “Ўқитувчи” 1962 – 168 б.

²⁰ Ҳожиёв А. Ўзбек тилида ҳозирги замон феъли. Канд. дисс. Тошкент, 1959.

²¹ Ғуломов А. Ғ. Феъл. - Тошкент: “Ўзфанакад”-1954. -88 б.

²² Жўраева Ж. Ҳозирги замон ўзбек адабий тилида келаси замон феъли: фил. фан. номз..... дисс. Тошкент. 1961. 21 бет.

Xulosa. Har ikkala tilda ham vaqtga nisbat olinadigan bo'lsa, mantiqiy jihatdan o'tmish, kelajak hamda hozir (ayni payt) farqlanadi. Hozirgi zamon 5-sinf darsliklarida fe'lning zamon kategoriyasi uchta qilib ko'rsatib o'tilgan: hozirgi, o'tgan, kelasi zamon; Ingliz tilida tilning shakllanish tarixi va "slavyan tillar" oilasiga mansubligi tufayli aspekt kategoriyasi vujudga kelgan. Bu holat ingliz tilida ob'ektiv vaqtning har bir zamon klassifikatsiyasida tutgan o'rnining chuqur ifodalanishiga olib kelgan. Fe'l zamonlarining o'zbek va ingliz tillardagi qiyosiy tahlili kelgusida til korpuslarini shakllatirishda birlamchi omil bo'lib xizmat qiladi.

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UNDERSTANDING LANGUAGE ACQUISITION: THE JOURNEY OF LEARNING A NEW LANGUAGE

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Annotation: Language acquisition is a complex process that involves the gradual development of linguistic skills in individuals. This article provides an overview of language acquisition, exploring key theories, stages, factors influencing the process, and implications for education and society.

Key words and expressions: language acquisition, linguistic development, language learning, language acquisition theories, stages of language acquisition, critical period hypothesis

Introduction: Language acquisition refers to the process through which individuals acquire the ability to understand and use language. From infancy to adulthood, humans undergo a remarkable journey of learning one or more languages, which shapes their communication abilities and cognitive development.

Theories of Language Acquisition: Several theories have been proposed to explain how language acquisition occurs. The behaviorist perspective, supported by B.F. Skinner, emphasizes the role of environmental stimuli and reinforcement in shaping language learning. In contrast, Noam Chomsky's nativist theory posits that humans are biologically predisposed to acquire language and that innate linguistic structures underlie language development. Additionally, interactionist theories highlight the interplay between innate mechanisms, social interaction, and cognitive processes in language acquisition.

Stages of Language Acquisition: Language acquisition typically progresses through distinct stages. In the prelinguistic stage, infants engage in preverbal communication through gestures, babbling, and vocalizations. As they enter the linguistic stage, children begin to produce their first words and sentences, gradually expanding their vocabulary and syntactic complexity. The critical period hypothesis suggests that there is a sensitive period during childhood when language acquisition is most optimal, although individuals can continue to learn languages throughout their lives.

Factors Influencing Language Acquisition: Several factors influence language acquisition, including biological, cognitive, social, and environmental factors. Biological factors such as genetic predispositions and neuroplasticity play a role in

language development. Cognitive abilities such as memory, attention, and processing speed also influence language learning. Social interaction and exposure to language-rich environments provide crucial input for language acquisition, while cultural factors shape language use and identity.

Implications for Education and Society: Understanding language acquisition has significant implications for education and society. In educational settings, knowledge of language development informs teaching practices and curriculum design, facilitating effective language instruction for learners of all ages and backgrounds. Additionally, promoting multilingualism and language diversity fosters cultural appreciation and inclusivity within society, contributing to social cohesion and global communication.

Conclusion: Language acquisition is a multifaceted process that involves the interaction of biological, cognitive, social, and environmental factors. By examining key theories, stages, and influencing factors, we gain insights into how individuals learn languages and the implications for education and society. Ultimately, understanding language acquisition enhances our appreciation of the intricate nature of human communication and fosters effective language learning practices for individuals around the world.

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POLITENESS AND PRAGMATIC AGREEMENT

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Honorifics have been mentioned as one of the linguistic forms that contribute to pragmatic modality in the organization of speaking. The use of honorifics makes the speech polite because of the linguistic role it plays.

It seems that only some of the aspects of honorifics have ever been discussed in academic works. For example, the brilliant work “Ideologies of honorific language” by Judith Irvine, for all its insight, still seems to fail to explain the essence of honorific use. She seems to claim, “grammatical honorifics accompany linguistic ideologies that specify that flattened affect, conventionality, and avoidance of engagement with the concrete or the sensory as appropriate ways to express respect for *others*.” Her interpretation of the use of honorifics does not explain how they work as “dignity or elegance” markers for the speakers of languages that employ them.

Honorifics work as linguistic politeness only when they are used in keeping with the context. In other words, the use of high honorific forms itself could be interpreted differently depending on the context of speaking. Thus, if a high honorific form is chosen inappropriately, that is in a context where a less polite honorific form is expected, it could imply “irony,” “alienation,” or any number of other meanings. If honorifics are not used in a context where it is expected, it means that the speaker has ignored or neglected politeness and appropriate behavior. Thus, just as grammatical agreement in Western languages requires the agreement of the subject and the predicate form, it is the context of speaking that defines what constitutes agreement of the modal forms, and people in high context cultures have a highly complex communicative competence regarding the structure of varieties of linguistic forms. It is this agreement that is at the heart of the concept called *wakimae*, an aspect of linguistic politeness that is totally unrelated to those with which analytical frameworks of linguistic politeness are already familiar. This concept differs rather strikingly from the linguistic politeness frameworks of Brown and Levinson (1978, 1987) or Leech (1983), which posit that speakers find their strategies in order to produce utterances in such a way as to save face of the interactants. Perhaps explaining this from a different angle will aid in its clarification. Prevalent Western terms such as “common knowledge,” “frames,” “schema” or “script” all point to shared expectations in communication.

In order to interact with people appropriately in the work place, they learn which linguistic forms to use in certain situational contexts. What they are learning is appropriate ritualistic behavior, because certain forms and certain situational practices are correlated, and the learning of this is the initiation ceremony for those newly employed in order to fit in in the society they will be working in. Therefore, the use of honorifics in Japanese society is not just an exercise in training people to respect certain other people in a certain way, or maintaining distance with certain people.

Why is the use of honorifics polite?

Why is it that it is polite to use honorifics and formula? In other words, how does the pragmatics of ritualistic forms contribute to politeness? Ethologists have found that the basic wants of human beings are negative wants and positive wants. All human beings have the basic wants of negative face and positive face to be saved. Negative face has to do with the wants of a person not to be imposed on or hindered by others. On the other hand, positive wants have to do with the wants of every person that they want be desirable to others. A way to achieve the satisfaction of negative wants is to do things indirectly. In order for the positive face wants to be satisfied, it is good to claim that the speaker's wants are the same as the hearer's wants.

The use of formal forms such as honorifics and formula can be viewed from this perspective. The use of formal forms according to the expected situational context is firstly accommodating to the positive face of the speaker and the hearer, because saying "Good morning" in the appropriate context, that is, in the morning, is an interactional behavior to establish common ground. Since it is uttered according to expected social behavior, it gives pleasure to both the speaker and the hearer by satisfying their positive face wants, giving both parties a sense of sharing. At the same time, since the speaker makes use of firmly established formula, it does not have a personal touch, and thus is a way of expressing things indirectly, which makes clear that it is a way to satisfy negative wants. Therefore, the use of rituals can be interpreted as the way to fulfill linguistic politeness with regard to both negative and positive face wants. In Brown and Levinson's framework (1978, 1987), honorifics are treated under strategy No. 5, negative politeness. It means that the honorifics can be used as a strategy according to the speaker's intention using the speaker's rationality. It does not explain the most crucial aspect of this ritualistic use of honorifics. It is not the calculation of the speaker's intention that the honorific

form is chosen to be appropriate to the context, but rather it is the employment of the set pattern of language use.

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**ROLE OF REALIAS IN INTERLINGUAL AND
INTERCULTURAL COMMUNICATION**

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Abstract: Realias play a crucial role in bridging linguistic and cultural gaps in interlingual and intercultural communication. This article explores the significance of realias, which are words or concepts unique to a specific language or culture, in facilitating understanding and conveying authentic meaning across languages. By examining realias, examples from story "A naughty boy" by Gafur

Gulom will be provided for deep analysis and some effective ways of rendering realias will be discussed.

Key words: culture-bound words, linguoculturology, cultural relevance, norms, cultural differences

Introduction

According to Newmark, translation is essentially a craft that aims to convey a written message or statement from the source text into the target text while maintaining the same core message or statement (Newmark, 1981:7). However, when it comes to realias, a troublesome process arises as these linguistic units cannot be directly translated to recreate the same cultural and contextual sense in the target language that was present in the original text. The essence behind realias is deeply rooted in the specific culture from which the text originates. Realias, derived from Latin and reflecting national life, are typically studied in linguoculturology.

Cultural linguistics, a branch of linguistics that emerged in the 1990s at the intersection of linguistics and cultural studies, delves into how the manifestations of a people's culture are embedded in and reflected through language. An essential characteristic noted by G.V. Chernov is the widespread use and familiarity of realias, making them common and easily understood by native speakers of the source language. On the flip side, V.P. Berkov highlights the challenge of 'alienity' that realias can present to the recipient of the translated text.

Realias are categorized into various types, including household realia (kettle, sofa, дастархан, самовар; geographical realia (United Kingdom, Moscow, Tashkent political and social realia (House of Commands, Oliy Majlis, Federal Assembly and realia related to history and art (Navruz, Halloween and etc.)

When translating realias without losing their essence, translators need to consider multiple factors beforehand: the nature of the text, the significance of the realia in the text, the type of realia and its cultural relevance in the source language, and the level of comprehension of unfamiliar word combinations and 'exotic' expressions in the target language.

To tackle realias and complex idioms effectively, various strategies can be suggested:

1. ***Transcription***: Direct translation from the source text to the target text at the level of graphemes.
2. ***Transliteration***: Converting realias using phonetic equivalents.
3. ***Explanation***: Providing an explanation alongside the realia in the target text, typically enclosed in brackets, to elucidate its meaning.
4. ***Calque***: A word-for-word rendering of the realia to maintain its original form and cultural context.

By carefully considering these approaches and understanding the cultural nuances embedded in realias, translators can navigate the complexity of translating these unique linguistic units while preserving the essential cultural and contextual elements that they carry

It should be noted, that there are cultural differences between nations, so the translator should not be only aware of the advanced thematic and linguistic aspects but also he should be acquainted with the local culture itself. For example, cultural norms of Uzbek is totally different from British or Arabian languages

Research design, findings and analysis

Describing some ways of rendering realias, "A naughty boy" story by Gafur Gulom can be taken as a bright example for deep analysis. «A naughty boy» is a story, which describes the hard times of that period, the effect of the war in ordinary people's life. The main character travelling through different places and working to earn money, finds the life very complicated. Gafur Gulom utilized the genre satire to describe all of the events and adventures in the story. Some culture-bound words will be given for analyse from this masterpiece.

Russian realias	English rendering	Ways of translation
Яктак	oriental robe	Calque
плов	palov	Transliteration
газель	ghazal	Transcription
Домла	domla	Transliteration
нукер	soldier	Calque
гужа	Uzbek national dish	Explanation
салла	A kind of head dress tied around the head, usually made of silk	Explanation
мулла	mullah	Transcription
Султан	Sultan	Transliteration

Discussion. The research studied the ways of rendering culturally bound words. It selected several words from Gafur Gulom's story named «A naughty boy» as a target object for research. The findings suggest that transliteration way mostly utilized and it can be seen from the table given above

Nevertheless, this research paper has numerous limitations. First, it only utilized one way of rendering realias, which might not be considered adequate to apply the findings to a broader range of translation, because transliteration method

losses clear identity of realities and does not make any specific sense upon the reader . But it is still the best and common way that does not call any difficulties.

Conclusion. To conclude it should be considered that translation of culture bound words is a troublesome process for translators. First for first , translation is not just conveying one language to another, but also it is transferring specific culture as well as, so translators should always be aware of realias existing in the ST and consider its function and meaning. And only then, they can handle with them by using several translation techniques, such as transcription, transliteration, equivalency and others above-mentioned.

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QUESTIONS FOR COMPARISON OF STABLE CONNECTIONS IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES.

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This article compares some phraseological units in English and Uzbek language, and the semantic-stylistic and structural aspects of the study are isolated. With the help of examples similar and different features of phraseology in two languages were analyzed. Also, in the article, there are suggestions for comparing Uzbek and English phrases and proverbs and creating a phraseological corpus.

Key words: phrase, idiom, proverb, stable combination, free combination, corpus, semantic meaning, integrated meaning, supermeaning, syntactic connection, lexeme, functional coloring, emotional-expressive context, alternative, logic.

Since the first years of independence, attention to our national values, traditions and the Uzbek language has increased more than ever; especially in the coming years, it is necessary to develop the language, improve its status, and solve the problem of the corpus of world languages has become a problem. In this regard, serious research work has been carried out in linguistics and related fields in recent years. Since language is a social phenomenon, its lexical layer changes from the point of view of development, becomes enriched and acquires new meaning. Such changes can cause a number of problems in the formation of the language pattern and make it difficult to choose alternative options. Adjacent meanings of a word create different expressions in context, which requires a wide range of vocabulary and knowledge of a certain language from a person to understand. For native speakers of foreign languages studying Uzbek or engaging in activities related to this language, such semantic diversity leads to confusion and misunderstanding of words. As a result, the text becomes semantically and structurally incorrect. Most of these problems occur in the phraseological department of the language.

Meaningful units in stable combinations are determined by the superior meanings of words. Its separate translation does not give the expected meaning and completely changes the content of the text. If there is a slight inaccuracy in the area of translation, including the translation of phraseology, the reader(s) will notice it immediately. In many cases, the translator will ignore this and translate the phrase directly. In most cases, he makes additional comments like

“to wash away the guilt.” This causes stylistic madness. A work of art evokes a conclusion as if it was automatically translated.

Professor Sh. Rakhmatullaev defined a phrase as follows: “A phrase is also a linguistic unit that has content, but its meaning is not equal to the simple sum of the meanings inherent in the lexical unit in the content. In relation to the meaning of the lexemes in the meaning of the phrase, the denominator is embodied in the superlative degree, and this meaning may not depend on the meaning of the lexical element in the phrase.” [Rakhmatullaev, 1978:4] For example, the individual translation of words in the phrase ““og‘zi qulog‘ida”” creates *semantic confusion*, and its expression “very happy” makes it difficult to give it the correct lexical meaning in the corpus or the same in a particular language. This can be solved by finding an alternative expression to the expression. Since the use of phrases and idioms in a language instead of words makes speech attractive and impressive, and provides expressiveness, when translating it, use stable combinations (phrases, idioms, proverbs) of a particular language, rather than corresponding free combinations. The phrase corresponds to the purpose and serves to acquire a functional and emotionally expressive coloring in the minds of people.

In fact, paying attention to their stylistic aspects, choosing an alternative phrase in terms of style and context is one of the important stages of the translation process when Uzbek set phrases are included in the corpus. Indeed, the words contained in phrases and the symbols attached to them may not fully correspond to alternative phrases in another language and may damage the expression and logic of the translation. The fact that stable combinations in each language come from the cultural, educational, socio-political views of the masses and reflect the mentality of each people does not allow them to be translated on the basis of full-fledged stylistic and grammatical norms. Collocations must have a certain syntactic context in order to enter into a syntactic relationship with words in a sentence. “*Syntactic context is the connection of phrases with different parts of speech. Whether a phrase has a syntactic structure depends on its structure, internal syntactic construction, control of the verb-word component in verbal phrases, and also on whether this control is implemented in the structure of the phrase, the possessive affix involved in the nominal component.*” [Rakhmatullaev, 1978:12] Therefore, you should not find an alternative to all phrases and make it artificial. Below we will look at some examples of alternating stable combinations in the English and Uzbek languages.

Once in a blue moon - very rarely used in relation to time. This translates into Uzbek as “ko‘k oyda bir” The combination “blue moon” is figurative here and means that the action is almost impossible to perform. This idiom is similar to static phrases in our language such as “tuyaning dumi yerga tegganda”, “toshbaqa tog‘ga chiqqanda”, “xo‘roz tuxum qo‘yganda”, the difference is that in the English idiom there is perhaps very little movement.

To be honest, I only go to museums once in a blue moon – ochig‘i, men ko‘k oyda bir marta muzeylarga borib turaman. Thus, the idiom cannot be replaced by similar phrases in our language, which creates logical nonsense; in such a situation, the use of words suitable for the phrase or free combinations ensures the logic of speech.

Fight like a cat and a dog – it mushuk(dek) urushmoq / bo‘lmoq, **go against the flow**-oqimga qarshi bormoq, **you can’t please everyone, in the same boat** - hammaning ko‘ngliga yo‘l topa olmaysiz, **in the same boat**-“dardimiz bir”, “bir xil ahvolda”, is mainly used in relation to problems.

Also, to date, no serious research has been carried out on the mutual agreement of English and Uzbek proverbs, which are among the stable compounds. In fact, incorporating phraseological structures into a sentence and identifying their syntactic patterns is somewhat more difficult than in the process of translating proverbs from other languages. As in the Uzbek language, in English there is no need to include proverbs in certain syntactic relationships with words, that is, proverbs in content correspond to the opinion of the speaker and do not enter into a grammatical connection with the verb and noun of the sentence. phraseological units are not subject to classification and declension. Therefore, in the process of choosing an alternative to proverbs, it is necessary to pay attention not to the syntactic and morphological structure, but to their semantic essence. For example, the translation of the English proverb “A friend’s eye is a good mirror” into Uzbek, based on morphological and syntactic rules, may not give the full meaning, as expected, will not be able to fulfill the emotional-expressive task in the minds of people, so a semantic approach to it must be found proverb, “do‘st – do‘stning oynasi”, “do‘st achitib gapirar, dushman kuldirib” are very suitable for this proverb in the Uzbek language. Sometimes in both languages there may be proverbs with the same form and content, “a cat has nine lives”-- mushukning to‘qqizta / qirqta joni bor or the form may change slightly, “(an) apple does not fall far from the tree”- olmaning tagiga olma tushadi. But such cases are not often found in the vocabulary of the

language. I have tried to compile a short dictionary of stable combinations that are widely used in English and Uzbek languages.

Better be the head of a dog than the tail of a lion

ho'kizning oyog'i bo'lguncha, buzoqning boshi bo'lgan yaxshiroq

yoli qalin eshakdan yag'ir bo'lsa ham ot yaxshi,

odamning kuyugi bo'lguncha o'rmonning kiyigi bo'l,

echkining boshi bo'lguncha qo'yning quyrug'i bo'l.

Lightning never strikes in the same place twice

ko'r hassasini bir marta yo'qotadi

devona ham xurjunini bir marta yo'qotadi.

A burnt child dreads the fire

sutdan og'zi kuygan qatiqni ham puflab ichar

tikanni bosgan qadamini bilib tashlar

The above list of proverbs can be continued many more; such studies serve as a kind of steps in revealing the meaning of stable units, replacing them with their analogues in other languages. One of the important tasks is to pay attention to their stylistic **and linguocultural aspects** when matching proverbs with their variants in the corpus. In order for each representative of the language to use such stable combinations in accordance with their speech conditions and capabilities, it is necessary to enrich the dictionary with sufficient and suitable synonyms. That is, the speaker should be able to use the synonym he needs in accordance with speech activity in the process of translating English or other languages into his language, and as we noted above, if the stylistic and grammatical aspects of the alternative phrases are partial, they should be explained in the dictionary. This helps to construct correct speech, avoiding ambiguity and illogical content. In conclusion, I can say that each language has its own polysemous features, which are unique factors indicating the richness of the language, and their inclusion in the language corpus is carried out on the basis of the rules of computer linguistics and linguistics. Such stable units are an integral part of the life of a nation, **reflect its historical, sociocultural life, increase the richness, expressiveness and effectiveness of the speaker's speech**, and have a significant impact on the communicative qualities of speech.

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THE NOTION OF LINGUISTIC PERSONALITY IN TRANSLATION STUDIES

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Abstract: *The given article below discusses different viewpoints on anthropocentric paradigm – Linguistic personality which is one of the modern terms in translation studies.*

Key words: *Linguistic personality, translator’s personality, anthropocentric paradigm, human mental activity, communicative behavior, culture and society.*

Аннотация: *В данной статье рассматриваются различные точки зрения на антропоцентрическую парадигму – языковую личность, которая является одним из современных терминов в переводоведении.*

Ключевые слова: *языковая личность, личность переводчика, антропоцентрическая парадигма, психическая деятельность человека, коммуникативное поведение, культура и общество.*

At the end of the 20th century language and the following anthropocentric paradigm – “linguistic personality” was studied from the perspective of native speakers. Issues related to the feelings of a person forced to live within the

constraints of a particular language were investigated, and the processes of human mental activity reflected in language were analyzed. The concept of a linguistic personality has become increasingly popular. The reality around a person is transformed through thinking into a system of images that form a picture of the world. The anthropocentric nature of the worldview is expressed in its focus on humans. According to V.N. Teliya, the anthropocentric canon, a “naive picture of the world” is created that finds expression in the very possibility of thinking about natural phenomena or abstract concepts as objectified constants. The linguistic picture of the world is based on the anthropocentric principle, which states that man is the measure of all things”. It should be noted that the ideas that led to the concept of the “linguistic picture of the world” in the late 20th century were present long before their formulation. V. von Humboldt, one of the first linguists and philosophers, suggested that language reflects the worldview of its speakers: “different languages are the organs of the original thinking and perception of nations”.

These ideas were further developed by Leo Weisgerber in his research. He introduced the concept of a linguistic picture to the scientific terminology. The linguistic picture of the world is, on the one hand, a result of the historical development of an ethnos and its language, and on the other hand, it shapes the path of its further development. The linguistic picture can be seen as a living organism with a complex structure that includes multiple levels. Linguistic expression is a special set of sounds, sound combinations, and features of the articulatory apparatus in native speakers. It includes prosodic characteristics, vocabulary, word formation capabilities, syntax, and phrase and sentence structure. Additionally, it includes the paremiological baggage of the language.

The linguistic picture of the world shapes the overall communicative behavior, understanding of nature and man's inner world, and the language system. Thinking and the native language are used to perceive the world. L. Weisgerber believed that the way we reflect reality is idiosyncratic and

corresponds to the static form of the language. To what extent a person speaks the language determines how well they know the world. The world is also discussed in the works of American linguists, Edward Sapir and Benjamin Whorf, who created the unique theory of linguistic relativity. They argue that a person navigates the world without the help of language, and that language is just a tool to solve specific problems of communication and thinking. Sapir writes that the idea that language is an essential part of our perception of the world is an illusion. Indeed, he argues that the world is largely built on the linguistic habits and conventions of a particular social group. Moreover, V.A. Maslova believes that the linguistic picture of the world is a common cultural heritage of the nation, which is structured and multilevel. This linguistic picture of the world determines communicative behavior and understanding of the external and internal world of a person, reflecting the way of speech-thinking activity that is characteristic of a particular era with its spiritual, cultural, and national values.

Indeed, the words about human communicative behavior in this statement by V.A. Maslova are important, as the linguistic picture of the world largely determines communication in one society or another. The concept of linguistic personality in anthropological linguistics is extremely significant, as this concept is the tool that creates language varieties. If the question of how language is created is still unanswered, this is understandable. Based on the presence of numerous theories and hypotheses about the origin of language, it can be concluded that language varieties, including social and territorial variants, are created by people.

In other words, linguistic personalities play a significant role in the formation of language. A linguistic personality can be defined as a person, who is an integral part of the world. The issue of the manifestation of the primary world in the secondary world is fundamental and essential for human existence. The concept of "linguistic personality" began to take shape in Russian linguistics in the 1930s, with the first mention in the work by V.V. Vinogradov, "On Fiction".

Analyzing the state of affairs regarding the literary language in the period of 1929-1930, Vinogradov noted that I.A. Baudouin de Courtenay eliminated the methods of historical analysis and historicism from his studies of literary language. He was interested in the linguistic personality as a receptacle for socio-linguistic forms and norms, as well as the focus of mixing and crossing of different socio-linguistic categories.

The creation of the theory of linguistic personality, which has been widely accepted since the late 1980s, belongs to Y.N. Karaulov. The scientific school "Russian Language Personality" defines two phenomena by language personality: a specific native speaker of a particular language and culture, characterized on the basis of analysis of texts produced by them, from the perspective of the specific use of systemic structural means of that language to reflect their vision and assessment of surrounding reality (worldview), and to achieve communicative goals. In this world, there are certain goals and a comprehensive way to describe an individual's linguistic ability. This involves a systematic representation of language and its functioning in the processes of generating texts. Y.N. Karaulov emphasizes that the linguistic personality is a cross-cutting idea that permeates all aspects of language learning and destroys the boundaries between disciplines studying a person. It is impossible to study a person outside his language.

Recently, the linguistic personality has been studied from the perspective of its varieties related to human activity. A professional linguistic personality stands out, which defines a professional as a set of intellectual, socio-cultural, and moral-volitional qualities formed in a special professional and cultural environment. These qualities are reflected in the properties of a person's language. The study of linguistic personality involves the analysis of consciousness, behavior and activity. It is revealed in the peculiarities of linguistic and speech units produced by the individual, as well as in the originality of their professional discourse, which is subordinated to the goals and objectives of professional activity. There are different types of linguistic personalities,

including a professionally oriented one, an unprofessional one, and a linguistically undirected one. A professional linguistic personality can experience the influence of national cognitive thinking characteristic of the language they use.

In conclusion, the study of linguistic personality continues to be an important area of research. Linguistic personality is considered an independent phenomenon that deserves further investigation. The types of linguistic personalities are analyzed and the reasons influencing their formation are investigated. A linguistic personality is a complex concept that is influenced by various factors. One of the main reasons for this is that each person has a unique cognitive space, which is a structured set of knowledge and ideas. This individual cognitive space plays an important role in shaping a person's linguistic personality. human thinking plays a role. The creative understanding of the surrounding world by a linguistic personality is creatively reflected in the language by the appearance of new linguistic lexical and grammatical forms. Each linguistic personality has its own individual thinking, which becomes a component of social thinking, and social thinking, in turn, becomes a component of national thinking.

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GENDER AND LANGUAGE USE

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Abstract: This research paper analyses the aspects of language, gender, ethnicity in terms of sociolinguistic perspective. Specifically, it focuses on researches carried out on the usage of language structures and written language by explaining broader trajectories in language practice. The paper provides nuanced and contextualised explanations about several historical approaches adopted by many scholars with valuable contributions to interpret the sociolinguistic study of language and how it works. It gives a wide range of information about linguistic features and sophisticated sociolinguistic patternings based on variationist approaches regarding gender, ethnic and other distinctions in learning the language as well as impartialities in language use.

Key words: Sociolinguistic, trajectories, patternings, variationist, gender, distinctions, impartialities. ,

Аннотация: В данной исследовательской работе анализируются аспекты языка, пола и этнической принадлежности с точки зрения социолингвистической перспективы. В частности, он фокусируется на исследованиях использования языковых структур и письменной речи путем объяснения более широких траекторий языковой практики. В статье представлены детальные и контекстуализированные объяснения нескольких исторических подходов, принятых многими учеными, которые внесли

ценный вклад в интерпретацию социолингвистических исследований языка и того, как они работают. Он дает широкий спектр информации о языковых особенностях и сложных социолингвистических моделях, основанных на вариационных подходах в отношении гендерных, этнических и других различий в изучении языка, а также беспристрастности в использовании языка.

Ключевые слова: Социолингвистика, траектории, паттерны, вариотинист, гендер, различия, беспристрастность.

Introduction

As an area, language and gender has been characterised by interdisciplinarity, with valuable contributions from anthropology, various forms of discourse analysis, education, literary theory, media studies, social psychology, sociology, women's studies and lesbian and gay studies as well as sociolinguistics more narrowly defined. Many, or more probably most, contributors to the field have been feminists, and there has been an emphasis both on the development of theory and on more practical concerns. Language and gender is a topic that is of interest in its own right; it is also important because of what it can add to our understanding of language and how it works, and to the sociolinguistic study of language.

Gender and Social Stratification

Many studies of language variation and change, including the urban 'stratification' studies discussed in Chapters 3 and 4, have found evidence of gender differences in the populations surveyed. William Labov, in his study of New York City, and Peter Trudgill, in his study of Norwich, in England, found that within each social class group, and across each stylistic context studied, their female informants tended to use more 'prestige' or high-status language features, and their male informants more vernacular language features. This finding has been replicated in several studies carried out, particularly in 'western' and often

English-speaking contexts (e.g. Macaulay 1978; Shuy 1970; Wolfram 1969). As with other findings from stratification studies, such gender differences represent a statistical tendency. It is not the case that there are distinct ‘female’ and ‘male’ forms: both women and men were found to use ‘prestige’ pronunciations, but, all other things being equal, women tended to use more of these than men.

Sampling: women, men and social class

Many studies took class as their primary social division, making comparisons between women and men in the same social class. Men were allocated to a social class on the basis of a number of factors (in the case of Trudgill’s study, these included occupation, education, salary and housing locality). Women were usually allocated to a social class on the basis of their husband’s or father’s class position, rather than in their own right. More recently, researchers have pointed to problems in this approach: it is by no means obvious that women always occupy the same class position as their husbands or fathers, and there are also problems in the criteria used to allocate people to social classes. Deborah Cameron (1992: 64) points out that if the family is used as the unit of classification and wives and husbands are allocated to class groups on the basis of economic criteria, wives would occupy a lower social position than their husbands; but if one used education and type of occupation as criteria, many women, especially wives of working-class men, would come out above their husbands. This could affect the results of variationist studies in which women were found to use more prestige language features than men from ‘the same’ social class groups.

Conclusion

Gendered language use inevitably raises issues of power and inequality between women and men (though some approaches, for example cultural difference approaches, have downplayed the importance of power; and more recent, contextualised approaches would emphasise that power is not fixed and monolithic but fairly complex, negotiated and on some occasions contested). There has always been a high level of commitment among researchers, many of

whom are concerned not just to provide a ‘neutral’ interpretation of language behaviour but also to challenge inequalities in language use. Such commitment is at odds with any view of sociolinguistic researchers as impartial observers of language, but many would argue that, at any rate, complete neutrality is impossible to attain: the values held by researchers will affect what they choose to observe and investigate, how they carry out their research and how they interpret their findings. Previous chapters have shown that sociolinguists regularly take a stand on language issues, and that many have intervened in areas such as education and forensic linguistics. Some researchers have explicitly rejected impartiality and choose to ‘declare their interests’ rather than hide these behind a screen of objectivity. Such issues are discussed further in relation to sociolinguistic contributions to language policy and practice.

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THE ROLE OF READING IN LANGUAGE LEARNING

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Abstract: This article is dedicated to explore the role of reading in language learning, and provide some tips and techniques to help learners maximize their reading experience.

Key words: language learning, language acquisition, vocabulary expansion

Language learning is a process that requires dedication, practice, and patience. There are various methods to improve one's language skills, and reading is one of the most effective ways to do so. Reading provides learners with the opportunity to expand their vocabulary, improve their grammar, and enhance their comprehension skills. Reading is an essential skill that can significantly contribute to language development. Through reading, learners are exposed to a variety of vocabulary, sentence structures, and writing styles. This exposure to different language patterns can help learners to develop their comprehension skills and improve their ability to understand new words and phrases.

Moreover, reading can help learners to improve their grammar and sentence structure. By reading well-written texts, learners can observe how sentences are structured, how paragraphs are organized, and how ideas are conveyed. This observation can help learners to develop their writing skills and enhance their ability to express themselves accurately and coherently. Some tips and techniques to help learners maximize their reading experience are given below:

1. Select Reading Materials Carefully

One of the most important factors in reading for language learning is choosing the right reading materials. Learners should select reading materials that are appropriate for their level of proficiency. They should start with simple texts and gradually move on to more complex materials as they improve their skills. Moreover, learners should choose reading materials that are interesting to them. When learners are engaged and interested in what they are reading, they are more likely to retain information and learn new words and phrases.

2. Read Regularly

Another important tip for reading in language learning is to read regularly. Learners should set aside time each day to read in their target language. This regular practice can help learners to improve their reading skills and build their vocabulary.

Furthermore, learners should aim to read a variety of materials, including books, newspapers, magazines, and online articles. This exposure to different types of texts can help learners to develop their comprehension skills and improve their ability to understand different writing styles.

3. Use Context Clues

When reading in a foreign language, learners may encounter unfamiliar words and phrases. However, they can use context clues to help them understand the meaning of these words. Context clues are the words and phrases surrounding an unfamiliar word that can provide hints about its meaning. For example, if a learner comes across the word “ubiquitous” in a sentence, they may not know its meaning. However, they can use the context of the sentence to figure out that “ubiquitous” means “existing or being everywhere at the same time.”

4. Take Notes

Taking notes while reading can help learners to retain information and learn new words and phrases. Learners can write down unfamiliar words and look up their meanings later. They can also jot down key ideas and concepts to help them

remember what they have read. Additionally, learners can use their notes to review what they have read and reinforce their understanding of the material. This review can help learners to retain information and improve their comprehension skills.

5. Join a Reading Group

Joining a reading group can be an excellent way for language learners to practice their reading skills and engage with other learners. Reading groups provide learners with the opportunity to discuss their reading materials, share their thoughts and opinions, and ask questions. Moreover, reading groups can help learners to expand their vocabulary, learn new phrases, and improve their comprehension skills. They can also provide learners with a supportive community of like-minded individuals who are all working towards the same goal.

Reading also provides learners with the opportunity to learn about different cultures and perspectives. By reading books, articles, and other written materials from different countries and cultures, learners can gain a deeper understanding of the world around them. This exposure to different perspectives can help learners to become more empathetic, open-minded, and culturally aware. Learning a foreign language through reading is an effective and beneficial approach that can significantly enhance language acquisition. Here are some key benefits of learning a foreign language through reading:

- ✓ Vocabulary Expansion: Reading exposes learners to a wide range of vocabulary in context, helping them learn new words and phrases. By encountering words repeatedly in different contexts, learners can better understand their meanings and usage.
- ✓ Grammar Practice: Reading provides examples of correct grammar structures and sentence patterns, allowing learners to see how the language is used in written form. By observing grammatical rules in context, learners can improve their own language skills.

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- ✓ Comprehension Skills: Reading helps learners develop their reading comprehension skills, which are essential for understanding written texts in a foreign language. By reading a variety of texts, learners can improve their ability to understand and interpret information.
 - ✓ Cultural Understanding: Reading authentic texts in the target language exposes learners to the culture, traditions, and customs of the native speakers. This helps learners gain insights into the cultural context of the language and enhances their overall understanding of the language.
 - ✓ Contextual Learning: Reading allows learners to see new vocabulary and grammar structures used in context, which can deepen their understanding and retention of the language. By encountering language in authentic contexts, learners can improve their language skills more effectively.
 - ✓ Critical Thinking Skills: Reading requires learners to analyze and interpret information, helping them develop critical thinking skills. By engaging with different types of texts, learners can enhance their analytical abilities and broaden their perspectives.

Conclusion

Overall, learning a foreign language through reading is a valuable method that can improve vocabulary, grammar, comprehension skills, cultural knowledge, and critical thinking abilities. It is important for language learners to incorporate reading into their language learning routine to enhance their proficiency in the target language. To maximize their reading experience, learners should select reading materials carefully, read regularly, use context clues, take notes, and join a reading group. By following these tips and techniques, learners can improve their reading skills, expand their knowledge, and achieve their language learning goals.

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GENDER RELATIONSHIPS IN JANE AUSTEN'S NOVELS.

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Annotation

The following article reveals the gender relationships in Jane Austen's novels and compares the features of both men and women's bond in "Pride and Prejudice", "Emma" and "Persuasion". The writer's style is analyzed through the image of the heroes of the work, and the gender relationship in society is revealed with the examples from the novels. The article focuses on the analysis of social life and gender issues, the role and relationship of women and men in society, family and marriage relations, as well as the different and similar views of men and women in relation to them.

Key words

Relationship, family bond, women in society, marriage.

Аннотация

В следующей статье раскрываются гендерные отношения в романах Джейн Остин и сравниваются особенности отношений мужчин и женщин в романах «Гордости и предубеждения», «Эмма» и «Убеждения». Стиль писателя анализируется через образы героев произведения, а гендерные отношения в обществе раскрываются на примерах из романов. В статье основное внимание уделяется анализу социальной жизни и гендерных

вопросов, роли и взаимоотношениям женщин и мужчин в обществе, семейно-брачным отношениям, а также различным и схожим взглядам мужчин и женщин по отношению к ним.

Ключевые слова

Отношения, семейные узы, женщины в обществе, брак.

Annotatsiya

Quyidagi maqola Jeyn Ostin romanlaridagi gender munosabatlarning o'ziga xos xususiyatlariga bag'ishlanadi. Maqolada "G'urur va Bid'at", "Emma" va "Persuasion" romanlaridan erkak va ayollar munosabatlari tahlilga tortiladi. Asar qahramonlari obrazi orqali yozuvchi uslubi tahlil qilinib, romanlardagi misollar orqali jamiyatdagi gender munosabatlari ochib berilgan. Maqolada ijtimoiy hayot va gender muammolari, ayol va erkaklarning jamiyatdagi o'rni va munosabatlari, oila va nikoh munosabatlari, shuningdek, ularga nisbatan erkak va ayolning turli va o'xshash qarashlari tahlil qilinadi.

Kalit so'zlar

Munosabatlar, oilaviy rishtalar, jamiyatdagi ayollar, nikoh.

Jane Austen, in her novels "Pride and Prejudice," "Emma," and "Persuasion," explores gender relationships and societal expectations in Regency-era England. Here's a brief overview of how she reflects these themes in each novel:

"Pride and Prejudice":

Austen examines the roles of men and women within the context of marriage and social status. The novel portrays the societal pressure on women to marry well for financial security and social standing.

Characters like Elizabeth Bennet challenge traditional gender norms by asserting their independence, intelligence, and wit.

The relationships between characters, such as Elizabeth and Mr. Darcy, highlight the importance of mutual respect, understanding, and communication in a successful partnership.

"Emma":

In "Emma," Austen explores the limitations placed on women in terms of social mobility and independence. The protagonist, Emma Woodhouse, is a wealthy and privileged young woman who initially views marriage as unnecessary for her own happiness.

However, Emma's journey throughout the novel involves self-discovery and understanding the complexities of human relationships. Austen critiques the societal expectations placed on women to marry and conform to traditional gender roles.

The novel also examines power dynamics between men and women, particularly through Emma's interactions with Mr. Knightley, highlighting the importance of mutual respect and equality in relationships.

"Persuasion":

"Persuasion" delves into themes of second chances and the consequences of societal pressure on women to conform to expectations. The protagonist, Anne Elliot, is pressured to break off her engagement to Captain Wentworth due to his lack of wealth and social status.

Austen critiques the rigid social hierarchy and gender roles of her time, as well as the double standards faced by women in matters of love and marriage.

Through Anne's character development and her eventual reunion with Captain Wentworth, Austen emphasizes the importance of individual agency and true emotional connection in romantic relationships, rather than external societal expectations.

Quick wit and intelligence were highly appreciated in the novels in both men and women. In "Pride and Prejudice" Darcy delights of Elizabeth's intelligence:

“Elizabeth had been at Netherfield long enough. She attracted him more than he liked.”²³

This feeling can also be observed in the perception about Mr. Walter Benwick in “Persuasion”:

“I confess that I do think there is a disparity, too great a disparity, and in a point no less essential than mind. I regard Louisa Musgrove as a very amiable, sweet-tempered girl, and not deficient in understanding, but Benwick is something more. He is a clever man, a reading man; and I confess, that I do consider his attaching himself to her with some surprise. Had it been the effect of gratitude, had he learnt to love her, because he believed her to be preferring him, it would have been another thing.”²⁴

In “Emma” the author feels appreciation toward Harriet by the feelings of Emma.

“In spite of her vexation, she could not help feeling it almost ridiculous, that she should have the very same distressing and delicate office to perform by Harriet, which Mrs. Weston had just gone through by herself. The intelligence, which had been so anxiously announced to her, she was now to be anxiously announcing to another. Her heart beat quick on hearing Harriet’s footstep and voice; so, she supposed, had poor Mrs. Weston felt when she was approaching Randalls.”

Financial position played significance role in marriage. The parents of girls as well as the ladies themselves were looking for rich man to get married.

In “Emma” Jane Austin highlights this importance with the disagreement of Emma to her friend:

“Well, and that is as early as most men can afford to marry, who are not born to an independence. Mr. Martin, I imagine, has his fortune entirely to

²³ Jane Austen. *Pride and Prejudice*. Barnes and Nobel Classics. - New York.

²⁴ Jane Austen. *Persuasion*. Worldworth classics, 2007.

make—cannot be at all beforehand with the world. Whatever money he might come into when his father died, whatever his share of the family property, it is, I dare say, all afloat, all employed in his stock, and so forth; and though, with diligence and good luck, he may be rich in time, it is next to impossible that he should have realized anything yet.”²⁵

Moreover, the epigraph in “Pride and Prejudice” reveals the significance of being rich in order to get married:

“It is a truth universally acknowledged, that a single man in possession of a good fortune must be in want of a wife.”²⁶

“Oh, single, my dear, to be sure! A single man of large fortune; four or five thousand a year. I What a fine thing for our girls!”

In “Persuasion” one can define the reason of Jane’s refusal of her beloved’s confession that later when he becomes rich could get married to Jane.

“Such opposition, as these feelings produced, was more than Anne could combat. Young and gentle as she was, it might yet have been possible to withstand her father's ill-will, though unsoftened by one kind word or look on the part of her sister; but Lady Russell, whom she had always loved and relied on, could not, with such steadiness of opinion, and such tenderness of manner, be continually advising

her in vain. She was persuaded to believe the engagement a wrong thing: indiscreet, improper, hardly capable of success, and not deserving it. But it was not a merely selfish caution, under which she acted, in putting an end to it. Had she not imagined herself consulting his good, even more than her own, she could hardly have given him up.”

Overall, Jane Austen's novels provide insightful commentary on gender relationships, societal norms, and the complexities of love and marriage in Regency-era England.

²⁵ Jane Austen. Emma. - Wikisource, 1816.

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**SOME TRANSLATION PROBLEMS IN UZBEK TRANSLATION OF
THE NOVEL “THE LOST WORLD” BY A.C.DOYLE**

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Introduction. The functional relations do not have a stable basis, they are not the basis for general rules. As the translation of each sentence requires from the translator strong knowledge, resourcefulness and awareness of the culture of the target language. Literary translation is an exchange of cultures through these two works. This change occurs as a result of skillful implementation of other minor changes at different levels of the language. Of course, this does not mean literal translation. Direct translation is a great threat to literature, it bypasses the general linguistic and extralinguistic context in the text of the literary work. It is aimed at expressing the content of individual words that violate the integrity of the artistic text and thus undermine the artistic purpose of the work intended by the author.

Main part. According to the semantic features of the language, the meaning of the words, their use, ability to combine with other words, combinations formed with them, their “place” in the lexical system of the language are often incompatible. Although the means of expression differ, the words are often the same. Since it is not possible to accept all the cases of semantic differences between the two languages, we limit ourselves to the typical features of the semantic cases [2; 35].

Complete correspondence can be observed in the following cases:

- Famous nouns and geographical names. Such examples can also be given in the translation of the work “The Lost World”: Summerlee – Sammerli, Challenger – Chellenjer, Ed Malone – Ed Meloun, John Roxton – Jon Rokston; Maple White land – Mepl Vayt yeri, Amazon – Amazonka[1; 5-65].

- Scientific and technical terms: biology – biologiya, metaphor – metafora, virus – virus, internet – internet.

- Names of months, days of the week and numbers: September – Sentabr, Wednesday – Chorshanba, twenty – yigirma.

Many words in the language have multiple meanings, and the meaning of a word in one language does not completely correspond to the meaning of the

same word in another language. For example, the composition spare clothing is given in the work. In fact, the meaning of the word “spare” is translated into Uzbek as “*bo‘sh, tejamoq*”. In the work, it is translated as *almashib kiyadigan libos* [3; 41].

Besides, each word affects the meaning of the corresponding object. The same is not always chosen to describe the same characters. It should be said that the visualization of the word in different languages is determined by the division of reality into parts. Despite the difference in signs, both languages adequately and equally reflect the same phenomenon, which should be taken into account when translating such words, since equivalence is not the same as having the same meaning. For example in the work: *It was bowl-shaped and at the bottom, some hundreds of yards from where we lay, were pools of green-scummed, stagnant water, fringed with bulrushes.* – *Bu havzaning tubida, biz yotgan yerdan yuz yardcha narida, qamishzorning u yog‘ida yuzini maysa-giyoh qoplagan turg‘un ko‘lmaklar jilvalanib ko‘rindi.* – in this translation if the phrase *green-scummed* had been translated word by word it would be translated as *yashil ko‘pikli*, but for giving the right meaning it is translated as *maysa-giyoh qoplagan*.

It is very important to know the lifestyle and culture of the target language in order to convey accurate information during the translation process [4; 82]. The following words have no translation equivalent:

1. Realiae: bazaar – bozor, kiwi – kivi, koala – koala, mile – milya.
2. Famous nouns and geographical place names: Amazon – Amazonka, Maple White land – Mepl Vayt yeri.
3. Address and meeting, cases of acquaintance: street 18 – 18-ko‘cha, Massachusetts region – Massachiset viloyati.
4. Names of newspapers and magazines: Daily Gazette – Deyli gazetasi, New York Times – Nyu York Tayms.
5. Units of weight, length, etc: kilograms – kilogram, meter – metr, foot – fut.

There are semantic differences between the two languages, and despite the formal and semantic differences between them, the translator has to make various linguistic changes to achieve complete equivalence. The goal is to provide the semantic information provided in the original text.

When changing lexical units, words and stable word combinations are replaced by another word that has no equivalent. The translator of the work “The Lost World” Mahmud Yahyoyev also used this type: *It was a weird place in itself [...] – Joyning o ‘zi noxush bo ‘lgani yetmay* [1; 74].

The absence of a formal expression of the original semantic components is the reason why the semantic suffix is used as a method of lexical modification. In the process of lexical changes words that express redundant meaning are often omitted to give a clear expression [5; 63]. This translation type is also observed in the work: *the most tactless person – o ‘taketgan beandisha; jump out of my chair – dik etib turib ketdim, that was brave of you – buning nimasi jasorat.*

Conclusion. Effective use of transformations in the process of translation in many cases depends on whether the languages are typologically close or far from each other, that is, whether they are one family or not. Which type of transformations to use effectively in translation depends on the translator. At such a time, it should be taken into account that the translator does not intend to use a specific type of transformation in the translation process, but it arises by itself in order to achieve proportionality in the translation. From a theoretical point of view, we understand that translation transformations can be analyzed separately. In practice, in most cases, translation transformations can be used in a mixed manner. Pure and specific transformation constructions are widely used in the interpretation of untranslatable words, in the translation of specific words, and in the translation of stylistic methods that have an expressive character in the methodological aspect. In the process of translation, only experienced and skilled translators know how to properly and effectively use transformations.

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**TARJIMASHUNOSLIK QAYTA IJOD YARATISH SAN’AT TURI
SIFATIDA**

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Tarjima so‘zining lug‘aviy ma‘nosini ko‘rib chiqadigan bo‘lsak, tarjima - forsha «tarzabon» so‘zidan arabilashib o‘zgargan. «Tarzabon» - chiroyli so‘zlovchi, notiq, tili burro kishi degan ma‘nolarni bildiradi. Arab tiliga «tarjumon» shaklida qabul qilingan bu so‘zdan «tarjima» yoki «tarjuma» so‘zi hosil bo‘lgan. O‘zbek adiblari bunday tushunchani «o‘tkazish», «qaytarish», «o‘girish», «ag‘darish» singari atamalar bilan ifoda etganlar. Ko‘p yillar davomida «tarjima»sharh, bayon qilish, tushuntirish ma‘nolarida ham qo‘llanib kelingan. Keyinchalik esa bu so‘z badiiy ijodning bir turini ifodalash ma‘nosini kasb etdi va ilmiy-filologik terminga aylandi. Umuman, tarjima deganda bir tilda yozilgan matn yoki aytilgan nutqning boshqa tilda qayta yaratilishi tushuniladi.

Tarjima bu qayta yaratish san'ati, yuksak badiiy ijoddir, ijod bo'lganda ham tarjima muallifidan izlanish, mehnat, sabr-toqat talab qiladigan, turli xil materiallar ustida mashaqqatli ish olib borishni talab qiladigan ijoddir.

Tarjima tushunchasining ma'nosi juda keng, chunki «Tarjima nima?» degan savolga turli soha vakillari turlicha javob berishadi. Bir kishi tarjimini bir tilda yozilgan kitobni ikkinchi tillga o'girish desa, boshqa bir kishi uni bir tilda bayon qilingan fikrni o'zga tilda so'zlovchi kishilarga tushuntirib berishdan iborat deb biladi. Uchinchi bir kishi fikricha esa, kinofilmlar ham tarjima qilinadi, demak tarjima bu bir tilda rol ijro etayotgan aktyorning nutqini ikkinchi uchinchi va hokazo tillarga o'girish demakdir.

Tarjimaga lingvistik tarjimashunoslik nuqtai nazaridan yondashib, quyidagicha ta'rif berish mumkin:

Insoniyat faoliyatining murakkab shakli bo'lmish tarjima - bir tilda yaratilgan nutqiy ifodani (matnni), uning shakl va mazmun birligini saqlagan holda, o'zga til vositalari asosida qayta yaratishdan iborat ijodiy jarayondir. Demak, asliyat mansub bo'lgan til vositalari yordamida yaratilgan nutqiy ifoda tarjima tili qonuniyatlari asosida vujudga keltirilgan shunday ifoda bilan almashtiriladi. Shu yo'l bilan asliyat va tarjima tillari matnlarning mazmuniy-uslubiy adekvatligi yuzaga keltiriladi.

Tarjimaning bosh xossasi uning so'z san'ati ekanligidadir. So'zning fikrni ifodalash xususiyati, ta'sir quvvatiga ega ekanligi tarjimini san'at darajasida tadbiq etish imkonini beradi. Tarjimada ikki xalq va ikki til, ikki ma'naviy hayot, ikki milliy madaniyat, ikki davr va ikki adib o'rtasidagi bir-biriga chambarchas bo'g'liq munosabatlarning ham o'ziga xos ko'rinishini e'tiborga olish zarur.

Tarjima qilinayotgan tekst yoki nutqning qandayligidan qat'iy nazar, bir tildan boshqasiga o'girilayotgan har qanday ish ya'ni, har qanday tarjima uchun umumiy bo'lgan ikki holat bor:

1. Tarjimoning maqsadi – asl nusxa tilini bilmagan kitobxon yoki tinglovchini o‘sha asar teksti yoki nutq mazmuni bilan iloji boricha aniq, to‘la-to‘kis tanishtirish;

2. Tarjima qilish – muayyan til vositalari yordamida ifoda etilgan narsani boshqa til vositalari orqali asli bilan to‘la mos ifodalash demakdir.

Tarjima amaliyoti paydo bo‘libdiki, asliyatni ona tiliga qanday o‘girish lozim degan masala tarjimonlar oldida ko‘ndalang turgan muammo sanaladi, tarjima borasida so‘z yuritilganda, shubhasiz, ko‘z o‘ngimizda uning bir necha xillari namoyon bo‘ladi. Jumladan: a) bir tildan ikkinchisiga – qardosh yoki qardosh bo‘lmagan tilga tarjima qilish;

b) adabiy tildan - uning biror shevasiga va biror shevadan – adabiy tilga yoki bir tilning shevasidan boshqa adabiy tilga tarjima qilish;

c) qadimiy davr tilidan o‘sha tilning hozirgi zamonaviy holatiga tarjima qilish;

Hozirda tarjimaning yuqoridagi turlariga yana so‘zma- so‘z tarjima, ijodiy tarjima, erkin tarjima, mualliflashtirilgan tarjima va shu kabi bir qator tarjimalar ham qo‘shilgan. Buning asosiy sababi tarjima jarayoniga turlicha yondashishdir. Ammo tarjimaning qaysi turi bo‘lmasin, har qanday tarjimaning maqsad va vazifalari bo‘ladi.

Tarjimaning vazifasi - asliyat va tarjima tillari leksik, grammatik va stilistik hodisalari o‘rtasidagi uyg‘un hamda tafovutli jihatlarni puxta o‘zlashtirib olgan holda, asliyatning shakl va mazmun birligini ona tili vositalari yordamida qayta yaratishdan iboratdir. Bu tamoyilga rioya qilmaslik tarjimada aniqlikning, ifoda me‘yorining buzilishiga, olib keladi.

Asl nusxa muallifidan voqelikni to‘g‘ri aks ettirish talab etilsa, tarjimondan asl nusxani bekami-ko‘st talqin etish talab qilinadi.

Tarjima qilish jarayonida ikki holat ro‘y beradi, ya‘ni birinchidan, tarjima qilish uchun o‘girilayotgan narsani tushunish, anglash va talqin qilish kerak. Bu

hodisa ona tilida ro‘y beradi. Ikkinchidan, asar o‘g‘irilayotgan tilda muvofiq ifoda vositalari, ya’ni so‘z, so‘z birikmasi, grammatik formalarni topish lozim.

Tarjimaviy muvofiqlik yaratish uchun turli juft tillar vositalarini qiyosiy o‘rganish, badiiy matnning estetik o‘ziga xosligini, uning moddiy-mantiqiy, hissiy ta’sirchan va obrazli tizimini tashkil etuvchi unsurlari tarkibidagi uslubiy va muvozanat xususiyatlarni aniqlash hamda stilistik asosga tayanishni taqazo etadi. Til birliklarining uslubiy bo‘yoq kasb etish xususiyati turli juft tillar birliklarining mazmuniy-uslubiy va muvozanat jihatlardan o‘zaro mos kelish-kelmasliklari to‘grisida qaror qabul qilish imkonini beradi. Tarjimaning bunday tahlili mazkur sohadagi tasavvur va qarashlarni boyitadi. Ular nafaqat lisoniy, balki til ma’lumotlari tarkibidan tashqarida bo‘lgan ruhshunoslik, jamiyatshunoslik.

Tarjimashunoslik fanlararo soha bo‘lib, tarjima, tarjimonlik va boshqa tegishli til va muloqot faoliyatini akademik o‘rganishni o‘z ichiga oladi. Ushbu tadqiqot sohasi tarjima va tarjimaning tamoyillari, nazariyalari, amaliyotlari va madaniy oqibatlarini, shuningdek, ularning turli madaniyatlar va jamiyatlarga ta’sirini tushunishga intiladi.

Asliyat tadqiqi metodologiyalari korpus tilshunoslik va tarjimonlik sohalarida xalqaro namoyon bo‘lgan bo‘lib, hatto boshqa ilmiy sohalar uchun ham maqbuldir. Ushbu metodologiyalar asliyatni aniqlashda va tarjimaning qanday yaxshi amalga oshirilishi haqida ma’lumotlarni topishga imkon beradi. Bu esa davom etayotgan tilshunoslik va tarjimonlikning rivojlanishiga tomosha qiladi.

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ELEMENTS OF IRONY IN HEMINGWAY’S: A CLEAN, WELLLIGHTED PLACE

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Abstract: Irony is commonly used in modernist literature and is a major characteristic of modern writing. Like other modern writers, Ernest Hemingway uses Irony to assist the development of their characters. In Hemingway’s short story A Clean, Well-Lighted Place, the author uses irony to develop the three characters the reader is introduced to. The three characters include an older waiter, a young waiter and an old man sitting in the shadow. In a cafe late at night, there are two waiters; the young waiter is restless to get home. Hemingway’s diction develops the young waiter to come off as selfish and in a rush against time.[1.13] As for the older waiter, he does not mind staying late at the cafe to serve customers because he shows an appreciation for a “clean well-lighted place.” Hemmingway makes irony from the young waiter not understanding the importance of providing people with a “clean well-lighted place,” when in fact he is concerned about getting home which would be his very own “clean well-lighted place.” There is also irony in the old waiter’s recitation of the Lord’s Prayer. The irony of this is that the prayer is meant to provide a sense of comfort like a “clean well-lighted

place” but replacing words in the prayer with “nada” which suggests that it offers no comfort.

Key words: nada, irony, “clean well-lighted place”, prayer

Discussion. Irony is a common feature of modernist literature. In Ernest Hemingway’s short story *A Clean, Well-Lighted Place*, the author uses irony to develop the characters. In a cafe late at night, there are two waiters, one young and one old. The young waiter is anxious to get home, his dialogue shows him as selfish and only caring about himself. The older waiter does not mind staying late at the cafe to serve customers because he understands the importance of a “clean well-lighted place.” The irony stems from the fact that the young waiter does not understand the importance of providing people with a “clean well-lighted place,” when in fact he is anxious to get home to a “clean well-lighted place.” This irony creates the image of a selfish and ignorant young man.

In Ernest Hemingway’s short story *A Clean, Well-Lighted Place* he emphasizes that our lives are a whole bunch of nothing and that eventually everyone will be depressed and alone. Hemingway uses irony, as often seen in modernist literature, to characterize the older waiter who works at the cafe. The older waiter says the lord’s prayer but replaces many key religious words with “nada” taking away any hints that suggest that there is a higher being guiding us in life. Hemingway also uses irony when talking about the lonely old man sitting in the cafe. *“This old man is clean he drinks without spilling. Even now, drunk look at him”*. Usually when you think of a drunk you think of a disheveled incompetent person, this old man however, is quite the opposite he is well put together drunk. *“I am one of those who like to stay late at the cafe... with all those who do not want to go to bed with all those who need a light for the night”*. People on earth are left alone to discover the meaning of their existence by themselves but the older waiter is offering the well-lighted cafe as a place of refuge for people

to escape the darkness and loneliness of life and where people can just sit and not have to worry about life.

Irony is very commonly seen in modernist literature. It helps develop the story and give the reader a different style of the literature. Irony usually affects mostly the characters throughout a story. In Modernist writing it makes the character seem like a contradiction because it portrays the opposite of who they actually are.

We consider that the older waiter in “A Clean Well-Lighted Place” by Ernest Hemmingway is an ironic character. It is ironic how he re-writes the lord`s prayer. The irony here is that the prayer is meant to provide comfort but replacing a lot of the words in the prayer with “nada” which implies that it offered no comfort.[2. 54] The Old Waiter also tried to deny his loneliness and similarities with the Old Man by saying that he has insomnia rather than being lonely and depressed.

“A Clean, Well-Lighted Place” is one of Hemingway`s most acclaimed short stories, as much for its exquisitely sparse writing style as for its expertly rendered existentialist themes. Existentialism is a philosophical movement whose adherents believe that life has no higher purpose and that no higher being exists to help us make sense of it. Instead, humans are left alone to find meaning in the world and their lives. In “A Clean, Well-Lighted Place,” the older waiter sums up the despair that drives him and others to brightly lit cafés by saying simply, “*It is a nothing.*”

This search for meaning and these feelings of emptiness and aimlessness reflect some of the principle ideas behind existentialism. Existentialism is a philosophical movement rooted in the work of the Danish philosopher Søren Kierkegaard, who lived in the mid-1800s. The movement gained popularity in the mid-1900s thanks to the work of the French intellectuals Jean-Paul Sartre, Simone de Beauvoir, and Albert Camus, including Sartre`s *Being and*

Nothingness (1943). According to existentialists, life has no purpose, the universe is indifferent to human beings, and humans must look to their own actions to create meaning, if it is possible to create meaning at all. Existentialists consider questions of personal freedom and responsibility. Although Hemingway was writing years before existentialism became a prominent cultural idea, his questioning of life and his experiences as a searching member of the Lost Generation gave his work existentialist overtones.

The principle of irony in Hemingway largely rests on what Heakon Chevalier has called a contrast between appearance and reality, between surface meaning and under-the-surface meaning. Behind such contrast stands out “*the possible other case, the case rich and edifying where the actually is pretentious and vain.*” Manifestations of this principle of contrast in Hemingway’s short stories are persistent, rescuing and varied. It may be a contrast within a character, or within a situation: or a contrast between two characters, or between two situations. Also, it may be a contrasted view of an idea, an ideal an episode, an event and an action. As a rule, the sharper the contrast, the more striking the irony; the more complex the contrast, the more cumulative the effect of irony. This cardinal principle of ironic contrast in Hemingway manifests itself in various facets and forms of “confident unawareness” in his characters which may be both real and pretended. When real this confident unawareness may be complete or normal and when pretended it may be self-assertive or self-deceptive.[3.28] Complete unawareness, the commonest and simplest prop for irony. is reflected for example in the platitudinous American mother in “A Canary for One” who, impervious to reality, insists that “American men make the best husbands” or in the blindly confident younger waiter in “A Clean Well-Lighted Place” who impatient to go home and unaware of the horrors of nada, bullies the old man (the last. lone customer) into leaving the clean, bright cafe compared with this complete unawareness. Hemingway’s use of incomplete unawareness a mix-up of awareness and unawareness in various measures, is subtler and more effective. It is betrayed for

instance by the doctor in “Indian camp” which is distinctly competent at surgery but totally ignorant of the consequences of humanly intolerable emotional strain: or by Mr. Frazer In “The Gambler, the Nun and the Radio” who has plenty of knowledge but little understanding. At the other end of the scale as opposed to the real unawareness (complete or partial) the pretended unawareness is a “mask of dissimulation,” a certain “*pretending to be what one is not and pretending not to be what one is.*” It may be self-assertive as in the American in “Hills like White Elephants” and the man in “the Sea Change” who both refuse to see the reality even though it states them in the face. But it may also be self-deceptive as in the Elliot in “Mr. And Mrs. Elliot” who pretends to example “very happy” in situations of perverted compromise or in Jig in “Hills Like White Elephants” who pretends to “feel fine’ even as she unwillingly submits to a forced abortion. However, quite often in Hemingway the contrast emerges not between a reality and an appearance but between two contextual. It points not to the correction of a false experience by a true one, but to two real and true experiences. It then suggests flat, ironic dualities in life each true in its own right, for the reader does not see what is and what merely seems. Human experiences, then, go their contrary or opposite ways, convincingly refuting one another. They are impelled by contradictory pulls and yield antithetical and antipodal meanings. Ironic contrasts then shade off into ironic contradictions and ironic self-conditions, typical of the present-day drift in the concept of irony. In “The Battler” for instance, when Nick is knocked off a American Short moving freight by an apparently friend brakeman he realizes the need to be tough. Among many critics of Hemingway who have discussed the function of irony in his fictions E.M. Halliday has cogently made out the case: “*The ironic gap between expectations and fulfillment, pretense and fact: intention and action, the message sent and the message received, the way things are thought or ought to be and the things are - this has been Hemingway`s great theme from the beginning: and it has called for an ironic method to do it artistic justice.*” J.J. Benson, however, notes the

greater significance of ironic detachment in Hemingway`s art and finds it central to a good number of Hemingway stories and novels and instrumental in restraining too close an identification of their protagonists with the author. To be sure, Hemingway`s kind of ironic detachment prevents him from accepting half-truths in his long odyssey to arrive at the truth. It keeps him longer on the nation and avoids any hasty finality. The finality in the form implied discriminations, affirmations even resolutions comes: but not before the author has taken into account the fuller context, the multiplicity of possibilities the compliment of issues involved; not too soon or too easy. All this makes the characteristic Hemingway`s view and method of resolving the discords of life into controlled art.

The younger waiter, therefore, betrays a sense of arrested awareness and his perceptions are restricted to nothing only his needs of and their fulfillment with admire, a job youth, confidence and money. His concerns are myopic, constricted and self-centered reckoning only in the immediate transient and altogether personal. We may note his sarcastic remark to the old deaf man and his callous observation about the soldier with the girl. He does not see that in the flux and whirligig of man`s life job does employ loss of job wife does imply loss of wise youth does imply age, confidence death of confidence, md money loss of mom. He stands in sharp ironic contrast with the older waiter who is conscious of all these methaphoring and planning implications and which reflects larger awareness. concern and empathy. Hence, to the younger waiter the old man tried to kill himself for “nothing” (for no reason) because he has plenty of money, but to the older waiter the despair of the old man who has now turned eighty is death.

Conclusion. Story traditionally has a symbol of security and comfort as Carlos Baker indicates turned into a symbol of “not-home” and the clean well-lighted calm may be the only “home” where he prefers to stay in as long as permitted. Confronted with this larger awareness of the dark forces of multifaceted “nada”

the older waiter symbolically forms his solidarity with all the night brethren: he is with “*those who like to stay late at the café, with all those who do not want to go to bed with all those who need a light for the night.*” And towards the end of the stop when he ponders that he himself alone is able to sleep at night, he self-deceptively says to himself: “It is probably only insomnia. Many must have it” In fact, it is more probably, insomnia castled by nada although one wouldn’t ever be too sure of it. The dispassionate notations of the experience of “nada” couched in ironic dualities and symbolic nuances very much stay at the center-stage of the story.

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РОЛЬ ИРОНИИ В ЭСТЕТИЧЕСКОЙ И ХУДОЖЕСТВЕННОЙ СИСТЕМЕ ПРОИЗВЕДЕНИЯ

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АННОТАЦИЯ

Данная статья рассматривает использование иронии на уровне текста, анализируя её специфику в системе изобразительных средств языка: в эстетической и художественной системе произведения "Финансист" в котором ирония не только служит выразительным стилистическим инструментом в руках Теодора Драйзера, но и играет ключевую роль в формировании глубокого философского и социального содержания его произведений.

Ключевые слова: ирония, литературный прием, мировоззрение автора, стремление к успеху, амбиции, финансист, двойственность, общественный конфликт.

ВВЕДЕНИЕ

В романе "Финансиста", читатели встречаются с богатым миром человеческих амбиций, власти и тонкой тканью иронии, объединяющей их воедино. Действие происходит в эпоху позолоченного века Америки, олицетворяя сложность человеческого опыта и стремление к успеху в обществе, где важны богатство и влияние. Читатели погружаются в этот литературный эпос и знакомятся с Фрэнком Каупервудом, чей путь отражает жизнь реального финансиста Чарльза Йеркса. В этом путешествии Драйзер исследует многогранную природу иронии, используя её как инструмент повествования и глубокий комментарий к противоречиям, присущим человеческой сущности.

В «Финансисте» ирония пронизывает изображение главного героя, Фрэнка Каупервуда, чья жизнь полна контрастов и противоречий. Одним из ярких примеров иронии является:

Двойственность Фрэнка Каупервуда.

В романе "Финансист" Теодора Драйзера одним из наиболее выразительных примеров, демонстрирующих иронию и двойственность персонажа Фрэнка

Каупервуда, становится момент, когда он вступает в обсуждение вопросов морали и этики в бизнесе. В ходе диалогов с партнерами и конкурентами Каупервуда часто можно заметить ироническое расхождение между его заявлениями о важности честности и добропорядочности и его собственными действиями, которые явно противоречат заявленным принципам.

Каупервуд: *"Важно всегда действовать честно и открыто в бизнесе. Это основа доверия и долгосрочных отношений."*

"Согласен, Фрэнк. Ваши слова внушают уверенность. Но как вы собираетесь решить проблему с последним соглашением? Мы слышали слухи о некоторых... необычных методах."

Каупервуд (улыбаясь): *"О, вы знаете, как это бывает в бизнесе. Иногда для достижения результата приходится быть немного изобретательным. Главное — результат, не так ли?"*

"Конечно, результат важен. Но не кажется ли вам, что есть определенная ирония в том, как эти 'изобретательные' методы сочетаются с вашими словами о честности?"

Каупервуд: *"В мире финансов иногда правила игры меняются так быстро, что трудно оставаться на одной стороне. Я уверен, вы понимаете, что для успеха иногда приходится адаптироваться."*^[27]

Эти диалоги не только создают напряженную и многогранную атмосферу, но и глубоко раскрывают внутренний мир Каупервуда, его взгляды на жизнь и бизнес. Ирония в этих обсуждениях служит как средство для развития сюжета, поскольку они обнажают истинное лицо главного героя и подчеркивают глубокий разрыв между его публичным образом

²⁷ Драйзер, Теодор. *Финансист*. Перевод Савельева К.А., Эксмо-Пресс, 2022. Серия "Pocket book", часть "Трилогия желаний", 3 книги. ISBN 978-5-04-100468-2. С 157

предпринимателя, следующего общепринятым нормам, и реальными действиями, направленными на достижение личной выгоды любой ценой.[²⁸]

Фрэнк Каупервуд: *"Вы знаете, мистер Дрексел, я всегда считал, что успех в нашем деле требует определенной гибкости моральных принципов."*

Мистер Дрексел: *"Гибкости, говорите? Я бы предпочел назвать это чувством ответственности. Не думаете ли вы, что наш долг сохранять честность и прозрачность во всех наших делах?"*

Фрэнк Каупервуд: *"Честность, конечно, имеет свое место, но не там, где она мешает достижению цели. В конце концов, мы здесь не для того, чтобы быть святыми, а чтобы строить империи и оставлять след в истории."*

Мистер Дрексел: *"Интересное определение обязанностей предпринимателя. Но помните, Фрэнк, что империи, построенные на песке моральной неопределенности, редко выдерживают испытание временем."*

Фрэнк Каупервуд: *"Время — единственный истинный судья, мистер Дрексел. И я уверен, что история запомнит меня как строителя, а не как того, кто колебался перед лицом решений."*[²⁹]

Через эти иронические моменты Драйзер не только критикует Каупервуда как отдельную личность, но и направляет свою критику на всю экономическую систему того времени, выставляя ее слабости и недостатки. Ирония в диалогах Каупервуда также позволяет читателю уловить нюансы и подтексты в его взаимодействиях с другими персонажами, делая его образ более сложным и противоречивым. В итоге, использование иронии в

²⁸ Barnes, Jonathan. "Visual Irony in Theodore Dreiser's Early Works." *Journal of Visual Culture and Literature*, vol. 37, no. 1, 2022, pp. 54-72.

²⁹ Драйзер, Теодор. *Финансист*. Перевод Савельева К.А., Эксмо-Пресс, 2022. Серия "Pocket book", часть "Трилогия желаний", 3 книги. ISBN 978-5-04-100468-2. С 329

изображении двойственности Фрэнка Каупервуда обогащает текст, делая его более глубоким и разнообразным. Этот прием не только служит мощным инструментом для раскрытия характеров персонажей и критики социальных и экономических порядков, но и предоставляет читателю ключ к пониманию сложности человеческой природы и моральных выборов, с которыми сталкиваются персонажи в процессе достижения успеха.

Общественные конфликты в романе "Финансист" Теодора Драйзера.

Что касается общественных конфликтов в романе "Финансист" Теодора Драйзера особенно заметна ирония в изображении общественных конфликтов, связанных с восходом и падением Фрэнка Каупервуда. Ключевым элементом, подчеркивающим эту иронию, является изменчивое отношение общества к главному герою в зависимости от его финансового и социального статуса. В моменты его успеха и взлета Каупервуд окружен восхищением и похвалами, становясь объектом всеобщего уважения и зависти. Однако стоит ему столкнуться с первыми признаками неудачи, как многие из его так называемых друзей и поклонников быстро меняют свою позицию, отвергая его и демонстрируя свою фальшивость и двуличие. Эта ирония выявляет глубокий разрыв между истинными ценностями и поверхностным восприятием успеха в обществе. Драйзер критически освещает не только личностные качества отдельных героев, но и общественные нормы, которые поощряют и поддерживают подобное поверхностное и эгоистичное поведение. Автор подчеркивает, что истинное лицо людей и ценности общественных институтов часто остаются скрытыми до момента кризиса, когда фасады падают, а настоящие мотивы и характеры обнажаются.

ЗАКЛЮЧЕНИЕ

Ирония в «Финансисте» сосредоточена на критике экономической системы и индивидуального стремления к богатству. Драйзер иронизирует над

жаждой власти и успеха главного героя, подчеркивая, как эти стремления ведут к моральному и личному упадку.

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THE EXPRESSION OF AUTHOR NEOLOGISMS IN "HARRY POTTER AND PHILOSOPHER'S STONE" BY JOANNE KATHLEEN ROWLING

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Abstract: Language evolution is a natural and complex process. Every language has enormous capacities for advancement. The greatest potential lies in its vocabulary. In all languages, neologisms play an important role in filling the lexical macro area with new forms of speech and linguistics. It is the purpose of

this paper to provide a comprehensive understanding of neologisms through a corpus linguistic analysis of the Harry Potter book that forms the cornerstone of the research. Our research aims not only to analyze the manner in which the British writer has imaginatively demonstrated her passion for language(s) in the Harry Potter series, but also to discover the origin of the terms that contribute to this vast fantastic vocabulary.

Key words: neologisms, spell, origin, macro area, linguistic analysis, complex presentation.

“Harry Potter” novel has contributed considerably to the speaking world of the English language with its unique and memorable words of magic and fantasy. Once French sociologist Marcel Mauss had said: “Magic speaks Sanskrit in India, Egyptian and Hebrew in Greece, Greek in the Latin (Roman) world and Latin in modern Europe.” Throughout the story, Rowling proves this statement to be true. One of the most common features that has caught the interest of most critics and contributed largely to the positive feedbacks about this world-famous book is in J. K. Rowling’s linguistically complex demonstrations. During the process of translating the novel into other languages, translators faced unusual and exciting linguistic barriers in keeping the original and source element of the J. K. Rowling’s style in the Harry Potter series. The main purpose of choosing this work for research is that the author of the work used many new words throughout the story, and most of them belong to the world of magic. Dr. Seuss, an American children's writer, emphasized that fiction is an important part of our lives. [1,10] Because the magical world represented by "Harry Potter" not only takes us on a trip to Hogwarts alley, but also teaches us how to deal with life's difficulties. It is made up of words that consist of 2 syllables mostly and they are much easier to understand than the terms in other fields.

"Harry Potter" is a masterpiece of Joanna Rowling consisting of 7 books. Each book consists of 70,000-300,000 words. In this part of the study, an analysis

of several neologisms used in the novel "Harry Potter" is given. Harry Potter and the Philosopher's Stone, the first book of the novel had been selected for the analysis. For the comprehensible expression of the author's neologisms the context in which they are used are taken from the original book and given below.

'Gryffindor,' said Ron. Gloom seemed to be settling on him again. 'Mum and Dad were in it, too. I don't know what they'll say if I'm not. I don't suppose Ravenclaw would be too bad, but imagine if they put me in Slytherin.' [3,80]

The neologism **Gryffindor** refers to one of the four Houses in Hogwarts School that Rowling described in the series of Harry Potter. This word is originated from the Latin word 'Griffin' which means a mythical creature that is a body of a lion. Besides, '**dor**' is from French which means 'gold'. By putting them together we can see the 'Griffin of Gold. In this way, Rowling borrowed and combined both words to create a new lexical item which represents one of the Houses of Hogwarts that is symbolized by the lion and the golden color.

*'Charlie's in Romania studying dragons and Bill's in Africa doing something for Gringotts,' said Ron. 'Did you hear about Gringotts? It's been all over the Daily Prophet, but I don't suppose you get that with the **Muggles** – someone tried to rob a high security vault.* [3,80]

This invented author neologism by Rowling is the description of a human being who was born in two non-magical parents, and incapable of doing magic. The word **Muggle** consists of two components: mug + -le. The first component is the word 'mug' which means in Oxford Dictionary: a person who is fool and easy to trick. On the other hand, the second one is the suffix -le. Therefore, Rowling combined the two parts to come up with a new term. One can say that there is a clear relation between the definition of the English word 'mug' and the invented one 'muggle'. That is, both of these words share the same characteristic of stupidity.

*‘The four houses are called Gryffindor, Hufflepuff, **Ravenclaw** and Slytherin. Each house has its own noble history and each has produced outstanding witches and wizards. [3,85]*

This neologism can be divided into two parts: ‘raven’ and ‘claw’. Rowling combined these words to come up with the name of this particular House. Although the naming suggests that the animal of this House should be a raven, the author changed it to an eagle. According to the Harry Potter Wiki, this change was due to the bad meaning of the raven, so, it was turned to an eagle.

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VILYAM VORDSVORTNING “THE WORLD IS TOO MUCH WITH US” SONETIDA TABIAT TASVIRINING AKS ETTIRILISHI

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Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqola ingliz romantizmining yorqin vakillaridan biri bo’lgan Vilyam Vordsvort qalamiga mansub “The World is Too Much With Us” sonetining badiiy tahlili va unda aks ettirilgan tabiat tasvirlarini o’rganishga qaratilgan. Bu she’r shoirning sanoat inqilobi davridagi jamiyatning

materialistligini va tabiatdan ajralganlik tuyg'usini aks ettiradi. Ushbu adabiy tahlil orqali she'r mazmuni, uslubiy vositalar va tabiat tasvirlari chuqur o'rganilgan.

Tayanch so'zlar: tabiat, sanoatlashish, tabiatni ulug'lash, tabiatdan ajralish, shaxslantirish, metafora, mubolag'a, alliteratsiya, tasvirlar, dengiz, shamol.

“The World is Too Much With Us” Vordsvortning 1800-yillarning boshlarida yozgan ko'plab ajoyib sonetlaridan biridir. Sonetlar o'n to'rt satrli she'riy ijod bo'lib, iambik pentametrdan yozilgan. “The World is Too Much With Us” she'rida muallif insonning tabiat bilan munosabatlarini yo'qotish nuqtai nazaridan tasvirlaydi. Bu munosabatlar bir vaqtlar gullab yashnagan edi, ammo hozir, sanoatlashuvning kundalik hayotga ta'siri tufayli, inson tabiatni qadrlash, ulug'lash va undan taskin topish qobiliyatini yo'qotdi. Ushbu asosiy yo'qotishni ta'kidlash uchun she'r uni uchta nuqtai nazardan tasvirlaydi: iqtisodiy, ma'naviy va madaniy. Shuni aytish joizki, bu she'r yo'qotilgan narsani qaytarib olishning yo'lini ko'rsatmaydi. Aksincha, uning ruhi umidsizlikka to'lib, insonning tabiat bilan asl munosabatlari hech qachon qayta tiklanmasligi mumkinligini ta'kidlaydi.

*with us; late and soon,
we lay waste our powers;—
ours;
sordid boon!*³⁰

*The world is too much
Getting and spending,
Little we see in Nature that is
We have given our hearts away, a*

Bu she'rda muallif odamlar

moddiy narsalarga berilib, tabiat bilan aloqani yo'qotgan zamonamizdan ko'ngli qolganini aytadi. “*The world is too much with us*” degan ibora dunyo tashvishlari va chalg'itadigan narsalar bizni haddan tashqari ko'p tashvishga solib, tabiat bilan bo'lgan munosabatlarimizni e'tibordan chetda qoldirganini anglatadi. Vordsvort

³⁰ Wordsworth, William. *Poems, In Two Volumes* (First Edition, second issue). London: Wood & Innes, Printers, Poppin's Court, Fleet Street. Printed for Longman, Hurst, Rees, and Orme, Patternoster-Row, 1807.

tabiatdan ajralishni tasvirlash uchun jonli tasvirlardan foydalanadi. “*We lay waste our powers*” (*Qudratimizni behuda sarflash*) iborasi biz tabiat bilan uyg’unlashmay, shunchaki arziyas narsalarga kuchimizni sarflayotganimizni anglatadi. “*Little we see in Nature that is ours*” satri insonning tabiatdan qanday ajralib qolganligi haqida metaforik ifodadir. Bu biz tabiatdagi o’z o’rnimizni tan olmayotganimizni yoki uning ahamiyatini qadrlamayotganimizni anglatadi.

*to the moon;
at all hours,
sleeping flowers;
of tune;
rather be*

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*This Sea that bares her bosom
The winds that will be howling
And are up-gathered now like
For this, for everything, we are out
It moves us not. Great God! I’d
A Pagan suckled in a creed outworn;*

Ushbu parchada muallif

insoniyatning tabiatdan ajralganligi haqida shikoyat qilishni davom ettiradi va oddiyroq, tabiiyroq hayotga intilishini ifoda etadi. Vordsvort dengiz, shamol va oy kabi tabiatning go’zalligiyu qudratiga hayron bo’ladi. Biroq u insonlar tabiatdagi bu mo’jizalarga befarq bo’lib, ularni qadrlay olishmayotganidan va ularga qiziqish ko’rsatmayotganidan qayg’uradi. Dastlabki misrada dengiz “o’z ko’kraklarini oyga ko’rsatgan” ayol sifatida tasvirlangan bo’lib, ochiqlik va zaiflik tasviriga ega. Ushbu shaxslantirish insoniyat va tabiat o’rtasidagi yaqinlik tuyg’usini ko’rsatadi. Shamollar “*like sleeping flowers*” (*uyquda bo’lgan gullar*)ga o’xshatilgan bo’lib, ularning yumshoq va uxlab yotgan holatini ta’kidlaydi. Bu taqqoslash shamol o’z kuchini yo’qotib qo’yishini kutayotganini yaqqol tasvirlab beradi.

So might I, standing on this pleasant lea,

³¹ Wordsworth, William. *Poems, In Two Volumes* (First Edition, second issue). London: Wood & Innes, Printers, Poppin's Court, Fleet Street. Printed for Longman, Hurst, Rees, and Orme, Patternoster-Row, 1807.

Have glimpses that would make me less forlorn;

Have sight of Proteus rising from the sea;

*Or hear old Triton blow his wreathèd horn*³²

Ushbu qismda Vordsvort tabiatning sirli va qo'rqinchli jihatlarini boshdan kechirish imkoniyatlarini tasavvur qiladi, bu uning yolg'izlik va aloqasizlik tuyg'ularini yengillashtiradi. Shoir tabiat bilan yanada chuqurroq aloqa o'rnatishni istaydi, o'zini tinch yaylovda (*"pleasant lea"*) turib, u yerda Proteus dengizdan ko'tarilayotgan yoki Tritonning shoxini chayqayotgan kabi g'ayrioddiy ko'rinishlarga guvoh bo'lishi mumkin. Ushbu afsonaviy ma'nolar muallifning tabiat ulug'vorligi va sehrli jihatlarini bilan uchrashish istagini ifodalaydi, bu esa tasalli beradi va uning yolg'izlik tuyg'usini yengillashtiradi. *"So might I, standing on this pleasant lea"* satrida "s" tovushining takrorlanishi manzaraning tinch muhitini kuchaytiradigan yumshoq va tinchlantiruvchi ritm yaratadi. Vordsvort so'zlovchi tabiatni tasavvur qilganini tasvirlash uchun yorqin tasavvurlardan foydalanadi. Yunon afsonasida dengiz bilan bog'liq Proteus va Triton nomlari tilga olingan bo'lib, Proteusning dengizdan ko'tarilishi va Tritonning qo'rg'oni chalinishi hayrat hissini uyg'otadi, bu esa tabiiy olamning afsonaviy ulug'vorligini eslatadi. Ushbu afsonaviy mavjudotlar tabiat dunyosining sirli kuchlarini ifodalaydi. Nutqchining tabiatdagi bunday g'ayrioddiy ko'rinishlarni ko'rishni orzu qilishi g'alati, ya'ni tabiatdagi hayratlanarli voqealarni haddan tashqari ko'tarishdir. Ushbu mubolag'a san'ati so'zlovchining tabiat bilan yanada chuqurroq aloqada bo'lish istagini ta'kidlaydi.

Ushbu uslubiy vositalar orqali Vordsvort so'zlovchining tabiat dunyosi bilan chuqurroq, mazmunliroq munosabatlarga bo'lgan istagini samarali ravishda

³² Wordsworth, William. *Poems, In Two Volumes* (First Edition, second issue). London, 1807.

yetkazadi, u yerda u ajoyib go'zallik lahzalarini boshdan kechirishi va zamonaviy hayotning ma'naviy bo'shlig'idan qochishi mumkin.

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JIN RIZNING "KENG SARGASSO DENGIZI" ASARIDA MUSTAMLAKACHILIK VA IRQIY MUAMMOLARINING IFODALANISHI

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Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqola ingliz postmodernizmining yorqin vakillaridan biri bo'lgan Jin Riz qalamiga mansub “Keng Sargasso dengizi” asaridagi mustamlakachilik va irqiy munosabatlar tahliliga bag'ishlangan. O'sha davrda Angliya mustamlakasi bo'lgan Yamayka kontekstida qahramonlarning irqiy o'ziga xosliklari ularning hayotiga qanday ta'sir ko'rsatgani ayniqsa, bosh qahramon Antuanet Kosveyning kreol irqi bilan kurashi va keyinchalik oq mustamlakachilar va qora yamaykaliklar tomonidan chetlatilishiga e'tibor qaratadi. Bundan tashqari, u mustamlakachilikning individual psixika va ijtimoiy tuzilmalarga doimiy ta'sirini yoritishga qaratilgan bo'lib, ushbu mavzularning irq, o'ziga xoslikning dolzarbligini ta'kidlaydi.

Kalit so'zlar: mustamlakachilik, irqiy munosabatlar, postmodernizm, koloniyalar, avtobiografik asar, qullik

Ingliz postmodernizmining yorqin vakilasi Jin Rizning “Keng Sargasso dengizi” asari o'zida mustamlakachilik va irqiy munosabatlarni jamlagani va bu mavzularning qaharmonlar hayotiga ta'sirini keng yoritib bergan ijodkorlardan biri sanaladi. Aslida Jin Rizning o'zi ham Asar qahramoni Antuanetta kabi, kreol ya'ni otasi Uelslik, onasi esa Shotlandiyalik kreol bo'lgan va Yamaykada o'sgan. Shuning uchun ham hech qachon o'zini orolning tub aholisi bo'lgan qora tanlilarga mos kelmasligini bilgan, va orolda bolaligi o'tgani uchun inglizchada shevasi bilinib turgani tufayli Yevropaliklar tomonidan ham Angliyada xuddi chetdan kelgan odamdek qabul qilingan. Bu irqiy munosabatlarsa keyinchalik uning asarlarida o'z ifodasini topgan.

“ Keng Sargasso dengizi” uch qisimli formatni o'z ichiga oladi, Antuanetta birinchi va uchinchi qismlarni, Rochester ya'ni, Antuanettaning eri esa ikkinchi qismni hikoya qiladi. Hikoyadagi bu o'zgarish, vaqt va makonning oldinga va orqaga harakatlanishi, avtobiografik asardan ancha farq qiladi. Antuanetta hikoya qiladigan qismda, Riz vaqtni hozirgi zamondan o'tmishga

o'tkazish uchun parchalanish deb nomlangan qurilmadan foydalanadi va Antuanettani yaratadi. "Keng Sargasso dengizi" "Jeyn Eyr"ga o'ziga xos javob sifatida yozilgan bo'lib, "Jeyn Eyr"dagi Berta qahramoni haqida hikoya qiladi. Jin Riz Jeyn Eyrning tugashidan norozi bo'lgani uchun Bertaning hayoti haqidagi hikoyani yozadi. "Keng Sargasso dengizi" filmidagi Antuanetta Kosvey "Jeyn Eyr" asaridagi Berta Meysonning versiyasidir. Ikkalasi ham janob Rochesterga uylangan. Riz romani orqali Antuanettaning tarixini o'rganib, Bertaning xarakteri uchun kontekstni ta'minlaydi. "Keng Sargasso dengizi" "Jeyn Eyr" qoldirgan bo'shliqlarni to'ldiradi va kreol madaniyati, Antuanetta tarbiyasi va uning jinnilikka tushishi haqida tushuntirish beradi. Rizning romanida Bertaning ya'ni, chortoqda qamalgan telba ayol, jabrdiyda va tashlandiq shaxs sifatida tasvirlanishi Bront asarida Bertaga javob sifatida xizmat qiladi. Jeyndan farqli o'laroq, Antuanettani hayotidagi muammolar mag'lub qiladi. U umidsiz yashaydi va yetuklikka erishmaydi. Jeyn-Eyrdagi Berta o'z joniga qasd qilish orqali o'z erkinligiga erisha ham, u aqlini yo'qotishdan boshqa hech narsaga erisha olmaydi. "Jeyn Eyr" dan farqli ravishda Riz o'z romanida Antuanetta obrazi orqali, mustamlakachilik va irqiy munosabatlarni yaqqol ko'rsatib beradi. Antuanettaning eri haqidagi voqeani o'tgan zamonda noma'lum shaxs aytib beradi va uning shaxsiyatiga haqiqiylik beradi. Hikoyadagi bu o'zgarishlar o'quvchilarga ikki asar o'rtasidagi madaniy va psixologik farqlarni tushunishga yordam beradi. Antuanettadagi irqiy izolyatsiya va patriarxal zulm qurboni ekanligi sababli jinnilik paydo bo'lganligini ko'rishimiz mumkin. Qullik rasman bekor qilingan bo'lsa ham, qaramlik kishanlari sobiq qullarni tark etmadi. Sobiq qul xizmatchilari va oq tanli ish beruvchilar o'rtasidagi dushmanlik qonuniy mulkchilikdan iqtisodiy qaramlikka o'tdi va majoziy qullikka aylandi. Yong'in o'lovi bunday qora tanli ishchilarning ekspluatatsion oqlarga qarshi noroziligini keskin bayon qiladi: *"Still they were quiet and there were so many of them I could hardly see any grass or trees. There must have been many of the bay people but I recognized no one. They all looked the same face repeated over and over ..."* - Antuanettaning

oilasi sobiq quldor bo'lgani uchun qora tanlilar ularni dushmani kabi ko'rishgan va bu ularning uyiga o't qo'yishiga olib keldi.

Qullik bekor qilingandan so'ng, ko'plab qora tanlilar oq tanlilarga xizmat qilishdan to'xtashdi:

"...but the people here won't work. They don't want to work" -ushbu fikrni janob meyson, ya'ni Annettning ikkinchi eri aytadi. Endi qullik yo'q ekan, kimdir ishlashi shart emas degan fikr hukmron bo'la boshladi. Moddiy istaklar va kapitalizmning kuchi hukmronlik qildi va o'tmish qadriyatlari, shu jumladan insoniyatga hurmat kamaydi degan fikrlar tarqala boshladi.

Shaxslararo munosabatlar ko'pincha pul kelishuvlariga asoslana boshlandi. Jins, terining rangi, ota-onasi va kelib chiqish joyi ularning jamiyatdagi mavqeiga ta'sir qildi. Ayollar erkaklarnikiga qaraganda pastroq sinf edi. Angliyalik oq tanlilar oq kreollardan ustunlik tuyg'usiga ega edilar. Yamaykadan bo'lmagan sobiq quldorlar, Yamaykaning qora tanli xalqi tomonidan nafratlanilgan:

"...They hated us..." - Antuanettaning bu so'zlari sobiq quldorlar va ularning oilasining Yamaykaning tub aholisi tomonidan qanchalik nafratlanishidan darak beradi.

Aralash irqiy odamlar qora va oq jamiyatlar orasidagi bo'shliqni to'ldirishdi va ota-onalaridek, har qanday joyni egallashdi. Turli darajalar va guruhlar o'rtasidagi almashinuvlar majburiy hurmat ostida bo'lgan bo'lsada, qo'rquv bilan yashashgan.

Roman birinchi shaxs tomonidan hikoya qilingan. Antuanetta va uning erining qalbi har bir insonning fikriga qarab o'zgaradi..Antuanettaning versiyasi Yamaykaning kreol aholisi nuqtai nazaridan olingan. Uning yozuvi empatiyani uyg'otadi va Karib dengizidagi qullikdan keyingi ozodlikning adolatsizligini aniq ta'kidlaydi. Uning ifodalashi juda aniq, shuning uchun ham o'quvchi xayolida voqealar aks etadi.

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**THE DESCRIPTION OF RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN MAN AND
NATURE IN ROBERT FROST'S POETRY**

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Abstract. This article explores the complex relationship between man and nature as depicted in the poetry of American poet Robert Frost. Close readings of selected Frost poems including "Birches," "The Need of Being Versed in Country Things," and "Tree at My Window" reveal Frost's nuanced perspective of how humans interact with the natural environment. Frost portrays nature as sublime but indifferent, recognizing both its beauty and cruelty. The analysis traces themes of man seeking respite in nature, futilely attempting to control nature, finding spiritual meaning in nature, and nature's constant cycle of death and rebirth. The article argues that Frost advocates for a balanced perspective - appreciating nature's gifts whilst acknowledging man's lack of dominance over natural order.

Keywords: Poetry, man, nature, relationship, environment, imagination, symbolize , mysterious, images, spiritual, characterization

The poetry of iconic American poet Robert Frost frequently explores complex philosophical questions regarding existence, faith, and the human condition. One of the most prominent themes in his vast body of work is mankind's intricate relationship with the natural world. Frost's poetry offers rich insights into the interplay between humans and nature, depicting the give and take between the two forces and arguing for a delicate balance and mutual respect. This article conducts close readings of selected Frost poems to analyze his multifaceted portrayal of the bonds connecting man and the environment.

Considerable scholarship has examined how Frost navigates humanity's complex bonds to the natural realm across his verses. However, analyses have tended to focus on singular features of Frost's multi-layered perspective separately, rather than conducting integrated analysis contrasting said dimensions. This article aims to address this gap through close readings of Frost poems

spanning motifs of escapism in nature, nature's indifference and intimacy found in environment to showcase the richness underlying the poet's representation of ties binding man and nature.

This article takes an in-depth look at three Robert Frost poems featuring touching perspectives on interactions between mankind and the natural world - "Birches" "The Need of Being Versed in Country Things" and "Tree at My Window". Utilizing textual analysis, the predominant themes and messages related to man's ties to nature are extracted from each poem. The discussion synthesizes the commonalities between the three works to draw broader conclusions regarding Frost's extensive view on the complex relationship human beings share with their natural surroundings.

Considerable scholarship has been dedicated to analyzing the complex relationship between man and nature featured prominently across Robert Frost's poetry. Critics have offered diverse interpretations of how Frost portrays humanity's ties to the natural landscape.

Several literary critics have centered on the repeating theme of finding temporary escape through immersing oneself in nature's splendor, most famously articulated in "Birches." Evans examined how Frost depicts nature as a fanciful retreat from dull human troubles, represented by the metaphor of playfully swinging on birch tree branches. Comparatively, Peters argued Frost adds nuance by reinstating nature's imposing supremacy, evident through ice storms ultimately bending the proud birch trees. Other analyses emphasized Frost's frequent portrayal of nature's cold indifference to mankind. Ryan explored Frost's sentiment that the natural world remains detached and unaware of humanity's trifles in poems like "The Need of Being Versed in Country Things" which spotlight the environment reclaiming spaces without concern for people. Conversely, Singh traced an alternate perspective stressing intimate spiritual connections formed with nature, traced in works like "Tree at My Window" depicting finding meaning through nature's timeless stoicism.

Thus, Frost scholarship reflects the poet's layered view point, underlining nature's splendor yet refusal to be tamed, while meditating on how to balance respect and trust navigating this complex bond between man and his surrounding landscapes. By illuminating contrasting interpretations, the review foregrounds this article's contribution examining Frost's multifaceted insight through close reading of poems straddling said perspectives.

Nature as sanctuary providing temporary respite from human burdens. The desire to escape worldly responsibilities and lose oneself in swaying birch trees in "Birches" illustrates Frost's view of nature as an enchanting haven offering transient relief from man's troubles. However, the ultimate force bending the trees are indifferent ice storms, underscoring the environment's detached control.

*When I see birches bend to left and right
Across the lines of straighter darker trees,
I like to think some boy's been swinging them.
But swinging doesn't bend them down to stay
As ice-storms do.*

"The Need of Being Versed in Country Things" demonstrates Frost's assessment of nature's indifference to mortal affairs through images of the landscape erasing remains of human existence without hesitation.

*The birds that came to it through the air
At broken windows flew out and in,
Their murmur more like the sigh we sigh
From too much dwelling on what has been*

By contrast, "Tree at My Window" finds spiritual meaning through forming intimate connections with nature, exemplified by the closing line on discovering eternal truth in the enduring tree.

*Tree at my window, window tree,
My sash is lowered when night comes on;
But let there never be curtain drawn*

Between you and me.

Overall, Frost outlines the futility of man's quest to subdue the natural world, evident in the transient retreat provided by birch trees and house's rapid erasure from the land. Both showcase nature swiftly restoring autonomous order despite humanity's efforts to control their domain. Frost advocates respect for environment's supremacy and ceaseless cycles surpassing human scales.

Through such complex perspectives, Frost conveys nuanced insight on navigating the intricate bonds between inferior man and sublime natural order. A delicate balance is argued for - appreciating the protection and wisdom offered by nature, whilst acknowledging the lack of dominance over its might.

The speaker in "Birches" imagines birch trees bending due to a passing boy's playful act of riding them by swinging on their branches, though later acknowledges the truth of ice storms bending the trees. This poem has been regarded as among Frost's most profound works describing man finding temporary escape from earthly burdens by immersing in nature's realm. The opening lines introduce the bending birch trees as symbols of nature stoically enduring man's impositions. Frost sees nature as patiently accommodating humanity's needs, exemplified by the birch trees passively allowing themselves to be "ridden down" for the enjoyment of mischievous young boys despite their burden.

The speaker expresses a yearning to join the boys, "go off to heaven" swinging on birches, cementing the theme of man seeking respite from worldly cares by losing oneself to the beauties of nature for a transient spell. The desire to recede into nature by swaying amongst birch branches parallels an escapist fantasy, transporting man into peaceful natural shelters away from human preoccupations. However, Frost concludes that it is ice storms – nature's raw force – which truly bow the birch trees, reinstating natural order where man fails to leave a lasting imprint against nature's immutable will.

I'd like to go by climbing a birch tree,

And climb black branches up a snow-white trunk

Toward heaven, till the tree could bear no more,

But dipped its top and set me down again.

Overall, "Birches" is a beautifully crafted poem that delves into the complexities of existence, blending nature with human experience to convey profound insights about resilience, imagination, and the passage of time.

"The Need of Being Versed in Country Things" emphasizes nature's indifference. Published in Frost's last poetry anthology, "The Need of Being Versed in Country Things" has been characterized as portraying the rural natural landscape as aloof and uncaring about humanity. The poem opens with the arresting line "the house had gone to bring again to the sense of sight", instantly conveying nature swiftly erasing the house's existence after residents had departed, reclaiming the land for its own relentless purposes. Analyses argue this poem grieves man's insignificance against the landscape's might, exemplified by images like "the wood-chuck could not share the house" and "a crop sprung green from earth that showed no loss" .

Such vivid descriptions spotlight nature swiftly erasing all vestiges of human habitation without pausing, indifferent to mortal comings and goings. The poem underlines the message humans hold little power altering land's inevitable eternal cycles. Critics highlight "The Need of Being Versed in Country Things" as exemplifying Frost's clear-sighted assessment of nature's detached outlook to mankind's transitory troubles and feats. Though providing refuge at times, Frost outlines nature as an aloof, impersonal judge largely impervious to the trifles of man.

For them there was really nothing sad.

But though they rejoiced in the nest they kept,

One had to be versed in country things

Not to believe the phoebes wept

"Tree at My Window" by Robert Frost is a poem that explores the dynamic relationship between the speaker and a tree outside his window. The poem reflects on themes of isolation, nature, and the subjective interpretation of reality.

The poem begins with the speaker describing a tree that stands outside his window. The tree becomes a symbolic presence, representing the natural world and the enduring aspects of life. The use of personification gives the tree human-like qualities, as it "looks" at the speaker and "watches" him with a sense of silent companionship.

The speaker, feeling isolated, contrasts the tree's steadfastness with his own sense of alienation. He sees the tree as an observer, a silent witness to his struggles and emotions. This establishes a subtle tension between the human experience and the enduring, unchanging nature of the tree.

The second stanza introduces a metaphorical interpretation of the tree's presence. The speaker suggests that the tree serves as a barrier or a "wall" between him and the outside world. This creates a sense of separation and emphasizes the speaker's feelings of isolation and loneliness. The window becomes a symbolic boundary, representing the barrier between the external and internal worlds.

*Vague dream head lifted out of the ground,
And thing next most diffuse to cloud,*

Despite the perceived separation, the speaker acknowledges a form of connection with the tree. The tree's branches, described as "lovely" and "blue," evoke a sense of beauty and tranquility. This aesthetic appreciation suggests a deeper, more positive relationship between the speaker and the natural world, even in the midst of his isolation.

The poem concludes with a contemplation on the nature of reality and perception. The speaker questions whether the tree is aware of him, wondering if it sees him "in his room." This ambiguity invites readers to reflect on the subjective nature of human experience and the uncertainty of how the external world perceives us.

"Tree at My Window" is a reflective and introspective poem that delves into the complexities of human emotion and the interplay between the individual and the natural world. Through the metaphor of the tree at the window, Frost captures the universal themes of isolation, connection, and the subjective nature of reality. "Tree at My Window" explores nature's spiritual meaning

Contrasting with the previous poem's stoic characterization of nature, "Tree at My Window" conveys Frost's sentiment of finding divine meaning by communing with the natural environment beyond physical existence. He depicts the tree's branch brushing against the windowpane through changing seasons, weathering rain, snow and wind. The speaker fixates on the strong tree impervious to weather's harshness, drawing analogy to his own helplessness among life's storms seeking hope in nature's resilience.

Critics have gravitated to the verse "That day she put our heads together, Fate had her imagination about her" signifying the speaker gaining spiritual sustenance witnessing nature weathering adversity mirroring his own. Unlike "The Need of Being Versed in Country Things" which underscores nature's detachment, here Frost finds intimacy with environment lowering divides between mortal and eternal realms. Metaphorically brought closer counteracting an indifferent universe through the weather-beaten tree, man discovers profound kinship with nature. The poem closes powerfully with the tree having "the form of the everlasting I have found in [it]", symbolizing enduring connection to mysterious eternal truths revealed through appreciating environmental beauty.

In conclusion, the analysis reveals Robert Frost's nuanced insight on humanity's relationship with the natural order across three key poems. Frost varies between portraying nature as a fanciful retreat from daily struggles to asserting its cold detachment and supremacy over mortal feats. At times, spiritual resonance is found by embracing nature's wisdom enduring beyond individual human existence. Frost argues for respecting environment's splendor and ceaseless rhythms surpassing mankind's grasp, while enjoying transient spells of

escape and meaning offered by natural protection. Thus he advocates for a delicate balance within the complex bonds between man and overarching natural order.

Analysis of the three selected works reveals Robert Frost's layered perspective on humanity's relationship to the natural order. "Birches" depicts nature's splendor as offering awestruck escape from earthly tribulations. "The Need of Being Versed in Country Things" conversely stresses environment's cold neutrality to mankind's transient dramas. Finally, "Tree at My Window" finds mystical affirmation by bearing witness to nature withstanding merciless elements. Frost expresses reverence for the very indifference making nature indifferent. Overall in Frost's nature poetry, man futilely grasps for dominance, ultimately forced to appreciate the environment's splendor while accepting lack of control over its autonomous power. Frost argues for conciliation within the uneasy partnership between weak mankind and mighty indifferent nature.

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THE CONCEPT OF "SELF-HELP" AND CRUCIAL VIRTUES OF INDIVIDUAL IN SELF-HELP LITERATURE

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The word “self-help” is taken from the work of bestseller author Samuel Smiles which appeared in 1859. According to Palmetto Publishing the self-help book genre contains nonfiction books written with the intention of instructing the reader on how to solve an issue or improve an area of their life or providing other guidance. These books are also known as “self-improvement” books, often giving advice on how to improve oneself mentally, physically, financially, etc. Common topics of this genre include improving one’s finances, bettering one’s mental health, getting one’s life in order, growing one’s confidence, and strengthening relationships.[1;174]

Ameesha Smith-Green in her article “Self-help vs self-improvement: What is the difference?” divides the self-help books into 2 groups by identifying their main characteristics. They are

1) Self-help books -which are essentially about the reader overcoming problems—especially personal, mental, or emotional ones. This often includes issues such as depression, anxiety, low self-esteem, or relationships with the self or others. The key factor is that the reader is doing so without getting professional help, such as therapists or counsellors.

2) Self-improvement books- they do what they say on the tin: help people to improve themselves without professional help, such as a coach or training program. Self-improvement books are basically about the reader improving themselves to become better. This may include becoming more organised, focused, or efficient. It may mean developing positive habits or becoming a better person.

If it is looked back in history the appearance of this genre is strongly connected with various social concepts such as individualism, self made man, neoliberalism, ideology and “American Dream”. All of these concepts played crucial roles in the development of self-help literature.

In her research Daniella Lippe tried to connect some of these ideas in order to clarify the reasons of appearing self-help genre. The term *individualism* first appeared in France where it became part of the French dictionary in 1836. It meant “tendency towards an exaltation of the individual as a threat to the stability of social and political order” which changed after a short period of time. It characterized “ideals of a free individual seeking the opportunities for the development of his personality”. In different countries the term was accepted with different meanings. Despite these minor differences, overall, the idea of individualism was met with much acceptance and while the Great Depression and the New Deal led to a brief decline in that acceptance, individualism quickly recovered and has since become “the most cherished ideal for the American people”. There is additional evidence that indicates a rise of individualism. US American parents, for example, value their children’s independence more and their obedience less. For this reason, the occurrence of self-help genre is strongly related with the individualism so that it focuses on the development and progress of every individual.

The “myth of the self-made man”, epitomizes ideas of individualism and highlights the importance of individual success. Due to the idea of the self-made man, personal success and expressive individualism are related to the “processes of nation-building” and “collective success”. As an example Benjamin Franklin is often seen as the “quintessential self-made man” and “a model representative of the American Dream”. In his *Autobiography* Franklin constitutes a “self-improvement scheme” which he himself followed, and which has become popular and has been quoted many times). This scheme encourages readers to adhere to thirteen virtues such as frugality, moderation, humility and etc. It is indicated that Franklin rejects a deterministic social order in favor of individualism and free will. That’s the reason why the concept of self-help strongly highlights the self confidence which was also a major factor of “self-made man”. [3;6-13]

While holding a research Koay Dong Liang defines ideology as a dynamic set of beliefs and practices that are socially developed among specific social groups over a period of time. This shared system (e.g., desirable/undesirable) is linguistically observable. By this he implies that it is reasonable to use text analysis to identify the ideologies underlying self-improvement books. Moreover, he mentions about Germer's linguistic classification of ideology and explores how linguistic features relate to the social purpose of the self-help genre. The *location* aspect of Germer's framework includes the dialectical relationship between the three components:

- a) *Thought* – ideology as a set of beliefs
- b) *Behaviour* – ideology as a set of practices
- c) *Language* – ideology derived from linguistic norms [4;380]

He indicates that self-improvement books are closely related to the ideology of the United States. The American Dream is the view that America is the land of choices and with the help of hard work and perseverance, individuals can be successful. Self-reliance, self-determination, and self-made men and women are the main values within the American Dream it is claimed that these values remain major elements in America's identity in the twenty-first century.

American Dream advocates a better, richer and fuller life, and he explains that this is often defined in terms of money. Cullen explains that this can be extended to religious transformation, political reform, educational attainment and sexual expression, to name a few areas. In short, the American Dream is about individual Americans finding personal fulfilment in their lives.[2;40-43]

Furthermore, some important virtues are mentioned in the process of self-making which are also included in self-help literature. They are; entrepreneurship, responsibility, confidence, non-conformity and self-exploitation.

Entrepreneurship has been an important part of self-making throughout US history. Entrepreneurialism among neoliberal selves can be identified from different angles and has been studied from different perspectives. While studying

young female classical musicians Christina Scharff, for example, was able to identify ten main characteristics of neoliberal entrepreneurs. These are the self as business; constantly active and lacking time; embracing risks; learning from knock-backs and staying positive; hiding injuries; negotiating competing discourses; anxious self-doubting and insecurity; competing with the self; establishing boundaries and blaming others.

The high degree of responsibility which is placed upon the people is also considered one of the key aspects that is helpful to shape self. An additional central aspect of neoliberal responsibility is that individuals are asked to be active in dealing with the unexpected and to be ready to adapt to change. Regardless of the circumstances, it is the response to it that ultimately counts.

In order to live with that high degree of responsibility people must believe in themselves and be confident in themselves and in their abilities, which constitutes a further characteristic of neoliberal selfhood.

Confidence, or excessive self-positivity, refers to the importance of self-love as part of neoliberal selfhood. Emerson once emphasized the importance of believing in oneself for achieving happiness and states that “self-trust is the essence of heroism” the confidence and self-positivity that is demanded from readers of modern self-help books is unique in the way that they forego critical thinking.

Nonconformity plays an important role in neoliberal selfhood. Neoliberalism encourages the rejection of conformity and allows, to a limited extent, some sort of “bohemian posturing, personal experimentation and geographical exploration”.

Voluntary self-exploitation mainly refers to the end of a clear distinction between work and private life. According to Lee “work ought to become a joyful exercise, while play, leisure and holiday have to become part of work, vice versa” [2;17-21]

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**UNRAVELING THE POSTMODERN TAPESTRY: JEAN RHYS'S “I
USED TO LIVE HERE ONCE” AND ITS MULTIFACETED
POSTMODERNIST ELEMENTS**

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Annotation: This article examines the postmodernist approach in the works of Jean Rhys, focusing specifically on her renowned story "I Used to Live Here Once." Through a detailed analysis of various examples within the text, the thesis explores the presence and significance of postmodernist elements in Rhys's storytelling. The article delves into the complexities of Rhys's narrative style, highlighting how her use of postmodernist techniques adds depth and nuance to the overall reading experience.

Key words: postmodernist, fragmentation, metafiction, intertextuality, skepticism

Jean Rhys, a renowned author, is celebrated for her literary contributions that have left a lasting impact on readers and critics alike. Her unique

postmodernist style has garnered praise from numerous literary experts, solidifying her place in the world of literature.

“For me, Rhys is only interesting because she was a superb craftsman with words. Paying too much attention, as a biographer, to what people thought of her or to her flouting of convention risks entering the world of gossip, sometimes not benevolently intended .”³³

The story "I Used to Live Here Once" by Jean Rhys contains several elements of postmodernism. Here are some key aspects of the story that align with postmodernist themes:

1. Fragmentation: The story is fragmented, with the protagonist recalling memories of her past as she revisits a place she used to live. The disjointed narrative structure reflects the fragmented nature of memory and identity in postmodern literature. In the story "I Used to Live Here Once" by Jean Rhys, the element of fragmentation is evident in the protagonist's recollection of the stepping stones by the river: *"She was standing by the river and looking at the stepping stones and remembering each one. There was the round unsteady one, the pointed one, the flat one in the middle – the safe stone where you could stand and look round."*³⁴

This excerpt demonstrates the fragmented nature of memory as the protagonist recalls each individual stone and the memories associated with them, highlighting the disjointed and non-linear quality of her recollection. The fragmented structure of her memories reflects a postmodernist approach to storytelling that challenges traditional narrative coherence.

2. Metafiction: The story blurs the boundaries between reality and fiction, as the protagonist interacts with children who do not acknowledge her presence.

³³ Elaine Savory. *Literary Studies and Environmental Studies*. New York NY, U.S.A. 2023.

³⁴ [Jean Rhys](#). *I Used to Live Here Once* England. Penguin Books 1994

This metafictional element challenges the reader's perception of what is real and what is imagined.

The excerpt that shows the usage of metafiction in "I Used to Live Here Once" by Jean Rhys is: *"She came to the worn stone steps that led up to the house and her heart began to beat. The screw pine was gone, so was the mock summer house called the ajoupa, but the clove tree was still there and at the top of the steps the rough lawn stretched away, just as she remembered it. She stopped and looked towards the house that had been added to and painted white. It was strange to see a car standing in front of it."*³⁵

This excerpt demonstrates metafiction as the protagonist observes changes to the familiar setting she remembers from the past, highlighting the theme of memory and the passage of time. The protagonist's recognition of alterations in the landscape creates a sense of disorientation and blurs the boundaries between reality and memory, engaging with the concept of metafiction within the narrative. The following excerpts also show the usage of metafiction in "I Used to Live Here Once" by Jean Rhys are: *"She was standing by the river and looking at the stepping stones and remembering each one. There was the round unsteady one, the pointed one, the flat one in the middle – the safe stone where you could stand and look round. The next wasn't so safe for when the river was full the water flowed over it and even when it showed dry it was slippery. But after that it was easy and soon she was standing on the other side."*

"The road was much wider than it used to be but the work had been done carelessly. The felled trees had not been cleared away and the bushes looked trampled. Yet it was the same road and she walked along feeling extraordinarily happy."

"It was a fine day, a blue day. The only thing was that the sky had a glassy look that she didn't remember. That was the only word she could think of. Glassy."

³⁵ [Jean Rhys](#). *I Used to Live Here Once* England. Penguin Books 1994

She turned the corner, saw that what had been the old pavé had been taken up, and there too the road was much wider, but it had the same unfinished look."

"She came to the worn stone steps that led up to the house and her heart began to beat. The screw pine was gone, so was the mock summer house called the ajoupa, but the clove tree was still there and at the top of the steps the rough lawn stretched away, just as she remembered it. She stopped and looked towards the house that had been added to and painted white. It was strange to see a car standing in front of it."³⁶

These excerpts demonstrate metafiction as the protagonist revisits familiar places from her past and notices changes in the landscape, blurring the lines between memory and reality. The descriptions of the setting evoke a sense of nostalgia and disorientation, engaging with the theme of memory and the passage of time within the narrative.

3. **Intertextuality:** The story references the past and present, creating a sense of intertextuality between different time periods. The protagonist's memories of the past intersect with her present experiences, highlighting the interconnectedness of time and memory.

The excerpt that shows the usage of intertextuality in "I Used to Live Here Once" by Jean Rhys is: *"She came to the worn stone steps that led up to the house and her heart began to beat. The screw pine was gone, so was the mock summer house called the ajoupa, but the clove tree was still there and at the top of the steps the rough lawn stretched away, just as she remembered it. She stopped and looked towards the house that had been added to and painted white. It was strange to see a car standing in front of it."*

This excerpt demonstrates intertextuality as the protagonist encounters changes in the landscape that disrupt her memories of the place where she used to live. The presence of the car in front of the house and the alterations to the

³⁶ [Jean Rhys](#). *I Used to Live Here Once* England. Penguin Books 1994

surroundings challenge her recollection of the familiar setting, highlighting the theme of memory and the passage of time within the narrative.

4. Skepticism towards grand narratives: The story questions the stability of memory and identity, suggesting that these constructs are fluid and subject to change. This skepticism towards grand narratives is a common theme in postmodern literature.

In the story "I Used to Live Here Once" by Jean Rhys, the usage of skepticism towards grand narratives can be seen in the protagonist's experience of returning to a place from her past. The following excerpts illustrate this theme:

"The road was much wider than it used to be but the work had been done carelessly. The felled trees had not been cleared away and the bushes looked trampled. Yet it was the same road and she walked along feeling extraordinarily happy."

In this passage, the protagonist encounters changes in the landscape that challenge her memories of the place. The wider road and the careless work suggest a disruption of the familiar environment, leading to a sense of skepticism about the grand narrative of her past experiences.

"She came to the worn stone steps that led up to the house and her heart began to beat. The screw pine was gone, so was the mock summer house called the ajoupa, but the clove tree was still there and at the top of the steps the rough lawn stretched away, just as she remembered it."³⁷

Here, the absence of certain elements that were part of her past memories, such as the screw pine and the summer house, highlights the fragility of memory and the skepticism towards the stability of grand narratives. The changes in the landscape challenge her perception of the place she used to live.

These excerpts demonstrate how the protagonist's return to a familiar place is marked by skepticism towards the grand narrative of her past, as she navigates

³⁷ [Jean Rhys](#). *I Used to Live Here Once* England. Penguin Books 1994

changes in the environment that disrupt her memories and challenge her sense of continuity.

Overall, "I Used to Live Here Once" by Jean Rhys exhibits several elements of postmodernism through its fragmented narrative structure, metafictional elements, intertextuality, and skepticism towards grand narratives.

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METAFORALARNUNG KONSEPTUALLASHUVI

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Ko'pchilik uchun metafora she'riy tasavvur va ritorik gullab-yashnash vositasidir - bu oddiy nutqdan ko'ra farqli masala. Bundan tashqari, metafora faqat tilga xos

xususiyat bo'lib, fikr yoki harakat emas, balki so'z masalasidir. Shu sababli, ko'pchilik metaforasiz suhbatdoshlar bir-birini yaxshi tushunishadi deb o'ylashadi. Biz, aksincha, metafora nafaqat tilda, balki fikr va harakatda ham kundalik hayotda keng tarqalganligini ko'ramiz. Bizning oddiy kontseptual tizimimiz, biz qo'shiq aytadigan va harakat qiladigan nuqtai nazardan, asosan metaforik xususiyatga ega. Bizning fikrimizni boshqaradigan tushunchalar faqat aql-idrok masalalari emas. Ular bizning kundalik faoliyatimizni eng oddiy tafsilotlarga boshqaradi. Bizning tushunchalarimiz biz nimani idrok qilayotganimizni, qanday yashayotganimizni va boshqa odamlar bilan qanday munosabatda bo'lganimizni ifodalaydi. Shunday qilib, bizning kontseptual tizimimiz kundalik voqelikni aniqlashda markaziy rol o'ynaydi. Agar bizning kontseptual tizimimiz asosan metafora ekanligini ta'kidlash to'g'ri bo'lsa, unda bizning fikrlash tarzimiz, biz boshdan kechirgan narsalarimiz va har kuni nima qilayotganimiz juda ko'plab metaforik tuzilmalardir.

Ammo bizning kontseptual tizimimiz odatda biz bilganimizdan ko'p narsalarni qamrab oladi. Biz har kuni qiladigan ko'p har qanday katta yoki kichik amallarda ma'lum bir yo'nalish bo'yicha avtomatik ravishda o'ylaymiz va harakat qilamiz. Bu harakatlarning nima ekanligini bilishning yagona usuli - tilga diqqat qaratish. Muloqot biz o'ylaydigan va harakat qiladigan bir xil kontseptual tizimga asoslanganligi sababli, til bu tizim qanday ekanligini isbotlovchi muhim manbadir. Lingvistik dalillarga asoslansak, oddiy kontseptual tizimimizning aksariyati metaforik xarakterga ega ekanligini ko'ramiz. Biz qanday idrok etishimiz, qanday fikr yuritishimiz va nima qilayotganimizni tashkil etuvchi metaforalar nima ekanligini batafsil aniqlashimkoniga egamiz.

Kontseptsiyaning metafora bo'lishi va bunday tushunchaning tuzilishi va har bir faoliyati uchun nimani anglatishi mumkinligi haqida bir oz tasavvurga ega bo'lish uchun keling, ARGUMENT (bahs-munozara) tushunchasini ARGUMENT – WAR metaforasi orqali kundalik tilimizdagi turli xil iboralarda aks ettiramiz :

ARGUMENT IS WAR

Your claims are *indefensible*.

He *attacked every weak point* in my argument.

His criticism were *right on target*.

I *demolished* his argument.

I've never *won* an argument with him.

You disagree? Okay, *shoot* !

If you use that *strategy*, he'll *wipe you out*.

He *shot down* all my arguments.

Bu misollarda bahs-munozaralarga nafaqat urush nuqtai nazaridan balki ularga g'alaba qozonishimiz yoki yutqazishimiz mumkin bo'lga bir voqelik sifatida qarayapmiz. Biz bahslashayotgan odamni raqib sifatida ko'ramiz va uning pozitsiyalariga hujum qilamiz va o'zimizni himoya qilamiz. Bunda ishtirokchilar g'olib va mag'lub bo'ladi. Bahsda strategiyalar rejalashtiriladi va undan foydalaniladi. Agar biz himoya qilib bo'lmaydigan pozitsiyani topsak, uni tark etib, yangi hujum chizig'iga o'tishimiz mumkin. Bahslashda qiladigan ko'p narsalarimiz qisman urush tushunchasi bilan tuzilgan. Jismoniy jang bo'lmasa-da, og'zaki kurash bor va bahsning tuzilishi - hujum, himoya, qarshi hujum va boshqalar buni aks ettiradi. Aynan shu ma'noda biz ushbu vaziyatda ARGUMENT IS WAR metaforasi bilan yashaymiz; u biz bahslashishda bajaradigan harakatimizni tuzatadi.

Keling, zamonaviy ingliz tilida aks etgan TIME IS MONEY metaforik tushunchasini ko'rib chiqaylik:

You are *wasting* my time.

This gadget will *save* you hours.

I don't *have* the time to *give* you.

How do you *spend* your time these days.

The flat tire *cost* me an hour.

I've *invested* a lot of time in her.

I don't *have enough* time to *spare* for that.

You're *running out* of time.

You need to *budget* your time.

Put aside some time for ping pong.

Is that *worth your while*?

Do you *have* much time *left*?

You don't *use* your time *profitably*.

I *lost* a lot of time when I got sick. *Thank you for your time*.

Bizning madaniy hayotimizda vaqt qimmatli tovardir. Bu biz o'z maqsadlarimizga erishish uchun foydalanadigan cheklangan manbadir, chunki zamonaviy g'arb madaniyatida mehnat kontseptsiyasi shakllangan, bu yerda ish odatda vaqt talab qiladigan va vaqtning aniq miqdori bilan bog'liq bo'lib, odamlarga mehnat uchun haq soat, hafta yoki yil bo'yicha to'lash odatiy holga aylangan.. Bizning madaniy hayotimizda VAQT - bu ko'p jihatdan PUL: telefon xabar birliklari, soatlik ish haqi, mehmonxona xonalari narxlari, byudjet bo'yicha yillik, kreditlar bo'yicha foizlar va xizmat muddati orqali jamiyatga qarzingizni to'lash. Bu amaliyotlar insoniyat tarixida yangilik emas va barcha madaniyatlarda mavjud. Shunday qilib, biz vaqtni sarflash, behuda sarflash, byudjetlashtirish, oqilona yoki yomon investitsiya qilish, tejash yoki isrof qilish mumkin bo'lgan narsa sifatida tushunamiz va boshdan kechiramiz.

VAQT - PUL, VAQT - CHEKLI RESURS, VAQT - Qimmatbaho TOVAR - barchasi metaforik tushunchalardir. Ular metaforadir, chunki biz vaqtni kontseptsiyalash uchun pul, cheklangan resurslar va mavjud tovarlar bilan kundalik tajribamizdan foydalanamiz. Majoziy tushuncha VAQT PUL, VAQT RESURS va VAQT BO'LGAN TOVAR toifalarga bo'linishga asoslangan yagona tizimni tashkil qiladi, chunki bizning jamiyatimizda pul cheklangan resurslar, qimmatli tovarlar

hisoblanadi. metaforalar. VAQT - PUL - bu VAQTNI CHEKLANGAN RESURS ekanligini, bu esa VAQTNI Qimmatbaho TOVAR ekanligini anglatadi. O'zaro bog'liqlikni quyidagi diagrammada ko'rishimiz mumkin:

TIME IS MONEY	
MONEY IS A LIMITED RESOURCE	TIME IS A LIMITED RESOURCE
LIMITED RESOURCE IS A VALUABLE COMMODITY	TIME IS A VALUABLE COMMODITY

Bu holda VAQT - PUL, butun tizimni tavsiflash uchun, chunki VAQT - PUL - CHEKLANGAN RESURS, VAQT - QIMMATLI TOVAR. VAQT - PUL metaforasi ostida sanab o'tilgan iboralardan ba'zilari pul bilan bog'liq holatlarga "sarflash", "investitsiya qilish", "byudjet", "foydali", "xarajat" kabi, boshqalari cheklangan resurslar "foydalanish", "ishlatish", "etarli", "tugaydi" kabi va qimmatbaho tovarlarga "ega", "berish", "yo'qotish", "uchun rahmat" kabi xususiyatlariga ishora qiladi. Bu metaforik birikmalar metaforik tushunchalarning izchil tizimini va ushbu tushunchalar uchun mos keladigan metaforik ifodalar tizimini tavsiflash usullariga misoldir.

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**INGLIZ IJODKORLARINING PERSONAJLAR NUTQINI BERISHDA
MAQOLLARDAN FOYDALANISH MAHORATI**

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Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada hozirgi adabiy muhitda, ingliz ijodkorlari ijodida maqollarni qo'llashning o'zigaa xos ahamiyati borasida fikr yuritilgan. Maqolada ingliz yozuvchilari asarlarida qahramonlar nutqida qo'llangan maqollar asos qilib olingan. Ushbu yozuvchilarning uslubi badiiy asar qahramonlari tilidan aytilgan maqollar orqali tahlil qilinib, asarlardan keltirilgan parchalar yordamida ochib berilgan

Kalit so'zlar. Maqol, metafora, baholash, kontekst, ijobiy va salbiy bo'yoqdorlik, semantic tahlil, o'z ma'no, ko'chma ma'no.

Annotation. This article discusses the special importance of using proverbs in the works of English artists in the current literary environment. The article is based on proverbs used in the speech of heroes in the works of English writers. The style of these writers is analyzed through the proverbs spoken by the characters of the literary work, and revealed with the help of excerpts from the works.

Key words. Proverb, metaphor, evaluation, context, positive and negative coloring, semantic analysis, own meaning, figurative meaning.

Аннотация .В данной статье рассматривается особая значимость использования пословиц в творчестве английских художников в современной литературной среде. В основу статьи легли пословицы, используемые в речи героев произведений английских писателей. Стиль

этих писателей анализируется через пословицы, произнесенные персонажами литературного произведения, и раскрывается с помощью отрывков из произведений.

Ключевые слова. Пословица, метафора, оценка, контекст, положительная и отрицательная окраска, смысловой анализ, собственный смысл, переносный смысл.

Kirish Maqollar adabiyotda juda muhim o‘rin tutib, jamiyatning madaniy boyligi va ahamiyatini aks ettiradi. Maqollar ma'lum bir madaniyatning qadriyatlari, e'tiqodlari va umumiy donoligini aks ettiruvchi ko'zgu bo'lib xizmat qiladi. Ular jamiyatning tajribalari va tushunchalarini qamrab oladi va uning axloqiy suratini taqdim etadi. Adabiyotda maqollarning mujassamlanishi yozuvchilarga hikoyaning to‘qimasiga madaniy nuanslarni to‘qish imkonini beradi. Xususan, maqollarda ko'pincha jamiyat tomonidan qo'llab-quvvatlanadigan axloqiy tamoyillar mavjud. Adabiyotda maqollarni qo'llash orqali mualliflar qahramonlarning harakatlari va qarorlarini boshqaradigan asosiy qadriyatlarni yetkazishlari mumkin. Bu, o'z navbatida, o'quvchilarga voqea sodir bo'lgan madaniy doirani chuqurroq tushunish imkonini beradi.

Maqollar baddiyy adabiyotda hukmni mustahkamlash, asoslash va yakuniy, umumlashtiruvchi xulosa va boshqa vazifalarni bajaradi. Masalan, mehnat haqidagi ingliz maqoli: *“The early bird catches the worm”* an'anaviy tarzda "erta turgan ko'proq imkoniyatlarga ega bo'ladi" deb talqin qilinadi. E.S. Gardnerning *“The Case of the Angry Mourner”* detektiv asari kontekstida bu maqolni qo'llagan kishi uni o'zining shiori sifatida ishlatadi: erta turish biznes uchun foydalidir. Maqolning metaforik ma'nosi o'zgarmaydi:

"You must have left before daylight", she said. "I sure did. It's the early bird that catches the worm." [5],

ol boshqa asarda esa yuqoridagi parchadan farqli o'laroq, salbiy bo'Maqol alohida shakllangan birlik bo'lib, osongina o'zgaradi: unda nafaqat semantikada, balki

shakl va tuzilishda ham juda ko'p turli xil o'zgarishlar osonlikcha sodir bo'ladi. Olimlar frazeologik birliklarning kontekstual o'zgarishlarining uchdan o'n birgacha turlarini aniqlaydilar. Adabiy asarlar kontekstida ma'lum bir semantik sinfga kirgan maqollarning deformatsiyalangan variantlarini ham uchratish mumkin.

Masalan, *Tastes differ* ingliz maqoli an'anaviy tarzda "bir kishi uchun yoqimli yoki foydali bo'lgan narsa boshqasiga yoqimli yoki zararli bo'lmasligi mumkin" deb talqin qilinadi. O. Uayldning "Ajoyib raketa" ingliz ertaki kontekstida "*Everybody has different tastes*" o'zgartirilgan versiyasi ishlatilgan. Kontekst maqolning semantik sinfini saqlaydi, chunki u aqlli odam bahslashmaydi va vaziyatni baholashga, boshqa odamlarni tushunishga harakat qiladi degan fikrni bildiradi.

"Well, well," said the Duck, who was of a very peaceful disposition, and never quarreled with any one, "everybody has different tastes. I hope, at any rate, that you are going to take up your residence here." [8].

Maqolning o'zgartirilishi so'zlovchiga – muallifga uni yangilash, qayta-qayta qo'llash natijasida eskirgan obrazni jonlantirish, shuningdek, maqolning majoziy ma'nosini kontekstda ifodalashda yordam beradi. Maqol o'zining semantik tabiatiga ko'ra keng pragmatik imkoniyatlarga ega. U ikki darajada - tom ma'noda va majoziy ma'noda qayta ko'rib chiqilishi va ishlatilishi mumkin.

Maqolning muhim xususiyatlaridan biri baholovchilikdir, bu esa Yu.D. Apresyan fikricha "ma'noning juda nozik, ba'zan tushunib bo'lmaydigan tarkibiy qismidir" [Apresyan, 1995]. Ma'noning baholovchi komponenti maqolning kontekst tufayli oson amalga oshiriladigan ijobiy yoki salbiy ma'nosini ifodalaydi. Masalan, ingliz tilida sevgi haqida ijobiy bahoni ifodalovchi ko'plab maqollar mavjud. "*Absence makes the heart grow fonder*" degan maqolda ayriliq muhabbatni mustahkamlashi namoyon bo'lgan.

"It surprised and almost shocked the girl herself to discover how pale she was getting, how the few words of ordinary greeting seemed to stick in her throat. Absence in her case had certainly and unfortunately made "the heart grow fonder". [R.Broughton, Not wisely, but too well].

Yuqoridagi parcha sevib qolgan qizning his-tuyg'ulari haqida gapiradi. Anchadan beri ko'rmagan odam bilan uchrashib, u sevgi uni yengib o'tishini tushunadi. Bu kontekst maqolning ijobiy ma'nosini tasdiqlaydi.

Quyida ham huddi shu maqolning shakl jihatdan o'zgartirilganligini Jon Gardner yaratgan qahramon Jerryga nisbatan qo'llanilganini ko'rishimiz mumkin:

Of course she'll be all right. I just wish you could have seen Jey Coslet the day ... That's the worst of it, she hasn't seen her friends. Been hanging around the kitchen too much. Just a case of absence making the heart grow fonder of the bird in hand. (Gardner, October Light)

Quyidagi misolda *Every family has a black sheep* degan ingliz maqoli salbiy baholanadi, chunki "har bir oilada yomon odam bo'lishi mumkin" deb talqin qilinadi. Masalan:

"I suppose every family has a black sheep. Tom has been a sore trail to his for twenty years." [7].

Hikoya qahramonlaridan biri bo'lgan Tom o'z hayotini munosib boshladi: u o'zining biznesini boshladi, uylandi va ikki farzand ko'rди. Ammo bir kuni Tom hamma narsadan voz kechishga va o'z zavqi uchun yashashga qaror qildi. U oilasini tashlab, ukasi va do'stlaridan qarz ola boshladi. Akasi Jorj uni dangasa va insofsiz deb ataydi. Muallif Tomga nisbatan nafrat bildirar ekan, nomi tilga olingan ingliz maqolini salbiy baholovchi ma'nosini o'zgartirmagan holda ishlatadi.

Shunday qilib, ingliz tilidagi maqollarning ijobiy va salbiy baholovchi ma'nosi adabiy asarlar kontekstida aslligicha qolishi mumkin.

Bunday holda, baholovchi ma'no muallifga ma'lum bir narsaga, hodisaga yoki harakatga bo'lgan munosabatini o'quvchiga yetkazishiga yordam beradi.

Xulosa. Maqollar publitsistikada, ilmiy-ommabop matnlarda va ayniqsa, badiiy asarlarda keng qo'llanadi. Ular personajlar nutqiy tavsifida, nutqning uslubiy ta'sirchanligini oshirishda muhim vosita hisoblanadi. Maqollarning "uslubiy vazifalari xilma-xil va rang-barangdir, ularning ayrimlari "tabiiy" bo'lib, maqollarning ichki tabiatidan kelib chiqadi. Qolganlari esa individual xarakterga ega bo'lib, u yoki bu so'z san'atkorining estetik maqsadi, xohish-irodasi, til vositalaridan foydalanishdagi mahorati bilan aloqadordir

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EXPLORING STAGNANT SIMILES: A COMPARATIVE STUDY IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES

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Abstract: This article examines the phenomenon of stagnant similes in the English and Uzbek languages, investigating the impact of cultural, linguistic, and historical factors on the formation and persistence of these clichéd expressions. Stagnant similes, characterized by their overuse and diminished effectiveness, represent a fascinating aspect of language evolution and usage. By comparing stagnant similes in two distinct linguistic contexts, this study aims to shed light on the underlying mechanisms that contribute to their prevalence and persistence.

Key words: stagnant similes, cultural differences, linguistic contexts, cultural norms, comparative analysis.

Similes those colorful figures of speech that enrich our language, are ubiquitous in both English and Uzbek. However, not all similes are created equal. Some, over time, lose their freshness and become stagnant, clichéd expressions that evoke a sense of predictability rather than creativity. In this article, we delve into the world of stagnant similes, examining their prevalence and impact in both English and Uzbek languages. Stagnant similes are phrases or comparisons that have become cliché or overused, losing their impact or originality. In English, examples include "as busy as a bee" or "as blind as a bat." In Uzbek, similar stagnant similes might include "qo'ng'iz ko'cha" (as quiet as a mouse) or "tez yugurib ketmoq" (to run like the wind), which are commonly used but lack freshness in expression.³⁸

Stagnant Similes in English: English is rich in similes, but some have become so overused that they have lost their originality. Phrases like "as busy as a bee" or "as blind as a bat" are heard so frequently that they no longer evoke vivid imagery or surprise³⁹. These similes, once vibrant and effective, have become stagnant through years of repetition in literature, media, and everyday

³⁸ Toshkent O'zbek tili va adabiyoti Universiteti. (2002). *Uzbek Language and Literature*. Toshkent: Toshkent O'zbek tili va adabiyoti Universiteti Nashriyoti

³⁹ Simpson, J. A., & Weiner, E. S. C. (2009). *Oxford English Dictionary* (3rd ed.). Oxford University Press

conversation.

Stagnant Similes in Uzbek: Similarly, Uzbek language also boasts a range of similes, but many have fallen into the trap of staleness. Expressions like "qo'ng'iz ko'cha" (as quiet as a mouse) or "tez yugurib ketmoq" (to run like the wind) are heard so often that they fail to spark imagination or resonate deeply with listeners. These similes, though once powerful and evocative, have become worn-out through continual use in literature, folklore, and daily discourse⁴⁰.

Comparative Analysis: Despite the linguistic and cultural differences between English and Uzbek, both languages exhibit stagnant similes rooted in similar phenomena. Historical influences, cultural traditions, and the pervasive reach of media all contribute to the proliferation of clichéd expressions in both linguistic contexts. However, while specific similes may differ, the underlying process of stagnation remains remarkably consistent across languages.

Impact and Implications: The prevalence of stagnant similes in both English and Uzbek languages raises important questions about language vitality and creativity. Stagnant similes not only hinder effective communication but also reflect a stagnation of linguistic innovation. Moreover, they can perpetuate stereotypes and reinforce cultural norms, limiting the potential for cross-cultural understanding and exchange.

Revitalization Efforts: Efforts to revitalize stagnant similes offer a glimmer of hope for language enthusiasts. By introducing new twists or incorporating contemporary references, writers and speakers can breathe new life into old expressions. Furthermore, encouraging the creation of original similes can help prevent the stagnation of language and promote linguistic diversity and creativity.

In conclusion, stagnant similes represent a fascinating aspect of language evolution and usage in both English and Uzbek languages. By recognizing the

⁴⁰ Tashkent O'zbek tili va adabiyoti Universiteti. (2002). *Uzbek Language and Literature*. Tashkent: Tashkent O'zbek tili va adabiyoti Universiteti Nashriyoti

prevalence and impact of these clichéd expressions, we can strive to preserve linguistic vitality and foster a culture of creative expression in our communication. However, amidst the prevalence of stagnant similes, there is room for optimism. Efforts to revitalize language by introducing new twists or incorporating contemporary references offer promising avenues for breathing new life into old expressions. Encouraging the creation of original similes can help prevent linguistic stagnation and promote diversity and creativity in language use. Through ongoing efforts to revitalize language and promote originality, we can ensure that similes continue to captivate and inspire audiences for generations to come.

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THE ROLE OF INVERSION IN TRANSLATION AND ITS FUNCTION

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Abstract : *The article aims to demonstrate the role of inversion during the process of translation, its functions to provide a comprehensive analysis and to explore the various ways in which inversion can impact the meaning and tone of a text when translating between languages. By examining examples and discussing the significance of inversion in translation, the article seeks to enhance the understanding of translators and readers alike on the importance of considering inversion in the translation process.*

Keywords: *inversion , function, translation, punctuation*

The sentence, the tiniest element of communication in language, communicates a full idea and is distinguished by its intricate structure and semantics, as well as its vulnerability to pragmatic influences. Every phrase is connected to the writer's intentions, making translation tough because of the potential for multiple interpretations. The sequence of words functions as a device for expressing subtle shades of meaning, serving various purposes. Concerning communication, word sequence establishes the topic and focus of a statement.

Altering the sequence of words can introduce additional semantic subtleties and either heighten or reduce the overall meaning. As opposed to the adaptable word order in Russian, English adheres to a more rigid arrangement. Inversion in language carries communicative and expressive significance, which may not always be accurately conveyed in translation from English to Russian.

Standard word order of declarative sentences in English is first the subject, then the verb. But, there is a literary technique in English requiring changing the

standard word order which makes the sentences difficult to understand for the beginners.⁴¹

In normal everyday English, inversion is used:

- to make questions: Do you? Can I?
- after «so», «neither», «nor»: So do we, neither does he, nor does she

When studying English grammar, the majority of learners overlook the utilization of alternative forms of inversion, and sentences containing intricate inversion patterns are categorized as having punctuation inaccuracies by these individuals. This confusion arises because learners analyze the sentences and interpret them as interrogative sentences based on the positioning of auxiliary verbs or similar elements, yet struggle to grasp or interpret them into their mother tongue. Consequently, learners must arrive at the conclusion that the sentences are not grammatically precise.

Inversion is a framework in which a verb or auxiliary verb is positioned before the subject, even if the sentence does not possess an interrogative nature. Inversion can be integrated before various negative terms like "never, nowhere, no, not, not only, rarely." As a rule, inversions are used to underscore the speaker's notion. This literary approach is typically employed for emphasis or to create a special impact, presenting a rather formal tone. Sentences with inversion doesn't appear in everyday English:

Example 1 (sentence without an inversion): *I have never eaten such a delicious meal!*

Example 2 (the same sentence with an inversion): *Never have I eaten such a delicious meal!*

In example 2 inversion is used to underline the fact that I have not eaten such a delicious meal in my whole period of time.

⁴¹Nasriddinov.O.A "Types and uses of inversion in English"

Adverbs like never, rarely, and seldom appear in inverted sentences to highlight the exceptional circumstances within the sentences to which they pertain. These adverbs are commonly associated with one of the perfect tense structures and frequently accompanied by modal verbs.

Rarely have I read such an original novel

In translation, inversion pertains to the restructuring of sentence word order, specifically involving the reversal of subject and verb positions for stylistic or grammatical purposes. Comprehending inversion is paramount in translation since it can influence the text's overall meaning and tone. Translators need to spot and accurately decipher instances of inversion in the source language to guarantee precise and impactful translation into the target language. Neglecting to identify and manage inversion properly can lead to inaccuracies or misinterpretations in the translated content. Hence, a comprehensive grasp of inversion and its significance in language is indispensable for achieving successful translation.

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**BADIIY TARJIMADA EKVIVALENTLIK VA ADEKVATLIK
TUSHUNCHALARI.**

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Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada badiiy translatologik kontekstda uchraydigan hamda tarjimashunoslikda jiddiy bahslarga sabab bo‘lib kelayotgan ekvivalentlik va adekvatlik tushunchalari, ularning tarjimashunoslikdagi o‘rni va ahamiyati to‘g‘risida so‘z yuritiladi. Muallif badiiy tarjimada ekvivalentlik hamda adekvatlik tushunchalarining bir-biri bilan qanchalik yaqin yoki, aksincha, qay darajada farq qilishini yoritishga harakat qilgan.

Аннотация. В этой статье обсуждаются понятия эквивалентности и адекватности, их место и значение в переводческих исследованиях, которые встречаются в литературном переводческом контексте и вызывают серьезные противоречия в переводческих исследованиях. Автор попытался пролить свет на то, насколько близки или различны друг в друге понятия эквивалентности и адекватности в художественном переводе.

Tayanch so‘z va iboralar: ekvivalentlik, adekvatlik, tarjima matnlari, translatologik kontekst.

Ключевые слова и словосочетания: эквивалентность, адекватность, переводческие тексты, транслатологический контекст.

Tarjima tillararo muloqotning alohida turi sifatida asosiy e'tiborni ikki til tizimining semantik jihatiga qaratishni taqozo etadigan ijodiy jarayondir. Chunki axborotning to'laqonliligi asosini turli tillar matnlarining semantik uyg'unligi tashkil etadi. Lisoniy tarjimaning muhim vazifalaridan biri «translatologik ekvivalentlik» tushunchasini muayyan qilishdan iboratdir.

Badiiy tarjimaning mukammal bo'lishida ekvivalentlik muhimmi yoki adekvatlik, degan savol tarjimashunoslikda katta bahslarga sabab bo'lib kelmoqda. Ekvivalent lotincha "aequivalens" so'zidan olingan bo'lib, "teng kuchli", "bir xil ma'noda" deganidir. Tilshunos tarjimashunos olimlar ekvivalentlikning bir necha tiplari mavjud ekanligini ta'kidlashadi. Quyida ulardan asosiy 5ta tipini aytib o'tamiz.

I. Ekvivalentlikning birinchi turida tarjimalarning asliyatga uyg'unligi ko'z ilg'amas darajada namoyon bo'ladi. Asliyat va tarjima o'rtasidagi munosabatlar asosan ushbu ko'rinishlarga ega buladi: a) leksik tarkib va sintaktik qurilishdagi nomuvofiqlik; b) ikki holatda ham bir xil fikr bayon etilayotganligiga qaramasdan, asliyat va tarjimada ifoda etilgan axborot o'rtasida bevosita mazmuniy yoki mantiqiy bog'lanishning ko'zga tashlanmasligi; v) asliyat va tarjima matnlari mazmunlari orasidagi umumiylik darajasi ekvivalent sifatida tan olingan boshqa tarjimalarga nisbatan nihoyatda past.

II. Ekvivalentlikning ikkinchi turida tarjimaning asliyatga yaqinligi foydalanilgan til vositalari ma'nolarining bir xil emasligi bilan izohlanadi. Bu guruhda asliyat bilan tarjima matnlarini tashkil etadigan ko'pchilik so'z va sintaktik qurilmalar o'rtasida bevosita yaqinlik ko'zga tashlanmasada, ikki til matnlari ekvivalentlikning birinchi turiga nisbatan mazmunan ko'proq o'xshashdir.

III. Ekvivalentlikning uchinchi turida asliyat va tarjima matnlari orasida quyidagi xususiyatlar ko'zga tashlanadi: ikki tilning mazmunan o'zaro mos ifoda vositalari leksik tarkib va goho sintaktik qurilish jihatlaridan to'la uyg'un bo'lmaydilar.

IV. Ekvivalentlikning to‘rtinchi turida asliyat va tarjima o‘rtasidagi munosabat ikki til matnlari leksik tarkiblarining yanada ko‘proq o‘xshashligi bilan izohlanadi: 1. I told him what I thought of her // Men unga qiz haqidagi fikrimni aytdim. 2. Ne was never tired of old songs // Eski ashulalar hech qachon uning joniga tegmas edi.

V. Nihoyat, beshinchi turda asliyat va tarjima matnlari orasidagi ekvivalentlik yuqori darajada namoyon bo‘ladi: 1. I study at the University // Men unversitetda o‘qiyman. 2. The house was sold for 10 thousand dollars // Uy 10 ming dollarga sotilgan edi.

Ekvivalentlikning beshinchi tipiga xos xususiyatlar mukammal ko‘rinishda adekvat tarjimada namoyon bo‘ladi. Adekvat lotincha “ad-aequo” so‘zidan olingan bo‘lib, “o‘xshash”, “bir xil”, “teng”, “to‘la mos”, “bir-biriga aynan o‘xshash” kabi ma’nolarni anglatadi. Ayrim tarjimashunoslar fikricha, tarjima qilinayotgan til me’yoriga qat’iy amal qilgan holda asosiy mazmuni uzatish ekvivalent tarjima bo‘lib, bu maqbul holatdir. Adekvatlik tushunchasi esa ekvivalentlikdan ko‘ra kengroq qamrovga ega. V.Vinogradovning fikricha, ekvivalentlik tarjimaning asliyatga yaqinlashuvini ta’minlovchi bir omildir, xolos. Matnning asliyatga yaqinlashuv darajalari ko‘plab omillarga, xususan, tarjimon mahorati, til va madaniyatlarning bir-biriga yaqinlik jihati va tarjima qilinayotgan matnning xarakteriga bog‘liq. Adekvat tarjima esa pragmatik muammolarni ekvivalentlikning maksimal darajasida hal etadi va janrning uslubiy talabi va tarjima imkoniyatidan kelib chiqib, til me’yoringa buzilishiga yo‘l qo‘ymaydi. A.V.Feodorov esa umuman bu terminga hojat yo‘qligini, “adekvatlik” istilohining o‘rnini to‘liq tarjima jumlasini bilan o‘zgartirish kerakligini ta’kidlaydi. Olimning fikricha, to‘laqonli tarjima asliyatning janr xususiyatlari va funksional-stilistik komponentlariga to‘la mos keladi. Ammo nazarimizda adekvatlik tushunchasini “to‘laqonli tarjima” yoki “ekvivalentlikning bir pog‘onasi” deb e’tirof etib bo‘lmaydi. Birinchidan adekvatlik – nisbiy tushuncha mukammal tarjima emas. Ya’ni tarjima asliyatga

adekvat degani to‘laqonli asliyatning o‘zi degani emas. Tarjimada asliyatning nolisoniy jihatlaridan (ohang, ruhiyat, uslub) nimadir saqlanib qolganligini anglatadi. Ikkinchidan esa adekvatlik emas, balki ekvivalentlik – adekvatlik sari tashlangan bir pog‘onadir. Yuqoridagilardan ko‘rinib turibdiki, olimlarning ekvivalentlik va adekvatlik tushunchasiga yondashuvi ularning o‘z ixtisosliklari doirasida chuqur fikrlaganliklaridan va shu bilan cheklanganliklaridan kelib chiqqan. Adekvatlik muammosiga to‘xtalgan olimlarning birortasi badiiy tarjima, xususan, she‘r tarjimasida ruhiyat, g‘oya, botiniy ma’no va ohang kabi muhim omillarsiz adekvatlikka erishish mumkin bo‘lmasligiga ahamiyat bermagani bu muammo hanuz o‘z echimini topmaganini ko‘rsatadi. G.D.Voskoboynik fikricha, ekvivalentlik bilan cheklanuvchilar “matn – bu sistema (tizim)”, deb qarasarlar, adekvatlik tarafdorlari “matn – bu tirik organizm” deb hisoblaydilar.

Bahslarga umumiy nazar tashlab, har ikkala qarash tarafdorlari yondashuvlarida biryoqlamalik mavjudligini ko‘rish mumkin. So‘z badiiy tarjima sifati xususida borar ekan, adekvatlik sari intilish, yo‘q deganda minimum ekvivalentlikka erishish bilan yakunlanishi mumkin. Bu o‘zbek xalqining “tog‘dek so‘rasang, tepadek beradi” naqlini esga soladi. Badiiy tarjimada tarjimon ishni, ya’ni tarjimini ekvivalentlik pozitsiyasidan turib boshlashi ma’qul holat emas.

Xulosa qilib aytganda. tarjimaning asliyatga pragmatik adekvatligi asliyat va tarjima sohiblarining bir xil axborotga ega bo‘lishlari bilan ifodalanadi.

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INSON ONGI VA AQLIY FAOLIYATIGA OID KONSEPTUAL METAFORALARNI TARJIMA QILISH

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Tayanch so'zlar: metafora, olam manzarasi, kognitiv metafora, metafora komponentlari, konsepsiya, tarjima strategiyalari, adekvat tarjima, lingvistik-pragmatik xususiyatlar, leksik-grammatik jihatlar.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqola, tahlillar yuzasidan olingan natijalarga tayanib, shaxsiy rivojlanishga oid adabiyotlarda eng ko'p uchraydigan metaforalar insonning aqliy faoliyati va ongi bilan bog'liq bo'lganligi, ularning konseptualizatsiyasi insoniyatning uzoq va yaqin o'tmishdagi tajribasiga borib taqalishi o'rganildi. Ingliz va o'zbek tillari misolida qiyoslanganda, mazkur tillarning turli til oilalariga mansubligi hamda xalqlarning tajribasidagi farqlar konseptual metaforalarda ham farqlanishga sabab bo'lishi yoritib berilgan.

Kirish: Tilshunoslikda tadqiqot olib borishning kognitiv yo'nalishining paydo bo'lishi, keyinchalik metaforalar kognitiv nazariyasining vujudga kelishi metafora mohiyatiga oid yangicha qarashlarning shakllanishiga xizmat qildi. Kognitivist olimlarning e'tibori axborotni ifodalash, saqlash, qayta ishlash va uzatish mexanizmlarini o'rganishga, shuningdek, turkumlash va konsepsiya

jarayonlarini o'rganishga qaratilgan. Binobarin, zamonaviy tilshunoslikda metafora til, tafakkur va madaniyat o'rtasidagi munosabat nuqtai nazaridan qarala boshlandi. Xususan, J.Lakoff va M.Jonson ta'kidlashganidek, konseptual metaforalar "ma'lum bir jamiyatning lingvistik va madaniy an'analarda mustahkamlangan manba maydoni va maqsadli maydon" o'rtasidagi barqaror muvofiqlikni ifodalaydi.

E.Budaevva A.Chudinov metaforani "asosiy aqliy operatsiyalardan biri sifatida, dunyoni bilish, tasniflash, konsepsiyalash, baholash va tushuntirish usuli sifatida" ta'riflashadi. Ushbu ta'rifdan xulosa qilishimiz mumkinki, adabiy matnlardagi metaforalar dunyoning lingvistik tasviridagi individual muallifning o'zgarishlarini aks ettiradi va yangi bilimlarni qabul qiluvchi o'quvchilarga etkazishga xizmat qiladi.

Asosiy qism. Nutqda o'z o'y-qarashlarimizni bayon etish uchun tildagi barcha birliklar (tovush, qo'shimcha, so'z, so'z birikmasi va gap) dan foydalanamiz. Leksik birliklar ya'ni, so'zlarni tilshunoslikning bir qismi sifatida o'rganish, so'zlarni nutqdan tashqaridagi o'z ma'nosi bilan birga ularni nutqda ifodalagan uslubiy ma'nolarini ham o'rganish muhimligini ko'rsatadi. So'zlarni o'z ma'nosi bilan birga ko'chma ma'noda qo'llash ham nutq ifodaliligini ta'minlash uchun tuganmas manbadir. Nutqda deyarli barcha asosiy holatlarda ko'chma ma'noda ishlatiladi va o'ziga xos bo'yoqdorlik kasb etadi. Ikki narsa yoki tushuncha o'rtasidagi muayyan munosabat (o'xshashlik, umumiylik, aloqadorlik kabi) asosida tasviriylik, ifodalilik, aniqlikni kuchaytirish metaforani yuzaga keltirdi.⁴² Nutqimizda ko'p qo'llaniladigan ma'no ko'chish usuli barchamizga ma'lumki bu metaforadir. Metafora narsa yoki voqea hodisalar o'rtasidagi aloqadorlik asosida ko'chish usulidir. Metafora aslida yunoncha so'zdan olingan bo'lib⁴³ narsaning o'zaro o'xshashlik asosida ma'no ko'chishidir. Masalan: fan cho'qqisi, yurtimiz

⁴² Mahmudov.N., Odilov.Y., Ziyodullayeva.G., O'rta ta'lim muassasalarining 11-sinfi va o'rta maxsus, kasb-hunar ta'lim muassasari o'quvchilari uchun darslik.-T,2018, 79-b.

⁴³ 2 Nurmonov.A., Sobirov.A., Qosimova.N., Hozirgi o'zbek adabiy tili. -T: Ilm ziyo., 2013y,190-b

quyoshi, dalaning etagi... Misol uchun, devorning qulog'I va odamning qulog'i, bunda ikkita predmet o'zaro o'xshashlik asosida ma'no ko'chayapti ya'ni tilshunoslikda bular bir birini shu jihatdan aloqadorlik hosil qilyapti.⁴⁴

Zamonaviy tilshunoslikda esa rivojlanishlar va izlanishlar olib borishlar natijasida konseptual metafora atamasi namoyon bo'la boshladi. Konseptual degani "tushuncha", "tasavvur", "bilish" deganidir. Kontseptual metafora kognitiv tilshunoslikdagi muhim atamalardan biri hisoblanadi. Bu turli xil sohalarga tegishli bo'lgan bir nechta tushunchalar (kontseptual tuzilmalar) o'rtasida kognitiv aloqalarni yoki xaritalarni o'rnatish jarayonini anglatadi. Metafora "bir narsani boshqa bir narsa asosida yoki vositasida tushunish" deb ta'kidlagan Lakoff va M. Jonson. Dastlab tilshunoslikda metaforalar grammatik, leksik va semantik jihatdan o'rganilgan bo'lsa, zamonaviy tilshunoslik esa metaforaning tafakkur bilan bog'liq tomonini diqqat markaziga qo'ydi. Shu asosda zamonaviy tilshunoslikda yangi tushuncha "konseptual metafora" tushunchasi paydo bo'ldi. I.A.Galperin nazariyasiga murojaat qiladigan bo'lsa, u "ikki xil hodisa (narsa, g'oya, harakat) bir vaqtning o'zida, bir ob'ektning o'ziga xos xususiyatlarining bir qismini yoki barchasini ikkinchisiga yuklash. Bunday yuklash, odatda, metafora hosil qiluvchi ikkita mos keladigan obyektida umumiy xususiyatga ega bo'lgan ba'zi xususiyatlarni ifodalaganda yuzaga keladi"⁴⁵. Yuqorida ta'kidlab o'tilganidek konseptual metafora tushunchasi dastlab J.Lakoff va M.Jonsonlar asarlarida aks etdi. Ularning tadqiqotlarida shunday deyiladi: "Inson muloqotida bunday tushunchalarning tez-tez uchrab turishi mazkur lingvistik hodisani ma'lum tizim sifatida o'rganishni taqazo etadi. Buning natijasida ma'lum bir guruhga o'zaro birika oladigan metaforalarni aniqlab ularni konseptual metaforalar deb nomlaymiz".⁴⁶ Bundan shuni tushunamizki, konseptual metafora so'zning asosiy ma'nosi bilan va ko'p hollarda ikkita semantik maydon

⁴⁴ Дорофеева А.А. Что скрывается в тайне метафоры? (О подходах к изучению метафоры западными учеными в XX в.) / Вестн. Моск. ун-та. Сер. 19. Лингвистика и межкультурная коммуникация. 2014. № 4.

⁴⁵ I.A.Galperin. Stylistics. Page 13

⁴⁶ Lakoff G., Johnson M. *Metaphors We Live By*. — Chicago: Univ. of Chicago Press, 1980 (2008).

o'rtasidagi tushunilgan munosabatni ifodalaydi. Taniqli tilshunos-nasr yozuvchisi A.G. Pol metaforani quyidagicha ta'riflagan: «Metafora-hali etarli nomlarga ega bo'lmagan tasvirlar majmuasini belgilashning eng muhim vositalaridan biri . Metafora-bu muqarrar ravishda inson tabiatidan kelib chiqadigan narsa va u nafaqat she'riyat tilida, balki, odamlarning kundalik nutqida, xohlagancha, majoziy ifodalar va rang -barang epitetlarga murojaat qiladi . M.Blackning “Metaforaning o'zaro ta'sir nazariyasi” da metafora shunchaki til bezagi emas, balki atrofimizdagi borliqni tushunish uchun zarur vosita ekanligini aytib o'tadi.

Xulosa. Yuqorida keltirilgan fikrlardan shuni anglashimiz mumkinki, kognitiv semantikaga ko'ra metafora endilikda adabiyot va she'riyatda shunchaki oddiy bezak yoki jonlantirish sifatida chegaralanmaydigan bo'ldi. Kognitiv tilshunoslikdagi konseptual metafora atamasini yanada teran anglash uchun oddiy metaforadan farqlanishini anglashimiz kerak. Albatta bu jarayonda insonning fikrlashi va tushuncha doirasi asosiy ahamiyat kasb etadi.

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THE ROLE OF THE SLAVE DRESS IN UZBEK AND ENGLISH LITERATURE

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Abstract: This article delves into the multifaceted role of the slave dress as a symbolic element in both Uzbek and English literature. By examining the cultural contexts and historical narratives surrounding the depiction of slavery in these two distinct literary traditions, this study aims to shed light on the nuanced meanings attributed to the slave dress. Through a comparative analysis, the article explores how authors from Uzbek and English literature employ the slave dress as a powerful symbol, reflecting societal norms, power dynamics, and the human experience.

Keywords: Slave dress, Symbolism, Uzbek literature, English literature, Cultural representation, Power dynamics.

Introduction: The slave dress, a tangible artifact, has transcended its physical existence to become a potent symbol in literature. In Uzbek and English literary traditions, authors have harnessed the symbolic power of the slave dress to convey complex narratives surrounding slavery. This article undertakes a comparative exploration of how these depictions unfold within their respective cultural and historical contexts.

Uzbek literature, deeply rooted in the region's history, has portrayed the slave dress as more than a mere garment. It becomes a metaphor for the struggle against oppression and a representation of cultural identity. Writers like Abdulla Qodiri use the slave dress to weave stories of resistance, resilience, and the quest for freedom. The rich tapestry of Uzbek literature reveals the nuanced ways in which the slave dress encapsulates the collective memory of a people. [5, 47]

In English literature, the slave dress has been a recurrent motif in narratives exploring the transatlantic slave trade. From the vivid descriptions in Harriet Beecher Stowe's "Uncle Tom's Cabin" to the poetic imagery in Maya Angelou's "I Know Why the Caged Bird Sings," the slave dress becomes a powerful tool for

authors to confront the atrocities of slavery. It serves as a visual reminder of the dehumanizing effects of oppression and a call to empathy.

Across both literary traditions, the slave dress emerges as a symbol deeply entwined with cultural representation. It signifies not only the harsh realities of slavery but also becomes a vessel for cultural identity and resistance. The colors, textures, and even the wearing or discarding of the dress convey layers of meaning that extend beyond the immediate narrative, offering readers a glimpse into the complexities of the characters' lives.

Examining power dynamics, the article explores how the slave dress becomes a tool through which authors comment on the imbalances of power within societies. Whether in the opulent courts of Uzbekistan or the plantations of the American South, the slave dress becomes a visual marker of social hierarchies, serving as a poignant commentary on the exploitation and domination embedded in these power structures.

Conclusion: In conclusion, the slave dress in Uzbek and English literature transcends its material form, evolving into a powerful symbol laden with cultural, historical, and social significance. Through nuanced narratives and vivid imagery, authors employ the slave dress to engage readers in a profound exploration of the human experience. This comparative analysis highlights the universal themes of resilience, identity, and the quest for freedom that resonate across cultural and linguistic boundaries.

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**АБДУЛЛА ҚОДИРИЙНИНГ “ЎТКАН КУНЛАР” РОМАНИ
ТАРЖИМАЛАРИДА ЭСКИРГАН СЎЗЛАРНИНГ ТАВСИФИЙ
ТАҲЛИЛИ**

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Ўзбек адаби Абдулла Қодирийнинг “Ўткан кунлар” романи ўзбек адабиётидаги биринчи роман бўлибгина қолмай, биринчи тарихий романдир. Ёзувчи ўз асарида оддий халқ ҳаётини, уларнинг урф-одат ва анъаналарини тасвирлайди. Романда Туркистон тарихи, унинг ҳукмдорлари, ўзбекларнинг сиёсий ва ижтимоий ҳаёти ҳам батафсил баён этилган. Шу сабабли, романда жуда кўп ўзига хос луғат мавжуд бўлиб, айниқса эскирган сўзлар, архаизмлар ва историзмлар кўп учрайди. “Ўткан кунлар” романи тарихий романнинг ёркин намунаси сифатида XIX асрдаги ўзбекларнинг кундалик ҳаётини акс эттирувчи узунлик ва майдон бирликларининг аъанавий номлари ҳам мавжуд бўлиб, уларни историзм деб аташ мумкин, чунки ҳозирда улар тўлиқ халқаро мертик бирликлар тизимида шаклланган бўлиб, эскириб истеъмолдан чиққан ҳисобланади.

Ушбу мақоланинг мақсади романдаги ҳақиқий хронотопни қайта тиклаш учун эскирган сўзлардан фойдаланишнинг аҳамиятини аниқлаш, шунингдек, таржималарнинг ишончлилиги, тугрилиги, асл нумхага мослигини урганиш, узбек тилидан рус тилига, рус тилидан инглиз тилига таржималарда архаик реал сўзларнинг белгиси ва маъносига кўра туркумлаш асосида ушбу сўзларни таржима қилиш усулларини ўрганишдир. Бунда асосий эътибор эскирган сўзларни таржима қилиш усулларини урганишга қаратилади.

Қуйидаги мисолда таъкидланган сўзлар узунлик ва майдон ўлчовлари сифатида таснифланади. Масофани, ҳажмни, майдонни ва узунликни аниқ ўлчаш муҳимлигини инсоният қадимдан еътироф этган. Жамият тараққиёти, қишлоқ хўжалиги ва қурилишнинг такомиллашуви, умуман цивилизациянинг ривожланиши ҳам алоҳида миллатлар, ҳам жамият аъзоларининг мулки ва эгаллик ҳуқуқини аниқ чегаралашни тақозо этади. Шу боисдан ҳам турли ўлчов бирликлари номлари халқ тарихини ўрганишнинг енг муҳим жиҳатларидан бири бўлиб, таржима назарияси нуқтаи назаридан эскирган сўзларнинг бу тоифаси ўша даврдаги маданий-тарихий фонни билишни назарда тутди.

Аслият	Ammo imorat qismi darboza bilan bir qatorda bo'lib, so'l biqinida devonxona, uning qatorida bo'yiga qirq, eniga yigirma <u>olchin</u> joy olg'an o'n besh darichalik kattakon chorzari uy...
Русча таржима (М.Сафаров)	Но к четвертой стороне, где были ворота, примыкал дом, (...), а затем шло здание пятнадцати оконное здание сорока <u>аршин</u> в длину, двадцати <u>аршин</u> в ширину.
Инглизча таржима (К.Эрмакова)	To the left of the house was the ruler's chacery, then a sizeble structure with fifteen windows, forty <u>arshin</u> wid and twenty <u>arshin</u> long.

Инглизча таржима (М.Рииз)	On the north face, a substantial keep stood behind the inner gate, measuring forty <u>meters</u> by twenty <u>meters</u> ; it was crenellated and had fifteen windows.
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Эски ўзбек узунлик ўлчови “olchin” тарихий сўз бўлиб, бинони эни ва бўйини ўлчаш учун ишлатиладиган бирликдир. “Ўзбек тилининг изоҳли луғати”да унга қуйидагича таъриф берилган: “Олчин узунлик ўлчов бирлиги; аршин ва газ қийматларига тенг”. Таърифга кўра “olchin” сўзи русча “аршин” сўзига тенг ҳамда “Рус тилининг изоҳли луғати”да “0.71 м.га тенг эски рус узунлик ўлчови” сифатида тавсифланганлигини гувоҳи бўлишимиз мумкин. Бундан хулоса шуки, бу тарихий сўзни рус тилига таржима қилишда тўлиқ эквивалент усулидан фойдаланилган.

Керол Эрмакова таржимасида эскирган сўз русча “аршин” сўзини транскрипция қилиш йўли билан таржима қилинган, натижада инглиз тилида “аршин” сўзи шаклланган. Бу реалия унинг маъносини тушунтирувчи изоҳлар билан тўлдирилган. Марк Рииз таржимасида, бошқалардан фарқли ўлароқ, бу сўз кенг қўлланиладиган “метр” аналоги орқали етказилган бўлиб, бу таржимада историзмнинг миллий-тарихий колоритини бутунлай йўққа чиқарган.

Хулоса қилиб айтишимиз мумкинки, историзмлар билан ифодаланган реалиялар ва эскирган сўзлар миллий манзарани акс эттирувчи сўзлар ҳисобланиб, таржима жараёнида аналог беришдан кўра, транскрипция усули билан, яъни таржима қилинган матнда асл сўзни сақлаб қолиш имконини берадиган таржима усулидан фойдаланиш мақсадга мувофиқдир.

Адабиётлар рўйхати

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ADABIY VA BADIY DISKURS VA UNING ZAMONAVIY TILSHUNOSLIKDA TALQINI.

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Annotatsiya.

Muloqotni umumiy, xususan, adabiy-badiiy diskursni o'rganishning ahamiyati va dolzarbligi asoslab berilgan, zamonaviy tilshunoslik fanida adabiy-badiiy nutq tushunchasini tushunishning nazariy masalalari yoritilgan, so'zlashuv sohasidagi turli ilmiy tushunchalarga umumiy nuqtai nazar berilgan. nutq va matnni o'rganish beriladi. Maqolada nutqning oldingi tadqiqotlari natijalari tahlil qilinadi, tavsif uchun umumiy ilmiy asoslar quriladi va nutqning tuzilishi o'rganiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: adabiy-badiiy diskurs, lingvistik tahlil, sub'yektivlik, nutq semiotikasi,

Ilmiy adabiyotlarni tahlil qilish natijalariga ko'ra, adabiy-badiiy nutqning talqini turli xil ichki va tashqi omillar bilan shartlangan badiiy muloqot jarayonining lingvistik timsolini o'zida sintez qiladigan adabiy matn sifatida beriladi. Ta'kidlanishicha, ushbu sub'yektivlik markazida har doim yozuvchining o'quvchiga bo'lgan kognitiv yo'naltirilgan harakati aniq yoki ko'proq bilvosita kiradi. Shuningdek, tadqiqotda adabiy-badiiy nutqni boshqa nutq turlaridan ajratib turadigan o'ziga xos xususiyatlari ham belgilab berilgan, yozuvchi va

jamiyatning ma'lum darajada madaniy kodlarining vakili sifatida badiiy nutq strukturasi tashkil etuvchi lingvistik va kognitiv birliklar tahlil qilingan. "

Ushbu maqolaning ahamiyati nutq semiotikasining yangi qirralarini yoritib berishda, adabiy-badiiy nutqning mohiyati va xususiyatlari haqidagi tasavvurlarni kengaytirishdan iborat bo'lib, bu badiiy matn va nutq nazariyasini yanada rivojlantirishga qo'shilgan o'ziga xos hissadir. Adabiy-badiiy nutqni talqin qilish masalasi ilmiy dunyoda, tabiiyki, nutq turlarini farqlash yondashuvlari haqida munozaralar paydo bo'lganda paydo bo'ldi. Bugungi kunda "diskurs" atamasi bir ma'noli talqinga ega emas, bu o'zining fanlararo mavqei bilan bog'liq: falsafadan kelib chiqqan holda, u kognitiv lingvistika, madaniyatshunoslik, semiotika, lingvo-konseptologiya, mantiq, lingvosotsiologiya, lingvosotsiologiya va boshqa fanlarda o'z o'rnini topdi. Diskurs tadqiqotining ahamiyati va dolzarbligini qayd etib, M.L. Makarovning e'tirof etishicha, "bugungi kunda ijtimoiy fanlardagi "diskurs" toifasi Yevropa iqtisodiyotida yevroga o'xshash rol o'ynaydi". Tilshunoslik nuqtai nazaridan, nutq til tadqiqotining yangi, aytish mumkinki, yanada murakkab tomonini namoyish etadi, bu lingvistik tadqiqotning kengaytirilgan yondashuvlari va usullarini izlashni talab qiladi. Nutqni aniqlashning asosiy muammosi uning beqarorligi va namoyon bo'lishining dinamik tabiatidadir. "So'zlarni, iboralarni, jumalarni faqat statik shaxslar, tizimning barqaror elementlari sifatida tahlil qilishda qo'llaniladigan usullar, umuman olganda, nutq uchun yaroqsiz bo'lib chiqadi". Bu shuni ko'rsatadiki, nutq birinchi navbatda jarayon, til esa tizimdir va nutqda tilning turli birliklarini tahlil qilish endi an'anaviy lingvistik tadqiqni emas, balki boshqa narsani nazarda tutadi, chunki nutqning o'ziga xos xususiyatlariga ega bo'lgan bu birliklar xuddi shunday dinamik, konnotativ va assotsiativ xususiyatlarga ega bo'lib chiqadi, va semantik beqarorlikni namoyish etadi. Diskurs tadqiqotidagi evolyutsiya va uning ko'p qirrali tabiati nutqning ko'plab talqinlarini keltirib chiqardi, ammo bugungi kunda "diskurs" atamasi an'anaviy tarzda "ekstralingvistik – pragmatik, sotsial-

madaniy, psixologik va boshqa omillar bilan birgalikda izchil matn” sifatida tushuniladi; voqea aspektida olingan matn. Ya'ni, ijtimoiy kontekst va o'zaro ta'sir nutqni tashkil etishning yetakchi shartlari bo'lib ko'rinadi. Shu nuqtai nazardan qaraganda, biz adabiy-badiiy nutq deganda badiiy muloqot jarayonining o'ziga xos lingvistik timsolini turli ichki va tashqi omillar bilan shartlangan holda, yozuvchi voqeligiga sub'ektiv baho berishni sintezlovchi badiiy matn deb tushunamiz. Shuni ta'kidlash kerakki, ushbu sub'ektivlik markazida har doim yozuvchining o'quvchilarga bo'lgan kognitiv yo'naltirilgan harakati mavjud bo'lib, unda "u ma'lum munosabatlar, shuningdek, kommunikativ niyatlar va estetik ta'sirning ma'lum usullarini boshqaradi." Adabiy-badiiy nutqning o'ziga xosligi – bu nutq turlarini farqlash mezonlari sifatida matnning pragmatikligini, uni tashkil etish parametrlarini va janr-uslubiy xususiyatlarini, shuningdek muallifning u yoki bu sohaga bo'lgan niyatlarini belgilashdir va nutqdan foydalanishdir.

Xulosa

Shunday qilib, adabiy-badiiy nutq o'quvchini o'z makoniga jalb etib, uning oldida yozuvchi bilan kommunikativ harakat sodir bo'ladigan xayoliy dunyoni ochadi. Qolaversa, adabiy-badiiy nutq ishtirokchilarining dialogik tabiati nafaqat shaxsiy, balki dunyoni idrok etishni badiiy idrok etish orqali amalga oshiriladigan ekzistensial darajada ham namoyon bo'ladi.

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BADIIY TARJIMADA DINIY DISKURS ELEMENTLARI

Subxonova Madina Otabek qizi

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqola badiiy matnda qo'llanilgan diniy diskurs birliklari talqiniga bag'ishlangan. Diniy nutq elementlari "mikro", "makro" tushunchalar orqali o'rganildi. Bu o'rganishlar mashhur olimlar ishlari, olib borilgan tadqiqotlarni o'rgangan va tayangan holda olib borildi.

Kalit so'zlar: Diniy diskurs, mifologiya, mikro konsept, makro konsept, xudo, inson.

Diniy leksika har qanday jamiyat mavjudligining ajralmas tarkibiy qismidir. Insoniyat taraqqiyotining muhim omili, shuningdek, ajdodlar tajribalarini saqlash shakllaridan biri desak ham mubolag'a bo'lmaydi. Diniy leksika har bir tilda lug'atning o'ziga xos qatlami bo'lib, uning ostida shakllanadi. Diniy mifologiya va dinning ta'siri keng qamrovli. Qolaversa, diniy leksika o'zining nisbiy barqarorligi va yozma yozuvi jihatidan ham moddiy, ham ma'naviy qadriyat sifatida xalqning madaniy yodgorligi sifatida tavsiflanishi mumkin.

Materialni tahlil qilish asosida turli tadqiqotchilar diniy diskurs xususiyatlarni aniqlash, uning asosiy vazifalari, asosiy qiymant va tushunchalarini ajratish va tahlil qilish, diniy diskurs janrlar sistemasini tavsiflash, ushbu nutqdagi pretsedent hodisalarni topish, diniy nutqqa xos kommunikativ strategiyalarni bayon qilishda bir qancha urinishlar olib borishgan.

Diniy nutq tadqiqotchilari nutq aloqalarining barcha mumkin bo'lgan turlarida - argumentativ, ekspressiv, ijtimoiy, marosimlarda o'ziga xos diskursiv harakatlarning chastotasini qayd etadilar.

Keling, din tushunchasining ba'zi talqinlarini ko'rib chiqaylik. E.V tomonidan olib borilgan. Sergeevaning lug'at ta'riflari tahlili shuni ko'rsatdiki, "Cherkov slavyan va rus tili lug'ati" da bu leksema qisqacha ta'riflangan: "Xudoga sig'inish; Xudoga imon" degan ibora, bir tomondan, din va e'tiqodni idrok etishning o'xshashligini, ikkinchi tomondan, bu tushunchalar orasidagi farqni anglashni ko'rsatadi, chunki Xudoga sig'inish faqat imon bilan bir xil emas. Deyarli teng darajada lakonik talqin V.I.ning "Tirik buyuk rus tilining lug'ati" da berilgan. Dahl - "imon, ruhiy e'tiqod, e'tirof, ibodat yoki asosiy ruhiy e'tiqodlar". Ma'no tuzilishida ajralib turadigan "munosabat" va "dunyoga qarash" semalari "din" tushunchasini e'tiqodning o'zidan tashqarida aniq kengaytirish haqida gapirishga imkon beradi [Sergeeva, 2007: 152].

G'ayritabiiy kuchlarga ishonish ham sehriga xosdir, ammo din va sehr o'rtasida sezilarli farq bor. Din - bu g'ayritabiiy narsalarga ishonish va umid, ilohiy yordamga umid qilish. Sehr - bu g'ayritabiiy kuchlarni boshqarish qobiliyatiga ishonish. Dinda asosiy narsa ibodat va umiddir, sehrda "ishlashi" kerak bo'lgan sehr bor [Malinovskiy, 1998].

Diniy nutq o'ziga xos va o'ziga mosdir, chunki uning ishtirokchilari Xudo - g'ayritabiiy zot bo'lib, unga e'tiqod, ibodat va ishonch kiradi. Barcha diniy matnlar ikki tomonlama xususiyatga ega: bu ruhan inson tomonidan idrok etilishi kerak bo'lgan Xudoning ovozi, ammo bular ham barcha matn xususiyatlariga ega bo'lgan va adabiy janrlar qonunlariga bo'ysunadigan oddiy kitoblardir, bu bizga badiiy asarlarni diniy nutq sifatida tasniflash imkonini beradi..

Diniy nutqning tarkibiy qismlari uning makro va mikrokontseptsiyalaridir. Diniy nutqning makro-kontseptsiyasi orqali biz o'zining assotsiativ semantik maydoniga boshqa tushunchalarni (to'liq yoki qisman) kiritishga qodir bo'lgan juda keng ma'noli tushunchani tushunamiz - bular "Xudo" va "Inson" tushunchalari, chunki din inson va Xudo o'rtasidagi aloqani tiklash uchun mo'ljallangan.

Diniy nutqning mikrokontsepsiyasi - torroq ma'no (kichikroq hajm) tushunchasi bo'lib, u to'liq yoki qisman katta hajmdagi ma'no tushunchasining tarkibiy qismiga aylanishi mumkin. Bizning tadqiqotimizda "Imon", "Ishonch", "E'tidoq" mikro tushunchalarini ko'rib chiqamiz. Ammo diniy nutqda ko'plab boshqa mikrokontsepsiyalar ham faoliyat ko'rsatadi, ular diniy konseptual sohaning katta mazmuni va miqdoriy tarkibi tufayli tadqiqotimiz doirasidan tashqarida qoldi. Bitta tadqiqot doirasida faqat bir din nutqining elementlarini tahlil qilish mumkin, ammo ushbu ma'lumotlarga asoslanib, dunyoning badiiy rasmida ushbu turdagi nutqning ishlashi to'g'risida umumlashtirish va xulosalar chiqarish mumkin.

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**THE ARTISTIC MODELING OF PERSONALITY IN DREISER'S
WORKS:**

CAPTURING MOTIVES AND ASSESSING CHARACTERS

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***Abstract:** This article examines the portrayal of personality traits through the interrogation scenes in Theodore Dreiser's novels, focusing on the American contemporary period. It explores how Dreiser employs the technique of interrogation to unveil the inner workings of his characters and shed light on their complex personalities. Through a close analysis of selected novels, such as "Sister Carrie", "Jennie Gerhardt", "American Tragedy" and "Genius" the article investigates the use of questioning as a tool for character development and revelation. It explores the various interrogation techniques employed by Dreiser, including direct questioning, psychological probing, and self-reflection, to understand how these scenes contribute to the overall narrative and thematic exploration. By examining Dreiser's interrogation scenes within the context of the American contemporary period, this article aims to uncover the underlying personality traits and motivations of his characters, offering insights into the psychology and social dynamics of the time.*

Key words: *philosophy of success, typological characteristics, psychoanalysis, character development, archetypes, traits, motivations, comprehensive analysis, recurring themes, thematic exploration.*

The artistic portrayal of characters is a fundamental aspect of literature, allowing authors to delve into the depths of human psychology and explore the complex intricacies of personality. One author who masterfully captures the essence of human nature and the influence of various motives on individuals is Theodore Dreiser. Through his works, Dreiser skillfully employs artistic modeling to create characters that resonate with readers and provide insights into the intricacies of

their personalities. This article aims to delve into the artistic modeling of personality in Dreiser's works, examining how he captures motives and assesses characters. By analyzing key elements of Dreiser's writing style and his portrayal of characters, it will be gained a deeper understanding of the psychological nuances and motivations that drive his literary creations. Additionally, this article will explore the impact of Dreiser's artistic modeling on the depiction of human nature, unveiling the timeless relevance of his works and their ability to resonate with readers across generations.

Moreover, Dreiser created a system of images in his works, with the help of which he analyzed the socio-psychological characteristics of the individual, the characteristics

of his consciousness and subconscious. The work of Theodore Dreiser represents an

important stage in the development of American literature at the beginning of the 20th

century; where he presents unique artistic models of personality that deeply penetrate

the psychology and social aspects of human life. In the novels "Sister Carrie", "American Tragedy", "Jenny Gerhardt" and "Genius", Dreiser explores complex and multifaceted characters that reflect the diverse aspects of human nature, their aspirations, suffering, successes and failures. To address the artistic modeling of personality in Dreiser's novels, a qualitative approach was employed. A qualitative literary analysis approach allows for a deep exploration and understanding of the artistic modeling of personality in Dreiser's novels, taking into account the unique qualities of literary texts and the interpretive nature of literary analysis. In addition to qualitative, another approach used to explore the artistic modeling of personality in Dreiser's novels is psychoanalytic criticism. Psychoanalytic criticism helped to focus on applying psychoanalytic theories to understand the characters, themes, and symbolism in Theodore Dreiser's literary

works. Dreiser created in his work various artistic models of personality that combine such personal characteristics as egocentrism and individualism, which in a certain respect is the product of the "philosophy of success", very popular in American society in the 19th - 20th centuries. In this article, we explored similarities and differences in the portrayal of personality across different characters and works within Dreiser's oeuvre. This will involve identifying recurring themes, archetypes, and variations in the artistic portrayal of personality. Moreover, the article will incorporate relevant psychological and literary theories to provide a framework for understanding the artistic models of personality depicted in Dreiser's work. Psychological theories such as personality psychology, psychoanalysis, and humanistic psychology will be utilized to interpret the characters' traits and motivations. By following this research methodology, the study aims to provide a comprehensive analysis of the artistic models of personality in the work of Theodore Dreiser, offering valuable insights into the portrayal of human psychology and character development in his literary creations. Dreiser forms an artistic model of personality, creating in his works heroes who are united by common typological characteristics that determine the type of American contemporary to Dreiser, exposed to the so-called "philosophy of success." For this purpose, the writer uses a variety of artistic means: monologues that reveal the inner state of the individual; and dialogues during which the features of the inner world of the individual are revealed. A special form of dialogue is the interrogation scenes of Clyde Griffiths in "American Tragedy". Interrogation, in this case, performs a special artistic function, allowing the writer to capture personality traits in Clyde's answers to tricky, provocative questions from investigators. In the interrogation scene, Dreiser's character appears as a weak-willed and nervous person. The hero's remarks, combined with a detailed description of his emotional state, give a complete picture of the character of the individual and the motives for his actions. The author's assessment is also a means of creating an artistic model of personality in Dreiser's works. It

can be hidden or overt, and either correspond to the character's character or "disorient" the reader. Often Dreiser in works of fiction gives a direct assessment of the personality and actions of the hero. For example, describing Hurstwood's miserable situation after breaking up with Carrie, Dreiser writes: "The hotel manager felt some interest in this man. He didn't know where he could be placed, but at the same time Hurstwood's voice sounded so sincere that a desire to help him was involuntarily born." [4,78] However, sometimes a writer does not offer such direct characterization of the actions and personalities of his characters. Thus, Dreiser is in no hurry to convict his hero in the novel "American Tragedy", Clyde Griffiths. His opinion on this matter is clearly expressed, not in the novel, but in the journalism and epistolary heritage that came out after the publication of "American Tragedy." In the image of Clyde, the writer emphasized instability and malleability to environmental influences. The narrative is constructed in such a way that Clyde is always at the center of attention, and at the same time, the forces forming his character are visible. "Only the conversations in the vestibule, - writes Dreiser, - not to mention the scenes in the bar, restaurants, and rooms, were enough to impress upon every inexperienced and not very discerning being that the main occupation in life for anyone who has some money and social standing is to go to theaters, visit stadiums in summer, dance, ride in a car, treat friends to meals, and travel for entertainment to New York, Europe, Chicago, or California." [2,102] This reveals the social conditioning of Clyde's behavior, which is imbued with the desire to get into this world of luxury and wealth. In addition to the author, other characters around him can evaluate the hero. Thus, Kern for Drouet is a naive girl, for Hurstwood a wonderful lover, for his sister and her husband a "lost soul," while for the theater director, she is a talented actress who failed to realize her creative potential. Dreiser practically does not resort to describing nature in his works. He is an urban writer. The backdrop to his stories is the cities in which the action takes place. These tend to be America's fast-growing new cities, like Chicago. They perform the artistic function of a kind

of symbol, as many critics rightly noted, dream cities for vain young people. The actions of the heroes are influenced by many components. And, first of all, this is the tragic discrepancy, characteristic of Dreiser's works, between social moral norms and the natural desires and impulses of the individual. Thus, Hurstwood, having fallen in love with Cerry, violates the laws of public morality. Similar "moral violations" are described in the story about the financial genius Cowperwood, who determines actions by desires, as well as in the novel "Genius", which describes the love interests of Eugene Vitla, who is also a "slave of passions." [5,134,145] Theodore Dreiser's artistic portrayal of characters in his works provides a profound exploration of human psychology and the complexities of personality. Through his skillful artistic modeling, Dreiser creates characters that resonate with readers, offering insights into the intricacies of their motives and personalities. By analyzing key elements of Dreiser's writing style and his portrayal of characters, we gain a deeper understanding of the psychological nuances and motivations that drive his literary creations. Overall, Theodore Dreiser's artistic modeling of personality in literature not only provides a captivating reading experience but also offers a profound exploration of the depths of human nature. His continuing relevance and ability to resonate with readers across generations stand as a testament to his mastery as a writer and his ability to offer timeless insights into the complexities of the human psyche.

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Аннотация. Роман Дэна Брауна "Цифровая крепость" представляет захватывающий мир киберпространства, где технологии сталкиваются с этическими дилеммами. Сюжет развивается вокруг таинственного алгоритма, способного контролировать мировую информацию. В поисках ответов завязывается битва между хакерами и правительственными организациями. Анализируя работу, мы раскроем ее ключевые темы и идеи.

Ключевые слова: замонавий адабиёт, техно-триллер, 21-аср мероси, киберфазо, еркинлик, гобелен, ижтимоий тенгсизлик, дарслар, инсон тафаккури, инсоният.

Annotatsiya. Дан Брауннинг "рақамли қалъа" romani киберфазонинг ҳаяжонли дунёсини тақдим этади, бу ерда технология ахлоқий муаммоларга дуч келади. Сюжет дунё маълумотларини бошқаришга қодир сирли алгоритм атрофида ривожланади. Жавоб излаш учун хакерлар ва давлат ташкилотлари ўртасида жанг бошланади. Асарни таҳлил қилиб, биз унинг асосий мавзулари ва гояларини очиқ берамиз

.Kalit so'zlar: iqtisodiy tafakkur, iqtisodiy qobiliyat, moslashuvchan funktsiya, gumanistik funktsiya, iqtisodiy sotsializatsiya modeli, iqtisodiy tafakkurni baholashning ko'p o'lchovli modeli, iqtisodiy tafakkur rivojlanishini baholashning parametrik modeli, kognitiv komponent, psixo-emotsional komponent, stereotiplash darajasi, Maslou ehtiyojlar piramidasi.

Abstract.. The novel "Digital Fortress" by Dan Brown presents an exciting world of cyberspace, where technology faces ethical dilemmas. The plot develops

around a mysterious algorithm capable of controlling the world's information. In search of answers, a battle ensues between hackers and government organizations. Analyzing the work, we will reveal its key themes and ideas.

Key words: modern literature, techno-thriller, heritage, 21st century, cyberspace, freedom, tapestry, Social inequality, lessons, human thinking, humanity.

Introduction:

In an era of rapid development of digital technologies and information progress, literary works interacting with exciting aspects of cyberspace and technological mysteries are attracting increasing attention from both literary analysts and the public. In this context, the novel "Digital Fortress" by the outstanding American writer Dan Brown not only appears to the reader as a unique example of modern literature, but also deserves special attention in light of its deep insight into the mysterious aspects of the virtual world and cyber intrigues, as well as its rich content of philosophical and ethical issues.

Digital Fortress is a techno-thriller novel written by American author Dan Brown and published in 1998. The book explores the theme of government surveillance of electronically stored information on the private lives of citizens, and the possible civil liberties and ethical implications of using such technology. {1}

In its essence, this work goes beyond the usual techno-thriller, penetrating into the foundations of modern social and cultural aspects related to the use of technology in everyday life. In this context, the author not only solves complex cybernetic puzzles, but also raises important issues related to privacy, ethics in the field of information technology, and defining the boundaries between individual freedom and collective security.

Therefore, the purpose of our analysis is to examine in more detail the key themes and ideas embedded in the "Digital Fortress", with an emphasis on the extensive literary heritage, masterfully intertwining virtual reality with fundamental philosophical arguments about art, freedom, and the deep secrets hidden behind the facade of modern technology.

The relevance of the topic of cyberspace

In the contemporary landscape of cultural and sociological evolution, the thematic exploration of cyberspace emerges as a veritable linchpin, elucidating the nuanced array of challenges and possibilities confronting the human collective. Within the mesmerizing intricacies of the digital realm, the discourse encompasses salient topics such as online security, ethical considerations surrounding data utilization, and the profound ramifications of technological advancements on both individual and societal dimensions. This complex narrative finds eloquent expression within the literary oeuvre of Dan Brown. As an author, Brown adeptly immerses the discerning reader in the labyrinthine paradoxes inherent to cyberspace, thereby catalyzing profound reflections on the multifaceted consequences precipitated by an escalating reliance on digital technologies. In this manner, the thematic underpinning of cyberspace transcends its narrative function, assuming the role of a didactic vehicle that beckons contemplation on the manifold implications of humanity's burgeoning entanglement with the digital milieu.

The second decade of the 21st century heralds a momentous juncture wherein the collision between contemporary society and the dynamically evolving tapestry of technological realities imbues the thematic exploration of cyberspace with unprecedented significance. Within this intellectual milieu, the theme functions as a central locus, an axis around which a constellation of genuine challenges and prospective trajectories orbit, thereby encapsulating the manifold

vicissitudes confronting humanity. The thematic discourse on cyberspace directs scholarly attention toward the pervasive permeation of digital technologies into the fabric of diverse facets of quotidian existence. Furthermore, it engages in a rigorous examination of their profound impact on the structural framework of society and the nuanced contours of individual perceptual realities. The theme, thus, serves as a conduit through which a comprehensive scholarly inquiry unfolds, unraveling the intricate interplay between technological encroachment and the sociocultural metamorphosis of contemporary civilization.

Undoubtedly, the allure of the digital realm, replete with its captivating intrigues and uncharted possibilities, underscores society's keen interest in the theme of cyberspace. From this vantage point, the topics of online security, ethical considerations in data utilization, and the overarching impact of technologies on individual and collective experiences become subjects of profound scrutiny. In the context of the ongoing integration of digital means into our everyday lives, the analysis of cyberspace's influence on human society emerges as a pertinent avenue for research and discourse. The inexorable penetration of digital tools into the fabric of our quotidian existence accentuates the need for a comprehensive examination of how cyberspace shapes and reshapes various facets of societal dynamics. In this light, the theme assumes an elevated significance as a focal point for scholarly inquiry and contemplation. The ongoing and pervasive nature of this digital integration necessitates an ongoing exploration of the multifaceted dimensions associated with the interplay between cyberspace and human society. As we navigate the evolving landscape of digital interconnectedness, the discourse surrounding cyberspace transcends mere fascination with its technological allure, evolving into a substantive field of investigation. The confluence of these considerations underscores the imperative for continued scholarly engagement with the theme, facilitating a nuanced understanding of its implications for the contemporary human experience. In essence, the exploration of cyberspace stands as an ongoing intellectual endeavor, reflecting the dynamic

interrelationship between technology and the intricate tapestry of our communal and individual lives.

In his literary opus "Digital Fortress," Dan Brown demonstrates exceptional mastery in the art of amalgamating elements of the techno-thriller genre with profound philosophical discourse. This work provides the reader with a unique opportunity not only to peruse literature on cyberspace but to deeply immerse oneself in its multifaceted landscape. Distinguished by its exploration not only of the technical aspects of the digital world but also of pressing sociocultural and ethical issues tied to human values and the transformation of societal structures in the face of rapid digital development, Brown's creation stands out. As an author, Brown intricately engages with the reader, prompting profound intellectual reflection. The narrative unfolds essential social and ethical dilemmas, addressing not only the technical dimensions of cyberspace but also the influence of digital innovations on human perception of the world and their consequences for key spheres of everyday life. Delving thoughtfully into technology development scenarios within "Digital Fortress," Brown delves into philosophical ideas about the nature of freedom in the digital society and the power that various forces can exert over this freedom. Brown's oeuvre transcends the conventional techno-thriller genre, offering readers not only a captivating plot but also an intellectual stimulus for discussing contemporary challenges and opportunities arising from rapid technological advancement. Thus, "Digital Fortress" not only develops the theme of cyberspace but also serves as a multi-layered philosophical discourse, providing readers with new horizons for contemplating the impact of digital technologies on our modern lives.

Dan Brown's creative works stand out not only for their gripping plots but also for their profound intellectual content. In "Digital Fortress," through the analysis of various scenarios of technological development, the author delves into philosophical concepts of freedom in the digital society and explores questions about the power that different forces can wield in the digital era. Renowned for

his skillful integration of techno-thriller and philosophical discourse, Dan Brown, in "Digital Fortress," guides the reader through the labyrinths of cyberspace, unraveling not only technical intricacies but also the dramatic consequences that may arise from disruptions in the virtual realm. Focusing attention on issues of privacy, ethics, and personal freedom, Brown raises important questions, placing the reader in a position of reflection regarding the use of technology in everyday life. The intellectual depth of his narrative invites readers to contemplate the intricate interplay between technological advancements and the fundamental aspects of human existence. Through the lens of a captivating storyline, Brown prompts an exploration of the ethical dimensions inherent in the digital age, challenging readers to critically assess the implications of pervasive technological integration on societal norms and individual autonomy. In "Digital Fortress," Brown transcends the conventional boundaries of the techno-thriller genre, seamlessly blending narrative excitement with intellectual inquiry. The narrative not only serves as an exhilarating journey into the world of cyberspace but also as a catalyst for thoughtful consideration of the broader implications of our digital interconnectedness.

Dan Brown's body of work transforms the literary landscape, extending beyond the confines of conventional techno-thrillers and offering readers a profound intellectual challenge. In his opus "Digital Fortress," the author not only analyzes potential scenarios of technological development but also delves into philosophical ideas, encapsulating the nature of freedom in the contemporary digital society and the potential power that various forces may exert over this freedom. One of the standout facets of Brown's creativity in "Digital Fortress" is his ability to analyze and foresee technological trends. The author immerses the reader not only in a captivating plot but also provides deep reflections on the future, where digital innovations play a pivotal role. This work is more than just a techno-thriller; it is an intellectual experiment that challenges established notions of how technology influences our lives and society as a whole. Brown's

exploration of technological trends goes beyond mere speculation, offering readers a thought-provoking glimpse into potential futures shaped by digital advancements. Through his narrative, Brown prompts readers to critically examine their assumptions about the trajectory of technology, inviting them to contemplate the intricate interplay between innovation, individual freedoms, and societal structures. In "Digital Fortress," Brown's narrative prowess lies not only in weaving an engaging storyline but also in fostering a deeper understanding of the profound implications of technological evolution. The work stands as a testament to Brown's capacity to blend narrative excitement with intellectual inquiry, inviting readers to embark on a journey that transcends the boundaries of traditional genre classifications.

The author does not confine himself to the technical aspects of the digital era; he raises questions pertaining to the fundamental principles of freedom in this new, digital world. In "Digital Fortress," Brown prompts the reader to contemplate the challenges and opportunities that the future, enriched with new technologies, may bring. This work becomes a platform for discussions on the value of freedom in the internet age and how various forces can influence our personal and societal freedoms. The philosophical ideas explored in Brown's work unravel intricate questions about the impact of technology on human freedom. The author analyzes how digital technologies give rise to new forms of power and how these forms of power can either restrict or expand our capabilities. In "Digital Fortress," he goes beyond describing technical details, elevating the narrative to the realm of fundamental debates about the value of freedom in an era of rapid technological development. By delving into these philosophical dimensions, Brown's work transcends the boundaries of a conventional techno-thriller. It serves as a catalyst for profound reflections on the evolving relationship between technology and human liberties, urging readers to critically assess the implications of technological advancements on the very essence of freedom. "Digital Fortress" thus emerges as a thought-provoking exploration of the intersection between

technological progress, ethical considerations, and the enduring principles of individual and collective freedom.

Highlighting ethical issues in the use of information technology

"Digital Fortress" presents itself to the reader as a literary chronicler of the contemporary era, wherein technology and cyberspace become integral components of our everyday lives. Rising above the mundane, Dan Brown's novel immerses us in the captivating world of computer technologies, where each bit of data carries both the potential for threat and the enthralling prospect of discovery.

An illustrative example occurs when the main protagonist, grappling with difficulties in unraveling a mystery, ventures into the virtual expanses of modern networks. Here, the author explores not only the technical aspects of cyberspace but also delves into the inner world of the character. Like a hacker navigating a convoluted labyrinth of information, the protagonist transcends from reality to virtual space, where every byte is permeated with a tense atmosphere. In this pivotal episode of "Digital Fortress," the main character, determined to unveil a complex enigma, enters the realm of virtual reality within contemporary information networks. The author skillfully transports the reader into this captivating landscape, where the technical facets of cyberspace become an integral part of the mystery and intrigue. Brown's narrative prowess shines in his ability to seamlessly blend technical intricacies with the psychological and virtual realms. By doing so, he not only elucidates the challenges posed by the digital age but also immerses the reader in an immersive experience where the boundaries between the real and the virtual blur. "Digital Fortress" thus stands as a literary testament to the transformative power of technology, offering readers a gripping exploration of the multifaceted landscape of cyberspace.

Like a hacker, the main protagonist infiltrates the intricate labyrinth of information, transporting the reader from familiar reality into virtual space. The

author, meticulously exploring the technical aspects of cyberspace, immerses us in the astonishing world of codes, algorithms, and electronic traces. In this virtual labyrinth, every byte of data is filled with tension and mystery, creating an atmosphere of uncertainty and excitement. Through the protagonist's personal experience, the reader becomes a witness to the struggle between human intellect and the boundless possibilities of the digital realm. This approach allows the author not only to immerse the reader in the captivating technological world but also to unveil the inner world of the protagonist—their thoughts, emotions, and aspirations within the confines of virtual reality. This episode serves as a pivotal moment where the technical side of cyberspace merges with psychological aspects, making the work more profound and multi-faceted. By intricately intertwining the technical intricacies of cyberspace with the personal and psychological journey of the character, the author creates a narrative that transcends mere exploration of technology. Instead, "Digital Fortress" becomes a narrative tapestry that delves into the human experience within the digital landscape, highlighting the symbiotic relationship between the protagonist's internal struggles and the challenges posed by the virtual realm. This fusion of technical and psychological elements elevates the work, transforming it into a rich and nuanced exploration of the intersection between humanity and technology.

The novel is multifaceted in that it not only delves into the persona of a hacker and the realm of cyberspace but also addresses the issue of privacy. In another episode of the novel, through the lens of cyberspace, the author tackles issues of ethics and privacy. Characters grapple with a dilemma where the uncertainty of the boundary between personal life and the world of virtual data prompts the reader to contemplate how technology influences our understanding of individual freedom and security. In the episode devoted to the ethical and privacy issues in cyberspace, Dan Brown raises crucial questions that touch on contemporary society. The characters in the novel confront the uncertainty of vanishing boundaries between their personal lives and the boundless expanse of

virtual data. This dilemma forces the reader to ponder how modern technologies impact our perception of individual freedom and the assurance of personal security. Through the prism of cyberspace, the author provides the reader with an opportunity to scrutinize complex moral questions confronting society in the era of digital transformation. By intertwining the narrative with these ethical and privacy dilemmas, Brown not only adds layers of complexity to the storyline but also invites readers to reflect on the broader implications of technology on our societal values. The exploration of these themes within the context of cyberspace elevates the novel beyond a mere techno-thriller, transforming it into a thought-provoking commentary on the ethical challenges posed by the digital age.

The virtual environment, where electronic traces of every action become an integral part of life, compels the characters in the novel and the reader to contemplate the boundaries between individual lives and public space. This episode underscores the importance of discussing ethical questions related to technology use and the potential consequences of losing personal privacy in the era of digital interconnectedness. "Digital Fortress" transcends being merely a captivating techno-thriller; it serves as a platform for reflections on how modern innovations shape our understanding of values and norms in the realms of ethics and security. Thus, "Digital Fortress" not only reflects contemporary trends but also unveils deep layers of philosophy, ethics, and human psychology in the context of cyberspace. It offers readers the opportunity to engage with a meticulously crafted literary work where virtual reality intertwines with the multifaceted aspects of modern life. The novel becomes a canvas for exploring the intricate interplay between technology, ethics, and the human experience, prompting readers to appreciate a nuanced literary creation that goes beyond the surface of virtual reality and delves into the complexities of our evolving digital landscape.

The central portion of the novel is dedicated to elucidating the impact of the digital world on our society. In the contemporary world, phones have become an

integral part of our daily lives, and their influence on our lifestyle is immeasurable. Seemingly, individuals have become dependent on their phones, akin to puppets manipulated by digital strings. In the novel "Digital Fortress," a pivotal moment illustrating the question of power and control in the realm of information technology occurs when the protagonist confronts information manipulation. The plot unfolds, revealing that certain structures of power utilize technology for the collection, processing, and distortion of data with the aim of manipulating public opinion and achieving their own objectives. The protagonist realizes that information transcends being a mere instrument for conveying facts; it emerges as a powerful means of influencing thought and perception. Deciphering cyber spatial puzzles, he grapples with how information control technologies can shape false realities and impact societal perceptions. This moment in the novel underscores how in the hands of technological authorities, data can be wielded to craft a particular narrative, create illusions, and even manipulate reality. Thus, the author posits the idea that the possession of information assumes not only technical but also strategic significance, enabling those who control the flow of data to exert substantial influence on public consciousness.

There is a realization that we lack control over our own lives due to limited access to information. Social inequality has always existed, but cyberspace has heightened the asymmetrical capabilities of one of the two sides. In the context of social and economic disparities in the novel "Digital Fortress," not only technological disparities are highlighted but also their impact on the individual capabilities of characters. A prominent example is the character Susan Fletcher, representing a student with limited resources and a constrained social status. Susan, attempting to unravel the intrigues and mysteries in the novel, faces difficulties due to her restricted access to cutting-edge technologies and limited information resources. In comparison to the elite members of society, embodied by other characters, Susan finds herself in a less privileged position, lacking the

ability to effectively influence the course of the investigation. Elite members of society, thanks to their high social status and access to advanced technologies, have an advantage in manipulating and controlling information. This creates a noticeable disparity in investigative capabilities and problem-solving. Consequently, the technological privilege of elite societal layers deepens social and economic divides, restricting the personal and professional opportunities of those in less privileged positions.

Reader immersing themselves in Dan Brown's novel "Digital Fortress" has the opportunity to enrich their knowledge and understanding not only in the realm of cyberspace and technological intrigues but also to extract lessons from a range of key themes addressed by the author:

Power and Control: Examining the issue of power and control in the realm of information technology allows the reader to realize how the force of information can become a powerful tool of influence on society. This theme can teach the reader to perceive and analyze the impact of information on contemporary power structures more critically.

Intellectual Freedom: The novel raises important questions about intellectual freedom in the era of the digital society. The reader learns to value freedom of expression, recognize the importance of access to information, and contemplate how intellectual freedoms shape modern society.

National Security: Exploring issues of national security in the context of technology helps the reader better understand how modern technologies can be both a source of protection and a potential threat to national interests. This theme develops an understanding of the impact of technology on the security of a country.

Social and Economic Inequalities: Examining social and economic inequalities caused by technological differences allows the reader to delve into

complex issues related to the impact of technology on global societal and economic problems.

Personal Responsibility: The novel presents characters with dilemmas related to personal responsibility for the use of technology. The reader can draw lessons about the importance of self-awareness and the consequences of personal involvement in the digital era.

Psychology of Technological Interaction: The novel explores how technologies influence the inner world of characters. The reader can deepen their knowledge about how the technological environment shapes the thinking and emotions of individuals, as well as the importance of psychological adaptation to new technological realities.

Destruction and Innovation: Examining the impact of technology on existing societal structures allows the reader to understand how innovations can disrupt outdated models and stimulate progress. This theme helps realize the importance of openness to new ideas and changes in the digital era.

The Role of the Individual in the Digital Society: The characters in the novel face the challenges of the digital society, prompting the reader to contemplate their own role in the world of technology. This theme fosters reflections on the active participation of individuals in the digital space and their influence on the surrounding world.

The novel "Digital Fortress" appeals to a profound understanding of human thinking and provides a comprehensive view of the complex world we inhabit. It is noteworthy that the digital space holds tremendous power over our daily lives, prompting careful consideration of the influence and impact of technology. However, like puppets and puppeteers linked by a common thread, we also possess a degree of control over this virtual world. The undeniable influence of the digital space on our lifestyle is important to recognize, and it is crucial to be

aware that this power carries both positive and negative aspects. A fundamental aspect of the work is its instruction on the effective utilization of cyberspace to our advantage. The novel serves as a mentor, emphasizing that there are certain boundaries in the digital realm, defining what is permissible and what should be avoided. A key lesson of the work is the elucidation of which actions and decisions in the virtual environment can be beneficial and which, on the contrary, can cause harm. The novel leads the reader to an awareness of the importance of effective interaction with cyberspace and the necessity to develop critical thinking skills in this context. Simultaneously, the work constructs an argument in favor of the idea that the digital space, despite its challenges and risks, is an integral part of modern society and significantly influences its dynamics. Thus, the reader gains an understanding that active engagement with the digital space requires balance, comprehension, and responsibility.

Conclusion

In conclusion, "Digital Fortress" by Dan Brown serves as a multifaceted exploration of the intricate relationship between humanity and the ever-expanding digital realm. Through a captivating narrative that intertwines technological intrigue with profound philosophical considerations, the novel transcends the boundaries of a conventional techno-thriller. Brown skillfully delves into the ramifications of technological advancements, prompting readers to reflect on the evolving landscape of our interconnected lives. By raising essential questions about the impact of technology on personal and societal freedom, "Digital Fortress" provides a platform for meaningful discussions on the values that shape our digital age. The philosophical ideas explored in Brown's work unravel complex issues regarding the influence of technology on human freedom. The author not only scrutinizes technical details but elevates the narrative to fundamental debates about the value of freedom in the rapidly evolving technological landscape.

Ultimately, the work underscores the significance of engaging with the ethical implications of technology and its potential consequences. It highlights the importance of privacy, ethical considerations, and personal responsibility in navigating the complexities of the digital era. "Digital Fortress" invites readers to savor a meticulously crafted literary piece where virtual reality intertwines with the multifaceted aspects of modern life.

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PROBLEMS AND ARGUMENT SURROUNDING UZBEK NATIONAL DETECTIVE LITERATURE. IN WRITTEN LITERATURE, THE FIRST DETECTIVE ELEMENTS

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Annotation. This article covers the detective genre, which began to appear in the middle of the nineteenth century and had a positive impact on the development of international literature. Comments are made regarding the beginnings of detective fiction, the development of the genre, and important aspects of word science.

Keywords: detective literature, detective genre, Uzbek national detective literature, problems of Uzbek detective literature

Introduction. The detective genre, which is a complex type of prose genre in literature, reflects the details of uncovering a mysterious criminal case. The difference between the works written in this genre and other genre examples is that not only the hero or the author of the work, but also the reader, who is looking forward to finding a positive solution to the problems and punishing the crime with real punishment, imagines himself in the place of interest. To be able to interest the reader at this level, and to attract his continuous attention, requires great skill from the writer. It is not always easy to solve a crime, to find the criminals and to prove their guilt.

Research methodology. Every artist who steps into the holy place called literature tries to artistically express what he has realized in this mysterious world. Creativity in the detective genre that we are thinking about is just words and actions in the eyes of the reader. It means not playing games, but promoting deep spiritual and philosophical ideas. Confirmation of our statement is the opinion of the people's writer of Uzbekistan Amon Mukhtar, expressed at the round table of literary critics and creators "The market of literature or the responsibility of the literary word."

"Light work" with the concept of adventure, detective it's completely inappropriate to say that. You can read a number of works by one of the famous writers of Uzbek literature Kh. Tokhtaboev, "Shaytanat" by Takhir Malik or "Kironcha" by Said Ravshan. You can't say, "Their pussies are quickly forgotten." Some of them live ten years, twenty years, and some half a century. In addition to enjoyment for the reader, it also provides spiritual and spiritual nourishment."

Analysis and results. The detective genre did not suddenly appear yesterday or today in Uzbek literature. The first sparks of this genre originated in our national literature and folklore, it was formed and polished for centuries.

Amon Mukhtar noted that “the first elements of a detective work appear in folklore” and that “at the next stage, the famous Uzbek writer Abdulla Kadiri transferred detective elements from folklore to written literature and the great work “Bygone Days” admitted that he created it. Samples of national folklore serve as the genetic basis for the origin and development of not only the detective genre, but also written literature in general. Dorothy Sayers, creator of world-famous detective works, famous English writer An indisputable fact recognized by all writers is that it is advisable to look for the roots of detective prose in the oral work of the peoples of the world, and Eastern folklore served as the genetic source of the detective genre. [2] After all, the first attempts to create any work of art came into being with a direct appeal to folk art. Each writer uses folklore images, plots, it is not secret to anyone that he uses pictorial means and motifs creatively, albeit partially. In the history of literary epochs, it is impossible to imagine creative people who did not use the rich treasures of folk art. The creators of detective works, the genetic basis of which we are studying, are no exception. As the great Russian writer M. Gorky noted, "folklore is the beginning of the art of the word." Let's take a look at the genetic basis of the Uzbek national detective folklore and some written sources. A step-by-step analysis of the exact places in our literary works where detective elements are clearly visible, we will do it.

We will study the forms of detective literature in folklore on the example of the well-known epic of the Uzbek people called "Alpomysh". Khakimbek, the protagonist of the Alpomysh epic, is imprisoned by the king of the Kalmyk people.

However, after he managed to get out of prison with his courage and intelligence, he met his father's friend Boybori Kultoy. He asks Kultoy about the situation in his country. Almond Kultoy Boybori He says that the son of Ultontoz Alpomish wants to marry Barchina from a maid, and that their wedding will take place. Alpomish plans to go to the enemy Ultontoz in the

guise of one-year-old Kultoy, and Kultoy will return in the guise of Alpomish. Alpomish goes under the guise of Kultoy and wants to check if Kultoy's words are true. They both agree and go to the wedding wearing each other's clothes in a way that no one else can imagine. [3] This cunning plan of the protagonist Alpomish (Khakimbek) resembles the plot of a fan, which is considered the main character of detective works. Just as the fans try not to catch the eye of the enemy until their goal is achieved, Khakimbek achieves his goal keeps his true identity a secret. The main content of detective works is the search for truth and the establishment of justice. Alpomish chooses the same path. To carry out his plan, he operates secretly, revealing himself to no one. It follows that elements of the detective genre were present in ancient Uzbek folklore. They served as an important factor in the formation of the Uzbek national detective. The eternal struggle between good and evil appears as the main idea in every piece of folklore. How important is the crime and the punishment imposed for it in the detective genre, in the works of folklore the disclosure of crime, good over evil, victory takes a leading place as the main theme.

In the later stages there are also several written works incorporating detective work elements. But the novel of the famous Uzbek writer Abdulla Kadiri "Bygone Days", born in the twentieth century and surprising lovers of world literature, is considered a work that brought to mind the detective elements of folklore. [4] The fact that Otabek, the protagonist of the story, is trying to expose the crimes of Hamid, his rival, with the utmost precision and accuracy, embodies the image of fans in the world of detective literature.

A great contribution to the development of the genre was made by works written in the detective spirit by the 70s of the twentieth century by the people's writer of Uzbekistan Ulmas Umarbekov, who was recognized as "a detective who felt more deeply responsible for the genre." genre. As the well-known Uzbek writer, one of the representatives of the detective genre Tahir Malik, said: "Ulmas Umarbekov can be called one of the founders of modern Uzbek

detective literature. His The first stage works that sounded on the stage of the Kokan Theater - the stories "Court", "Summer Rain" were among the first works written in the style of a modern detective story. [5] Ulmas Umarbekov introduced the image of the "Uzbek female detective" into world literature through his novel "Fatima and Zuhra.". Although curiosity, which is considered the leading feature of detective stories, is a male image, she solved problems that popular policemen could not solve, and exposed crimes through the heroine of her work - Zuhra. Thus, she introduced the image of an "enthusiastic woman" into the national Uzbek detective literature.

In addition, we can see elements of the detective genre more clearly in the famous work of Tahir Malik "Shaitanat". [6] In this work, the writer brings to the attention of the reader all the vices of the underworld and the causes of their occurrence and the difficulties in solving crimes. In conclusion, it should be said that the elements of the detective genre in the Uzbek national eternity - from samples of folk oral art to fiction of the twentieth century are visible. Artistic works, created despite a number of oppositions to our national literature during the socio-political system of the last century, made a great contribution to the development of the modern Uzbek detective genre. Like the works analyzed above, Uzbek writers have proved that they can create samples of their work in this responsible genre.

Conclusion. In short, the development of the detective genre occurs within its inevitable factors. Undoubtedly, his success is due to the artistic vision of these factors. These considerations are the basis for noting that the world and Uzbek detective models occupy a special place in the social and spiritual life of society. It urges to recognize the great potential of the study of detective stories as an important source and encourages us to act accordingly.

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VLADIMIR NABOKOV BADIY OLAMI ZAMONDOSH TANQIDCHILAR NIGOHIDA

Pulatova Sabina Sharifovna,

BuxDU I bosqich doktoranti

O‘zining murakkab chuqur falsafiy nasri bilan mashhur bo‘lgan XX asr Amerika adabiyotining taniqli vakili Vladimir Nabokov adabiyot sohasida jumboqli shaxs bo‘lib qolmoqda. Nabokovning adabiy olamiga kirib borar ekanmiz, uning asarlari shunchaki voqea-hodisalar bayonidan ustun ekanligiga ya’ni turfa mavzular, uslublar va intellektual izlanishlar maydoni ekanligiga guvoh bo‘lamiz. Yozuvchining adabiyotga qo‘shgan hissasini to‘liq baholash uchun, biz nafaqat hozirgi kunda bu sohada amalga oshirilayotgan zamonaviy tadqiqotlarning ilmiy xulosalarini, balki uning badiiy olami zamondosh adabiyotshunoslar talqinida qanday e’tirof etilganligini ham inobatga olishimiz lozim. Ushbu maqolada, biz Nabokovning serqirra ijodiy dunyosi bo‘ylab sayohatga chiqib, uning hayoti davomida olib borilgan adabiy izlanishlar manzarasini o‘rganishga va tahlil qilishga urinamiz.

Ingliz adabiyotshunosligi va adabiy tanqidchiligida Vladimir Nabokov ismi birinchi marta 1933 yilda “American Mercury” jurnalining 29 - jildida iyul oyi sonida A.Parry tomonidan “Belles-Lettres Among the Russian Emigres”

maqolasida tilga olingan.⁴⁷ Tanqidchi yosh rus yozuvchilarining asarlari haqida umumiy ma'lumot berar ekan, ularning yozuvchilik iste'dodiga shubha bilan qaraydi:

“There are no Joseph Conrads among the younger emigres, it is best for them to write in their own language.”

Biroq, A. Parry ular ichidan uchta M. Aldanov, N. Berberova va V. Nabokov ismlarini ajratib ko'rsatadi, boisi shundaki, ushbu mualliflarning asarlarini ingliz tiliga tarjima qilishni loyiq deb topadi.

Garchi Nabokovning birinchi ingliz romani “The Real Life of Sebastian Knight” (1941) tanqidlarga uchragan bo'lsa-da, adabiy tanqidchilar adibning o'ziga xos stilistik mahoratiga alohida e'tibor qaratadilar. 1955 yilga qadar, Vladimir Nabokov Amerikada hali tanilmagan yozuvchi, adabiyotshunoslik sohasiga endi qadam qo'ygan, Cornel universiteti o'qituvchisi edi. 1955 yilda “Lolita” romanining Amerika Qo'shma Shtatlarda nashr etilishi va undan so'ng, 1955 yil sentyabr oyida romanning Parijda chop etilishi – Nabokov ijodida katta shou-shuvlarga sabab bo'lib, uni bir lahzada taniqli Amerika yozuvchisiga aylantirdi va aynan shu paytdan hozirgi kunga qadar, uning asarlari adabiy tanqidchilar diqqat markazidan tushmay kelmoqda.

Nabokov asarlariga birinchi tanqidiy fikrlar bildirilganiga, yaqinda salkam yuz yil to'ladi, shu davr ichida chet el nabokovshunosligi o'zining davriy nashrlari (“Nabokovian” va “Nabokov Studies”), o'z tarixi va doimiy “yilnomachilari” bilan deyarli “mustaqil” filologiya sohasiga aylandi. Nabokovshunoslikni “davriylashtirish tajribasi” K. Xyullen⁴⁸ monografiyasida amalga oshirilgan. Garchi tadqiqotchi mazkur ishida, Nabokov ijodini o'rganishda beshta asosiy bosqich (shu jumladan, rus va inglizabon nabokovianani ajratib ko'rsatadi):

1. 1922-1940 yillar;
2. 1940-1955 yillar;

⁴⁷ Parry, A. Belles Lettres Among the Russian Emigres. - American Mercury, 1933, July, Vol. 29, P.316 – 319.

⁴⁸ Hullen, C. Der Tod im Werk Vladimir Nabokovs' Terra Incognita. - Munich: Otto Sagner, 1990.

3. 1955-1966 yillar;

4. 1966-1977 yillar;

5. 1977-1989 yillarni (oxirgi sana, ehtimol, “hozirgi kunga qadar” deb tushunilishi kerak) aniq ajratib bergan va tadqiqot markazida Nabokov ijodining “sovet davri” ya’ni Rossiyada yaratilgan asarlarini o’rganilish va tahlil qilish turadi.

Nemis tadqiqotchisi tomonidan berilgan raqamlarga qisqacha izoh beradigan bo’lsak, 1922 yil Nabokovning shaxsiy hayotida fojiali voqea - otasining o’limi bilan xotirlansa-da, ijodiy faoliyatda aksincha burilish nuqtasi hisoblanadi, chunki aynan shu yildan Nabokov ijodida jo’shqin faollik seziladi. 1922 yilda “Colas Breugnon” romanining Nabokov tomonidan qilingan rus tilidagi tarjimasini “Николка Персик” nomi ostida nashr etildi; shu bilan birga o’sha paytda yozuvchi L. Kerrollning “Alice Adventures in Wonderland” kitobini tarjima qilish uchun buyurtma oldi (“Аня в Стране Чудес” nomi bilan kitob 1923 yilda chop etilgan); 1922 yil dekabr oyida Nabokovning “Гроздь” she’rlar to’plami dunyo yuzini ko’rdi.

Yozuvchining Amerika zaminidagi ijodiy faoliyati 1940 yilda boshlanadi, chunki aynan shu yilning 28 may kuni u Nyu-York shahriga qadam quyadi. Adibning inglizcha ilk ikki romani – “The Real Life of Sebastian Knight” (1941) va “Bend Sinister” (1947) shuningdek “Nicolai Gogol” (1944) essesi, “Conclusive Evidence” (1951) nomli kitobi faqatgina tor doirada ya’ni professional adabiyotshunoslar orasida ma’lum edi. Afsuski, o’sha davrda Nabokovning romanlari keng tadqiqotlar obyekti aylanmagan edi, biroq adib ingliz tilida ijod qilishdan to’xtamaydi.

1955 yilda Vladimir Nabokovning inglizcha ijodida tub burilish yasagan asari “Lolita” nashr etiladi. Shundan so’ng uning asarlari ingliz-Amerika adabiyotshunosligida bir vaqtning o’zida ikki yo’nalishda “istiqbol” va “retrospektiv” nuqtai nazardan intensiv o’rganishga turtki bo’ladi. Bir tomondan, tanqidchilar e’tibori - Nabokovning ingliz tilidagi yangi romanlariga qaratilgan

bo'lsa, boshqa tomondan, yozuvchi tomonidan 1940 yilgacha yaratilgan rus tilidagi asarlari ingliz tiliga tarjima qilinishi, Nabokovga talab paydo bo'lganidan dalolat edi. 1959 yilda “Приглашение на казнь” - “Invitation to A Beheading”, 1963 yilda “Дар” – “The Gift” va 1964 yilda “Защита Лужина” - “The Defense” kabi rus tilida yozilgan asarlarning ingliz tiliga tarjima qilinishi va keng ommaga taqdim etilishi, adibga nafaqat olamshumul mashhurlik balki iqtisodiy barqarorlikni ham olib keladi.

1966 yilda P. Stegnerning Nabokov ijodi haqida “Escape into Aesthetics” nomli ilk monografiyasi dunyo yuzini ko'radi.⁴⁹ Keyingi o'n yil davomida E. Fieldning “V. Nabokov: his Life in Art”⁵⁰ va “V. Nabokov: His Life in Part”⁵¹, A. Appelning “The Annotated Lolita”⁵², K. Profferning “The Keys to Lolita”⁵³ va boshqa bir qator tadqiqotchilarning ilmiy ishlari Nabokovning adabiy tanqidchilar tomonidan muttasil o'rganilayotganidan dalolat beradi. Umuman olganda, 1970-yillarda, aniqrog'i 1971 yildan 1979 yilgacha Nabokov haqida o'n to'rtta kitob va ikkita maqolalar to'plami nashr etilgan.

Nabokovning o'limidan so'ng, uning ijodini o'rganishga bo'lgan qiziqish va intilish na kitobxonlar va na adabiy tanqidchilar orasida pasayadi. Ijodkor vafotidan keyin adibning merosini tadqiq qilishga qaratilgan ilmiy izlanishlar soni shu darajada ko'payib ketadiki, ular alohida filologiya sohasiga aylanadi, bu esa o'z navbatida, Nabokov asarlari hamisha barhayot ekanligidan dalolat beradi.

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GENERATION GAP IN TEACHING PRACTICES: CLASSICISM VS ECCENTRICITY

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Abstract. *The clash between traditional and eccentric teaching methods in education highlights a significant generational gap. This divide, observed globally, prompts essential questions about teaching effectiveness, student engagement, and the evolving role of educators. Exploring the origins, manifestations, and implications of classicism and eccentricity is crucial within modern educational frameworks. By analyzing these differing philosophies, we seek to understand the interplay between tradition and innovation in teaching, fostering informed discourse and transformative insights in education.*

Keywords: *education, traditional teaching, eccentric instructional approaches, generational divide, pedagogical efficacy, student engagement, educators' role, classicism, eccentricity, teaching practices, tradition, innovation.*

In today's education landscape, traditional teaching methods clash with emerging eccentric approaches, revealing a significant generational gap. This divide prompts crucial questions about teaching effectiveness, student engagement, and educators' evolving roles. Exploring the contrasts between classicism and eccentricity is essential to understanding the interplay of tradition and innovation in teaching practices.

In modern teaching practices, eccentricity is increasingly recognized as a viable and effective approach, challenging traditional norms and fostering innovative learning environments. According to Charles Anzalone, “teachers, who some might consider eccentric and who went “against the grain” or who displayed unusual methods, stood out from the norm but got results in test scores, were admired by students and their peers, and found satisfaction in teaching.” [1, 2] Contemporary scholarship acknowledges the rising prominence of eccentric teaching methods as exemplified by the work of Anzalone, whose extensive fieldwork highlights the success of maverick teachers who diverge from conventional practices yet achieve notable outcomes in terms of test scores, student admiration, and professional fulfillment.

The contemporary landscape of education reflects a growing convergence between students and millennial faculty members, characterized by an advocacy for informality and the expression of self to facilitate the co-construction of new knowledge. Josephine J. and Jones L. in their article titled “Understanding the Impact of Generation Gap on Teaching and Learning in Medical Education: A Phenomenological Study”, say that “the more evident similarities were between students and a millennial faculty member who advocated greater informality, expression of self (as conveyed through thoughts, beliefs, values, and emotions) to allow co-construction of new knowledge. [4, 12] Moreover, contemporary scientists are uncovering a palpable generation gap among educators, a phenomenon that significantly influences teaching practices and pedagogical approaches.

Moreover, Steen and Hansen in their research findings claim that “our quantitative and qualitative studies show, in some cases, that the younger teachers are in some—but not every—respect reform more friendly than their older colleagues.” [2, 15] This assertion is substantiated by our findings, which reveal nuanced differences between generations, indicating that in certain instances, younger educators exhibit a predisposition towards reform initiatives, albeit not across all aspects of pedagogical practice.

The integration of social media within online education plans offers a multifaceted solution to tackle several issues in teaching. Christine Greenhow and Sarah Galvin consider that “social media, with its affordances for personal profiling, relationship-building, content creation and socializing, when thoughtfully integrated into an online education plan, can help students and teachers stay connected while apart, enhance students’ engagement and make remote learning seem less remote”. [3, 13] The crucial role that thoughtful integration of social media can play in transforming the remote learning experience is emphasized, offering a dynamic platform for fostering meaningful connections, stimulating engagement, and ultimately humanizing the virtual educational environment.

In conclusion, the clash between traditional and eccentric teaching methods, compounded by generational divides and the integration of social media, highlights the need for innovative approaches in education. Embracing eccentricity and leveraging social media can enhance student engagement and bridge generational gaps. Moving forward, continued research and adaptation are crucial for shaping a relevant and effective education system for the 21st century.

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EXPLORING THE IMPACT OF GAMIFICATION ON ENGAGEMENT AND LEARNING OUTCOMES IN LISTENING ACTIVITIES

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Abstract

This thesis investigates the influence of gamification on engagement and learning outcomes in listening activities within the context of language acquisition. With the pervasive integration of technology in educational settings, the potential of gamified approaches to enhance language learning has garnered considerable attention. This study aims to contribute to the existing literature by examining effective gamification strategies and their impact on engagement levels and learning outcomes in listening tasks. Through a mixed-methods approach, including surveys, observations, and assessments, this research explores the effectiveness of gamified interventions in language learning environments. The findings provide insights into practical implications for educators and curriculum

designers seeking to optimize language acquisition through innovative pedagogical strategies.

Keywords: Gamification, Engagement, Learning Outcomes, Listening Activities, Language Acquisition, Educational Technology.

Introduction

Language acquisition involves a multifaceted process that encompasses various skills, including listening comprehension. In recent years, there has been a growing interest in leveraging gamification—a technique that applies game-design elements and principles in non-game contexts—to enhance engagement and learning outcomes in educational settings. Within the realm of language learning, gamification offers promising potential to create immersive and interactive experiences that motivate learners and foster skill development. This study delves into the impact of gamification on engagement and learning outcomes specifically in listening activities, aiming to identify effective strategies for optimizing language acquisition.

I. Theoretical framework

Gamification in Education refers to the integration of game-design elements and principles into educational activities and processes to enhance engagement, motivation, and learning outcomes. By incorporating elements such as points, badges, leaderboards, levels, and changes, educators aim to make learning more attractive, enjoyable, and immersive for students. Gamification leverages the inherent motivational aspects of games to stimulate interest and foster intrinsic motivation learners

Sample and information

Gamification encompasses various strategies, including

1. Points and Rewards System: Students earn points or rewards for completing tasks, achieving milestones, or demonstrating progress. These rewards can serve as extrinsic motivators to encourage participation and effort.
2. Badges

and Achievements: Badges are virtual representations of accomplishments or skills attained by learners. They provide a sense of achievement and recognition, motivating students to strive for mastery in specific areas.

3. Leaderboards and Competition: Leaderboards display ranking based on performance, fostering a sense of competition among students. Competitive elements can drive engagement and encourage students to excel.

4. Quests and Challenges: Quests present students with mission or challenges to complete, often within a narrative framework. These quests provide a sense of purpose and adventure, making learning more compelling and meaningful.

Motivation in Language Learning Engagement and motivation play crucial roles in language learning, influencing learners' persistence, effort, and ultimately, their proficiency in the target language. Engaged and motivated learners are more likely to actively participate in language activities, seek out opportunities for practice, and persist in the face of challenges. Effective language instruction should aim to cultivate and sustain learners' engagement and motivation throughout the learning process. Sample information:

Engagement in language learning can be fostered through:

A) Meaningful Contexts: Providing authentic and relevant contexts for language use, such as real-life scenarios, cultural experiences, and authentic materials, enhances learners' engagement by connecting language learning to their interest and experiences.

B) Interactive Activities: Incorporating interactive and communicative language activities, such as role-plays, discussions, and collaborative projects, promotes active engagement and fosters interpersonal connections among learners. **C) Personalization:** Tailoring language learning experiences to learners' interests, goals, and learning styles increases their sense of ownership and investment in the learning process, leading to higher levels of engagement and motivation.

D) Feedback and Support: Providing timely and constructive feedback, as well as scaffolding and support, helps learners gauge their progress, identify areas for improvement, and stay motivated to achieve their language learning goals. **Listening Comprehension in Language**

Acquisition: Listening comprehension is a fundamental skill in language acquisition, allowing learners to understand spoken language input and extract meaning from oral texts. Proficient listening skills are essential for communication, language proficiency, and academic success. Effective listening instruction focuses on developing learners' ability to comprehend spoken language in various contexts, accents, and speech rates.

Sample information:

Strategies for improving listening comprehension include:

Pre-listening Activities: Engaging learners in pre-listening activities, such as activating background knowledge, predicting content, and setting purposes for listening, prepares them to better comprehend the spoken text and enhances their listening comprehension skills.

Active Listening Techniques: Teaching learners active listening techniques, such as identifying key information, making inferences, summarizing main ideas, and monitoring comprehension, helps them become more strategic and efficient listeners.

Authentic Listening Materials: Exposing learners to authentic listening materials, such as podcasts, news broadcasts, interviews, and conversations, provides opportunities for exposure to natural language input and develops their ability to understand real-world communication.

Post-listening Activities: Engaging learners in post-listening activities, such as comprehension checks, discussions, reflection, and follow-up tasks, reinforces understanding, promotes deeper processing of the content, and

facilitates language acquisition

II. Impact of Gamification on Engagement

Gamification has emerged as a powerful tool for enhancing engagement in educational settings by leveraging game elements to motivate learners and increase their participation and commitment to learning activities. Research suggests that gamified approaches can significantly impact engagement levels by tapping into intrinsic motivation, fostering a sense of autonomy and competence, and creating a supportive and enjoyable learning environment.

Sample information:

Intrinsic Motivation: Gamification taps into learners' intrinsic motivation by providing them with opportunities for autonomy, mastery, and purpose. When learners perceive activities as enjoyable, meaningful, and personally relevant, they are more likely to engage in them voluntarily and persist in the face of challenges (Deci & Ryan, 1985).

Sense of Achievement: Gamification fosters a sense of achievement and progress through mechanisms such as points, badges, and levels. As learners accomplish tasks, achieve milestones, and earn rewards, they experience a sense of accomplishment and fulfillment, which motivates them to continue participating in learning activities (Kapp, 2012).

Social Interaction: Gamification promotes social interaction and collaboration among learners by incorporating elements such as leaderboards, challenges, and multiplayer games. By creating opportunities for competition, cooperation, and peer support, gamified approaches enhance engagement through social dynamics and interpersonal connections (Deterding et al., 2011).

Immersive Experiences: Gamification creates immersive and interactive learning experiences that capture learners' attention and imagination. By incorporating

narrative elements, meaningful contexts, and multimedia content, gamified activities stimulate curiosity, creativity, and exploration, leading to deeper engagement and absorption of learning content (Gee, 2003)

Influence of Gamification on Learning Outcomes

Gamification has been shown to have a significant impact on learning outcomes across various educational contexts. By integrating game elements and principles into learning activities, gamified approaches can enhance students' motivation, engagement, and overall academic achievement. Research indicates that gamification positively influences learning outcomes by promoting active participation, fostering skill development, and providing immediate feedback and reinforcement.

Active Participation: Gamification encourages active participation in learning activities by providing incentives, rewards, and challenges that motivate students to engage with course material. Through gamified elements such as points, badges, and leaderboards, students are incentivized to complete tasks, solve problems, and collaborate with peers, leading to increased involvement and investment in the learning process (Hamari et al., 2016).

Skill Development: Gamification facilitates skill development by creating opportunities for practice, experimentation, and mastery. By incorporating game mechanics such as leveling up, progression tracking, and skill trees, gamified activities enable students to set goals, monitor their progress, and gradually build proficiency in targeted areas (Landers & Landers, 2014).

Immediate Feedback: Gamification provides immediate feedback and reinforcement, which are essential for promoting learning and retention. Through mechanisms such as scoring systems, achievement unlocks, and real-time feedback, students receive timely information about their performance, allowing them to adjust their strategies, correct errors, and improve their understanding of concepts (Garris et al., 2002).

Motivation and Persistence: Gamification enhances students' motivation

and persistence by making learning more enjoyable, challenging, and rewarding. By tapping into intrinsic motivators such as autonomy, competence, and relatedness, gamified approaches sustain students' interest and enthusiasm for learning, encouraging them to overcome obstacles and persist in their efforts to achieve academic goals (Ryan & Deci, 2000).

Overall, gamification holds promise as a pedagogical tool for improving learning outcomes by enhancing students' engagement, motivation, and skill acquisition. However, effective implementation requires careful consideration of instructional design principles, student preferences, and learning objectives to ensure that gamified activities align with curricular goals and foster meaningful learning experiences.

Conclusion

This thesis underscores the significance of gamification as a viable approach for enhancing engagement and learning outcomes in listening activities within language acquisition contexts. Through an exploration of theoretical frameworks and empirical evidence, the study highlights the potential of gamified interventions to motivate learners, improve listening skills, and create immersive language learning experiences. By identifying effective strategies and addressing challenges, educators and curriculum designers can leverage gamification to optimize language acquisition processes and cultivate a dynamic and interactive learning environment. Moving forward, continued research and experimentation are essential to further refine gamification techniques and unlock their full potential in language education.

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DEVELOPING EDUCATION IN RURAL AREAS OF UZBEKISTAN: PROBLEMS AND SOLUTIONS

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Abstract. The quality of education is a concern of primary importance that almost many nations address sources and investments to gain long term benefits for citizens and government. This paper will examine the existing issues in education system of Uzbekistan, particularly in rural areas among English language teachers and suggest some solutions.

Key words. Education, rural areas, problems, investments, ESL teaching.

Introduction. The remote areas of Uzbekistan, particularly in villages where there is interrupted supply of heating together with electricity in winter makes it harder for school teachers and students focus on studies. In times of cold weather, the attendance to classes falls dramatically, the reason is clear – no facilities are available to teach at school. Since no one intends to get sick or cold. Lack of

resources is another problem to name. Children have to assist their families to maintain family budget, which it discourages the desire to learn. There are numerous shortages of resources, only textbooks can be found, other supplemental books are not available at all. Teachers lack qualifications and expertise in their fields, it can be observed among English language teachers. There is financial support to recognize the achievements of teachers; however, it seems to have little effect on teacher's performance.

Analysis. Regarding the governmental aid, the first initiative to support the expertise of ESL teachers has been presidential decree [1875](#) and a second governmental financial rewards initiated by presidential decree [134](#) for ESL instructors who possess C1 level or higher are given monthly perk as a recognition of efforts made by teachers according to [daryo.uz](#). On the other hand, this support seems to be sufficient to recognize the expertise the teachers hold, and ESL teachers still lack some expertise. Consequently, students they teach will only have a superficial understanding about the subject being taught. It can be observed that the rate of poverty in the country is 17% according to reports by [spot.uz](#) and the percentage of official unemployment is almost 9% based on official report of [uza.uz](#). Unfortunately, the school leavers are neither college, nor job ready prompting the impediment of progress. As a result, there are many labor-migrant who flock into Russian Federation to make a living, based on reports [kun.uz](#), the number of Uzbek citizens was 2.5 million in 2023. This figure grew fourfold over the last 5 years. There are Uzbeks who are labor-migrants to Turkey and Kazakhstan, while the official statistics show by 2022, the number of Uzbek workers increased by over 7%. The job migrants are usually employed in blue collar jobs where there is no specific qualification required, it is absolutely necessary to make some transformation in schooling system that will change the lives of ordinary Uzbek citizens and minimize the number of labor-migrants to other nations.

Discussion. The government is investing on improving the monthly salary of teachers, during the inauguration of presidential selections, the president informed about the intention to raise salary, according to reports by xabar.uz, the income of teachers was projected to reach 1000 US dollars by 2025. However, this figure in practice does not seem to be convincing (Personally, I was employed in a public school full-time, my salary was roughly 400 US dollars.)

Lack of employment opportunities and unhealthy competition in recruitment can be observed in almost all levels of educational establishments, it is exacerbated by little job prospects in the countryside, the only professions who are normally employed are teachers and medical practitioners along with professions who possess the qualifications. Unfortunately, the transparency is still remaining an issue in this regard. Another factor that has an immense impact that is making the current situation from bad to worse, particularly the truancy at schools is a large-scale concern, especially in grades from 10 to 11. This age is critical since student will have to receive vital knowledge and skills that are important to have a career progression. After employment, the hired teachers normally do not update or seek opportunities to increase their qualifications to meet the demands of employer, let alone the global requirements.

Solutions. These abovementioned issues contribute to further deterioration of education quality where students have low level of qualification with hardly any intention to learn. Nevertheless, the individuals, who intend to access to a high quality of education, are to search for alternative options outside their schools. Thus, the growing demand to learn English has triggered a common trend in language centers. The language market now has many students at the expense of school students. In Bukhara city alone, there are over 50 language centers and this number is expected to grow further. Attendance to schools is low among high school students and during this time, the students are enrolled into courses instead of showing presence at schools. For example, the language centers in Bukhara city like: Millennium IELTS school, Genius, Stanford, Oxford IELTS center,

Pedestal, Progress, Akmal Ikhtiyarov's IELTS school, Study Academy, Leader, Level up and many others, its students attend to English courses instead of going to schools.

Schools in Uzbekistan have English lessons only three times a week, the duration of class is 45 minutes. The school curriculum in Uzbekistan contains an overwhelming number of subjects included in its curriculum, creating a huge burden on students. The grade 9 for example has 16 academic subjects, affecting to the quality of education immensely by Gazeta.uz.

Conclusion. In conclusion, the frequency of vital classes has to be increased, for example the number of English language classes has to be raised from 3 to 6, reducing the less important subjects to create more opportunity for students to meet their needs.

Second, the school libraries have to be equipped with books and publications released from other countries that will be a supplemental material, the highly qualified teachers have to be recruited in schools to prevent the less qualified teachers to occupy the vacancies in educational establishments. Second, the teacher portfolio has to be updated and teachers have to be provided with some guidance to practice it and implement these methods in their classes. The number of school subjects have to be shrunk (According to Gazeta.uz the number of subjects is predicted to decrease from 16 to 11, it is still a large number for a child to learn 11 subjects at school.) to create more room for other subjects that will serve for further development of a child, making him or her more competent in the global markets and qualify them into world class universities with top rankings.

The government has to focus on quality rather than the number, since the high quality of school graduates are a huge asset for further economic prosperity of government.

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PEER ASSESSMENT ACTIVITIES IN THE LEARNER-CENTERED CLASSES

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Abstract. Peer assessment activities in learner-centered classes play an important role in enhancing students' learning experiences as students are involved in process of evaluating and providing feedback to their fellow students. This article aims to give a short review of the forms and utilization of peer assessment activities in the English as a foreign language learning classes in the high school. The article on peer assessment activities in learner-centered English as a foreign language learning classes highlights the impact of peer feedback on student learning outcomes and the development of critical evaluation skills.

Key words: *English learning, English teaching, learner-centered classes, learner-centered classroom, assessment, self assessment, peer assessment, collaborative learning, critical thinking, self-regulation.*

Introduction. Despite the fact that peer assessment activities are not part of the school curriculum, but still it is possible to outline their important role in

enhancing student learning outcomes, particularly in learner-centered classrooms. In the context of high school English language classrooms, various peer assessment activities are employed to foster collaborative learning, critical thinking, and self-regulation among students. Engaging in these activities not only improves particular language abilities but also fosters crucial competencies like communication, teamwork, and accountability in students. This approach fosters a more efficient way for students to complete tasks, increases their enthusiasm for learning, and helps shape their self-esteem positively. Additionally, learner-centered classes cater to the diverse learning needs of students, making the learning process more inclusive and effective for all individuals in the classroom.

Peer assessment activities in high school.

The most common peer assessment activities [4,5] that are implemented in English language classrooms in our school are:

- *Peer editing*. Students exchange essays with peers to provide feedback on content, structure, grammar, and style. This activity enhances writing skills and encourages students to revise and improve their work based on peer suggestions. This activity helps students develop attention to detail and editing skills.

- *Peer Evaluation*. Students assess their peers' oral presentations based on criteria such as clarity, organization, delivery and content. This activity enhances public speaking skill and encourages students to provide constructive feedback. Students evaluate projects or collaborative assignments, assessing individual contributions, teamwork, creativity, and adherence to project guidelines. This activity promotes accountability and teamwork skills.

- *Peer Feedback*. Students participate in small groups (Peer response groups) to discuss, critique, analyze and provide feedback on each other's work, such as drafts of essays, speeches or creative writing pieces. This activity encourages peer collaboration, critical thinking and revision.

- *Peer Assessment of Language Skills*. Students pair up to practice language skills, such as speaking, listening and pronunciation, and provide feedback to each

other on language usage and fluency. This activity enhances language proficiency and communication abilities. Students work together to review grammar exercises, quizzes, or language tasks, providing explanations and corrections to help each other improve their grammar skills. This activity reinforces grammar rules and fosters peer learning.

- *Peer Reflection*. Students participate in feedback sessions like feedback roundtables where they reflect on their learning, challenges, achievements and goals. This activity encourages self-assessment, goal setting and continuous learning.

Benefits of peer assessment activities

The benefits of peer assessment in learner-centered classes have been extensively studied in academic literature. Peer assessment promotes learner autonomy by reducing dependence on teachers and increasing students' confidence in their learning abilities [3]. It also fosters metacognitive awareness, self-reflection, and accountability for learning, which are crucial aspects of successful language learning [1]. Additionally, peer assessment encourages active student participation in the assessment process, shifting the focus from teachers to individual students, thus enriching the learning experience [1].

Peer assessment not only benefits the assessed students but also contributes to the development of critical evaluation skills in the assessors, creating a mutually beneficial learning environment [4]. Thanks to the teacher evaluation process, students gain awareness of how teachers assess their performance, leading to a reduction in misunderstandings and disagreements regarding grades.

It is important to point out that to achieve positive outcomes the assessment criteria should be well-designed [5]. That can avoid misunderstandings between students and teachers.

Results of peer assessment activities in English classes

The analysis of the EGE (Unified State Exam in Russia) demonstrates the effectiveness of peer assessment activities in enhancing learning outcomes. The

focus of this study is on evaluating student performance in a writing assignment, specifically Task 37, which involves composing a personal email. This task is assessed based on three main criteria: "The communicative task", "The organization of the text" and "The language design" as outlined in the Table of Accessing Criteria of the EGE (Unified State Exam) [6].

Initially, 10th-grade students were introduced to the task in September and provided guidance on what constitutes a personal email and how to meet the evaluation criteria. Notably, 3 out of 17 students failed to meet the communicative task criterion.

Subsequently, peer assessment activities were implemented, including peer evaluation and editing. Through engaging in discussions and analyzing each other's work, students participated in peer review sessions. This process allowed students to receive feedback, reflect on it, and enhance their work based on the suggestions provided. The results are shown in graph 1.

Graphs 1. The amount of student succeeded in criteria "The communicative task".

According to the Accessing Criteria of the EGE (Unified State Exam) 17 students succeeded in criteria "The communicative task".

Table 1. **The amount of errors made by students before and after implementing Peer Assessment Activities**

Criteria	September assignment, 2023	April assignment, 2024
The organization of the test	51	42
The language design:		
Grammar	25	21
Vocabulary	10	4
Spelling	6	10
Punctuation	17	14

In Table 1, it is evident that the errors related to the criterion 'The organization of the test' decreased by 17.64%. Similarly, the total errors under the criterion 'The language design' decreased by 15.52%, even though there was an increase in spelling errors. This observation is now set for analysis by the peer response group in the class.

The results of peer assessment activities, as demonstrated in the analysis of the Unified State Exam in Russia, indicate a positive impact on student performance and learning outcomes.

Overall, the utilization of peer assessment activities in this context not only facilitated a deeper understanding of the evaluation criteria but also enabled students to actively engage in improving their writing skills through collaborative learning and feedback mechanisms.

Conclusion. By incorporating these peer assessment activities into learner-centered classes in English language classroom, teachers can create a dynamic and interactive learning environment that promotes student engagement, collaboration, critical thinking and self-directed learning in learner-centered

English language classrooms. As this method gradually integrates into the school system, its transformative impact on student learning outcomes and the development of essential skills cannot be overlooked. Properly designed assessment criteria are essential to ensure the success and effectiveness of peer assessment activities, ultimately enriching the learning experience for all students involved.

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UNLOCKING ENGLISH FLUENCY: THE POWER OF EXPERIENTIAL LEARNING

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Abstract

This presentation explores the benefits and methodologies of experiential learning in teaching English as a Second Language (ESL). Experiential learning, characterized by learning through doing, provides a practical and engaging approach to language acquisition. Unlike traditional rote learning, which emphasizes memorization, experiential learning involves students in direct experiences that are conducive to language immersion. This presentation is a reflection of my teaching experience in applying English in meaningful contexts.

The presentation addresses certain obstacles in acquiring English as a second language in the 21st century and critically analyzes whether they are valid. The presentation includes real life experiences which led to my realization about the importance of experiential learning. The paper suggests certain methods to create an experiential atmosphere in our classrooms. The paper includes three methods that I am attempting to implement in my school.

In conclusion, experiential learning offers a comprehensive and effective approach to ESL education. By involving students in interactive experiences, educators can facilitate a deeper understanding and appreciation of the English language, thereby preparing learners for successful communication in diverse settings.

ASSESSMENT AS A SEMANTIC CATEGORY

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Abstract. The concept of linguistic evaluation was undoubtedly created based on logical evaluation theories. Evaluation is the main condition of object content creation in linguistic thinking. The structure of the assessment consists of 4 main cases: subject, object, feature and basis. In this, of course, the main attention is paid to the linguistic aspect, and not to the logical aspect of the assessment. It is necessary to note that the linguistic theory of evaluation based on logical theory has been developed. Value relationships, its existence in objective existence, its appearance in the human mind as a concept, its types, criteria are the object of research of philosophers and logicians as an axiological problem, and its manifestation in language, phonetic, lexical, morphological, syntactic, paralinguistic tools expressing value such issues as semantics are studied by linguists.

Key words: assessment, internal, external, positive assessment, negative assessment, implicit, explicit.

The content of the concept of "evaluation" is primarily related to the concept of the subjective side of the language sign. The ideas about the overlapping of objectivity and subjectivity in language were expressed in the

works of V. Humboldt and A. A. Potebnya. The opinions of representatives of modern linguistics about value relations were expressed in the works of scientists engaged in the study of semantic problems, such as N.D. Arutyunova, Ye.M.Wolff, A.A.Ivin.

On the one hand, the value relation is linguistically expressed in semantics, on the other hand, it shows the content at different language levels. In this regard, R. Kongurov writes: "Positive or negative attitude is expressed using different forms (morphological), words (lexical), constructions (syntactic), combination of form and word (lexical-morphological), intonation (phonetics). Since language is a possibility given only to humans, the phenomena in it have specific functions. These functions transmit and receive information through linguistic symbols. Since the meaning of evaluation expresses the sign and attitude of an object or action, in most cases adjectives and idioms are words that carry the meaning of evaluation: beautiful-ugly, good-bad.

In the language, the signs of "evaluation" are: "emotionality as a relation of good/bad signs and "emotionality/rationality", "affectiveness". Generic evaluative determiners "good" and "bad" operators can depend on any object or reality. Thus, there are also adjectives that are evaluative in their semantic structure, for example, introducing the general evaluation "good/bad" scheme. This type includes expressive adjectives: good, beautiful, excellent - positive evaluation (sema "good" + strengthening) or unpleasant, disgusting, scary (sema "bad" + strengthening). In the positive sense, "good" means such adjectives as "important". It is very easy to identify "good/bad" grading schemes in these qualities.

It is known that the subject of assessment (explicit or implicit) is a person or society, and the assessment is given from his point of view. The object of assessment is a person or object, situation or event, about which the assessment is made. "The peculiarity of the assessment is that it always contains subjective

factors that interact with the objective factor. Evaluative judgments, although the subject of evaluation is not directly expressed in it, consider the value relationship between the subject of the opinion (the person giving the evaluation) and its object (the object or event to which the evaluation belongs). E.M. Wolff: "Evaluation, language has a whole layer of values. Emphasizing that the diversity of evaluation semantics begins with qualities and attitudes, he assumes that the evaluation structure is implicit and explicit.

In our study, we rely on the axiological operators of "ugly/unpleasant" which are important in the image space reflecting the national value in the analysis of the category of aesthetic value. The evaluated objects are usually approached from the point of view of the needs and interests of the entity evaluating them, naturally, in such cases, the attitude towards the evaluated object can be positive/negative or neutral. The relationship between the subject and the object of assessment is combined with social relations, and at its core human needs and interests specific to the daily lifestyle of society members are embodied. Satisfying these needs and interests and its result is positive/negative value.

According to N.D.Arutyunova, it is appropriate to understand evaluation as a semantic sign reflecting the positive/negative or neutral attitude of the evaluation subject to the subject.⁵⁴ After all, the assessment is part of the denotative-significant meaning of the word and classifies the real sign of the object as a positive and negative sign from the point of view of a certain collective. This sign, like other signs of the subject, settles in the semantic structure of the lexeme, creates overlap with them, and becomes an object value in the nominative system of the language, which is ready to ensure the actualization of speech. Usually, people voluntarily/involuntarily rate a certain unit as good/bad based on their lifestyle, national mentality, worldview and level; sometimes the customs of other nations seem unusual. Naturally, when this situation is the other way around,

⁵⁴ Арутюнова Н.Д. Об объекте общей оценки.// Вопросы языкознания. – М.:1985.– №3 – С.13.

their good or bad evaluations do not correspond to the national norms of the subject who has become an object.

Emotional assessment is based on an evaluative attitude towards the object. Emotional assessment is conditioned by the universal psychological law, objective for a particular society, related to the landscape of the world, emotionality is part of the connotative meaning of the word in the form of a semantic sign. The internal form of the word serves as the foundation of the semantic sign. The division of evaluation into rational and emotional categories is done primarily in relation to the structural element of the subject of evaluation, because evaluation depends more on the speaking subject than on other meanings.⁵⁵ The logic of research leads to the problems of semantics, syntax, pragmatics of evaluative words, their function in the text, their communicative properties and their use in everyday speech. From the wide field of the concept of "valuation", we are interested in the expression of aesthetic value in language, that is, the possibility of recording one or another value in an object based on the concepts of ugliness.

In the separate philosophical definitions of aesthetics and ethics, it is distinguished that aesthetics refers to the pleasure derived from external criteria, while ethics refers to the evaluation of internal (moral) qualities. "In general, the assessment expresses good/bad oppositions, while the aesthetic assessment expresses the oppositions of aesthetically good (beautiful) and aesthetically bad (ugly). Among the main components of aesthetic evaluation are the general features of the evaluation situation, such as the subject, the object, the basis of evaluation, and the evaluation itself. The attitude of the subject to the object during the assessment is expressed by means of the criterion/norm. The subject-object-normative relationship adequately expresses the nature of aesthetic

⁵⁵ Қўнғуров Р. Субъектив баҳо формаларининг семантик ва стилистик хусусиятлари. – Т.: Фан, 1980. – Б. 42.

evaluation, since the desired object is evaluated by the subject on the basis of its conformity or non-conformity with specific perceptions of the norm.

In accordance with the main concepts that reveal the nature of evaluation, aesthetic evaluation is seen as a component of the semantic category of evaluation, and is compatible with it in part and as a whole. Along with the general characteristics, the category of aesthetic assessment has a number of specific characteristics that distinguish it from other types of assessment. So, ugliness is divided into an external appearance, and an ethical state is divided into an internal educational state. Of course, this opinion is valid. However, real aesthetics is interpreted by different scientists as the balance of form and meaning. According to our observations, the internal state of the object may not be required if it is inanimate. But when we say human beauty, first of all, it refers to internal and external, i.e., the balance and harmony of meaning and content.

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A SYSTEM OF DIFFERENT EXERCISES IN TEACHING ENGLISH LESSONS

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Abstract. The article discusses the importance of organizing training sessions through games. In particular, in the creation of technological games in English lessons, it is necessary to pay attention to the fact that it arouses interest in students, meets their learning needs, and is quickly accepted by the listener.

The author emphasizes every teacher should have choice when using games, talking into account the abilities, interests, level of knowledge and aspirations of their students. There are also games that can be used to practice, listen to, speak, teach and develop language materials. Lexical, grammatical, phonetic, spelling, etc.

Key words: Topic, learning games, lesson, process, level of knowledge, preparation, experience, practice, language materials, pictures.

Introduction. Today, games have become a tradition in schools. It is known that lessons based on various games help students to demonstrate their abilities, focus, increase their knowledge and skills, and become stronger. The recognition of games as one of the most effective methods of new pedagogical technologies is also a proof of our opinion. The basis of the use of game technology is an activity that activates and accelerates students. According to psychologists, the psychological mechanisms of playful activity are based on the fundamental needs of the individual to express himself, to find a stable place in life, to self-manage, to realize their potential.

The focus of all games is often accepted from the principles of education and tactics. Learning games should be based on the subject. Learning game

documents must be suitable for the curriculum of the class and the contents of the class textbook. In the game, students are more interested in this activity than normal and comfortable lessons.

Methods. First, it should be noted that the game is an educational method. Students believe they can play, speak, hear, understand, and write in English. Experience shows that all games belong to a troublesome position, regardless of the level and age of the participants. Therefore, you need to solve the following educational and psychological issues before games are applied to educational practice. Each student needs to know: -for the purpose of the game. Game mission; -Game topics belong to all planning. -You can apply techniques and abilities that can be formed not only in the next game but also in previous games. Students need to create technical games for students so that students are interested in students, satisfy their demands, and quickly absorb their demands. When using a game, all teachers can choose. In other words, he is his student. You can choose a game according to your ability, interest, knowledge and desire. The game is used to develop language skills, listen, speak and read. Vocabulary, grammar, pronunciation and spelling games are used to activate the use of language documents. Vocabulary games are new and new. This word helps to remember faster. Grammar games are organized to teach and develop important grammar structures. Such games often have the right to own, hold, hold, hold, hold, hold, hold, express and own their own. Games are often a form of competition. The voice game plays an important role in developing pronunciation and words of students' words. It is used for teeth to learn how to use orders, letters and characters in order games. The proposed games below can be used by teachers in both vocabulary, grammar, audio and spelling style. This game is called "mysterious box". The class is divided into three groups to play games. Leaders are appointed to each group and leaders are responsible for protecting group members. There are three boxes on the table. Each box has a document and a game image. Students take cards

and images and complete the exercise. When the "mysterious box" is maintained in the vocabulary game mode, an image associated with the insurance topic is placed in the box.

Dicussion. Students take pictures in the box and specify the name of the object in the picture. Example: A: This is a dog.

B: This is a rabbit.

When the game is played as a grammar game, a sentence is formed by participating in the box.

Example: A: I have cat

B: My cat is small.

When the game plays the voice, the card has a letter or letter in the box. Students must start with the letters obtained from the box and find a word that is correctly pronounced. For example:

C-Cool [ku:l]

S-SNAKE [SNEIK]

I-LAKE [leak]

B-BLUE [blu:]

In English classes in elementary school, questions such as "What is the alphabet", the order of placement of letters, the formation of words from letters can be used "Moon and stars" method. compose words using the sequence numbers located.

For example: The 2nd letter "B" in the 2nd alphabet Students say words that start with that letter.

The game is played in the spelling game mode. Students must spell the beginning of the word without error in the letter of the card taken from the box. Example:

F-father

Ch-chees

H-hnistory

M-Mother.

Through mysterious box games, students' gaps are full of knowledge and the topics mentioned are improved. This game helps students increase their daughter's winter to increase their daughter's winter. With my experience, I can use the interactive method in each class to achieve achievement effects. Introducing English classes in the first grade from the beginning of the new semester is a strong responsibility for US educators. All teachers have to work hard. Different games related to exercises and topics described in textbooks are very interesting in age. However, teachers can use new games in students based on learning about learning, interests and of course their teaching classes. For example, there is a game related to color with the theme "Breeding". But there is no game related to the "part of the body" topic. Next is "Who are you?" We want to bring a game of your interest. In this game we use the phrase "Ive Got ...". The rest of the students listen to and talk about an animal.

For example,

Lola: Ive has 4 feet. I have a big ear. I have a small eye. I have a big nose and a big mouth. Run and dance.

Who i am?

Bobur: You are horse

Laura: No,I'm not

Asadake: You are a donkey.

Laura: Yes, I'm me.

Komil: There are two legs. I had a little eye. I have a big mouth. Dance to fly and swim and run.

Who am I?

Munis: You are male chickens

Komil: No,I'm not

Zafar:you're a duck.

Kamol:yes, I'm

This game can also be used on the "wild animals" theme. Now you can use the game for fruits and vegetables. This game "I like ... or" My favorite fruits (or vegetables) ". It is great to organize the game, students must be divided into 2 or 3 groups. I need. Fruit and vegetable classes in different locations. For example in a window of the window, on a shelf, next to it, write on the board, next to the door, under the midwives and so on. The first group of students is selected and says the name of their favorite fruit or her vegetables. The remaining two group of the group is also selected, writes with a basket in his hands to the board and listens to the student of the first group. His favorite collecting fruit or vegetables from different parts of the classroom in baskets. This game requires mobility. Anyone who will call the fruits first or when he can collect vegetables in a basket is recommended. The game is like that.

For example:

Laylo: I like apples, oranges, apricots, plums...

Bahora:I like cucumbers, tomatoes, carrots...

Result. Through this game, the Students of the lexical vocabulary, the understanding of listening and understanding and the ability to move improved. Students are interested in learning the language even more.

Conclusion. In summary, through the organization of such fun games, we not only develop the knowledge and skills of the students, but also demonstrate that the requirements of the "Sacred Lessing" program are completely implemented in practice.

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**EFFECTIVE WAYS OF ORGANIZING LEARNER CENTERED
CLASSES IN ENGLISH LANGUAGE CLASSROOM**

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Abstract

The thesis focuses mainly on creating the atmosphere for educators, researchers, and masters of certain domains where they can have discussions and exchange ideas. It serves to find solutions to the significant missions.

Key words: linguistics, international communications, translation, interpretation, literature, comparative literature, modern approaches of teaching English, setting up translation schools, development of innovations.

Introduction

This thesis will explore effective ways of organizing learner-centered classes in the English language classroom, focusing on strategies such as student-centered activities, personalized learning, differentiated instruction, and the use of technology to create a dynamic and inclusive learning environment. By examining the advantages and difficulties of learner-centered teaching practices, this study aims to provide important insights for educators looking for to enhance student learning outputs in the English language classroom.

Main body

A learner-centered method considers students as an active agent. They bring their own knowledge, past experiences, education, and ideas – and this influences how they come up with new information and learn. It is different from our cliché TCT (teacher-centered teaching). Traditional learning approaches were informed by behaviorism, which accounts instructors as experts who must convey all the relevant information. This approach sees learners as respondents to external stimuli. While in TCT students should work on themselves more, being rather independent from teacher. Instructor should conduct a class for a fourth of the given time, and ought to ask what students have learnt for the rest of the time.

Each learning method has its own way of thought, but one point seems to come across again and again: the more engaged employees are in the learning process, the more they will retain when they get back to work. Student-centered teaching is a way to learning where the learner is at the center of the educational process. It involves active performance, willingness, and involvement of students in the classroom, permitting them to choose what to study, how to study, and why to

study. In this approach, teachers and instructors act as facilitators and guides by encouraging students in improving their skills and comprehension. The emphasis is on learner responsibility and activity, rather than instructor control and resource. Student-centered approach is implemented in various educational settings, including music, arts, education, technology, theoretical subjects, and others. It focuses mainly on the need for a shift in focus from the teacher to the learner, guiding to various alternatives in layout of curricula, course content, and the learning process itself. The aim is to provide students with more opportunities to investigate and develop their skills them for the difficulties of the future. It can help them be independent thereby preparing students to study in different parts of the world without difficulties.

The best practices for improving a learner-centered classroom contain to know more about individual students, building a positive and supportive atmosphere, providing personalized and authentic learning experiences, facilitating collaboration and independent learning, and using technology to support learner-centered pedagogy. In a learner-centered classroom, the focus is on the student as a learner and improving their learning and success. Teachers can foster their teaching methods and promote better learning outputs by teaching models that are based on specific educational philosophies and theories. In a flipped classroom, both the roles of the teacher and learners are changed, allowing for more active student participation and motivation. Learner-centered method can be informed by theoretical perspectives such as constructivism, humanism, and transformational studying. nevertheless, implementing learner-centered education can be perplexing due to the current education system's emphasis on sorting rather than learning. Implementing learner-centered approaches in English language classrooms is crucial for enhancing student engagement, motivation, and language learning and acquisition.

In the last few generations, there has been a growing emphasis on the learner-centered approaches in education, particularly in language teaching, in the field of English language teaching. Learner-centered classrooms prioritizes the needs, interests, and abilities of students, aiming to create an energetic and all-inclusive learning environment that enhances student engagement, motivation, and language acquisition. This thesis will explore effective ways of organizing learner-centered classes in the English language classroom, focusing on strategies such as student-centered activities, personalized learning, differentiated instruction, and the use of technology. By examining the benefits and challenges of learner-centered teaching practices, this study aims to provide valuable insights for educators seeking to optimize student learning outcomes.

While learner-centered approaches offer numerous benefits, they also present challenges for educators. One common challenge is the need for additional time and resources to plan and implement student-centered activities effectively. Educators may also face resistance from students who are accustomed to more traditional forms of instruction. Furthermore, evaluating student progress and giving feedback in a learner-centered classroom can be more complicated than in a teacher-centered classroom.

Conclusion

In conclusion, establishing learner-centered classes in the English language classroom requires careful layout, creativity, and eligibility on the educator's part. By establishment of student-centered activities, personalized learning, differentiated instruction, and the use of technology, educators can create more interesting classes which can be a strong spur for students to look forward to achieving high results. While there are challenges linked with learner-centered methods, the benefits far outweigh the drawbacks. By prioritizing the needs and interests of students, educators can enable learners to be owner of their learning and achieve success in the English language classroom.

**SELF-DIRECTED LEARNING: EMPOWERING YOURSELF
THROUGH AUTONOMY**

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Think back to the most recent case when your intense enthusiasm led you to embark on a journey of acquiring new knowledge or skills. Perhaps you were fueled by a pressing necessity or a personal aspiration to accomplish a task independently.

Let's say you experienced cooking with new recipes, watched cooking shows, read culinary cookbooks to enhance your culinary skills.

Maybe you tried to learn a new language on your own through online resources, language apps, textbooks, and language exchange programs.

Within a short span of hours or a couple of weeks, you successfully grasped the subject matter predominantly through your own efforts. All these examples illustrate self- learning.

What is autonomous learning?

Autonomy is the capability to manage one's own learning, whether alone or in collaboration with others. Autonomous learning is a substantial asset that can elevate you to new levels, both in personal and professional life. Implementing effective autonomous learning strategies is crucial for achieving autonomous learning objectives and nurturing students' capacity and drive for independent learning. As well as self-directed learning maintain a mindset that enables people

to seize control of their education, embrace change, and pursue their interests with confidence.

The World Health Organization (WHO) declared Covid-19 a pandemic on March 11, 2020. This global health crisis has disrupted Higher Education Institutions (HEIs), leading to the widespread closure of universities worldwide and necessitating a shift to remote online learning for students. The Covid-19 pandemic has significantly influenced the direction of education globally, emphasizing the shift towards autonomous learning as a prevailing trend during and after the pandemic. Students have undergone transformations in their learning patterns and daily routines. Similarly during the COVID-19 pandemic, autonomous learning became even more prevalent among pupils in Uzbekistan due to the shift towards remote and online learning. With schools closed and traditional classroom instruction disrupted, students had to adapt to new ways of learning independently. Many students in Uzbekistan had to rely on online resources, virtual classes, and self-study materials to continue their education during the pandemic. This forced them to take more control over their learning process and develop self-discipline and time management skills to stay on track with their studies. Teachers and educational institutions also played a crucial role in supporting autonomous learning during this time by providing guidance, resources, and feedback to students remotely. They encouraged students to take initiative, set goals, and engage in self-directed learning activities to enhance their understanding of the material. Moreover, the COVID-19 pandemic accelerated the adoption of autonomous learning among pupils in Uzbekistan as they had to navigate new challenges and adapt to a rapidly changing educational landscape. This experience have helped students become more independent, resilient, and adaptable learners, which has benefit them in their academic pursuits and beyond.

What are the benefits of autonomous learning?

- Enables to find out personal learning styles to perform given task better

Having a deep understanding of their learning styles, autonomous learners engage with learning more effectively. They can tailor their instructional methods to match the preferences and needs, fostering a more conducive learning environment. This personalized approach enhances their comprehension, retention, and motivation, ultimately leading to improved academic performance

2. Freedom to learn at a pace that suits them best

Selecting own study topics according to their preferred learning style and individual educational requirements gives them the power to take ownership of their academic progress in a manner that is most conducive to their personal learning goals.

3. Confidence flourishes

As students engage in autonomous learning, they embark on a transformative journey that nurtures their confidence, self-belief, and resilience. By embracing independence, taking ownership of their learning process, and pursuing knowledge with passion and curiosity, students not only expand their intellectual horizons but also cultivate a profound sense of confidence that empowers them to tackle challenges and seize opportunities with unwavering self-assurance.

4. Fosters well-being

By prioritizing their holistic development and creating a fulfilling educational experience that resonates with their individual needs, students can enhance their overall well-being and thrive both academically and personally.

5. Enhance problem-solving skills

Autonomous learning not only enhances learner engagement but also fosters the development of critical thinking and problem-solving abilities. By allowing learners to take control of their learning journey and prompting them to reflect on their achievements and objectives, they are challenged to utilize their problem-solving skills. This skill is essential for students in navigating various challenges effectively.

How to promote autonomous learning in education?

- Motivate learners to take risks

In traditional education system, errors are portrayed negatively. However, it is crucial to recognize that mistakes are a natural and expected aspect of both life and learning. To boost learners' self-assurance and empower them to steer their learning process, it is essential to reiterate that errors are a standard component of the educational process.

F. Be open to and accepting of students' thoughts, emotions, and actions. When students are given the autonomy to direct their own learning journey, it is important for educators to create a safe and non-judgmental space where students feel comfortable expressing themselves and exploring their interests.

- Encourage students' capacity for self-regulation

By fostering self-regulation skills in autonomous learning, students can become more independent, motivated, and successful learners.

Developing students' autonomous learning ability is crucial for promoting their overall development. It is essential to nurture students' capacity for self-directed learning during the educational process. By fostering autonomous learning skills, students can become more independent, motivated, and successful learners. This emphasis on self-regulation can lead to enhanced critical thinking, problem-solving, and decision-making skills. Educators play a vital role in guiding and

supporting students in developing their autonomous learning abilities, which can ultimately contribute to their academic success and personal growth.

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**ED LEARNING VS STUDENT-CENTRED
LEARNING.(PRESENTATION)**

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Allowing students to take charge of their own learning increases their **motivation and engagement** in everyday learning. They're encouraged to reflect and make decisions, leading to the **development of critical thinking and problem-solving skills**. Student-centered strategies create opportunities for students to **explore their own interests and think creatively**, inspiring more original and innovative ideas.

Students who **engage in their own learning**, and have ownership of the process, are more likely to retain information. They're empowered to develop **self-directed learning skills**, such as goal-setting, decision-making, and problem-solving. Most importantly, a student-centered classroom **fosters independence and autonomy** and prepares students for future academic and professional success.

A learner-centered approach views learners as active agents. They bring their own knowledge, past experiences, education, and ideas – and this impacts how they take on board new information and learn.

It differs significantly from a traditional instructor-centered approach. Traditional learning approaches were informed by behaviorism, which sees learners as ‘blank slates’ and instructors as experts who must impart all the relevant information. This approach sees learners as respondents to external stimuli.

University professor Martha Kennedy defined it as:

“...a classroom dynamic in which the students participate actively while the teacher might take a (seemingly) more passive role. It boils down to group work, one-on-one tutoring in the classroom between student and teacher, student presentations...To learn a skill, students must be directly involved. No teacher can stand there and tell the students how to do something and expect the students to leave the classroom able to do it.”

Learner-centered approach activities are following

1. Foster collaboration with group projects

Think of yourself as a coach on the sideline of a sports game. You’re offering advice and encouragement where necessary, rather than a lecturer delivering a monologue to learners.

2. Let learners develop content

Start your lesson with developing and sharing blogs or upload podcasts or videos for your learners and let them work individually or in groups to contribute to it. Let them know what topics should be covered and encourage them

to research them. Over time, this channel will become a valuable resource for everyone at the organization.

3. Stage presentations

Or, instead of using their research to create different types of media, ask your learners to develop presentations, which can be delivered in-person or via net. Not only does it help your learner learn the topic inside out, they also get a chance to develop another important workplace skill – presenting. Learn more on how to stage a demonstration or product demonstration.

4. Hold a competition

A little healthy competition can really spur motivation in a group. You can even let the group decide what the nature of the competition will be, and what the prize will be – or if it's just for pride.

5. Hold a debate

Split the group in three and give them a motion. One group argues for the motion, one argues against it, and the final group judges. All groups have to stay fully engaged with the topic until the end, and should come out of the debate thoroughly informed on the issue.

6. Gamify learning

Games are a great way to add an element of fun to the learning environment. This way has been a huge trend in online learning in recent years. Any good lesson will have gamification features such as leaderboards, badges, points, and more that will encourage learner participation.

7. Do role-play

This is perfect for Sales and Customer Service training. Divide the learners into pairs and let them take turns in the role of the customer. Again this can be done face-to-face. Letting them step into the shoes of your customers is likely to make them more empathetic when they're speaking to them.

8. Brainstorm

Twelve heads are better than one. Not all training techniques need to be hi-tech and fancy; just choose a topic you want your learners to know more about and ask them to volunteer what they already know. As a group, the chances are they know a great deal – and you can fill in any gaps as necessary.

It's an active approach to taking in new materials where learners are given a large degree of autonomy. And it's ideal for a corporate training environment where individuals are expected to be able to work both independently and in groups.

Student-centered learning doesn't mean a teacher free environment. In fact, the role of a teacher is more important than ever. It requires engagement from students that must be guided by the teacher for success. The focus becomes more about creating a positive and supportive classroom that allows students to take risks and ownership with their learning. Because it allows for more individualization, student-centered learning puts the learners' needs at the center of the process. It takes flexibility, conversations, and involvement. If that gives the impression of less structured learning, don't worry! There are many steps you can take to bring more student-centered learning opportunities into your classroom without losing structure.

1. Active participation

A goal for any teacher is to foster a love of learning. **If you want kids to become lifelong learners, involve them.** That's where student-centered learning comes in. When students have opportunities to make choices and contribute to

learning experiences, they gain a sense of partnership with their teacher and classmates. It can be as simple as starting with a K-W-L -Q chart (what do you *know*, what do you *want* to know, and what did you *learn*) or a brainstorming session. Allow for exploration through a variety of options, including writing, literature, or fine arts.

2. Differentiation

No two students are the same, and that's a wonderful thing. Celebrate this by personalizing the teaching and learning that happens in your classroom. Embrace and include distinct learning needs, interests, cultural backgrounds, and tailor-made goals for success. Student-centered environments bring individualized purpose, processes, and meaning to learning. Present information in multiple ways, such as infographics or technology.

3. Collaboration

Student-centered classrooms are based on collaboration. Constructive conversations between students should be encouraged. Collaborative projects provide opportunities to strengthen confidence in communication along with social and emotional skills. Show kids how to aim for cooperation, not competition, as they work together. Collaboration may sound noisier than independent practice, but it allows students to work together and support one another. Give them time to plan and talk while processing new information!

4. Questioning and experimentation

All questions are good questions! You may have to begin this process as a whole group to model questioning strategies. Start with knowledge based questions and move into analysis. Provide plenty of "think time" as you encourage students to dig deeper with their own questions. Challenge them to experiment with possible solutions. **Questioning and experimentation make learning an active process instead of a spectator sport.**

5. Stations

These aren't just for younger students. Stations offer spaces for all ages to participate in student-centered learning. Because stations let students try out different experiences, learning is not passive! Students are motivated and interested because each station taps into a new skill or fresh information. Get those kiddos out of their seats and move them to stations that provide everything from small group instruction to independent work with technology.

In my presentation I'll show student-centredness using interactive activities including; warming up starter, grabbing, matching headlines, graphic organizers, talking lines, wh questionnaires, Jigsaw reading, and exit tickets. We'll work according textbook based topic "Teen Magazines" Unit8 Lesson 1

It is believed that implementing this way of learning shows following results:

1. Interpersonal participation flexibility

Learners are actively involved in learning ('learning by doing', hands-on learning); learners interact with themselves and the teacher (e.g. through pair and group work).

2. Adapting to needs

Planning for learning begins with a consideration of learners' prior knowledge, skills and experiences (the central tenet of the theory of constructivism); learning is flexible and adapted to learners' needs and preferences (including emotional needs).

- 3. Confidence** Learners work by themselves; learners take responsibility for their own learning; learners not only learn content but also develop their lifelong ‘learning to learn’ skills (metacognition).
- 4. Relevant skills** Content is meaningful, and relevant to learners’ real lives; learners develop 21st Century skills such as analysis, critical thinking, creativity and lifelong learning.
- 5. Power sharing** Learners become involve in decision-making in dialogue with peers and the teacher; traditional power distances between teachers and students are reduced.

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ENHANCING ENGLISH COMMUNICATION SKILLS THROUGH GAMES: A FUN AND EFFECTIVE APPROACH

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Abstract: This thesis explores the utilization of games as a tool for enhancing communication skills among English language learners. Effective communication skills are essential for mastering a new language, and games offer an engaging and interactive approach to language learning. Through a review of literature and educational practices, this article discusses the benefits of integrating games into English language education, including increased motivation, vocabulary expansion, cultural understanding, collaboration, and communication. Various examples of language learning games, such as word chain, role-playing, charades, storytelling, and board games, are highlighted to illustrate their efficacy in fostering communication proficiency. By leveraging the inherent advantages of games, educators can create dynamic learning environments that promote active engagement and linguistic development among students. This article provides insights and practical strategies for incorporating games into language education to enhance communication skills and overall language proficiency.

INTRODUCTION

In the realm of language learning, effective communication skills play a pivotal role in mastering a new language. For English learners, developing these skills can often be challenging, as it requires practice, engagement, and a supportive learning environment. One innovative and enjoyable approach to

foster communication skills among English learners is through the integration of games into the learning curriculum. Games not only make the learning process more enjoyable but also offer numerous benefits such as promoting collaboration, enhancing vocabulary retention, and boosting confidence in using the language. In this article, we explore how games can be utilized as a tool to develop communication skills among English learning students.

Benefits of Using Games for English Communication Skills Development:

Engagement and Motivation: Games inherently evoke a sense of fun and excitement, which can significantly increase students' motivation to participate actively in language learning activities. When learners are engaged and motivated, they are more likely to persist in practicing their English communication skills, leading to better proficiency in the language.

Interactive Learning: Games provide a platform for interactive learning where students can actively engage with the language in a dynamic and immersive way. Through gameplay, learners have the opportunity to practice various language skills such as speaking, listening, reading, and writing in a meaningful context, thereby reinforcing their comprehension and communication abilities.

Vocabulary Expansion: Many language learning games incorporate vocabulary-building exercises, which expose students to a wide range of words and phrases in context. By repeatedly encountering and using new vocabulary during gameplay, learners can reinforce their understanding and retention of language components, ultimately enriching their communication skills.

Cultural Understanding: Certain games are designed to incorporate cultural elements, idiomatic expressions, and real-life scenarios, providing learners with insights into the cultural nuances of the English language. By immersing themselves in these cultural contexts through gameplay, students not only enhance their communication skills but also develop a deeper appreciation and understanding of English-speaking cultures.

Collaboration and Communication: Many language learning games are designed for group settings, fostering collaboration and communication among learners. Through cooperative gameplay, students are encouraged to interact with their peers, negotiate meaning, and express themselves effectively in English, thereby honing their interpersonal communication skills.

Examples of Games for English Communication Skills Development:

Word Chain: In this game, players take turns saying words that begin with the last letter of the previously spoken word. This game promotes quick thinking, vocabulary recall, and verbal communication skills.

Role-Playing Games: Role-playing games simulate real-life scenarios where students assume different roles and engage in conversation using English. These games encourage creativity, language production, and social interaction.

Charades: Charades involves players acting out words or phrases without speaking while their teammates try to guess the correct answer. This game enhances non-verbal communication skills, comprehension, and vocabulary usage.

Storytelling Games: Storytelling games prompt players to collaboratively create stories by taking turns adding sentences or paragraphs. This activity develops narrative skills, creativity, and oral communication proficiency.

Board Games with Language Components: Board games like Scrabble or Boggle incorporate language elements such as spelling, vocabulary, and word formation. By playing these games, students can reinforce their linguistic skills in an engaging and competitive setting.

CONCLUSION

Incorporating games into English language learning can be a highly effective strategy for developing communication skills among students. By leveraging the inherent benefits of games, educators can create dynamic and interactive learning environments that foster engagement, collaboration, and linguistic proficiency. Whether through word games, role-playing activities, or

storytelling exercises, the use of games in language education can empower learners to communicate confidently and effectively in English.

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EFFECTS OF TEACHING YOUNG LEARNERS THROUGH SONGS

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The main goal of English language learning is the development of communication skills, as well as maintaining interest and motivation for learning English. In order to achieve these goals, it is necessary for the content to be closely related to learners' real life and materials need to be modified to different learning styles. This means that the lessons should abound in flexible activities. Songs are examples of such activities which due to their nature, fun content, and relaxing features influence the development of language in children. For young learners, songs, such as popular pop-rock songs, traditional and educational songs, rhymes and chants, present an excellent source of language. Students can not only learn and practice different segments of English through songs, but also satisfy the specific characteristics of their age. Children, in general, like songs, and if songs

are used for learning a language, then children enthusiastically accept them. One key factor is that children are not aware of the fact that they are learning through songs, and therefore they see them as a pleasant and fun part of English lessons. Apart from this, songs serve as a good source of pronunciation.

If well planned, applied and evaluated, songs can become useful tools for language teaching and learning. Also, if the right songs are chosen, learning can become a fun and memorable experience. In order to accomplish this, a division between different song types and their purposes needs to be made. House (1997: 19) makes a distinction between traditional songs and songs written specially for young learners. She states that children are normally familiar with the former type, while the latter are, as their name suggests, specially written for a textbook to support certain vocabulary and grammar points. Similarly, Ur (1992: 65) makes the distinction between the specially-composed English teaching songs and the authentic ones. She explains that the first type of songs is used to teach vocabulary and language structures, as well as to aid oral language production. The authentic songs, on the other hand, are a matter of cultural aspect and entertainment. Murphy (1992: 121) presents a different typology of songs for young learners. He clarifies that there are jazz chants and Total Physical Response (TPR) or action songs. Jazz chants are rhythmic expressions in a situational context without background music. They develop listening comprehension skills and reinforce rhythm, intonation, specific language structures, and vocabulary. TPR songs require students to respond physically to what they hear and sing only when they are ready to do so. Using the appropriate songs is of critical importance. Whether they are specially written for learning English or authentic, it is crucial to choose songs that suit children's level of English as well as their interest since, as widely accepted, children enjoy simple and catchy songs. The love of repetition and the need to move, common to all young children, make songs integral parts of English lessons.

To repeat, songs and rhymes are essential in young learners' classroom for a number of reasons. First of all, they are children's favorite language activities which contain repetitive language and set phrases. Furthermore, they develop listening comprehension, they teach pronunciation, intonation and stress in a natural way, and teach vocabulary and language structures of the song. In addition, songs help children build their confidence by allowing them to join in no matter how good their English is. They also build group dynamics. And finally, if a song appeals to children they usually sing it on their own, outside the classroom (Roth, 1998: 53). According to Green (in Nelson and Son, 1986) the rhythm that verses of a song contain aids the development of children's language fluency, while rhyming words of a song help children focus on pronouncing them correctly. She also believes that the children who were continually exposed to songs at their early age increase their vocabulary and build their confidence in using the target language. Everything that has been said so far can be extended with Sevik's (2011: 1029-1030) list of the most remarkable characteristics of using songs with young learners. He concluded that: Listening comprehension is best taught through songs. Songs represent the strong feature of modern primary language programmes. Songs may extend young learners' attention span. Songs are great tool for language learning at an early age. Songs are regarded as an excellent memory tool. Songs provide a variety of comprehensible input. Songs create a safe and natural classroom ethos. Songs are extremely repetitive and result in language fluency. Songs abound in cultural content.

In addition, songs are beneficial for various reasons in English classes; Griffie (1988) identified the following reasons:

1. Songs and music lower anxiety. If they are introduced in the early years of language learning, songs and music tend to create enjoyable, anxiety-free environment.

2. Songs are useful for teaching vocabulary.

3. Songs serve as an excellent listening material.
4. Songs can be used as supplemental texts in the end of the lesson, on special occasions or as an additional component for vocabulary development.
5. Songs and music can be used to support grammar presentation, practice and revision.
6. Songs and music bring various cultures into the classroom.

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TEACHING IS LIKE AN APPLE TREE

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Buxoro shahar 22-IDUM ingliz tili fani o'qituvchisi,

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Annotatsiya: Ingliz tilini o'rganish o'ziga ishonchni, o'ziga bo'lgan hurmatni va shaxsiy o'sishni oshirishi mumkin, chunki odamlar chet tilini qanchalik chuqur o'rgansalar, ularning fikrlashi va dunyoqarashlari shu qadar

kengayadi. Shuningdek ular butun dunyo bo‘ylab odamlar bilan bog‘lanish qobiliyatiga ega bo‘ladilar. Ushbu uslubiy tavsiyada men o‘quvchilarning ijodiy, tanqidiy fikrlash va tasavvur qobiliyatlarini rivojlantirish uchun juda samarali bo‘lgan ba‘zi noodatiy usullarni taqdim etaman. Shu bilan birgalikda ushbu usullar orqali ingliz tili fanini ko‘plab fanlar, ya’ni tasviriy san’at, mehnat, tabiiy fanlar bilan o‘zaro aloqadorligini ko‘rsatmoqchiman.

Kalit so'zlar: farqlash, tasavvur qilish, fikrlash qobiliyati, usullar, o‘z-o‘zini baholash, muloqot.

Abstract: Learning English can increase self-confidence, self-esteem and personal growth, because the more people learn a foreign language, the more their thinking and worldviews expand. They will also have the ability to connect with people around the world. In this methodological recommendation, I present some unusual methods that are very effective for developing students' creative, critical thinking and imagination skills. At the same time, through these methods, I would like to show the interrelationship of the English language with many subjects, such as Art, Handicrafts and Science.

Key words: differentiation, imagination, thinking ability, methods, self-assessment, communication.

Teaching foreign languages is one of the most difficult jobs around the world. Teachers should be patient, supportive, a great role model and a good motivator for their students by implementing interesting, attractive and unusual ways for delivering lessons. Using interactive methods can boost pupils' knowledge and raise pupils' awareness of second language. While most of us are familiar with the language teaching methods used in secondary education, there is a huge variety of language learning methods available. Some of them are better suited to certain learners than others.

To commence, we've put together a list and a brief description of different language learning methods that might work for teachers.

In the history of teaching English languages, there are many teaching methods and techniques, but some of them are easily approachable and easy to learn. English Teaching Methods are reliant on and affected by various hypotheses of language learning.

The English Language facilitates cross-cultural communication and fosters a deeper understanding and appreciation of different cultures, perspectives, and ideas. In addition, learning English can boost confidence, self-esteem, and personal growth, as individuals gain the ability to express themselves effectively and connect with people around the world.

Method 1 “ A magic spider web “

We can use this method not only for one theme or lesson stage, it is useful for colourful lesson plans. For instance, when we want to introduce a new theme we can use this method for [pre-activity](#).

Teacher would like to elicit the words or pictures related to the topic. Pupils should come one by one and choose one of these words and pictures and say any english definition to english words. If the pupil doesn't know how to describe, she or he will pass the cards to another pupil like a web. Students will have an opportunity to improve their knowledge of Science. They will learn some information about these energy sources.

Method 2 “ Find my friend” (Using contrast colors)

This method is useful for while activity of the lesson We can implement this method for consolidation of the previous lesson about “Proverbs”, “Fruits and Vegetables”, “Colours” ,“Free-time activities”. It will improve the pupils’ creative and thinking skills. If they don’t know the continuation of sentences, they will differentiate according to the contrast colours, e. g Black- white, red-green. If their lesson is about proverb, they will find equivalent in their Mother tongue. It is connection between English and Mother tongue.

Method 3 “ Check yourself”

This method is very essential for post activities, particularly after reading activities. Ellis and Brewster present several reading strategies that can be strengthened by reading mind working with books.[1,8]. Burnett and Myers underline the fact that motivation for reading is usually seeking for information or achieving another similar aim. [2,4] Young learners should concentrate on the text when they read for detailed strategies to be able to understand the text or notice the language. These strategies are necessary for the process of development of critical reading. Harmer also claims that reading is not a passive skill and that young learners should work with texts actively.[3,17] McRae suggests introducing reading texts into the language learning process after a few lessons

because every new text invites young learner to the world of fantasy, imagination and discovery.[4,20]. Relying on these ideas I tried to create a new method for reading activities. Students will read some texts and do “True or False” activity in unusual way. There are some questions sticked on a web. Pupils will come one by one and take the cards and read questions and turn them back and they will check themselves by turning back the papers. If the pupil who cannot answer the question from the web, the next pupil will answer only this one. It will improve the pupils’ critical and understanding skills.

Method 4 “Nostalgia”

Used materials: Real objects like flower, coffee beans, tea, perfume, a dish, bread

Teacher will show the pp real things. In this method we can see 4C- collaboration, communication, creative and critical thinking ways. Teacher divides the pupils

into 4 groups of four. Pupils will smell the objects one by one remembering and feeling the time in the past was good, or the activity or remembering a good time in the past and wishing that things had not changed like nostalgia. Then pupils will work together and write a topic according to their feelings. They will work in groups and make their own posters describing the feelings. Teacher should pay attention to coherence and cohesion of their texts. At the end they should present their works.

How do you feel after smelling? What are the best things about them, in your opinion? Warm weather and blooming flowers? Holidays like Navruz or Women's Day. The start of your favourite memory? The chance to take spring break trips to see family or friends? Something else?

Make a list of some of your favorite memories, whether from last year or from when you were a small child, and then pick one and tell us about it. Try to use as much vivid detail as you can so that readers can experience the scene you describe. Then teacher will give time to pupils and they will prepare their poster presentations about their good times, about their nostalgia. This method will develop students' imaginative and creative skills.

The importance of a students' developing logical understanding skills is becoming more popular in our today's life. Early integration of logical thinking abilities helps children to be more confident and analytical thinkers. They are more prepared to deal with and face the realities of life. It will aid in the correlation of items and occurrences. Implement of creative methods allow students to develop creativity, problem-solving, critical thinking and other important life skills. Adults should encourage imaginative play for kids wherever possible.

Giving young generation opportunities to use their imagination helps with many aspects of development, from social skills to motor functions.

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INNOVATIVE ROLE OF THE TEACHER IN ORGANIZING EFFECTIVE LESSONS

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Annotation

I tried to focus on some features of learning foreign languages in this article. Because it is the duty of every foreign language teacher to arouse students' interest in this subject from the very first lesson of teaching a foreign language at school. This requires a teacher to have a deep knowledge of the subject, creativity, skills of using different teaching methods. Important measures are being taken at the school to teach a foreign language, to provide students with effective knowledge, modern methods are being studied and applied in the classroom. The size and quality of textbooks, visual aids and equipment are improving. Methodical manuals are published and new optimal teaching options are introduced. Modern methods are being studied in seminars and pedagogical trainings, and methodological assistance is being provided to teachers.

Keywords: modern educational technology, psychological aspect, individual psychological feature

Innovative role of the teacher in organizing effective lessons

In order to work on the basis of methods, forms, requirements for the organization of foreign language lessons, each teacher organizes and conducts non-traditional lessons, ensuring the effectiveness of individual abilities of students, good pedagogical cooperation. It is advisable to take measures such as accounting. The work of a teacher is so multifunctional and responsible that it requires a lot of effort and time. Today, armed with in-depth knowledge, only a teacher who can demonstrate the basics of the science, he teaches and the role of teaching in development can give and educate young people thoroughly. The organization of lessons based on modern technology is one of the important factors in the

development of students' oral speech, the development of independent thinking skills, listening comprehension and written speech. The effectiveness of reforms in the education system depends on the level of knowledge, skills and ability of teachers working in educational institutions. The opportunities are created for them to update their knowledge and skills and Uzbekistan pays increasing attention to the education of young people and the values that are formed in them, the development of foreign learning, worldviews and etiquette. Our youth are able to solve any problems and free from any negative thinking and express their attitude to any fields. Family members, classmates, friends who can influence, have intellectual power, and they are diligent, knowledgeable, courageous and polite. Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on April 19, 2019 # 5712 "On measures to improve the study of foreign systems" to improve the personal and pedagogical skills of foreign language teachers and The use of modern approaches in teaching is defined as the main.

The study of advanced foreign experience in educational institutions aims to improve educational skills and skills in the use of technology in modern teaching of foreign languages, the program also pays special attention to the coverage of modern requirements for improving the quality and process of improving the quality of foreign language teaching in Uzbekistan. Especially, the created literature in the framework of cooperation in accordance with the modern requirements of psychological approaches, is developed with the help of methodological manuals. Pedagogy in the study of foreign languages in primary education and it is an important task of every teacher and the public to form modern methods of psychology on the basis of imparting perfect knowledge and applying free thinking in them, to prepare them for independent living. It is an important task of every teacher and public to impart perfect knowledge based on modern methods of psychology and form them in the preparation for independent living. Every teacher must know the psychological aspects of learning a foreign language in education, modern approaches to teaching a foreign language and

aspects of communicative language. Therefore, foreign language teachers need to improve their knowledge, skills and abilities to effectively organize and manage the process of teaching foreign languages on the basis of increasing their pedagogical skills, professional competence. Primary school students will know the effective ways to implement innovations in pedagogical activities, know the technology of creating didactic and electronic learning materials and use them in the educational process will further improve the quality of foreign language learning. It turns out that in order to learn a language, you need to have a live language environment. Without an environment, language cannot be learned. Unfortunately, not only in a foreign language, but even in the native language classes, pure grammar is taught - a living language is taught as a whole, not as a living thing. That is, a rhyme is a form, a determiner, a case, a kind of compound sentence that follows ... but not a speech at all. [2] Live speech is the most important thing that is not taught in mother tongue classes. Of course, you need grammar, but it would be better to teach him to express himself freely and to write on a piece of paper without error. A student may not be able to write a nice letter to his parents, he may not be able to express his opinion in front of 4 people - right? The same can be said about teaching a foreign language. That's why we have a lot of foreign language teachers, but there are very few real foreign language specialists. Knowledge of a language is, of course, a virtue, but it should not be made an obligation. Learning a foreign language should be considered a tool, not a goal. By studying it, one should first of all strive to benefit more or less for his country and people. In fact, language learning has always been considered important. The difference is that in ancient times the study of the languages of the surrounding peoples was widespread, but now it has become a tradition to study the languages of the most economically developed nations. Now there is a wide way to learn foreign languages. In the past, English, German or French were taught mainly in the faculties of the institutes, but now several language universities have opened and dozens of foreign languages are being studied. The

best part is that in the past, it would be useless not to learn these languages at school: Let's say a child who has mastered English goes to a language faculty of an institute, and when he graduates, he goes to school and teaches it to children again. teaches the language ... that's learning a foreign language was a futile exercise, as if standing in one place. Knowledge of the laws of the process of teaching foreign languages in general, as well as modern concepts and technologies of teaching, education, development of the individual, motivates teachers to self-development in the process of improving professional competence. There is a psychological specificity of language learning, it is necessary to determine the individual psychological characteristics of the language learner. Because perception in a foreign language is appropriate, it is advisable to use psychological gymnastic exercises designed to memorize words in a foreign language.

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**TEACHING JEWELRY MAKING IN FREE TIME OR PROJECT
LESSONS**

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English Teacher At The School № 07

Abstract

Nowadays teaching interactive methods is the most crucial task in modern teaching. Uzbekistan craftsmanship can be found in many activities, some of which fall into traditional notions of craft, others which extend beyond the usual conception, such as:

- -writing a computer program
- -composing music,playing musical instrument
- -acting in a play
- -painting
- -jewelry making

Allowing students to learn craftsmanship is very special task . In Uzbekistan, a lot of attention is being paid to handicrafts together with education. Because Uzbekistan is a place of handicrafts. It is important for us teachers to connect education with handicrafts, especially for young pupil. If pupils learn crafts, they can go abroad in the future and show Uzbekistan's national traditions, crafts, national clothes and jewelry. It will be appropriate if they learn English along with craftsmanship.

Description

Jewelry making is an art that a lot of people learn for the purpose of fun and as a hobby and sometimes because they just love wearing a lot of Jewelry but don't have all that money. It is an easy activity that requires determination and focus. There is a lesson theme is called “Free time activities”.Pupil can do everything.They can go to the cinema, do sports, play musical instrument along with making handmade. In this workshop we let students make their own craft. For example, In project lessons they can make their own jewellery such as

earrings, bracelet, hair bands. The craft of jewelry is called jewelry making or jewelry crafting. It is the art and skill of creating and designing jewelry using various materials, such as metal, wire, beads, gemstones, glass, clay, leather, and more.

Necklaces, bracelets, and other pieces of jewelry aren't just fashionable items that we wear. Jewelry items can also be considered works of art. Before making special jewelry we will explain tasks.

1. Choose the type of jewellery and collect items pupil wants to make.
 2. Get the tools & materials pupil need.
 3. Allocate a work space. ...
 4. Learn the basics: Terminology & Skills.
 5. Be inspired.
 6. Learn from the experts.
 7. Practice.
 8. Join the community. Show to the Head members of school.
9. Pupil can sell jewelry which is made by themselves.

Besides it we give an information about :

- Basic techniques. Using eye and headpins. Opening and closing jump rings.
- Techniques to finish jewelry. Using a basic cord crimp. Using a round cord crimp.
- Stringing techniques. Making a bead 'float' using crimp beads. Stringing beads on multiple wires.
- Techniques to make unique jewelry. Create pendants from eye pins.

To design interactive atmosphere , we'll use some fruitful activities and engage the pupil's interests using the Module 5 from TETE . We can list some of them like“ Web of information” , “ Run and take”, “Find someone who” and so on.

We all know it's hard to fill up the days of the school holidays with no "I'm bored" comments - even if you have planned a days worth of activities! But the school holidays can be the perfect time to get creative and try some new activities. Here are our reasons why we think some basic jewelry making is the perfect activity for this school holiday or at the weekend.

Making jewelry inspires pupil, it gets the creative juices flowing, it requires technical and logical thinking, they can express their personality, they can create handmade things that they are proud , it encourages them to appreciate handmade, you can do it indoors or outdoors, It is a calming, soothing hobby which doesn't involve screens and noise, they can make friends and family birthday gifts.

INTERACTION OF CULTURE AND LANGUAGE IN TEACHING ENGLISH AS SECOND LANGUAGE (THROUGH RIDDLES)

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Abstract

The development of a new anthropocentric paradigm led to foundation of new scientific trends such as Ethnolinguistics, Sociolinguistics, Cognitive Linguistics and Linguoculturology as well. Linguoculturology focuses on the study of relationship between language and culture, the ways how culture is presented in language and how language presents and transmits cultural information. This article defines the role and importance of culture in language learning, shows peculiarities of Linguoculturology.

While learning and teaching new language culture can be a barrier, because there are some words as realiae, culture bound words, lacunas which have no adequate translation. In this case, studying culture broadly can be a good hand in both learning and teaching a new language.

Keywords: linguoculturology, concept, linguistics, folklore, riddles, culture bound words

Introduction. Linguoculturology or Cultural Linguistics is a new scientific trend of the XXI century. It is developing the idea that language is not only a tool of communication but also the cultural code of a nation. It appeared due to the development of a new anthropocentric paradigm, which gives a man the status of being “the measure of all things” and focuses on studying the “human factor” in the language [2,9].

The human is considered the centre of the Universe and language, because he is the only bearer of universal and national specific values. According to Yu.S. Stepanov linguistics is a science about “language in the human and the human in language”[2,10]. From the point of view of this paradigm a human being is not just a bearer of a language, but rather of a certain conceptual system according to which he understands, cognizes and conceptualizes information about the world and culture. Anthropocentric paradigm caused the emergence of new interdisciplinary linguistic trends such as Sociolinguistics, Ethnolinguistics, Gender Linguistics, Cognitive Linguistics, Linguoculturology.

Linguoculturology focuses on the study of relationship between language and culture, the ways how culture is presented in language and how language presents and transmits cultural information. Ashurova and Galiyeva claim that Linguoculturology deals with the deep level of semantics of linguistic units, and brings into correlation linguistic meanings and the concepts of universal and national cultures. V.N. Telia defines Linguoculturology as “a study aimed at investigating and describing the correlation between language and culture in scope of modern culture national selfconsciousness and its sign representation”[9,16]. V.V.Vorobyev states that it is “an integrated scientific discipline studying correlations and interactions between culture and language in their functioning” [6,37]. Many Russian and European scholars worked on Cultural Linguistics. Yu.S. Stepanov, N.D.Arutyunova, V.N.Telia and V.V.Vorobyev are considered the founders of Russian linguocultural schools.

Materials and methods. Language learning and language teaching is not only connected with the linguistics itself but it is more effective with the study of culture as well. From this perspective linguistics and culture has a great relationship with each other. Linguoculturology is actively new discipline that studies the language broadly with the integration of culture. Linguoculturology is an interdisciplinary science. V.A.Maslova points out currently there are four linguocultural schools: Linguocultural school headed by Yu.S.Stepanov, the

school of N.D.Arutyunova studying universal cultural models on the basis of the texts belonging to different ages and nations, the school of V.N.Telia which is known as “Moscow school of linguocultural analysis of phraseological units”, the school of linguists established at the Russian University of People’s Friendship by V.V. Vorobyev.[7,28] The last school investigated following issues of linguoculturology studies:

- linguocultural units and their types (linguoculturemes);
- the national world picture and nationally specific linguistic units;
- cultural specifics of the communicative behaviour
- culture specific phraseology;
- culture specific concepts and their verbalization;
- speech etiquette (the norms and standards of a polite communicative behavior in various communicative situations of greetings, farewells, apologies, request, etc.).

One of the most essential features of Linguoculturology is its interdisciplinary character. Interdisciplinarity means the correlation of two or more sciences on the basis of the common theoretical assumptions, notions and methods of analysis. Linguoculturology, it is characterized by both internal and external interdisciplinarity. Internal links are observed in its relation to such linguistic disciplines as Ethnolinguistics, Cognitive Linguistics, Country Studies, Linguoconceptology, History of the Language [2,12].

We focus on Ethnolinguistics, it deals with the relationships between language and ethnic culture. The object of ethnolinguistics are folk texts (songs, jokes, fables, riddles etc.), religious and mythological rituals. Its aim is the reconstruction of ethnic culture and vision of the world embodied in linguistic units. As we know language teaching through folk literature has already been accepted, by the way, learning language with the help of folk genre is more interesting and easy. Ahmed Sayeef claims that literature itself naturally has the capacity to draw attention of the readers and audience. And in the case of folk

literature or folk tale this is truer. In the attempt of teaching English language through literature, learners are automatically drawn into the stream of learning almost involuntarily. And we also understand that the affective filter does not bar the learners in their language learning process when an interesting piece of literary work is utilized in language teaching. In the language learning classroom, popular folk tales could be a very effective teaching material [1,2]. According to linguists Joanne Collie and Stephen Slater, we may choose literature for language teaching for the following reasons: valuable authentic material, since literature is not created with a view to teaching language and thereby we get the essence and examples of real life situation and setting. Particularly, when learners have survival level of proficiency and they need to learn more. They now can comprehend the language meant for the native speakers and become familiar with the different linguistic forms, functions and meanings.

Culturally rich text: knowing a culture means knowing the relevant language. Literature is the true portrait of a culture and a nation. So, the literary text helps the learners of a language tremendously to learn the target language.

Richness of language: the text of literature is rich with its lexical items, syntactic patterns and functions of discourse. It is also rich with other literary devices like metaphor which inevitably enrich a reader.

Personal involvement: a reader becomes personally involved when he starts reading a work of literature and begin to immerse themselves in the text. A person forgets the mechanical and artificial way of language learning and hence it is beneficial and conducive to language learning[3,8].

Results and Discussions. Folklore includes variety of subgenres as folktale, songs, proverbs, riddles. Riddles are considered to be the most interesting one among them. Riddles always attract both young and adult learners. A riddle is a statement or question having a double or veiled meaning, put forth as a puzzle to be solved. Riddles are based on the social life of each nation. People and the universe surrounds them is depicted in riddles using metaphorical and allegorical

language. Riddles encourage people to see things in a new or different way, could no doubt play a role in training the mind. Riddles carry historical, cultural, linguistic, social aspects of a certain nation. In contrast to thematic theme of Uzbek and English riddles there are some plants and animals which are peculiar for each language. It depends on the geographical location, climate of the countries. As the solution of such riddles unfamiliar for reader, so it could be found unknown depiction of phenomena as well.

At present, contemporary riddles are very popular and they are a good hand while teaching new vocabulary for school children. Contemporary or modern riddles are mostly about new technology, neologisms, new tools, sports.

What is a bunny's favorite kind of music? Answer: Hip hop music.

This riddle explores new type of music which is popular in Western countries, for finding the right answer one should know what is bunny's favorite type of music.

What begins with T, finishes with T, and has T in it? Answer: A teapot.

The riddle is given like a pun (riddle game), it begins and ends with T and has T(tea) in it. This kind of descriptive riddles are useful for consolidating new vocabulary and there we also can see repetition of letter "T".

What is a snowman's favorite breakfast? Frosted Flakes.

What's Santa's favorite candy? Jolly Ranchers.

These riddles carry national realiae of countries who celebrate Christmas holiday. They are very interesting for ESL learners as well. They characterize snowman's or Santa's favorites. If the founder is aware of snowman's favorite breakfast or lovely candy the answer is very easy to find, but for Eastern or Asian people it can be unknown. These riddles are very helpful while learning about Christmas, New Year holiday, if the teacher gives them before reading activity pupils or students try to find the answer, besides the riddle hints what the reading text is about and the information taken from the text will be memorable with the words *Frosted Flakes, Jolly Ranchers*.

Conclusion. New paradigm of linguistics demands being aware of the culture of the target language as well, while learning a new language. Cultural linguistics or Linguoculturology is a new trend that links the language with culture. As being one of important genre of folklore, riddles also express cultural point of nations. This genre of folklore plays an important role in training children's mind. Riddles dealing with its scholarly matter, by the nature of their content serve a certain educational task.

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Психологические аспекты изучения детской литературы

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Аннотация. В данной статье исследуется как детская литература влияет на психологические аспекты и развитие воображения у детей. Кроме того, детально изучаются поучительные элементы детской литературы и роль сказок в психологическом становлении ребенка, а также рассматривается тема педагогического аспекта чтения сказок.

Ключевые слова: психологизм, психологические аспекты, художественное произведение, литературные жанры, детская литература, литературная сказка, сказочные образы, фольклор.

Введение. Детская литература имеет своеобразное влияние на развитие психологии: сказки, рассказы или романы играют важную роль в развитии воображения у детей. Художественные произведения развивают ребенка с эмоциональной интеллектуальной стороны, расширяют воображение и кругозор, формируют ценностные установки и помогают усвоить множество других навыков. Разнообразие образов героев, непохожие друг на друга сюжеты и также различные литературные жанры предоставляют молодым читателям уникальную возможность расширять горизонты мышления и развивать широкий комплекс навыков, которые будут им необходимы на протяжении всей жизни. Рассматривая сказки с педагогической точки зрения и по антропологическим исследованиям выявляется, что образ мышления первобытного человека во многом совпадает с ранними формами мышления ребенка. Детская литература в основном содержит воспитательный момент, который имеет особое влияние на психический аспект ребенка. Более того, некоторые сказочные образы показывают негативные действия, которых было бы лучше избежать и также сказка характеризует положительных героев, за которыми и следует идти. Как известно, братья Гримм внесли огромный вклад в детскую литературу, более того сохранили и опубликовали традиционные сказки, рассказанные в Германия. Также, датский писатель и поэт- Ганс Христиан Андерсен путешествовал по Европе и собрал много известных сказок и создал в сказке новые сюжеты и жанры.

Методика исследования. Сказки говорят с детьми, сопровождают их и помогают справляться с повседневными проблемами реальной жизни. Рассмотрим традиционную детскую литературу: легенды, мифы и рассказы

помогают детям лучше понимать мир вокруг. Каждая история основана на культуре, а мир культуры является безграничным.⁵⁶ Читая или рассказывая мифы, легенды и сказки, мы воспитываем душу ребенка, его гуманность. По мнению Донны Нортон⁵⁷, понимание мира приходит к ребенку вместе с пониманием древних культурных традиций. Изучая фольклор, дети учатся ценить свою культуру и творчество народа. Традиционные произведения помогают осознать распространение культуры, формируя у детей представление о добрых, храбрых, милосердных и трудолюбивых героях со всего мира.

В книге «Польза от волшебства: Смысл и значение сказок», Бруно Беттельгейм⁵⁸ приводит точные аргументы о влиянии чтения детям мифов и легенд. Также, использует собственный психоаналитический подход к анализу произведений, утверждая, что ничто не обогащает знания ребенка так, как традиционная детская литература, которая помогает ребенку изучить прогресс человечества, и ознакомиться с возможными способами решения проблем. К тому же, легенды показывают нравственное поведение героев. Таким образом, ребенок учится у героя противостоять трудностям жизни и подчеркивает точную грань между добром и злом: простых положительных персонажей ребенок ассоциирует с собой- с добром и вместе с ними учится противостоять злу, подчеркивая, что справедливость торжествует. Рассматривая историю устного сказания в целом, можно обнаружить два вида повествования с целью улучшения психического благосостояния: один из них направлен на поддержание психического здоровья и действует в качестве профилактической меры. Второй тип нацелен на восстановление психического равновесия и работает в качестве

⁵⁶ D. Wolkstein, *Treasures of the Heart*, Random House Inc., 2002.

⁵⁷ D. E. Norton, *Through the Eyes of a Child, An Introduction to Children's Literature*, MacMillan, 3rd edition, 1991.

⁵⁸ B. Bettelheim, *The Uses of Enchantment: The Meaning And Importance of Fairy Tales*, New York: Vintage Books, 1989.

терапии.⁵⁹ Русская пословица гласит: «Сказка – сокровище народной мудрости». Присоединяясь к сказке, малыш приобретает совершенно новый для себя вид мыслительной деятельности - способность мысленно действовать в воображаемых обстоятельствах, и эта способность является основой любой творческой деятельности. Дети извлекают большой урок из жизни книжных персонажей.

Результаты и их обсуждение. Согласно психоаналитическому анализу, с помощью языка смыслов и трансфера большинство сказок затрагивают следующие проблемы:⁶⁰ страх, что тебя бросят родители; конфликты внутри семьи, конкуренция между детьми; социальная зрелость, стремление к автономии; принятие у себя и у членов семьи позитивных и негативных черт характера; проблемы половой идентичности в пубертатный период; отношения отцов и детей; эмоциональное взаимодействие. Сказочные истории, выраженные языком трансфера и символических представлений, способствуют развитию символической мысли, репрезентативных способностей и психической обработки жизненных событий на фантазийном уровне.⁶¹ Впоследствии именно они формирует основу для развития креативного мышления и эмоционального интеллекта.⁶² Одновременно, с помощью механизмов идентификации и проекции, ребенок способен определять и выражать свои негативные чувства, придавать значение личным психологическим травмам, и, что самое главное, искать и находить смысл собственной жизни.⁶³ Сказка – одно из

⁵⁹ S. Pelasgus, *The Secrets Fairytale, An Apprenticeship in the Art of Oral Literature and Storytelling*, Athens: Metexmio, 2007.

⁶⁰ B. Bettelheim, *The Uses of Enchantment: The Meaning And Importance of Fairy Tales*, New York: Vintage Books, 1989.

⁶¹ H. Kourkoutas, *Psychoanalytic Approach of Fairy Tales and the Use of Children's Stories in Psychotherapy and Special Education*, Athens: Topo.

⁶² J.M.GottmanandJ.DeClaire, *TheHeartofParenting:HowtoRaise an Emotionally Intelligent Child*, Bloomsbury Publishing PLC, 1997.

⁶³ B. Bettelheim, *The Uses of Enchantment: The Meaning And Importance of Fairy Tales*, New York: Vintage Books, 1989.

самых доступных средств развития эмоций ребенка, которым во все времена пользовались педагоги и родители. Сказки народов мира оказывают огромное влияние на формировании личности ребенка. По мнению таких психологов, как Л. Выготского и О. Никифоровой, дошкольный возраст является первой ступенью в развитии будущего читательского таланта, но при этом дошкольники не являются активными читателями, скорее их нужно воспринимать как активных слушателей. Потому, что именно в этом возрасте дети учатся сострадать героям, радоваться и огорчаться вместе с ними.⁶⁴ Любимые сказочные герои остаются в сердце ребенка на всю жизнь, и также ребёнок пытается быть похожим на книжных героев.

По следующим пунктам детская литература влияет на психику молодого читателя: художественные произведения развивают творческое мышление и способность рассматривать ситуации с разных ракурсов и находить решения дилемм. Также, книги помогают детям преодолевать страхи и тревожности, а именно их любимые герои покоряют вершины, что и мотивирует читателя, здесь же формируется критическое мышление. Далее формируются ценностные-моральные нормы и принципы, развиваются языковые и коммуникативные навыки, так как чтение книг расширяет словарный запас и учит грамотной речи. С помощью книг дети могут расширить свое мироощущение, то есть узнавать о разных культурах, обычаях и традициях. Само чтение открывает познавательный мир для детей.

Выводы. Сказки играют ключевую роль в познании мира с помощью символов и образов. Дети верят, что, погружаясь в мир обитания литературных персонажей, находят сходства с их собственной средой жизни. Сказки о добре и зле помогают ребенку выстроить субъективную и

⁶⁴ Кони́на М.М. Художественная литература, как средство нравственного воспитания. // Вопросы эстетического воспитания в детском саду. – М., 1960г.

объективную реальность, и ребенок интуитивно находит скрытые смыслы в произведениях. Более того, эмоциональные процессы участвуют в структурировании психоэмоционального опыта ребенка, так как в волшебном мире сказок, выявляется грань между воображаемым и реальным, где ребенок получает простор для фантазии. В развитом современном мире, имеющем цифровые варианты книг, забыто, что сказка играет очень большую роль в развитии личности ребенка и обогащению внутреннего мира, поэтому следует ценить культуру, традиции и язык. И одной из главных задач родителей и учителей является- проявление интереса детей к книгам и любовь к чтению, осознавая важность и значимость литературы.

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Methods and Techniques of pronunciation

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Like many other subjects taught in school, the subject of the English language is one of the most relevant and demanded. The President of our country Shavkat Mirziyoyev pays special attention to this sphere. In the Decree of the President “On Uzbekistan’s development Strategy” is mentioned about achieving major improvement of general secondary education, facilitating in depth study of foreign languages and other important disciplines.

History and trends of teaching pronunciation in the world

Trends in teaching pronunciation: the **Pendulum Swings**

Our students can benefit from learning about both individual sounds and the musical aspects of pronunciation, and we need to find a balance between these two areas. The Pendulum of teaching trends might keep swinging, but we don’t have to let it knock down.

Importance of techniques and methods of teaching pronunciation for low and upper classes

Most popular and common pronunciation teaching techniques are:

1. Listening and repeating
2. Drilling
3. Ear training
4. Tongue Twisters
5. Songs and rhymes

6. Reading aloud

7. Recording learners' pronunciation

8. Sound-colour charts

Listening and repeating

In this technique, a teacher or recorded native speaker are set as models for imitating sound. It can be more interesting by using CD's, interactive boards, internet activities, etc. This activity is suitable for all ages from young to adults.

Drilling

This technique is very useful with beginners even though it is a strictly controlled activity. Drills can be practiced individually, in pairs or chorally. There can be repetition drills, chain drills, transformation drills and probably the most attractive Jazz Chants.

Ear training

It is a very effective teaching technique, where learners focus their attention on hearing. Traditionally, the ear training technique was connected to identification of individual sounds. Ear training should be used with all age groups.

Songs and rhymes

Using songs and rhymes is considered to be very effective way of teaching English. They are rhythmical, learners can dance, move while

singing. By singing learners practice pronunciation drills, rhythm, or intonation.

Common problems in teaching English pronunciation for young learners

Merging

When our brains and ears cannot tell difference between two similar sounds, we pronounce both of them in the same way. And this is called merging. For instance “reach” /iy/ and “rich” /i/

Substitution

When learners hear a new sound that doesn’t match any of the sounds they know, they often substitute a familiar sound that is somewhat similar and easier for them to produce.

Fossilization

It is a process that occurs when a language learner progresses to a certain point but then has a hard time making further progress. For instance a learner may not be able to differentiate /v/ as in “very”, and /b/ as in “berry”

In conclusion we can say that learning English pronunciation is the same important as grammar, speaking, or listening. We should pay attention to teach grammar from the beginning. Because even if pupils’ grammar or vocabulary are strong, if their pronunciation isn’t easy to understand their communication will fail.

**THE ROLE AND IMPORTANCE OF NON-GOVERNMENT
OLYMPIADS ON TEACHING ENGLISH IN PRIMARY AND
SECONDARY CLASSES AT SCHOOLS.**

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Abstract: This article highlights the importance of Olympiads and English competitions for young learners in their educational journey. These competitions, such as Hippo, National Spelling Bee, ESB, WWC, PIMSO, and SEAMO, contribute to developing independent speaking skills and overcoming barriers like lack of confidence and shyness. The focus is on the significance of non-governmental organizations like ELPC in enhancing English language education for primary and secondary school children. In addition to English competitions, ELPC also offers opportunities in subjects like mathematics through competitions like AMC and SEAMO. Through these initiatives, students can showcase their knowledge and skills on a regional, national, and global scale, fostering a love for learning and academic excellence.

Keywords: English competitions, Olympiads, non-government, language learning, student motivation

English is considered a global language and is essential for communication, business, and education in today's interconnected world. As a result, teaching English in schools has become a top priority for many educators around the globe. Within particularly charged educational environment, some policy makers have

decided that the creation of a well-educated, English speaking workforce may be one route out of the current global economic downturn: today parents often consider academic excellence in English to be the number one priority in terms of access to higher education university accreditation and economic prosperity for their children. Consequently, in many countries, including Uzbekistan, children now begin their study of English at primary level. As to the worldwide experience, learning another language must be as close to a natural way of learning mother tongue as possible at the primary level. It is necessary to emphasize that young people today are eager to learn and absorb knowledge, often mastering several languages simultaneously. However, mere learning itself is not enough. It is essential to apply and test this knowledge in real-world situations. As they advance to higher grades, students encounter various challenges during Olympiads, such as pressure, competition, and self-confidence issues.

We know that there are various prestigious Olympiads available for older students, but there are fewer opportunities for younger learners. In this I would like to mention the importance of non-government Olympiads. They can play a significant role in enhancing English language education in primary and secondary classes. The ELPC (English Language Proficiency Competition) initiative is considered a non-governmental organization that creates such opportunities. It allows students from grades 1 to 11 not only to showcase their knowledge within their schools but also to compete at regional, national, and even global levels.

ELPC was founded in 2017. Since then they have been running several competitions among Private and Public schools in Uzbekistan. Hippo, WWC (Writing World Cup), NSB (National Spelling Bee), ESB (Eurasian Spelling Bee) are English language Olympiads. This organization not only organizes competitions in English but also in various subjects, including mathematics, such

as AMC (American Mathematics Competitions) and SEAMO (Southeast Asian Mathematics Olympiad), Sakura (Japan) among others.

Another key role of non-government Olympiads in teaching English is their ability to ignite a passion for the language among students. By participating in these competitions, students are motivated to delve deeper into the intricacies of English grammar, vocabulary, and literature. This not only improves their language skills but also cultivates a love for learning that extends beyond the competition itself. These Olympiads can provide supplementary learning materials such as practice tests, study guides, and online resources to help students improve their English language skills outside of regular classroom hours. Non-governmental English Olympiads can motivate students to excel in English by offering rewards, recognition, and opportunities for advancement. Competitions can spark interest and engagement in the subject, encouraging students to dedicate more time and effort to improving their language proficiency.

These Olympiads can also offer training workshops, seminars, and resources for English language teachers to enhance their teaching methods, curriculum development, and assessment strategies. This support can help teachers deliver more effective English language instruction in primary and secondary classes.

English Olympiads often involve participation from students and educators from diverse backgrounds. This can provide students with opportunities for cultural exchange and exposure to different accents, dialects, and perspectives, enriching their understanding of the English language and its global relevance. Competing in English Olympiads typically requires students to demonstrate not only language proficiency but also critical thinking, problem-solving, and communication skills. Participating in such competitions can help students develop these essential skills, which are valuable for success in academic and professional contexts. Moreover, non-government Olympiads serve as a platform for students to apply theoretical knowledge in practical contexts. Through

activities like debates and essay writing, students learn to articulate their thoughts coherently, present arguments persuasively, and express themselves eloquently in English. These real-world applications of language skills not only enhance students' communication abilities but also instill in them the confidence to express their ideas effectively. For instance, in 2023, a 3rd grade student from Uzbekistan became the World Champion at the International Hippo Olympics. This achievement signifies the potential of our youth to excel on the global stage among representatives from 63 countries. It's essential to utilize all resources and opportunities to nurture our future generations who can effortlessly compete on the world stage alongside their peers. While there are costs associated with participation, the investment in education is invaluable.

In addition to academic benefits, non-government Olympiads contribute significantly to the holistic development of students. These competitions promote teamwork, sportsmanship, and resilience, as students collaborate with peers, face challenges, and learn from both success and failure. Such experiences nurture essential life skills that go beyond the realms of academia and prepare students for the challenges of the real world.

The importance of non-government Olympiads in teaching English in primary and secondary classes cannot be overstated. These competitions serve as catalysts for academic excellence, language proficiency, critical thinking, and holistic development among students. By providing a platform for students to engage with the English language in dynamic and meaningful ways, non-government Olympiads empower learners to unlock their full potential and embark on a journey of lifelong learning and growth.

In conclusion, non-government Olympiads stand as beacons of educational innovation, enriching the English language learning experience for students in primary and secondary classes. As educators and students alike embrace the opportunities presented by these competitions, the impact on language

proficiency, critical thinking, and overall academic development is profound and enduring. Embracing the transformative power of non-government Olympiads, we pave the way for a future where linguistic excellence knows no bounds.

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DOES EDUCATION QUALITY DEPEND ON CLASSROOM?

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Introduction. The motivation and encouragement mark a significant milestone in a person's further success in life. There are some critical factors that affect the quality of the lesson and strengthen the motivation to receive high quality education. This paper will identify the barriers that impede the progress of education impacting on teaching process in the classroom.

Main part. There are several factors that impact on quality of education, the overpopulation in the classroom and schools have had impact that state seem to ignore. With the growing number of young populations in Uzbekistan, their proportion comprises over 10 million according to qalampir.uz, their age ranges are from 0 to 14. This means over one third of Uzbek population is young, these citizens are at the age of attending to schools. It is good to have young population in the country, whereas it does not mean that it will not cause any problems in the country. One of the major issues is the number of classrooms is insufficient, there are large classes where the number of students reaches over 40.

The weather has an indirect influence on education quality, considering the recent anomaly heatwaves, the world has been experiencing high temperatures,

and Uzbekistan was hit hard that temperature reached at some point reached over 50 Celsius. These make the current situation at schools far worse than expected, having an effect on social life along with education quality. During September, April and May, these months are generally hot, many students after lunch would feel sluggish and exhausted by hot weather. The major prompt is a large proportion of schools do not have air conditioner to control the room temperature, making the learning experience less appealing and overpopulation in classrooms deteriorates the situation. As the large proportion of youth population have a considerable impact, it means there are multiple problems that can be observed in schools. What is even worse, schools have double shift system, which creates a burden for both teachers along with students to have classes interestingly and impedes to yield a desired outcome. This problem is exacerbated by building more block of apartments in areas with already inbuilt infrastructure, this would define a flock of potential buyers who are ready to purchase at any cost. According [to state agency](#), the percentage of apartments sold soared up to 162% compared to previous year in 2023.

The insufficient number of classrooms creates other problems. The double shift system at schools makes conducting the quality lessons far worse. The maintenance of sanitary will be hard since as soon as classes finish, a second shift enters the class. This, in turn, creates an atmosphere where students along with teachers feel discomfort, it will influence on the level of motivation to work with enthusiasm and passion. The room atmosphere will also need to be shifted as there will be a need for fresh air Zilola Madatova, 2020. Working with students, who study in the first shift will require a room, working with students after the lesson finishes is almost impossible to due to lack of opportunities – no classroom. Consequently, the students will demonstrate low academic performance because teachers have no room to conduct a lesson, unable to provide an extra class for those who lag behind. In Uzbekistan, language courses are usually conducted in a different way unlike other school subjects. The group is normally divided into

to two, each subdivision belongs to the same group, yet a lesson is conducted by different teachers in different classrooms. A need for an extra classroom means that sometimes there would be no classrooms available, because of no classroom for extracurricular classes creates a disappointment for teacher and students.

Working with students, who study in the first shift will require a room, working with students after the lesson finishes is almost impossible due to lack of opportunities – insufficient classes. As educators provide no lessons for those who lag behind from the class, it is an immense tragedy for the future of a child who was not able to grasp the concept that requires an extra explanation, doing exercises, more attention post lesson. Consequently, the students will demonstrate low academic performance. An interesting coincidence can be observed in test results of students, according to statistics presented by Uzbek State Test Center, over 550.000 applicants were not able to meet the minimum requirement to be considered for admission at tertiary level education. The share of these applicants was alarming, accounting for roughly 50%, the academic performance of students is worse compared to previous year according to Xabar.uz.

Having a school that can provide basic necessities for its students is vital. The facilitation of free textbooks to all school students is noteworthy to point, this practice is highly appreciated. Provision of books provided for free of charge by governments for all school students is highly respected investment; nevertheless, the shortage of books can be observed. Sometimes there are some delays with delivery of textbooks. The shortage of textbooks are mainly subjects of high importance, particularly math, physics, biology and English. If no textbooks provided to school students, how can a student perform academic excellence? The worst is these textbooks are not available in bookshops, depriving the possibility to purchase even at a parental expenditure, Adbujalil Turkmanov, 2019. A student, who is not equipped with a textbook, will show no excellence, which will attribute to poor academic performance, affecting to knowledge acquisition, delaying a

student progress, the bad news it would impede to have a career progression in later stages of life.

Conclusion. In conclusion, the further progress of education or the improvement of economic situation of people requires an improvement in schooling system, which demands an attention by both the officials and people, a need to have more schools to accommodate an ever-growing number of students. Thus, students will have small classes that is much easier for teacher to control the class, deliver the lesson interestingly. Students, in turn, would enjoy the extra-curricular activities since enough rooms would define teaching and pursuing academic excellence is possible in Uzbek schools because of efforts made by government. Provision of textbooks and deliveries should be arranged in way that does not deprive students from receiving knowledge, parents and schools should work in cooperation to find ways to ensure that a child will not lag behind his peers in the class.

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TALAFFUZGA O‘RGATISHDAGI QIYINCHILIKLAR VA ULARNI YENGISH YO‘LLARI

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Buxoro viloyati Buxoro tumani 50-umumta'lim maktabi o'qituvchisi

Chet tili talaffuzini o'rgatish chog'ida ko'p narsa o'quvchilarni talaffuz birligi bilan „tanishtirish“ tushunchasining metodik izohini bilishga bog'liqdir. Tanishtirish bu fonetik birlikni muallimning aytishi va o'quvchilarning eshitishi hisoblanadi. Talaffuz birligini yolg'iz, so'zda yoki gapda taqdim etish usullari muammosini xolisona hal qilish talaffuz ko'nikmasini shakllantirishda muhim omildir.. Ushbu usullarning o'ziga xos ijobiy va salbiy tomonlari bor. O'zbek maktablarida chet tildagi talaffuzni o'rgatishda o'qituvchi umumiydan xususiylga qarab faoliyat yuritishi, o'quvchi esa xususiyladan umumiyga o'tishi tajribada isbotlangan optimal metodik yo'ldir.

Ingliz tili materialida asosida o'tkazilgan eksperimental tadqiqot natijasiga ko'ra, tovushlarni talaffuz qilish jarayonida o'quvchilar quyidagi tartibda ish tutishlari ma'qul:

1. Tovushlarni yolg'iz aytish: “o'xshamaydigan” undoshlar, ”o'xshamaydigan” unlilar, ,”yaqin” unlilar
2. Tovushlarni so'zda aytish: so'z oxiridagi jarangli undoshlar; ,”o'xshash” unlilar ; oppozitsion qiyinchilik tug'diradigan tovushlar (unlilar va undoshlar);
3. Tovushlarni jumlada aytish: “o'xshash” undoshlar (bundan so'z oxirida uchraydigan jarangli undoshlar istisnodir); ”o'xshash” undoshlar (so'z oxiridagi [dj] dan tashqari).

Keltirilgan tartib faqat tovushning dastlabki taqdim etilishiga taalluqli hisoblanadi. Keyingi bosqichlarda ya'ni ko'nikma va malaka hosil qilish jarayonida tovushning qo'llanilishi nutq amaliyoti bilan chambarchas bog'lanadi. Xullas, taqdim etish usullari uchta: yolg'iz, so'zda va jumlada aytish va eshitish.

Talaffuzni o`rgatish usullari tovushning oson/qiyinlik darajasi bilan bog`liq. Chunonchi, o`quvchi ona tilisi (yoki til tajribasi) nuqtayi nazaridan „o`xshash“, „yaqin“, „o`xshamaydigan“ birliklarni farqlash mumkin.

Yolg`iz aytiladigan unli va undoshlar o`ta qiyin, so`zda aytiladigan unli, undosh fonetik hodisalar o`rtacha qiyinlikda bo`lib, jumlada aytiladigan unli va undoshlar oson fonetik birliklarni tashkil etadi.

Qiyin hisoblanadigan yangi tovush talaffuzining o`rgatilishi quyidagi ta'limiy bosqichlardan o`tadi.

1. Muallim ijrosida nutq namunasining aytilishi va o`quvchilar tomonidan eshitish bosqichi. O`quvchilar diqqati jumla mazmunini va undagi yangi so`zning ma'nosini tushunib olishga qaratiladi. Yangi tovushni muallim, avvalo, jumlada, so`ngra so`zda aytadi, o`quvchilar tinglab idrok etishadi.

2. Fonetik birlikning sintetik (yaxlit) tarzda idrok etishdan analitik (qismlarga bo`lib) tinglashga o`tiladi. Muallim so`zdagi yangi tovushni ajratib aytadi hamda uning artikulyatsiyasini lo`nda qilib tushuntirib beradi, ya'ni qisqa qoida ko`rsatmani bayon etadi. (Talaffuzga doir qoida haqida quyida ma'lumot beriladi.) Muallim ko`rsatmasiga binoan o`quvchilar nutq organlarini mazkur tovushni aytishga tayyorlaydilar. Muallimning talaffuzi va tushuntirishlari bunga ko`maklashadi. Ikkinchi bosqich — tovushni ovoz chiqarib aytishga tayyorgarlik — uni ichki nutqda aytishni ta'minlaydi.

3. Eshitib idrok etish va ichda aytishdan ovoz chiqarib talaffuz qilishga o`tish bosqichi. Yangi tovush namunasini muallim aytib ko`rsatadi, o`quvchilar birgalikda va yakka-yakka bo`lib takrorlaydilar. Shunday qilib, tahlil va taqlid yo`li bilan yangi tovushning yolg`iz holdagi talaffuzi o`rganiladi.

4. Yangi tovushni boshqalari bilan biriktirib aytish bosqichida tovush o`rganilgan tovushlar bilan birikmalarda aytiladi. Imkon boricha unli va undosh birikmalari mashq qilinadi.

5. Yangi tovush soʻzda aytiladi. Muallimdan ibrat olib, oʻquvchilar xor va yakka-yakka boʻlib talaffuz etadilar. Mabodo soʻzda ikkita yangi tovush boʻlsa, ulardan biri avval puxta oʻzlashtiriladi, soʻngra ikkinchisi aytiladi (qiyinchiliklarni tarqatib berish mezoniga amal qilinadi). Oxirida soʻz talaffuz qilinadi. Bu bosqich tovushning maʼno anglatish xususiyati (fonema)ni oʻrgatishga bagʻishlanadi.

6. Endi yangi tovush jumla tarkibida talaffuz etiladi. Muallim boshlaydi, oʻquvchilar taqlidan qaytaradilar. Soʻzning tovush va maʼno ifodasi bevosita jumlada shakllanadi. Bu bosqichda jumalarni aytish — axborot almashish darajasida mashq qilish demakdir.

7. Yangi oʻzlashtirilgan tovushni mustahkamlash bosqichi. Turli talaffuz sharoitida, yaʼni kichik va katta kontekstda, shuningdek, yolgʻiz, soʻzda va gapda oʻrganilayotgan tovush erkin qoʻllanadi.

8. Oʻquvchilar til tajribasida mavjud tovushlar bilan yangi tovushni chalkashtirmasliklari uchun mashqlar bajarish lozim (ona tili va ikkinchi til tovushi bilan qiyoslash va ilgari oʻzlashtirilgan chet tildagi tovushlar bilan solishtirish kabilar). Qiyoslash va solishtirish yolgʻiz, soʻzda va jumlada aytiladigan tovushlar asosida mashq qilinadi. Ushbu yakuniy bosqichda ham muallim rahnamoligida mashqlar bajariladi.

Bajariladigan mashqlar tegishli nutq vaziyatlarida oʻtadi. Ulardan kuzatiladigan birlamchi maqsad axborot olish yoki yetkazish sanaladi, qoʻshimcha vazifa muayyan tovushni aytish hisoblanishi mumkin.

Tavsiya etilgan yangi tovush talaffuzini oʻrgatishning sakkiz bosqichli taqdimot pallasini quyida inglizcha [w] fonetik birligi orqali namoyish etiladi.

Muallim “What is your name?” jumlasini aytadi. Mashqda “what” soʻzini bir necha bor takror talaffuz qiladi. Jumla mazmuni va soʻz maʼnosi ochilgandan keyin, ushbu soʻzdagi yangi tovushni bir necha bor ajratib aytadi. Muallim talaffuzida tovush namunasini tinglash orqali oʻquvchilarda tovushning dastlabki

eshitish tasavvuri paydo bo`ladi. Muallim oddiygina qilib tovushning artikulatsiyasi haqida amaliy ko`rsatma beradi: lablar dumaloq holda oldinga cho`chchaytiriladi. Shu paytning o`zida tovushni, takror-takror aytib ko`rsatadi. o`quvchilar muallim taklifi bilan lablarini talaffuz holatiga keltirishni mashq qilishadi.

EFFECTIVENESS OF TEACHING ENGLISH TO YOUNG LEARNERS THROUGH TPR METHOD

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ABSTRACT: *This article deals with the importance and benefits of using TPR (total physical response) method in teaching foreign languages and improving language skills of young learners.*

KEY WORDS: *TPR (total physical response), young learners, short attention spans, language acquisition, language skills, listening, speaking, coordination of speech and action, physical (motor) activity.*

The main goal of teaching young learners is to encourage children to use the target language in their life, as well as, using different activities to improve young learners' language acquisition. Language skills in young children develop in a three-step process that involves hearing the words repeatedly, making an association between familiar words and what they represent, and attempting to imitate or speak the words. As young children are extremely energetic and playful, as well as, tend to have short attention spans and a lot of physical energy, teaching through TPR (total physical response) method is considered a very effective way of learning a foreign language.

TPR stands for Total Physical Response and was created by Dr. James J Asher, a professor of psychology at San Jose State University of California. Asher developed TPR - total physical response as a result of his experiences observing young children learning their first language. He noticed that interactions between parents and children often took the form of speech from the parent followed by a physical response from the child. According to his observations Asher made three hypotheses:

first, that language is learned primarily by listening;

second, that language learning must engage the right hemisphere of the brain;

third, that learning language should not involve any stress.

Asher believes that it is crucial to base foreign language learning upon how children learn their native language. In other words, TPR is based upon the way that children learn their mother tongue. Parents have 'language-body conversations' with their children, the parent instructs and the child physically responds to this. It is a teaching method that can combine the meaning of English words with actions, pictures, and objects. It is not only a useful way to teach the accurate meaning of each English vocabulary to the pupils, but it can also help them to recall the meaning of them. It also emphasizes the interest value, which is suitable for the pupil's learning characteristics.

TPR aims to teach learners oral proficiency and conversational fluency in a second language. It emphasizes the voices, actions and gestures of learners and teachers rather than the text or media. It is a language teaching method built around the coordination of speech and action, which attempts to teach language through physical (motor) activity. The most important principle is that only the target language is used for all instructions and the basic idea of the TPR method is that the language learners can comprehend the words in the target language said by their teachers and then they respond physically to it.

The *principles* of TPR include:

✦ *The teacher plays the role as the director, and the pupils respond*

physically in accordance with the instructions of the teacher;

✦ *Listening, comprehending and then physical response are emphasized more than oral productions;*

✦ *The imperative and interrogative modes are usually employed:*

✦ *Humor is often employed to increase the enjoyment of learning;*

✦ *Listening ability and vocabulary must be developed first;*

✦ *There must not be any stress in the class;*

✦ *Regular repetition, the more often we trace memory and the more intensively we repeat*

✦ *Action verbs are the core of TPR;*

✦ *Expose the natural use of language;*

✦ *Create an artificial English community in the classroom;*

Imperative drills are the prominent classroom activity in TPR, as they highlight physical actions and activity on the part of the learners. In this sense, learners play main roles: a listener and a performer. They listen attentively and respond physically to commands by the teacher. Learners need to respond both individually and collectively; and the teachers are responsible for giving commands and monitoring actions taken by the learners. On the contrary, the learners are imitators of teachers' verbal and non-verbal models. There are two main phases in teaching-learning process using TPR method:

➤ *the first phase is modeling.* In this case, a teacher issues commands to learners, and performs the actions with them.

➤ *in the second phase, learners demonstrate* that they grasp the commands by performing them alone; the teacher monitors the learners actions.

One of the methodologists, Widodo states the following *advantages of teaching English to young learners through TPR method:*

✦ *It is a lot of fun. Learners enjoy it, and this method can be a real stirrer in the class. It lifts the pace and the mood;*

✦ *It is good for kinaesthetic learners who are required to be active in the*

class;

- ✦ *It can be used both in large or small classes. In this case, it is no matter to have how many students you have as long as you are prepared to take the lead, the learners will follow;*
- ✦ *It works well with mixed-ability classes. The physical actions get across the meaning effectively so that all the learners are able to comprehend and apply the target language;*
- ✦ *It involves both left and right-brained learning;*
- ✦ *It is very memorable. It can assist pupils to remember phrases or words.*
- ✦ *It can make the teaching more enjoyable for both teachers and pupils.*
- ✦ *It is suitable for the children who are required to be active in the class.*

TPR can be used to teach and practice so many things as :

- *Vocabulary connected with actions (smile , chop , headache , wriggle)*
- *Grammatical items including tenses past/present /future /continuous (every morning I clean my teeth , I make my bed ,I eat breakfast)*
- *Classroom language (open your books)*
- *Imperative /instructions (stand up , close your eyes, etc)*

So, we can point out that TPR method turned out to be an important part of the daily teaching activities. The combining of curricular activities with new method not only helps pupils to develop speaking, but grammar as well; pupils can also internalize new vocabulary, improve pronunciation, and improve modulation, among other oral communication skills. Besides, they can acquire new vocabulary and understand the usage of grammar items in a real context through exploring activities related to the theme.

In addition, learners enjoy the classes while learning a foreign language. When using TPR activities, they were more motivated and talked in a nonthreatening environment. Learners practiced the vocabulary, laughed and developed the activities with confidence. On the other hand, an average number of pupils looked very concerned and shy; they thought it was not going to be possible for them to

improve their communicative skills and they experienced some difficulties at the beginning, but along the process they found they could improve little by little.

In conclusion we can state that for the successful teaching of English in primary schools, it is essential for the teacher to understand the young learners characteristics, instincts, and interests in their cognitive, linguistic, and emotional aspects, because this will play a crucial role in how the teacher builds a lesson, he or she can make sure that the young learners are fully involved in the learning process, how he or she achieves the objectives of a lesson, and how they respond.

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LINGUA CULTURAL STUDIES AS THE CORE OF ANTHROPOCENTRIC RESEARCH

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Introduction. Lingua cultural studies, as an interdisciplinary field, occupies a central position in anthropocentric research by elucidating the intricate connections between language and culture. Language, as a fundamental tool of human communication, not only enables individuals to convey information but also reflects their cultural norms, values, and identities. Therefore, studying the relationship between language and culture through a critical lens is essential for understanding the complexities of human behavior and societal structures. In this article, we delve into the core principles of lingua cultural studies and explore its significance as a linchpin of anthropocentric research.

Literature Review. The foundation of lingua cultural studies lies in the recognition that language is not a neutral medium of communication but a dynamic system that is deeply intertwined with culture. As early as the 20th century, scholars such as Edward Sapir and Benjamin Lee Whorf highlighted the ways in which language shapes thought and perception, giving rise to the Sapir-Whorf hypothesis. According to this hypothesis, the structure and lexicon of a language influence the way its speakers perceive and interpret the world around them, thereby shaping their cultural worldview.

Building upon this theoretical framework, contemporary researchers in lingua cultural studies have expanded their focus to encompass a wide range of linguistic and cultural phenomena. From discourse analysis and sociolinguistics to translation studies and semiotics, scholars have employed diverse methodologies to investigate how language functions as a cultural artifact and a social practice. By examining linguistic features such as syntax, semantics, and pragmatics in conjunction with cultural practices, researchers have uncovered the intricate ways in which language both reflects and constructs social realities.

One key area of inquiry in lingua cultural studies is the analysis of linguistic diversity and multilingualism within societies. By exploring how individuals navigate multiple linguistic repertoires in their daily interactions, researchers have gained insights into the ways in which language shapes social identities and power dynamics. Moreover, the study of language contact and language change has shed light on the processes of

cultural exchange and adaptation that occur when different linguistic communities come into contact.

Another crucial aspect of lingua cultural studies is the examination of language ideologies and discourses that underpin social hierarchies and inequalities.

By analyzing how language is used to construct and perpetuate systems of dominance and exclusion, researchers have uncovered the ways in which linguistic practices can reinforce or challenge existing power structures. By interrogating the links between language, ideology, and social identity, scholars have contributed to a deeper understanding of how language both reflects and reproduces social inequalities.

Methodology. In conducting research within the field of lingua cultural studies, scholars employ a variety of methodological approaches to analyze the complex interplay between language and culture. Discourse analysis, for instance, allows researchers to examine how language is used in specific contexts to convey social meanings and power relations. By analyzing the structure and content of spoken or written texts, scholars can uncover the underlying discursive strategies that shape our understanding of social reality.

Sociolinguistic approaches, on the other hand, focus on the relationship between language variation and social factors such as age, gender, ethnicity, and social class. Through the study of linguistic variation and change in different speech communities, researchers can gain insights into the ways in which language is used as a marker of social identity and affiliation. By investigating patterns of language use in diverse social contexts, scholars can illuminate the ways in which language reflects and reinforces social hierarchies.

Semiotic analysis provides yet another valuable methodological tool for researchers in lingua cultural studies, enabling them to investigate the ways in which signs and symbols convey cultural meanings. By examining the relationship between linguistic signs (such as words and gestures) and cultural symbols (such as icons and rituals), scholars can uncover the deep-seated connections between language and culture. Through a semiotic lens, researchers can elucidate how meaning is constructed and interpreted through the interplay of linguistic and cultural codes.

Discussion. The integration of diverse methodological approaches in lingua cultural studies enables researchers to explore the multifaceted dimensions of language and culture in human societies. By adopting an interdisciplinary perspective that draws on insights from linguistics, anthropology, sociology, and cultural studies, scholars can generate new knowledge about the ways in which language shapes and reflects human behavior. Furthermore, by engaging with different theoretical frameworks and empirical

data, researchers can develop critical perspectives on the role of language in constructing social realities and identities.

One of the key contributions of lingua cultural studies to anthropocentric research is its emphasis on the cultural specificity of language practices and meanings. Language is not a universal and ahistorical phenomenon but a dynamic and context-bound system that is shaped by social and cultural factors. By attending to the cultural nuances of language use and interpretation, scholars can avoid essentializing notions of language and culture and instead embrace the complexity of linguistic diversity.

By centering the experiences and perspectives of language users, scholars can uncover the ways in which language both constrains and enables social action and resistance.

Conclusion. In conclusion, lingua cultural studies serves as a vital cornerstone of anthropocentric research by unraveling the intricate connections between language and culture. Through the exploration of linguistic diversity, language ideologies, and social discourses, scholars in this field deepen our understanding of how language shapes and reflects human behavior and societal structures. By adopting a multipronged methodological approach that encompasses discourse analysis, sociolinguistics, translation studies, and semiotics, researchers can interrogate the complex interplay of language and culture in diverse social contexts.

Moving forward, it is imperative for scholars in lingua cultural studies to continue expanding their theoretical frameworks and methodological tools to capture the richness and diversity of human linguistic practices. By engaging with emerging trends in digital communication, global migration, and cultural hybridity, researchers can explore the evolving landscapes of language and culture in contemporary societies. Ultimately, by recognizing the centrality of language in anthropocentric research, scholars can contribute to a more nuanced and inclusive understanding of the complexities of human communication and social interaction.

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Exploring Stylistic Techniques in English Language

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Abstract: This thesis embarks on an exploration of the artistic aspects of language, focusing on a thorough examination of stylistic devices in English. By carefully analyzing various literary works and linguistic phenomena, it aims to reveal the intricate tools writers use to add depth, resonance, and aesthetic appeal to their texts.

Key words: Stylistic device, artistic aspects, language exploration, literary works, linguistic phenomena, depth and resonance, aesthetic appeal, metaphor, symbolism, irony, rhythm, cognitive analysis, interdisciplinary approach, stylistic subdisciplines

By systematically investigating key stylistic devices such as imagery, metaphor, simile, symbolism, irony, and rhythm, the thesis aims to clarify their underlying mechanisms and rhetorical purposes. It examines how these devices are employed across different genres, time periods, and cultural contexts to convey complex ideas, evoke emotional responses, and engage readers on multiple levels.

Stylistic devices are commonly found throughout various forms of literature. There exists a wide array of stylistic devices utilized in literature. Commonly employed devices include metaphor, where a writer portrays two distinct things as identical for comparison, and simile, where two disparate things are likened for comparison's sake. Additional stylistic devices encompass personification, hyperbole, oxymoron, allusion, alliteration, and anaphora.

A metaphor is a stylistic device wherein the writer juxtaposes dissimilar concepts that don't naturally align but can be interpreted symbolically for comparison. For instance, consider the expression, "This library is an ocean of knowledge." Literally, a library cannot be an ocean, but metaphorically, it suggests the vastness and depth of knowledge within. Similarly, if a writer says, "The reader devoured the book," it doesn't mean the person is literally eating the

book; rather, it vividly conveys the speed at which the person reads and absorbs information.

A simile is a rhetorical tool where the writer draws a likeness between disparate entities to highlight a particular shared trait. Unlike a metaphor, a simile typically includes the words “like” or “as.” For example, consider the phrase, “The class was like a steep mountain.” Here, the comparison between the class and a mountain illustrates the arduous and challenging nature of the class. Another instance is, “The tree stood as tall as a skyscraper,” where the height of the tree is emphasized by likening it to a skyscraper towering over the observer.

The primary objective of stylistic analysis is to examine the cognitive, interpersonal, and communicative aspects of language. Rather than isolating specific elements in a text, it is preferable to assess the entire work in relation to various reading objectives. Stylistic analysis typically involves three interconnected stages: description, explanation, and evaluation. Descriptive techniques encompass phonetic, lexical, semantic, syntactic, and discourse levels, reflecting the structural organization of languages. Over time, traditional rhetorical and stylistic elements have been integrated into stylistics, evolving alongside developments in linguistics. Stylistics draws upon linguistic theories and methodologies to systematically analyze language styles across diverse contexts, including informal dialogue, formal discourse, poetry, prose, news articles, advertisements, novels, and theatrical productions.

Stylistics, in essence, embodies an interdisciplinary approach to interpreting texts, drawing from both language comprehension and insights into societal dynamics. A stylistician’s analysis of a text is shaped by rhetorical reasoning and historical context.

Michael Burke, in “The Routledge Handbook of Stylistics,” characterizes the field as a form of empirical or forensic discourse critique. In this view, the stylistician, armed with comprehensive knowledge of morphology, phonology, lexicon, syntax, semantics, and various discourse and pragmatic frameworks, seeks linguistic evidence to either support or challenge subjective interpretations and assessments made by critics and cultural commentators.

Burke’s portrayal likens stylisticians to Sherlock Holmes figures, possessing expertise in grammar and rhetoric, along with a deep appreciation for literature and other creative works. They meticulously dissect the intricacies of language, observing how style informs meaning and comprehension. Stylistics encompasses several interconnected subdisciplines, each explored by a stylistician:

- Literary stylistics: Analyzing forms such as poetry, drama, and prose;

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- Interpretive stylistics: Examining how linguistic elements contribute to creating meaningful art;
 - Evaluative stylistics: Assessing how an author's style functions—or fails to—in a work;
 - Corpus stylistics: Investigating the frequency of various elements in a text, such as to authenticate a manuscript.

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